

IUCLID 6.9 MICROBIAL ACTIVE SUBSTANCE APPLICATIONS

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

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INTRODUCTION

This manual is intended to support applicants in compiling Microbial Pesticide Active Substance applications in line with the relevant changes released with IUCLID 6.9.

Note: Applicants are encouraged to regularly check the Highlights section of the **Toolkit** (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/applications/toolkit>) as it may include relevant information on the latest development.

Disclaimer on Legacy documents: over time a number of IUCLID documents have been replaced with a completely new version. In such cases the old version remains accessible as a Legacy document for data migration reasons and for applicants with previously submitted dossiers to reuse. Such documents must never be used when preparing a new dossier.

Regulations and data requirements

Regulatory background for microbial pesticide active substances applications

The procedures for approval and renewal of approval of active substances are set by **Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009**¹ for rules governing plant protection products and the active substances contained in those products, as amended by **Regulation (EU) 2019/1381**² (**Transparency Regulation**), and as implemented by **Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/428**³ and by **Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 2020/1740**⁴ – that applies as from 27 March 2021 and replaces the previous procedure under Implementing Regulation (EU) No 844/2012⁵ – respectively.

Active substances (including micro-organisms) can only be approved for use in plant protection products if they fulfil the approval criteria that are laid down in **Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009**¹, as amended by Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1438⁶, where relevant, subject to conditions or restrictions. Companies may apply for amendments of conditions of approval, which follow the same regulatory process.

The initial approval of an active substance is valid for a limited period and the approval of an active substance needs to be reviewed periodically. A renewal of approval is only granted after the substance is re-evaluated and at least one safe use of the substance is demonstrated.

Data Requirements for Microbial Pesticide Active Substances Applications

Following the entry into force of the **Transparency Regulation**, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002⁷ (General Food Law Regulation) was amended by introducing **new requirements regarding**

¹ Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market and repealing Council Directives 79/117/EEC and 91/414/EEC

² Regulation (EU) 2019/1381 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on the transparency and sustainability of the EU risk assessment in the food chain and amending Regulations (EC) No 178/2002, (EC) No 1829/2003, (EC) No 1831/2003, (EC) No 2065/2003, (EC) No 1935/2004, (EC) No 1331/2008, (EC) No 1107/2009, (EU) 2015/2283 and Directive 2001/18/EC

³ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/428 of 10 March 2021 adopting standard data formats for the submission of applications for the approval or the amendment to the conditions of approval of active substances, as provided for in Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council

⁴ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/1740 of 20 November 2020 setting out the provisions necessary for the implementation of the renewal procedure for active substances, as provided for in Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council, and repealing Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 844/2012

⁵ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 844/2012 of 18 September 2012 setting out the provisions necessary for the implementation of the renewal procedure for active substances, as provided for in Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market Text with EEA relevance

⁶ Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1438 of 31 August 2022 amending Annex II to Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards specific criteria for the approval of active substances that are micro-organisms

⁷ Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety

transparency of submitted data, including the **submission of dossiers** for pesticide active substances (including micro-organisms) **applications using IUCLID format**.

These new requirements, as implemented by the Practical Arrangements⁸ laid down by EFSA, are reflected in the EFSA "Administrative guidance on submission of dossiers and assessment reports for the peer-review of pesticide active substances and on the MRL application procedure"⁹ and apply to all pesticides applications submitted as of 27 March 2021.

Four implementing Regulations relevant to micro-organisms are applicable from 21 November 2022 onwards (https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/pesticides/micro-organisms_en).

The new rules reflect the latest scientific developments and are based on the specific biological properties of micro-organisms.

- [Commission Regulation \(EU\) 2022/1438](#), amending Annex II to [Regulation \(EC\) No 1107/2009](#) as regards specific criteria for the approval of active substances that are micro-organisms
- [Commission Regulation \(EU\) 2022/1439](#), amending [Regulation \(EU\) No 283/2013](#) as regards the information to be submitted for active substances and the specific data requirements for micro-organisms
- [Commission Regulation \(EU\) 2022/1440](#), amending [Regulation \(EU\) No 284/2013](#) as regards the information to be submitted for plant protection products and the specific data requirements for plant protection products containing micro-organisms
- [Commission Regulation \(EU\) 2022/1441](#), amending [Regulation \(EU\) No 546/2011](#) as regards specific uniform principles for evaluation and authorisation of plant protection products containing micro-organisms

Information on the updated tables of content in alignment with the new data requirements is available in the Crosswalks IUCLID 6 v9 EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product) to Data Requirements: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7188149>.

Confirmatory information dossiers

In case the (renewal of) approval of an active substance is subject to the condition of the submission of further **CONFIRMATORY INFORMATION** to Member States, the Commission and EFSA, studies necessary to meet that condition are likewise subject to the obligation to use the IUCLID software for their submission¹⁰.

Important! If the submission contains confirmatory information, the dedicated box in the dossier header must be ticked.

Inclusion of active substance in Annex IV to Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 as part of an active substance approval or renewal process

If the assessment of the approval/renewal of an active substance leads to a proposal to include an active substance in **Annex IV** of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005¹¹, this should be highlighted directly in the endpoint summary (Section 6.3) **of the approval/renewal dossier**. There is **no need to submit a separate MRL dossier** in IUCLID.

How to build an IUCLID Dossier

Before starting to compile a dossier, it is recommended to check [EFSA's Applicants Toolkit](#) for the latest resources available to support its preparation.

⁸ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate-pubs/transparency-regulation-practical-arrangements>

⁹ Administrative guidance on submission of dossiers and assessment reports for the peer-review of pesticide active substances and on the maximum residue level (MRL) application procedure. 2021 [updated on 3 June 2024] <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/it/supporting/pub/en-6464>

¹⁰ This does not apply to substances conditionally approved under Implementing Regulation (EU) No 844/2012.

¹¹ Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC Text with EEA relevance. OJ L 70, 16.3.2005, p. 1–16

For specifics on the IUCLID tool, it is recommended to consult the [IUCLID 6 user manual](#) describing the functionality of IUCLID 6, accessible via its web interface.

For further details on how to use IUCLID check the “[IUCLID for Applicants](#)” training available in EU Academy.¹²

For further details on confidentiality, please refer to the [User guide on confidentiality](#).

The **first step** is to create a Legal Entity for the organisation which is submitting the application and to create **user accounts** for the people authoring the dossier. See the Overview of ECHA Cloud Services section of ‘IUCLID Training for applicants’, [Video 8](#) and the image below. More details on user management can also be found in [ECHA accounts manual](#).

Important! A functional mailbox address and the number of a switchboard must be provided in the ‘Legal entity’ since this is always published. Personal contact details should be included in the ‘Contact’ entity.

Legal entity name*	EFSA IUCLID demo
Legal entity type	company
Remarks	
Other names	New item Imp
#	Flags
Address	Address 1 Via Carlo Magno, 1A Address 2
Postal code	43126
Town	Parma
Region / State	
Country	Italy
Phone	+390521036111
Fax	
Email	generic.company.email@mail.com
Web site	www.company.com

The **second step** to build a valid IUCLID dossier is to create a new “Mixture” dataset and select the Working context ‘**EU PPP Micro-organisms – active substance application (product)**’.

For further details, see the ‘Overview of IUCLID cloud services’ and ‘Creating a dossier section’ of ‘IUCLID Training for applicants’ <https://zenodo.org/record/4778345>.

Note: Carefully check the instructions for setting the confidentiality flag/s since a non-confidential version of the dossier will be made publicly available once the application is deemed ‘valid for further evaluation’. In line with Article 39f of the General Food Law, and for the purposes of, inter alia, point (c) of Article 38(1) of the General Food Law, the public version of any attachment should not be in word/rtf format, but rather in pdf format.

The **third step** is to compile the IUCLID dossier with relevant information.

The **dossier header** must be completed. It should identify the type of submission and provide administrative information to support the processing of the dossier:

- **Purpose of the application:** depending on the process, select: ‘approval of an active substance for use in plant protection products’ or ‘renewal of an active substance for

¹² Please note that EU Login is required for accessing the training platform

use in plant protection products'. Additional information can be included in the remarks box.

- **Confirmatory information:** this box must be ticked if the submission contains confirmatory information.
- **European Reference Number** – this must be maintained for all submissions within a regulatory action and should only be amended if requested to do so by EFSA.
- Notification of studies pre-application identifiers.
- The Rapporteur Member State (RMS).
- Reason for re-submission (if the dossier is updated).

Two main **datasets** must be completed:

1. one or more **MIXTURE DATASET/s**: with data on the representative mixture/s (including the GAP, as a mandatory document). The mixture dataset and corresponding table of contents (TOC) are equivalent to the data requirements in Reg. (EU) No 284/2013 as amended by Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1440;
2. one **ACTIVE SUBSTANCE DATASET**: with data on the TARGET active substance. The active substance dataset and corresponding table of contents (TOC) are equivalent to the data requirements in Reg. (EU) No 283/2013 as amended by Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439.

If appropriate, **one/several METABOLITE dataset(s)** can be created in the document [FLEXIBLE SUMMARY.Metabolites](#) (Section 1.4.1 Information on metabolites - product dataset), with data on secondary metabolite(s) of (potential) concern produced by the micro-organism (as requested in the data requirements). See dedicated chapter [below](#) for detailed information on how to report data on secondary metabolites.

Information on **other substances** relevant for the assessment can be reported creating an additional row under the mixture composition document and compiling the relevant newly created dataset, e.g. in case of relevant impurities, co-formulants and killed/deactivated micro-organisms where the toxin is to be assessed (see '[Special cases: submission of dossiers on deactivated/killed micro-organisms](#)' paragraph).

Basic information on **Safeners, synergists and co-formulants** (i.e. names and chemical identifiers) can be entered in the [FLEXIBLE RECORD.MixtureComposition](#) document (Section 1.4 'Detailed quantitative and qualitative information on the composition of the preparation' – Product dataset) even when they are mixtures (e.g. a co-formulant dissolved in a solvent). Information on the alternative co-formulants should be entered similarly to other co-formulants.

Multiple representative products can be listed in the **product composition section** (1.4.2 'Other representative products' – Product dataset).

Watch [video n.2](#) to see how you can access the different datasets in an IUCLID dossier ([Navigating through datasets within a product/mixture](#)).

Note: the dataset in which a study is reported is **dependent on the test material**. All studies should generally be reported only once. The cross-reference function should be used for studies within same dataset to avoid duplicate data entry.

Since it is currently not possible to cross-reference between different datasets, when data provided for the product dataset are needed also for the active substance dataset (or vice-versa), a waiver should be included to indicate where the scientific data can be found. In such cases, reference to the UUID of a IUCLID document can be made in the Reason field of the cross-reference section.

In case of studies including micro-organism and metabolites the following approaches should be used:

- If the test material is the **micro-organism**, studies should be included under the **active substance dataset**;
- If the test material is a **metabolite**, studies should be reported under the **metabolite dataset**;

- If the test material is a **micro-organism and metabolite/s**, studies should be reported under the **active substance dataset**.

As a general principle, IUCLID documents should be fully completed. The required data **must be reported in the relevant IUCLID documents** (Dossier Header, Endpoint summaries, Endpoint study records, Flexible records, Flexible summaries, etc).

Duplication of information should be avoided. Attachments should be provided only as indicated in the instructions provided in this manual.

Where the IUCLID document does **not contain a structured section** and **templates** have been recommended by evaluators, the data should be entered as specified in the published templates and attached to the IUCLID dossier following the instructions provided in this manual.

When no study is provided for a data requirement/endpoint, a detailed **justification for data waiving** must be completed in the endpoint study record. Only a short description of the justification for data waiving should be reported in the relevant endpoint summary to avoid duplication of information.

Dossier and study naming – best practices

Dossier naming

- A dossier name must always be provided
- The dossier name should include the name of the active substance
- An additional indication on whether the dossier is NAS/AIR if wanted
- AVOID details on (re)submissions, versioning, dates, etc

Study naming

Personal data must be avoided, e.g. Endpoint study records should not include author names.

It is recommended to name the study with the shortest name possible.

It is recommended to use the Year of the study, the endpoint and additional relevant context where multiple studies exist for an endpoint.

Examples:

- Analytical methods: 2007_Post-approval control and monitoring purposes_cereal
- Identity, taxonomy and phylogeny: 2021_A.s.name_WGS_analysis
- Infectivity and pathogenicity: 2018_pathogenicity_rat
- Toxicity aquatic invertebrates: 2012_pathogenicity_daphnia magna
- Good agricultural practices (GAP).001: Crop_zone.001, ex. Apples_NEU.001

Additional suggestions

When completing **rich text fields** (e.g. [Any other information on results incl. tables](#) or Description of key information), it is recommended to **avoid** using table numbers or numbered bullet points, as this can cause conflicts with the automatic numbering system used in generated reports. Instead, use plain text or bullet points without numbers to ensure that the content is displayed correctly and consistently in the printed report.

Special cases: 1 - Submission of Dossiers on deactivated/killed micro-organisms

When the active substance is a *deactivated/killed micro-organism*, it does **not** fall under **part B** of Commission Regulations (EU) 283/2013 and 284/2013, as amended by Commission Regulations (EU) 2022/1439 and 2022/1440.

To ensure that information relating to the original micro-organism (e.g. taxonomy, fermentation details, whole genome sequencing) can still be reported correctly, the **EU PPP Micro-organisms working context** must be used. Follow the steps above:

1. **Create a product dataset.**

2. **Describe the composition in the Mixture composition document:**

- Create a **substance dataset** for the micro-organism
- Set **Type of Substance** to '*micro-organism or toxin produced by a micro-organism*'
- Assign the function '*active substance*'
- This enables completion of the relevant documents, including biological properties.

3. **Add the deactivated/killed component:**

- In the same mixture composition document, create a **substance dataset** for the *killed/deactivated component*.
- Assign the **function** '*active substance (other not to be assessed)*'
- Set **Type of Substance** to '*UVCB*'.
- The attached dataset will then follow the standard Table of Contents for a (chemical) active substance. All relevant studies should be included under this dataset.

4. **Clarify the actual active substance in the dossier:**

- In the **Dossier Header**, add a note in the '*Dossier submission remarks*' field explaining that the active substance under evaluation is the *deactivated/killed micro-organism*, even though technical constrains require the original micro-organism to be flagged as the active substance throughout the dossier.

5. **Ensure clear identification for evaluators and the public**

- The naming of both the micro-organism and the dossier (as these will be public available) must clearly indicate that the evaluated substance is the *deactivated/killed* form (see screenshots below).

6. **Confidentiality rules:**

- The '*active substance (other, not to be assessed)*' **must not** be flagged as confidential either at the reference substance level or in the mixture composition. This is essential, as this component is actually the active substance under evaluation.

Note: Due to the complexity of this configuration, some **Validation Assistant errors** may occur. If this happens:

- export the Validation Assistant Excel report,
- provide the necessary justifications,
- and submit it to the RMS

PPP containing Deactivated micro-organism
a9358044-0e35-4b0e-9ed3-90adff82dba3

View Dossiers Validate Create dossier

1 Identity of the applicant, identity of the plant protection product and manufacturing information

1.1 Applicant, trade name or proposed trade name

1.2 Producer of the preparation and the microorganism(s)

1.3 Producer's development code number of the preparation if appropriate

1.4 Detailed quantitative and qualitative information on the composition of the preparation

Composition of PPP name

- Deactivated micro-organism/s name/s (part B dataset)
- Deactivated micro-organism/s name/s (part A dataset)
- Water

UUID: d3092544-678c-4b65-a68c-29e850f71a51

Active substance approval Notification of studies Specific submissions Other submission related information

Dossier name (given by user)
Deactivated/killed <<micro-organism/s name/s>> approval dossier

Dossier submission remark
The active substance under evaluation consists of deactivated/killed <<micro-organism/s name/s>>, no live components are present.
A set of data according to part A of Commission Regulation (EU) No. 283/2013 is provided under the dataset "deactivated <<microorganism/s name/s>> (part A dataset)" in the mixture composition document.
Specific information on the microorganisms (e.g. biological properties, pathogenicity, etc.) is provided under the dataset "deactivated <<microorganism/s name/s>> (part B dataset)" in the mixture composition document.

Active substance approval
European reference number*
664211a5-fcdd-46c2-a8c3-e50b84cf259

PPP containing Deactivated micro-organism
a9358044-0e35-400e-9ed3-909df2a2aa3

EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)

PPP containing Deactivated micro-organism

1 Identity of the applicant, identity of the plant protection product and manufacturing information

1.1 Applicant, trade name or proposed trade name

1.2 Producer of the preparation and the micro-organism(s)

1.3 Producer's development code number of the preparation if appropriate

1.4 Detailed quantitative and qualitative information on the composition of the preparation

Composition of PPP name

UID: 35:83331-6544-491c-8eea-23590130430a

Administrative data General information Components

Mixture/product name
PPP name
Trade names + New item Import file

Brief description
PPP is a plant protection product containing deactivated/killed <<micro-organism/s name/s>>

Formulation type
WP Wettable powder

Components

#	Compo...	Name	Function	Typical concen...	Concentration ...	Remarks
1		Deactivated micro-organism/s name/s (part B dataset)	active substance	0 CFU/g	0 - <= 0 CFU/g	This is not the actual active substance, as the micro-organism was deactivated/killed
2		Deactivated micro-organism/s name/s (part A dataset)	active substance (other, not to be assessed)	ca. 20 % (w/w)	> 10 - < 30 % (w/w)	This is the actual active substance, i.e. the deactivated micro-organism
3		Water 7732-18-5	solvent	ca. 80 % (w/w)	> 70 - < 90 % (w/w)	

Edit Deactivated micro-organism/s ...

Substance name*
Deactivated micro-organism/s name/s (part A dataset)
Public name

Legal entity
EFSA Agency | Helsinki | Finland
Third party

Other substance identifiers + New item Import file

#	Flags	Identifier	Identity	Country	Relation	Remarks	Actions

Contact persons + New item Import file

Identification of substance
Reference substance

Type of substance
Type of substance
UVCB
Origin
organic

Role in the supply chain
Manufacturer
Importer
Only representative
Downstream user

Edit Deactivated <<micro-organism...>>

Substance name*
Deactivated <<micro-organism/s name/s>> (part B dataset)
Public name

Legal entity
EFSA Agency | Helsinki | Finland
Third party

Other substance identifiers + New item Import file

#	Flags	Identifier	Identity	Country	Relation	Remarks	Actions

Contact persons + New item Import file

Identification of substance
Reference substance

Type of substance
Type of substance
microorganism or toxin produced by a microorganism
Origin

Role in the supply chain
Manufacturer
Importer
Only representative
Downstream user

Special cases: 2 - Submission of Dossiers on micro-organisms whose mode of action is based on secondary metabolites present in the product

When a **secondary metabolite** is the *actual active substance* present in the product, a dossier compliant with **Part A of Regulation 283/2013** (data requirements for *chemical* active substances) is required **in addition** to the dossier for the micro-organism.

As in the previous case, the **EU PPP micro-organisms working context** must be used. Follow the steps below:

1. Create a product dataset.

2. Describe the composition of the Mixture composition document:

- Create a **substance dataset** for the micro-organism
- Set **Type of Substance** to '*micro-organism or toxin produced by a micro-organism*'
- Assign the **function** '*active substance*'.
- This enables completions of the relevant documents (e.g. biological properties).

3. Add the metabolite acting as the actual active substance:

- In the same mixture composition document, create a **substance dataset** for the *metabolite*
- Set **Type of Substance** to '**mono-constituent substance**'.
- Assign the **function** '*active substance (other not to be assessed)*'
- This dataset will follow the standard Table of Contents of a *chemical* active substance, allowing all relevant studies to be included here.

4. Link the metabolite in the metabolite section of the product dataset:

- In the [FLEXIBLE SUMMARY.Metabolites](#) document (Section 1.4.1 'Information on metabolites', product dataset), add the metabolite to the '**List of metabolites**'
- Select the checkbox indicating that "**the metabolite is claimed active metabolite**".

5. Clarify the actual active substance in the dossier:

- In the **Dossier header**, add a note in the "*Dossier submission remarks*" field explaining that the *metabolite* is the real active substance present in the product, even though technical constraints require it to be flagged as "*active substance (other, not to be assessed)*" throughout the dossier.

6. Confidentiality rules:

- The '*active substance (other, not to be assessed)*' (i.e., the metabolite) **must not** be marked confidential either at the reference substance level or in the mixture composition because it is the active substance under evaluation.

Note: Due to the complexity of this configuration, some **Validation Assistant errors** may occur. If this happens:

- export the Validation Assistant Excel report,
- provide the necessary justifications,
- and submit it to the RMS

Special cases: 3 – Submission of Dossiers for Products containing multiple microbial active substances (not consortia)

When a product contains **two or more microbial active substances** that are **not submitted as a consortium**, a **single dossier cannot be used** for all active substances. This is because:

- Each microbial active substance must be **evaluated and approved at strain level**;
- Certain documents in the product dataset **strain-specific**, such as the **Information on metabolites** document, which differs depending on the strain under evaluation.

Required approach

Create two (or more) separate IUCLID dossiers, one per micro-organism.

The **product dataset** may be duplicated and reused across dossiers, except for elements that are specific to an individual strain, such as the strain-dependent metabolites information.

Mixture composition requirements

The mixture composition document in each dossier must include **all microbial substances present in the formulation**, using the following logic:

- In the dossier for **microbial active A**:
Include in the mixture composition document:
 - "**Microbial active A**"
 - as a **substance** (with a complete dataset)
 - with function: '**active substance**'
 - "**Microbial active B**"
 - as a **reference substance** (no dataset needed)
 - with function: '**active substance other, not to be assessed**'
- In the dossier for **microbial active B**,
Include in the mixture composition document:
 - "**Microbial active A**"
 - as a **reference substance** (no dataset needed)
 - with function: '**active substance other, not to be assessed**'

- “**Microbial active B**”
 - as a **substance** (with a complete dataset)
 - with function: ‘**active substance**’

Add additional *reference substances* following the same principle for any further microbial strains included in the product.

Special cases: 4 – Submission of Dossiers for active substances composed of multiple microbial strains (consortium)

When a product contains **two or more microbial active substances** that must be evaluated as a **consortium**, a **single dossier** must be created, which consists of the combined consortium members.

Documentation requirements

In the product dataset, the document “**Microorganisms defining consortium**” (Section 1.4.4) must be fully completed. It should contain:

- Detailed information on the **consortium as a whole** (the active substance)
- Detailed information on **each individual consort**

Additional guidance is available in the dedicated instruction document for this section

Secondary metabolites in IUCLID

The ‘Guidance on the risk assessment of metabolites produced by micro-organisms used as plant protection active substances’ (SANCO/2020/12258 Rev. 1)¹³ should be followed to collect data on secondary metabolites before compiling the IUCLID dossier.

In the subsection ‘**Information on the production of relevant metabolites and toxins**’ of the ‘**Biological properties of the micro-organism**’ document (Section 2 – active substance dataset) the following information must be provided:

- A summary of the **main results** of the **broad-range literature search** performed in accordance with Stage 2 of the SANCO/2020/12258 Guidance, which aims at identifying ‘a first batch of information on the production and/or relevance of metabolites’.
The full search process must be documented in the **Literature Search** document (Section 3.5 ‘Literature data’ – Active substance dataset), ensuring that literature reference entities are created for all relevant and reliable studies and linked through the *FlexibleRecord.LiteratureSearch - link to Relevant Studies* field(s).
A link to the corresponding Literature Search(es) **must be included** in the **biological properties** document, in the ‘**Literature search**’ field.
- A **summary** and **conclusion of the applicant’s assessment** of **secondary metabolites**, including all information submitted in the dossier that is used to identify or exclude metabolites as being of concern. This includes **evidence demonstrating that certain metabolites are not produced**.
If **Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS)** or other **genetic sequencing data** are used as supporting evidence to demonstrate the absence of genes required for producing specific metabolite(s) of potential concern, this information must be reported in Section 1.3 “*Identity, taxonomy and phylogeny of the microorganism*”, within the ‘**Genomic Characterization Micro-organism**’ document document.
When WGS confirms that the gene(s) needed to produce the metabolite(s) are absent, this conclusion should be reflected here, and no targeted literature search for such metabolite(s) is required, as their non-production has been demonstrated.

Based on the outcome of the **assessment** carried out in accordance with the relevant guidance, secondary metabolites must be reported in IUCLID following the instructions applicable to each of the cases described below:

¹³ https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/ffdf09b5-77a5-45b5-95f9-b16272f7535a_en

1. Secondary metabolites that constitute the principal mode of action

If the **principal mode of action** of the active substance is based on the **presence of secondary metabolite(s)** in the formulated plant protection product (i.e. the metabolite/s is/are the actual active component(s) present in the product), this/these **metabolite/s** must be reported in the '**Mixture composition**' document (Section 1.4 – Product dataset).

All relevant studies must be provided in the corresponding **linked dataset**.

2. Metabolite(s) of concern (MoC)

If any metabolite is identified as **metabolite of concern** in line with the SANCO guidance, it must be reported in the '**List of metabolites**' Section of the FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.Metabolites document (Section **1.4.1 'Information on metabolites'**, product dataset).

Metabolites of concern must be **linked** as '**substances**', and any strain-specific **studies** or **experimental data** must be reported in the **linked metabolite dataset(s)**.

3. Metabolite(s) of potential concern (MoPC)

If any metabolite is identified as a **metabolite of potential concern** based on the literature search (as described in the SANCO guidance), the following rules apply:

a. When WGS excludes the presence of the gene(s) required for its production

If a **WGS analysis demonstrates** that the gene(s) responsible for producing the metabolite(s) are absent (see point 2.8 of Reg 283/2013), the MoPC should be listed in the **free-text field** of the subsection 'Information on the production of relevant metabolites and toxins' in the 'Biological properties of the micro-organism' document (Section 2 - active substance dataset).

The following template may be used:

"The following secondary metabolites, identified as potentially produced by the strain through a systematic review according to steps 3 and 5 of the guidance on secondary metabolites, were excluded from further assessment because WGS analysis demonstrated the absence of the gene(s) required for their production:

- SM 1
- SM 2
- SM 3
- ..."

b. When no WGS data are available, or WGS confirms potential production

If no WGS data are available **or** if WGS analysis indicates that the metabolite(s) may be produced, the metabolites must be reported in the '**List of metabolites**' section of the FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.Metabolites document (Section 1.4.1 'Information on metabolites', product dataset).

Metabolite(s) of potential concern should be linked as '**reference substances**', unless studies exist, in which case they should be linked as '**substances**' and the studies reported in the associated metabolite dataset.

4. Metabolites excluded from being MoC or MoPC

If a metabolite is **excluded** from being either a metabolite of concern or metabolite of potential concern according to the SANCO guidance, it should be listed in the in the **free-text field** of the subsection 'Information on the production of relevant metabolites and toxins' of the 'Biological properties of the micro-organism' document (Section 2 - active substance dataset).

Figure 1 – Diagram clarifying how to report information on secondary metabolites in IUCLID

In line with **Step 4** of the SANCO/2020/12258 Guidance, an **additional targeted literature search** must be conducted for:

- **each identified metabolite**, and
- any **hazardous/antimicrobial effects** associated with both **identified** and **unknown** metabolites resulting from earlier steps of the guidance.

The outcomes of these targeted literature searches for **metabolites of concern** and **metabolites of potential concern**, as listed in the **Flexible_Summary.Metabolites** document (Section 1.4.1 – Product dataset), must be reported in **two dedicated IUCLID summary documents** within the **Active Substance dataset**, that should be completed to **conclude on the assessment** of metabolites of (potential) concern:

- **Section 5.5.1** - Information and toxicity studies on metabolites ([Flexible_Summary.InformationToxicityMetabolites](#))
- **Section 8.8** - Information and ecotoxicity of metabolites ([FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.InformationEcotoxicityMetabolites](#))

Documentation of the literature search process

The entire targeted search process must be documented in the [Literature Search](#) document (Section 3.5 – *Literature data*, Active Substance dataset). This includes:

- creating **literature reference entities** for all relevant and reliable studies,
- linking these references within the **FlexibleRecord.LiteratureSearch** under the "*link to Relevant Studies*" fields.

A link to the corresponding Literature Search record(s) must also be provided in **Sections 5.5.1 and 8.8** of the Active Substance dataset under the field '[Link to Literature search](#)'.

Evaluation of the scientific literature

Within the same two Summary documents, the body of scientific evidence must be evaluated in accordance with **Step 5** of SANCO/2020/12258. This evaluation must determine whether the available information is sufficient to conclude on the assessment of metabolites of (potential) concern.

LITERATURE SEARCH(ES) ON SECONDARY METABOLITES

Figure 2- Reporting Literature searches on secondary metabolites in accordance with SANCO/2020/12258 rev.1 in IUCLID

To support efficiency and ensure harmonised assessment of secondary metabolites, it is **strongly recommended** to use the **overview table for secondary metabolites** provided in **Appendix I** of the document 'Explanatory notes for the implementation of the data requirements on micro-organisms and plant protection products containing them in the framework of Reg. (EC) No 1107/2009' (Available at: https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-10/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_imp-data-reg_micro-organisms-ppp_imp-reg-11072009.pdf).

APPENDIX I: OVERVIEW TABLE IN SUPPORT OF THE METABOLITE ASSESSMENT ACCORDING TO SANCO/2020/12258

Metabolite identifier ¹⁾	Stage 1		Stage 2				Outcome chemical analysis ⁴⁾	Stage 3		Stage 4		
	Active substance (Y/N)	Claimed active metabolite (Y/N/?)	Verification of MoPC-status					Relevant exposed group ⁵⁾	MoC (Y/N)	Ref. values (TOX) and endpoints (ECOTOX)	Exposure level	Unacceptable risk (Y/N)
			Toxic / antimicrobial effect observed, test species, and strain ²⁾	Potential relevance for micro-organism ³⁾	WGS-evidenced (Y/N)	MoPC (Y/N/?)						
Name, CAS, and/or IUPAC	Y/N	Y/N/?	Study 1: Effect / test species / strain Study 2, etc...	Metabolite / Effect	Y/N	Y/N/?	MPCA-AM: Y/N or max. PPP: Y/N or max. Induced: Y/N	TOX; TOX... / ECOTOX; ECOTOX.	Y/N	TOX; TOX... / ECOTOX; ECOTOX.	TOX; TOX... / ECOTOX; ECOTOX.	TOX; TOX... / ECOTOX; ECOTOX.
The row below presents the SANCO/2020/12258 step-numbers associated with the respective table column												
1, 3, 7, 10	1	1	3, 4, 6, 10, 12, 18	4, 6, 8, 10, 12	9, 10, 12	11	7, 12	13, 14	15	14, 17, 19	14, 16	20

¹⁾ Typically the name that is unambiguously used throughout the dossier to refer to the metabolite.

²⁾ For each relevant study (author and year are entered on the 'Study x'-position) the nature of the observed toxic / antimicrobial effect (? = data unavailable; null = no effect observed; ACU = acute toxicity; CYT = cytotoxicity; MUT = mutagenicity; GEN = genotoxicity; CAR = carcinogenicity; REP = reprotoxicity; NEU = neurotoxicity; AM = antimicrobial activity), the test species (or at least a detailed description of the exposed organism / material), and the name of the strain for which the effect has been observed (could be the micro-organism itself, a closely related strain, or both) is stated.

³⁾ In this column, the potential relevance of an identified metabolite and observed effect is made explicit for the micro-organism in particular. If the potential relevance is confirmed for the metabolite or the effect, 'Y' is entered on the respective position in the cell. In case non-relevance is established, an 'N' is added.

⁴⁾ This column states whether or not a metabolite has been detected in the MPCA-AM or PPP. Whenever relevant for the assessment, the 5-BA-established max. content (max.; average + 3xSD) for a metabolite is entered for the MPCA-AM (if available) and the PPP (either measured or derived).

⁵⁾ The following codes may be used to refer to any relevant exposed group. For TOX: OP (operators), WO (workers), BY (bystanders), RE (residents), and CO (consumers). For ECOTOX: MAM (mammals), BRD (birds), REP (reptiles), AMP (amphibians), FSH (fish), AQI (aquatic invertebrates), ALG (algae), AQM (aquatic macrophytes), BEE (bees), ART (non-target arthropods other than bees), MMO (non-target meso- and macro-organisms in soil), and PLA (non-target terrestrial plants). When proposed use does not lead to exposure of any of these groups, add '-'.

IMPORTANT NOTE: All metabolites listed in the **FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.Metabolites** document (Section 1.4.1 'Information on metabolites' in the product dataset), in accordance with the instructions provided above, **must be included** in the overview table.

Generation of the overview table

The **report generator** can **automatically** produce the overview table based on the data contained in the dossier. However, some fields may still require manual completion.

To generate the report:

1. Open the Report Generator.
2. Select "**Metabolites Overview Table**" from the available default reports.

Submission of the final overview table

After completing any missing information, the finalised overview table must be uploaded in the 'Reports and administrative information' section of the [Flexible Summary.SummaryEvaluation](#) document (**Section 10.2 'Other Reports'** - active substance dataset).

Components of an IUCLID dossier

Data is entered in IUCLID in **entities** and **documents**.

Entities are data elements that can be re-used and are usually managed in inventories, for example Substance entity, Legal Entity, Literature Reference entity.

Documents gather all relevant data fields for a specific type of information, for example Endpoint study record on acute oral toxicity or Flexible summary on Proposed residue definition.

ENDPOINT STUDY RECORDS

An Endpoint Study Record is a document (template) with predefined fields in which data is entered to describe a study carried out within the subject area defined by the section's title.

For data requirements where experimental data can be provided, the relevant endpoint study record should be completed for each study which has been notified and is used as evidence of safety in the submitted dossier.

The IUCLID format captures information complying with the reporting requirements of the OECD Test Guidelines, as well as other national/international methods used for chemical studies. The OECD Harmonised Templates for Reporting Chemical Test Summaries (OHTs) are standard data formats designed to be used in a wide range of regulatory contexts. More information on OHTs can be found on the [OECD website](#)¹⁴. ECHA has recently published a [Guidance and Standard Procedure for Drafting Robust Study Summaries](#) which can be consulted for generic guidance on the completion of OHTs.

The endpoint study records usually consist of the following data entry blocks: 'Administrative data', 'Data source', 'Materials and methods', 'Test material', and 'Results and discussion'. There are also sections for any 'Overall remarks, attachments' and the 'Applicant's summary and conclusion'.

Important note: The main information requested in the data entry boxes of the endpoint study record document (e.g. materials and methods, results and discussion) must always be filled in, also for endpoints which are considered supportive by the applicant and it are based on literature data.

ENDPOINT STUDY SUMMARIES

Endpoint summaries are found in the same Section as the endpoint study records and are used to provide a conclusion from the available studies.

The link/s for the endpoint studies considered to be relevant and reliable should be added in the Endpoint summary. When linking endpoint study records with multiple results make sure to check the relevant checkboxes to identify the **KEY RESULTS**. Provide the scientific conclusion for the endpoint/s reported in the endpoint study records. Information provided in this document will be used to generate lists of endpoints with Report Generator.

The final values for assessment must be provided under the section "Key value for assessment" in all summaries.

¹⁴ <https://www.oecd.org/ehs/templates/>

Note: None of the fields in ENDPOINT SUMMARIES are subject to the UNLESS_CONF flags, as they are not expected to contain confidential business information ('CBI'). These documents should be completed in a clear and transparent manner as they will be published without redaction as part of the Public Consultation Process foreseen in the Transparency Regulation.

FLEXIBLE/FIXED RECORDS

Similarly to endpoint study records or to endpoint summaries, this name is used for documents in IUCLID where the information stored in the record is not a study and it is not based on an OHT.

- A fixed record is created in a section where there can be only one record.
- A flexible record is created in a section where there can be more than one record.

Attachments

Applicants should provide the following as attachments:

- full study reports (in line with the provisions of the Transparency regulation)
- or
- other supporting material (e.g label of packaging) in case they cannot be entered in a specific IUCLID document

Full study reports (including publications and (Q)SAR, QMRF or QPRF reporting forms) must be uploaded as attachments **ONLY to the relevant literature reference entities**. The "Attachments" field of the endpoint study records (when present) **should be not used** to attach the full study reports and duplication of attachments should be avoided. The public version of any attachment **should not be in word/rtf format**, but rather in pdf format.

Note: In case a study report is revised during the dossier life-cycle, do not provide additional attachments – this not only contributes to unnecessarily increasing the size of the dossier but might also create confusion on versioning of the files. Remove the obsolete files and replace them with a newer version in which, ideally, the changes are highlighted in order to facilitate the assessors' work.

The literature reference entity allows different types of attachments to be uploaded. Only one attachment with the Attachment type = 'full study report' is permitted.

Other **supporting material** (e.g. excel templates, kinetic fitting reports, MSS/DER composers xml files) can also be added as attachments completing the 'Attachment type' to classify the material.

For attachments other than the full study report, indications are provided below.

Table of contents	Attachment
10.2 Other Reports – active substance dataset	The overview table for secondary metabolites , as provided in Appendix I of the ' Explanatory notes for the implementation of the data requirements on micro-organisms and plant protection products containing them in the framework of Reg. (EC) No 1107/2009 ', must be uploaded in the 'Reports and administrative information' Section of the Flexible_Summary.SummaryEvaluation document. Note: The report generator can automatically create this overview table using the information contained in the dossier; however, certain fields may still require manual completion. To generate the report, select ' Metabolites Overview Table ' from the list of available default reports.
1.5.1 Production and quality control – active substance dataset 1.6 Method of production of the preparation and quality control – product dataset	Document J (see dedicated paragraph below) Picture of the manufacturing process/flow chart for the active substance and the plant protection product should be added in the "Attached background material" section in 1.5.1 - active substance dataset and 1.6 – PPP dataset, respectively.

1.7 Packaging, compatibility of the preparation with proposed packaging materials – product dataset	Picture of label of packaging.
12. Summary and evaluation – product dataset	Safety data sheets for the formulants (attached to “Other references” field) Administrative documents such as cover letters (attached to the “Reports and administrative information” field). <i>Important note:</i> Such letters do not need to be provided via email or post, but solely attached in the respective IUCLID section.

DOCUMENT J

Doc J can be uploaded in the FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Manufacturer_EU_PPP:

- Doc J for plant protection product: in ‘1.6 Method of production of the preparation and quality control’ – Product dataset
- Doc J for active substance: in ‘1.5.1 Production and quality control’ – active substance dataset

Please note that the information contained in doc J must also be provided in the correct sections of the IUCLID documents. To the extent information typically provided via Document J can already be provided in and flagged confidential via relevant IUCLID records/summaries, applicants should abstain from including the same information in Document J with a view to avoiding duplication of information.

ATTACHMENT SIZE

Attachments greater than 100MB will cause issues upon dossier submission. In case of large attachments please follow the instructions below. Reducing the size of attachments in IUCLID documents will result in better performance for dossier processing steps and it is therefore always recommended as best practice.

1. Generate the attachment report for the dossier / dataset to be submitted to get an overview of all the attachments. The most detailed report is shown below and the .ftl files can be downloaded from the IUCLID 6 website. Similar reports for datasets are also available. These attachment reports generate a .csv file (that can be opened in Excel) and list all attachments with their size and type.
2. Identify all the PDF attachments that have an excessive size (e.g. >100MB)
 - a. Download the large PDF attachments and use Adobe features to reduce the PDF file size: In the past this feature was called “Reduce File Size” in Adobe Acrobat Pro
 - b. In latest version of Adobe Acrobat Pro you can find the following menu item: “Compress File”

3. Upload smaller version of the PDF as attachment to the dataset.

This approach can be applied to PDF attachments only, though similar size reduction solution can be applied for other attachment types as well: e.g. extremely large images (with some loss in resolution quality).

When reduction of the size of the attachments is not possible, documents can exceptionally be split. In such cases, please pay special attention in naming the files.

Notification of Studies (NoS)

In accordance with Art. 32(b) of Regulation (EU) 2019/1381, “business operators must, without delay, notify the Authority of the title and the scope of any study commissioned or carried out by them to support an application or a notification, as well as the laboratory or testing facility carrying out that study, and its starting and planned completion dates.

Laboratories and other testing facilities located in the Union shall also, without delay, notify the Authority of the title and the scope of any study commissioned by business operators and carried out by such laboratories or other testing facilities to support an application or a notification, its starting and planned completion dates, as well as the name of the business operator who commissioned such a study”.

Pursuant to the [EFSA Practical Arrangements on pre-submission phase and public consultation](#) a justification must always be provided in the dossier header of each application in IUCLID for:

- studies notified but not submitted in the application;
- studies notified with delay, i.e., after the study starting date;
- studies notified and later withdrawn;
- studies commissioned or carried out after 27 March 2021, not notified but submitted in the application

IUCLID Report Generator allows applicants and Evaluators to generate a NoS extraction report listing all the studies submitted in the application that were notified, justified and without notification.

Further information on Notification of Studies are available in the User Guide on Notification of studies at the following link: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-07/user-guide-notification-of-studies.pdf>

Validation Assistant

Before submitting a dossier, it is important to run the validation assistant to check the dossier is technically complete. Authorities can run the validation assistant before declaring a dossier admissible. As the rules applied are dependent on the information included in the Dossier Header, make sure this is completed correctly. If the report shows a **business rule failure** (anything starting with BR e.g. BR_PPP_033) this will prevent the applicant from successfully submitting the dossier. If the report shows a **validation warning** (anything starting with QLT e.g. QLT_PPP_001) the applicant will be able to submit the dossier but may encounter problems during the admissibility check.

It is important to resolve all validation assistant warnings, since this will support the ‘admissibility check’ of the RMS. If Applicants cannot resolve all the warnings re-run validation assistant, it is recommended to download the “Validation assistant Report” in excel format (this excel file replaces document O) and include in this file the justification for not resolving the warning and provide this directly to the RMS. Note that missing studies for a specific data requirement/endpoint should be justified using the data waiver section in the relevant endpoint study record.

In addition to the automated checks, it is important to make sure all the IUCLID documents are well completed and that all the relevant scientific data is provided.

Information on the applicable validation rules is available here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5141356>

Watch the video on validation assistant:
<https://zenodo.org/record/6603483#.YpoTY6hBxD9>

Common mistakes training **5. Validation rules:**
https://zenodo.org/record/6603483#.Y1_cZHbMKUm

Compare tool

The Compare tool can be used for comparing different versions of a dossier and highlights the differences between the latest submission and any previous versions. It can be used by Applicants before re-submitting a dossier to check which changes were made but also by Evaluators who receive re-submitted dossiers.

The compare tool can be accessed from the Dossier actions menu (three dots next to the Validation button)

A window will open showing all related dossiers. Select the version of the dossier you want to compare with the current version. An .HTML file is downloaded, open this in a browser application.

Select dossier to compare

🔍 Type at least 3 characters

6 results found | Show only dossiers of MO testing new DR

Show results 25 ▾

MicroorganismWithErrors		14/04/2023 14:59		
Subject name	MO testing new DR	Submission type	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	Dossier UUID 263fce4f-6266-485e-8dbe-8e61c9ac7368

MicroorganismWithErrors		14/04/2023 14:56		
Subject name	MO testing new DR	Submission type	EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)	Dossier UUID 703f409f-3589-4722-9a30-49ab15746d6b

If nothing has changed for a specific section/document in a dossier the report indicates 'identical'

7.1.4.2 - Experimental exposure data water		
● ExpressionInAFreshwaterEnvironment: Experimental exposure data water.001	Identical	● ExpressionInAFreshwaterEnvironment: Experimental exposure data water.001

If there is a difference in a section/document in the dossier the report indicates 'different'

9.1 - Predicted concentrations in the environment		
● EstConcOtherRoutes: Predicted concentrations in the environment.001	Different	● EstConcOtherRoutes: Predicted concentrations in the environment.001 (content reference: <Ref3>)

Clicking on the 'different' link will provide more information on the nature of the changes in the dossier when compared with the selected comparator.

Field	Source	Target
Estimation of concentrations from other routes of exposure > Description of key information	default Predicted concentrations in the environment	
PEC other routes Estimation of concentrations from other routes of exposure > PEC from other routes of exposure > PEC other routes	PEC other routes Use description <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● GAP: Data on application (GAP).001 Parent / metabolite parent Substance Microorganism a.s. Genus species Route of exposure default Freshwater Method of calculation default OECD Calculation method	

In this case a Predicted concentrations document has been completed in the newer dossier. Using compare, deletions can also be checked, in this case the target column would be completed and the source would not.

Watch these Videos on how to use the compare tool:

- Comparison of **Dossiers**: SPC Comparison tool demonstration - YouTube
- Comparison of **Documents**: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cUy6ahta3dE>

Report Generator

IUCLID provides a feature called "[Report Generator](#)". This feature allows to extract data from single IUCLID dossiers or datasets and generate a readable, user-friendly, customised report of IUCLID information in different output formats, for example, RTF, PDF, CSV and HTML.

Where available, Report generator should be used to compile the reported information into the format required for evaluation.

Many reports are ready to use and made available by default inside IUCLID 6. Templates to create PPP-specific reports are published in Zenodo Knowledge Junction and new versions, including changes and bug fixes, are published regularly and included in the list of "Default IUCLID reports" at each IUCLID release. These templates can also be uploaded in Report Manager as indicated in [the IUCLID user manual](#). After downloading they will appear under the section "Uploaded IUCLID reports" of Report Generator.

The list of available reports for PPP can be found on the Applicants toolkit page: [Toolkit | EFSA \(europa.eu\)](#)

Note: report generator and other tasks are now run as 'Background tasks' which can be accessed from the IUCLID dashboard.

Mapping of Appendices of EFSA administrative guidance on submission of dossiers and assessment reports¹⁵ to IUCLID documents

Appendix old name	New name, link and mapping
Appendices C1-C4	Dismissed. Public consultations are managed through the OpenEFSA platform
Appendix D Template for the overview table for analytical methods used for risk assessment	The overview table for analytical methods should be included in the field 'Description of key information' of the ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.AnalyticalMethods document (Section 5 - Product dataset; Section 4 - active substance dataset) based on Template 4.1 - Template for the overview table for analytical methods for risk assessment (available in zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4556992)
Appendix I Template for presentation of assessment of endocrine disrupting properties	Dismissed / Not relevant for microbial pesticide active substance
Appendix J Template for presentation the assessment for the equivalence of batches	The Template 1.1 for the assessment of batch equivalence, available on the EFSA knowledge Junction , replaces the Appendix J of the former EFSA administrative guidance (EFSA, 2019). The completed template should be included in the Document J , which can be uploaded in the "Production and quality control" document (Sections: 1.5.1 – Active substance dataset; 1.6 – product dataset).

¹⁵ EFSA, 2019. Administrative guidance on submission of dossiers and assessment reports for the peer-review of pesticide active substances. <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1612>

In addition, the new [Analytical profile of batches – Flexible Summary](#) document must also be used and completed (Section 1.4.3 – Active substance dataset).

Joint Submission and sharing of studies

In accordance with Art. 5(2) of Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 2020/1740, “where there is more than one applicant requesting the renewal of the approval of the same active substance, those applicants shall take all reasonable steps to submit their dossiers jointly.” In light of the above, companies submitting a renewal of approval of the same substance, should reach an agreement on sharing studies and data within a Joint Submission. There are **different ways of building a joint Submission in IUCLID**:

1. **Standar joint submission**
2. **Individual submission with inherited templates**
3. **Individual submission including datasets from different data owners**

1. STANDARD JOINT SUBMISSION

A Lead applicant must be identified and is expected to submit a renewal dossier which includes joint information submitted by the lead on behalf of all the members including all studies to be evaluated and presented in (robust) study summaries. The lead applicant would also add his own confidential information in the main lead dossier. Any data which are not to be shared in full with other members of the joint submission can be included in the supplementary renewal dossiers submitted by each member. **This type of submission can be created and submitted with/without the support of a third party consultant.**

Lead and member dossiers should not contain and/or refer to the same study reports since it is sufficient for the data to be provided once¹⁶. All members of a joint submission must provide the same unique UUID in the “European Joint submission number” field of the dossier header. All members of a joint submission must use the same reference substance entity for the active substance in all submitted dossiers.

The role within the Joint submission is selected using the Joint submission role field in the Dossier Header. There can only be one Lead (which is subject to the full validation rule package) and any applicant who contributes to the joint submission task force and whose name should appear on OpenEFSA associated to the submission MUST submit a member dossier in order to be listed (note that a Member dossier does not need to be complete from a validation perspective).

N.B. This is the recommended way to jointly submit data.

2. INDIVIDUAL SUBMISSION WITH INHERITED TEMPLATES

It is possible to submit one dossier which has a main applicant (the equivalent to a Lead in scenario 1 above) and additional data from other companies which are “annexed” to the dossier by means of Inherited templates.

Each template has an own legal entity (which will not be listed on OpenEFSA as an applicant) and can be added to the active substance/product dataset as needed to include the data provided by a specific legal entity. **Data segregation among applicants is guaranteed provided that a third party is involved and manages the submission as a whole.** To include a template, use the inherited templates link at the end of the dataset. More information can be found in the [IUCLID User Manual Page Section 7 page 96](#).

¹⁶ In case the same study report is linked in an IUCLID record/summary of two or member dossiers forming part of the same joint submission, the confidentiality justification as well as the earmarks in the confidential version of the study report and the blackening in the public version of the study report must be consistent in the member dossiers concerned.

▼ Inherited templates

 Renewal impurity 222196

3. INDIVIDUAL SUBMISSION INCLUDING DATASETS FROM DIFFERENT DATA OWNERS

If one company owns the data for the active substance (typically considered to be the applicant) and different company/ies own the data for the product/s it is important that the correct legal entity is provided in the substance (SUBSTANCE.OwnerLegalEntity) and mixture datasets (MIXTURE.OwnerLegalEntity).

This approach can also be applied to metabolite and other representative product datasets. The 'Third party' information in all datasets must be completed with the legal entity of the consultant preparing the dossier, **the use of a consultant is mandatory in order to maintain data segregation between data owners.**

In this case the data from different legal entities must be submitted in one dossier and the consultant can use IUCLID advanced export options to provide separate versions of the dossier to the members of this 'joint submission' once the dossier has been submitted to EFSA Agency IUCLID.

LETTER OF ACCESS

In relation to sharing of studies among companies which own separate data and which give data citation rights (Letter of Access) to each other for active renewal purposes, the approach would be as follows.

To indicate that a Company has a letter of access, follow these instructions in relation to the "Data Source (Literature Reference)" compilation:

- In the data access field: indicate that data submitter has a letter of access
- In the data protection claimed field: indicate data protection was claimed by the data owner
- In the Attached document field: upload the letter of access in the literature reference entity and set type to 'Letter of access' (if you wish to provide the LoA)

N.B. In order to comply with the obligations on proactive transparency and public consultation on the data foreseen by the Transparency Regulation, providing a Letter of Access to the data is not sufficient to fulfil the data requirements since all studies supporting the approval/renewal must be provided. Applicants must ensure that the full text of each test/study report, together with the sanitised version if the full text version contains confidential material is either included in their dossier or provided by the data owner in a linked submission (or in the applicant's submission by means of inherited templates).

An alternative option for managing data in this situation is to use the **Contributor role** in IUCLID. If the submission is already a joint submission, the data can be submitted in a separate dossier by selecting "Contributor" from the Joint submission role field in the dossier header and otherwise following the indications provided under scenario 1 for joint submissions. The owner legal entity will be published on OpenEFSA but not listed as an applicant. This can also be done in support of an individual submission by flagging it as a joint submission which will have one dossier alongside one or more contributors.

The Submission Portal

When preparing a dossier for submission please ensure that your dossier is compliant with the published submission portal rules: European Food Safety Authority. (2021). IUCLID submission rules for PPP dossiers (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5141356>

Ensure the correct legal entities are assigned in the datasets and in the dossier header.

During the submission process the DOSSIER.EU_PPP_ACTIVE_SUBSTANCE_FOR_MIXTURES.subject.legal_entity is checked. The owner of the dossier or the lead applicant in the case of a taskforce must be indicated in the **Mixture document**. If a third-party consultant has prepared the dossier the legal entity of the consultant must also be indicated (see below).

UUID: 3541e6f9-4f20-4e61-9957-501c4deab044

Mixture/Product name*
TOPIK_ACR

Public name
Product A

Legal entity owner*
🇮🇹 Producer of plant protection product | Parma | Italy

Third party
🇮🇹 Consultant ABC | Roma | Italy | 98645235438 465985

During the processing of dossier submissions in the portal the information on the active substance is taken from the MIXTURE.composition document. It is essential this is filled in before you submit your first dossier. For every submission there is a check that the Legal Entity and the Active Substance are the same for a given European Reference Number.

Ensure that the submitter has the role of Submission Portal Manager: If the submitter is a user of the Legal Entity owner organisation, ask the Legal Entity Manager to give the user the Submission Portal Manager role.

Username	Name	Email	User roles
EFSA_DGSANTE	EFSA Pilot DG SANTE	iuclid6@echa.europa.eu	IUCLID Beta Full Access Submission Portal Manager

If the submitter is a third-party consultant, then they need to ask the Legal Entity Manager of the owner/lead applicant organisation to add the submitter as a foreign user with the role Submission Portal Manager

Please see this short explanatory video for more information on foreign users:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YH5edrjBkxI&list=PLGDvgn1aAEEbL7dMwwWAjoAiK-DgoJmZrY&index=9>

If the dossier is being prepared by an organisation other than the Legal entity owner the recommended approach is that the Legal entity owner exports their legal entity details and provides them to the organisation authoring the dossier. This legal entity information can be exported from within ECHA's Identity Management solution (IDM) and not from within IUCLID. Exporting from IDM ensures alignment with Legal Entity in ECHA IDM when the dossier is submitted.

Note that by submitting the dossier as a foreign user, this person only has access to the submission report in the submission portal and would therefore see the substance name and other basic information. There is no follow-up communication within IUCLID/the submission portal as all subsequent steps are managed by email using the main contact person(s) for the dossier i.e. the third-party consultant. If the submitter should not see equivalent details for other submissions, the Restricted (Submission Portal) role should be applied (see page 9 of the ECHA accounts Manual for Industry Users).

Exporting the Legal Entity: To view the details, please visit: <https://ulem.echa.europa.eu/ui/dashboard>. Log in with a user account that has the Legal Entity Manager role assigned. Navigate to the Legal Entities tab (on the left) and from the updated central page select the legal entity of the dossier. From the page, find the Export button to export the legal entity details.

The Legal Entity information will be exported as a IUCLID .i6z file which you can then import in IUCLID.

Importing the Legal Entity in IUCLID: The organisation authoring the dossier should add this legal entity to their Legal Entity inventory and use this legal entity in the dossier. The easiest way to import the legal entity details is from the IUCLID dashboard landing page and to import it directly¹⁷, i.e. either by dragging the file onto the import box or by browsing for it.

If the Legal entity owner is not in the dossier header, you will need to recreate the dossier and ensure the 'Include legal entity' is checked from the advanced settings of the 'Create dossier' function.

The advanced settings can be accessed from the 'three dots' button.

Proceed to submission: If you are using the IUCLID 6 ECHA Cloud services to author the dossier, simply use 'Create Dossier' and 'Proceed to submission' function. Then follow the submission portal steps listed below

¹⁷ It can also be imported through the Configuration management page () and using the Legal Entity section of Inventory Manager

Create dossier ×

 Dossier creation was completed successfully.

Open dossier

Proceed to submission

Export dossier: For Client or Server versions of IUCLID the dossier should be exported as an **i6z file** (the ZIP format for IUCLID). The **export** is accessed from the top level of the application window.

For the first submission of a dossier the standard '**Export**' function should be used.

Note: Exporting and importing large dossiers e.g. larger than 3GB, can result in errors during the dossier download and upload processes. We advise companies to consider requesting their IT team to set up the 'IUCLID Drive' feature in their IUCLID instance as this feature improves the reliability of file transfers therefore eliminating potential sources of issues. See IUCLID server manual for further details (https://iuclid6.echa.europa.eu/documents/1387205/1506740/installation_manual_server_en.pdf).

The submission portal: Log in to the submission portal and upload the i6z file. Do not forget to switch legal entity if you are submitting for another organisation. Please note the speed of your submission will be dependent on the size of your dossier and the upload speed of your internet connection. It is important that you check the submission report for your dossier submission. If the Submission event in the report shows "Dossier received by EFSA" then your submission is complete. If the Submission event is 'Dossier failed validation checks' your dossier has been rejected. In this case, 'View Validation report' to identify the issues with your submission, update the dossier and repeat the submission process.

Once a valid submission is received EFSA, RMS and EC are informed via an automated e-mail. Additional confirmation of IUCLID submissions via email or letter is NOT necessary unless specifically requested to do so within a certain process. Any cover letters should be added in the 'Summary and Evaluation' section. Dossier submissions via any route other than the Submission Portal will not be accepted for evaluation.

Submit a IUCLID dossier
Search for EFSA Applications
Create a dossier in IUCLID Cloud

Please upload your dossier for submission. Only i6z files are permitted for upload.
● Note that currently only **PCN, SCIP and PPP dossiers** can be submitted.

Drop file to upload or Browse

Submission events

04/01/2022 16:02 Dossier submitted
04/01/2022 16:02 Dossier passed validation checks
04/01/2022 16:02 Dossier received by EFSA

Export as a light dossier (preferred option for resubmissions): This is the preferred option in case of a resubmission since the file that is generated is always smaller than the full dossier. A light dossier includes the full IUCLID dossier with the exception of the attachments that had been provided previously (in the base dossier) and have not been modified.

The screenshot shows a dropdown menu with the following options: Export, Export annotations, Export as light dossier (highlighted with a red arrow), Export as editable dataset, Create component PDF/RTF, Compare, Generate report, and Dissemination preview. In the background, a table titled 'Select the base dossier' shows one item found:

1	29/01/2021 17:18
Subject name	M1
Submission type	EU PPP Active substance application (product)
Dossier UUID	4e4501e9-48d3-4fe4-b4c2-5c33421c491b

This option can also be used to sequentially load a large dossier if issues importing a dossier into the submission portal are encountered. The first submission should include as a minimum the Mixture dataset, a completed mixture composition dataset including the active substance component with a completed substance and reference substance document. Once this dossier has 'Dossier received by EFSA' status additional datasets (e.g. metabolites, other representative formulations) can be linked to the main Mixture dataset and exported as 'light dossier' until the full dossier has been submitted.

Resubmission Of Applications

For information regarding **re-submissions of the IUCLID dossiers** please consult the EFSA "Administrative guidance on submission of dossiers and assessment reports for the peer-review of pesticide active substances and on the MRL application procedure".

Dossier publication

Information not meant to be published, e.g. names of authors of unpublished studies, along with information considered confidential, is removed from the dossier, as defined in the published filter rules. The public version of the dossier is then made available via the OpenEFSA Portal (<https://open.efsa.europa.eu/>).

Prior to submitting a dossier, the 'View report and create filtered dossier' function under 'Dissemination Preview' can be used to create a filtered dossier.

Although a visual check of the filtered dossier can be useful to check how the published dossier will look, it is recommended to also use the dissemination preview excel file to filter for sensitive documents and check the publication status of each completed field in that document. All fields with the outcome = Published will be visible in the dossier available on the OpenEFSA portal. Dossier filtering is an automated process.

Pay attention to remark fields in open and closed picklists as currently they are not published if a corresponding confidentiality flag has been set in the relevant IUCLID record/summary.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	entity	sectionName	documentName	field	outcome	sourceDocumentKey	referencedDocumentKey	path
2	Dossier		Efsa basic	EU PPP Basic substance	Not published	de84bbd8-7acf-42db-b09a-c3735c1f94b5/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	DOSSIER/EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE_NA	
3	Dossier		Efsa basic	EU PPP Basic substance	Not published	de84bbd8-7acf-42db-b09a-c3735c1f94b5/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	DOSSIER/EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE_LEX	
4	Dossier		Efsa basic	EU PPP Basic substance	Not published	de84bbd8-7acf-42db-b09a-c3735c1f94b5/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	DOSSIER/EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE_RE	
5	Dossier		Efsa basic	EU PPP Basic substance / Basic substance a	Published	de84bbd8-7acf-42db-b09a-c3735c1f94b5/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	DOSSIER/EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE_Ba	
6	Dossier		Efsa basic	EU PPP Basic substance / Basic substance a	Published	de84bbd8-7acf-42db-b09a-c3735c1f94b5/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	DOSSIER/EU_PPP_BASIC_SUBSTANCE_Ba	
7	Mixture/Product	1 Identity and applicant	efsa test basic 1	Mixture / Mixture/Product name	Published	69295a37-e087-4416-aa8e-8f840b506c95/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	MIXTURE.MixtureName	
8	Mixture/Product	1 Identity and applicant	efsa test basic 1	Mixture / Legal entity owner	Published	69295a37-e087-4416-aa8e-8f840b506c95/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	MIXTURE.OwnerLegalEntity	
9	Mixture/Product	1 Identity and applicant	efsa test basic 1	Mixture / Contact persons / 1	Not published	69295a37-e087-4416-aa8e-8f840b506c95/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	MIXTURE.ContactPersons[0]	
10	Mixture/Product	1 Identity and applicant	efsa test basic 1	Mixture / Contact persons / 2	Not published	69295a37-e087-4416-aa8e-8f840b506c95/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	MIXTURE.ContactPersons[1]	
11	Mixture/Product	1 Identity and applicant	efsa test basic 1	Mixture / Role in the supply chain / Manufact	Published	69295a37-e087-4416-aa8e-8f840b506c95/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	MIXTURE.RoleInSupplyChain.Manufact	
12	Flexible Record	2 Preparation of the substance for use	Mixture composition.001	Composition (mixture) / Components / 1 / Ne	Published	3fe10c84-2eb8-4c8c-961c-8340efb6-efea-4086-9c06-4667854	FLEXIBLE_RECORD/MixtureComposition	
13	Flexible Record	2 Preparation of the substance for use	Mixture composition.001	Composition (mixture) / Components / 1 / Fu	Published	3fe10c84-2eb8-4c8c-961c-dabd08fbd14/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	FLEXIBLE_RECORD/MixtureComposition	
14	Flexible Record	2 Preparation of the substance for use	Mixture composition.001	Composition (mixture) / Components / 1 / Ty	Published	3fe10c84-2eb8-4c8c-961c-dabd08fbd14/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	FLEXIBLE_RECORD/MixtureComposition	
15	Flexible Record	2 Preparation of the substance for use	Mixture composition.001	Composition (mixture) / Components / 2 / Ne	Published	3fe10c84-2eb8-4c8c-961c-4094f25d-7eb4-412d-af25-767d92b5	FLEXIBLE_RECORD/MixtureComposition	
16	Flexible Record	2 Preparation of the substance for use	Mixture composition.001	Composition (mixture) / Components / 2 / Fu	Published	3fe10c84-2eb8-4c8c-961c-dabd08fbd14/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	FLEXIBLE_RECORD/MixtureComposition	
17	Flexible Summary	4 Application template, studies, bibliograp	Application template, studies, bibliography and confidentiality requests.001	Not published	523fb0f-59c3-438e-bfce-b8f632da782b/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY/SummaryEvaluat		
18	Legal entity	Breaking Bad	Legal entity / General information / Legal ent	Published	ECHA-fc3c9382-ed4a-4990-bdf2-70041a08d423/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	LEGAL_ENTITY.GeneralInfo.LegalEntityN		
19	Legal entity	Breaking Bad	Legal entity / General information / Address	Published	ECHA-fc3c9382-ed4a-4990-bdf2-70041a08d423/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	LEGAL_ENTITY.GeneralInfo.ContactAddr		
20	Legal entity	Breaking Bad	Legal entity / General information / Address	Published	ECHA-fc3c9382-ed4a-4990-bdf2-70041a08d423/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	LEGAL_ENTITY.GeneralInfo.ContactAddr		
21	Legal entity	Breaking Bad	Legal entity / General information / Address	Published	ECHA-fc3c9382-ed4a-4990-bdf2-70041a08d423/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	LEGAL_ENTITY.GeneralInfo.ContactAddr		
22	Legal entity	Breaking Bad	Legal entity / General information / Address	Published	ECHA-fc3c9382-ed4a-4990-bdf2-70041a08d423/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	LEGAL_ENTITY.GeneralInfo.ContactAddr		
23	Legal entity	Breaking Bad	Legal entity / General information / Address	Published	ECHA-fc3c9382-ed4a-4990-bdf2-70041a08d423/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	LEGAL_ENTITY.GeneralInfo.ContactAddr		
24	Legal entity	Breaking Bad	Legal entity / General information / Address	Published	ECHA-fc3c9382-ed4a-4990-bdf2-70041a08d423/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	LEGAL_ENTITY.GeneralInfo.ContactAddr		
25	Reference substance	Water	Reference substance / Reference substance r	Published	8340efb6-efea-4086-9c06-4667854269b/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE.ReferenceSubst		
26	Reference substance	Water	Reference substance / IUPAC name	Published	8340efb6-efea-4086-9c06-4667854269b/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE.IupacName		
27	Reference substance	Water	Reference substance / Inventory / CAS numbe	Published	8340efb6-efea-4086-9c06-4667854269b/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE.Inventory.CASN		
28	Reference substance	Bis(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethyl) et	Reference substance / Reference substance r	Published	4094f25d-7eb4-412d-af25-767d92b5cee0/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE.ReferenceSubst		
29	Reference substance	Bis(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethyl) et	Reference substance / IUPAC name	Published	4094f25d-7eb4-412d-af25-767d92b5cee0/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE.IupacName		
30	Reference substance	Bis(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethyl) et	Reference substance / Inventory / Inventory	Published	4094f25d-7eb4-412d-af25-767d92b5cee0/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE.Inventory.Inven		
31	Reference substance	Bis(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethyl) et	Reference substance / Inventory / CAS numbe	Published	4094f25d-7eb4-412d-af25-767d92b5cee0/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE.Inventory.CASN		
32	Contact	kon; Breaking Bad		Not published	d4e869be-babf-45dd-bba7-4b2a074a6eb2/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	CONTACT		
33	Contact	tds; Breaking Bad		Not published	dbc9040f-57c4-471d-af76-1760772e417f/de84bbd8-7acf-42db	CONTACT		

Note: The Dissemination preview works on **dossiers** and **not datasets**.

If report generator is being used to prepare reports for inclusion in the dossier, a sanitised version of the report can be created by running report generator on the filtered dossier.

Validation rules

IUCLID submission rules for PPP dossiers currently applicable in the Submission portal are available in a separate document at the following link: [IUCLID Validation Assistant rules for PPP dossiers](#)

Filtering rules

IUCLID filtering rules for PPP dossiers currently applicable are available in a separate document at the following link: [IUCLID for PPP Filter rules | Zenodo](#)

Confidentiality of dossiers submitted via IUCLID

For guidelines on requesting confidentiality in IUCLID dossiers, please refer to the "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available on the EFSA toolkit page: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/applications/toolkit>.

EU PPP ACTIVE SUBSTANCE APPLICATION

DOSSIER HEADER

The dossier header contains administrative data and information about the type and purpose of the application. Information in the dossier header is used by IUCLID tools to process the dossier, for example different validation assistant scenarios could be applied depending on the selection of the purpose of the application. This information is also used in automated e-mail notifications.

Please note that all information in the dossier header is published by default. Confidential data should be provided elsewhere in the dossier as appropriate.

DOSSIER.EU_PPP_MICROORGANISMS_FOR_MIXTURES		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Dossier template		Block
Dossier name (given by user)	Report short name for the dossier (this should be maintained in all versions). Refer to the active substance name in the text (e.g. "Active substance name_Renewal" or "Active substance name_New active substance authorization"). Avoid additional information such as Company codes, company name and dossier versioning.	Text
Dossier subject		Block
Submitting legal entity	Select submitting legal entity	Link to entity
Dossier submission remark		Text
Active substance approval		Block
European reference number	The European Reference Number (ERN) is the unique identifier used for linking all versions of a dossier submitted under a regulatory action. It can be generated within the IUCLID application and must NEVER be changed with subsequent submissions unless specifically requested to do so by EFSA.	Text
Purpose of the application	Only one context can be listed as the purpose of the application. If 'Amendment of the approval conditions for an active substance' is selected, provide the justification for an amendment of the approval conditions for an active substance in the remarks.	Multi-Picklist
Confirmatory information	Check this box if the submission relates to the 'submission of further confirmatory information to Member States, the Commission and the European Food Safety Authority where new requirements are established during the evaluation process or as a result of new scientific and technical knowledge.	Check box

European joint submission number	Contains the unique identifier which links all dossiers submitted for renewal of the same active substance within a joint submission. The lead applicant should generate a UUID and this number should be included in the same field in the dossier headers of the additional identity dossiers submitted by members of the task force.	Text
Joint application	If the purpose of the application is 'renewal of an active substance for use in plant protection products' then whether the submission is a 'Joint application' must be indicated.	Picklist with remarks
Role in the Joint Submission	If the submitter is the lead applicant and the dossier is the main dossier of the joint submission select 'Lead applicant'. If the dossier is submitted by the member applicant and is not the main dossier of the joint submission select 'Member applicant'. If the aim of the dossier is to provide supplementary data for the dossier (e.g. by means of a Letter of Access) but the submitter is neither the lead applicant nor a member, select 'Contributor'.	Picklist with remarks
Rapporteur Member State (RMS)	Indicate the Member State assessing the dossier.	Picklist with remarks
Competent authority	Provide the name of the competent authority providing the assessment report.	Text
Co-RMS	Indicate the Member State(s) acting as the co-rapporteur.	Multi-select list
Specific submissions		Block
EFSA Question number	If the dossier is a re-submission, provide the assigned EFSA question number in EFSA-Q-YYYY-NNNNN format	Text
The submission is an update	Indicate whether the submission is an update by selecting Yes or No	List
Official request		Block of fields (repeatable)
Requester	Indicate which organisation has requested the resubmission	Picklist with remarks
Request type	<p>Select one or more reasons for the resubmission from the options available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Request for update during admissibility check Request for update linked to dossier publication Request for update following a request for clarification in the context of the confidentiality assessment process (after declaration of admissibility) request for update during application evaluation request for update of confidentiality claims after conclusion of the evaluation (only for renewal applications) request for update during peer review resubmission following identification of potentially harmful or unacceptable effects 	Multi-select list

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • other 	
Remarks	Add Remarks if needed	Text
Spontaneous update		Block of fields (repeatable)
Reason for resubmission	<p>Select one or more reasons for resubmission from the options available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • changes in administrative information • update following a legal entity change • change of role in joint submission • change to members of a joint submission • change in the access granted to information • change in classification and labelling • new confidentiality claim(s) • new knowledge of the risks for human health and/or environment • new studies available • other 	Multi-select list
Remarks	Add remarks if needed	Text
Notification of studies		Block
Pre-application identification	Enter any pre submission identifiers issued whilst notifying studies for inclusion in regulated product dossiers relevant for this dossier subject	Block of fields (repeatable)
Pre-application identifier	Enter any pre submission identifiers issued whilst notifying studies for inclusion in regulated product dossiers relevant for this dossier subject	Text
Studies requiring NoS justification		Block of fields (repeatable)
NoS ID	List all Notification of Studies identifiers which require a justification	Text
Justification	<p>Justifications for any deviations from notification obligations e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (i) justifications explaining the non-notification in the database of studies that have been included in the application; - (ii) justifications explaining the non-inclusion in the application of studies notified in the database; - (iii) justifications for the withdrawal of a study notification submitted in the database in support of the application; - (iv) justifications for the delayed submission of a study notification in support of the application in question after the starting date of the study; - (v) justifications explaining any other deviation from the process 	Text

Other submission related information		Block
Proposal for inclusion in Annex IV of Regulation (EC) 396/2005 is included in this dossier	Select this option if a Proposal for inclusion in Annex IV of Regulation (EC) 396/2005 is submitted within this renewal/approval IUCLID dossier.	

ACTIVE SUBSTANCE DATASET

This section includes instructions on how to compile the IUCLID documents in the active substance dataset in line with the relevant changes released with IUCLID 6.9.

1. Identity of the applicant, identity of the active substance and manufacturing information

1.1 Applicant, name and species

Purpose

All relevant information on the identity of the active substance must be provided in this document.

All relevant microbial identifiers of the active substance (e.g. genus/species information, deposition number, etc.) and the relevant chemical identifiers for metabolites (e.g. such as the CAS number, EC number, IUPAC name, molecular and structural formula, SMILE, InChI, ISO common name, and CIPAC number) must be provided in the REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE entity linked to the 'Reference substance' field. This document should be completed also for metabolites and impurities for which studies were performed and need to be reported.

SUBSTANCE		
Name	Instructions	Type
Substance name	For the microorganism(s) : the name of the active substance including species, subspecies and strain/isolate For chemicals/metabolites: The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) common name, or proposed ISO common name	Multi-line text
Public name	Public name of the active substance	Multi-line text
Legal entity flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Legal entity	Include here the name of the legal entity i.e. Company name for the applicant.	Entity reference field
Third party flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Third party	If appropriate, include link to the legal entity of a third party. This option is to be filled in by consultants if they are working on a dossier.	Entity reference field
Other substance identifiers	Code numbers used to identify the active substance, during development work, shall be reported. For each code number reported, the material to which it relates, the period for which it was used should be reported in the Remarks field. The Member States or other countries in which it was used and is being used, should be reported in the Country field	

Flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Identifier	Select the type of identifier you wish to provide using the picklist. If none of pre-defined items apply, select 'other:'. A text field is then activated next to the list field in which you can specify the type of identifier you wish to provide.	Open list
Identity	Enter here the identity (name, number, code) corresponding to the identifier type selected.	Multi-line text
Country	Provide the country where the identifier is relevant. The field is a multi-select field; several countries can be selected for the same identifier. If none of pre-defined items apply, select 'other:'. A text field is then activated next to the list field in which you can enter information on the country.	Multi select open list
Relation	If relevant, indicate the reason for providing an identifier other than the reference substance identifiers used to identify the Substance.	Open list
Remarks	Include remarks if relevant.	Text area
Contact persons	Contact entity	Header 1
Person flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Person	Select contact person or create new contact.	Entity reference field
Identification of substance		Header 1
Reference substance flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Reference substance	Link to the reference substance	Entity reference field
Type of substance		Header 1
Type of substance	'Microorganism or toxin produced by microorganism' must be selected. The other types can be used for chemicals	Open list
Origin	Picklist to indicate class of active substance e.g organic or inorganic	Open list
Role in the supply chain	Check 'Manufacturer' to indicate the applicant is the Producer of the active substance	Header 1
Role flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality

Links to supporting material:

[Legal entity](#)

[ISO/TC 81](#) Common names for pesticides and other agrochemicals

1.2 Producer

Purpose

The name, address and other contact information of the producer must be provided in this document, by referencing the LEGAL_ENTITY under the 'Name' field.

In case of more than one producer, a separate document for each of them must be created in this section.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Suppliers		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Manufacturer / Importer / Formulator		Header 1
Name	Indicate the name of the Supplier. Click the Link button to select the Supplier and establish the link. If the desired Supplier is not present in your database, click the New button. It will trigger the opening of the Legal entity creation dialogue. The Supplier is created and simultaneously linked to the Substance or Mixture/Product dataset. To complete the information of this newly created Legal entity, click the Go-to button. The modifications will be automatically updated by clicking the Save button. The Back button will lead back to section Suppliers. The link can be deleted by clicking the Delete button.	Entity reference field
Remarks		Text area
Only representation information		Header 1
Assignment from non EU manufacturer	Insert the official assignment documentation from the non EU-manufacturer. Click the Attachment button and the green Plus button in the context menu appearing. Specify the path and the name of the file to be inserted and indicate any remarks if useful in the Properties window.	Single file attachment
Other importers	The other Importers of the same substance, from the same non EU manufacturer, are considered to be downstream users for the only representative, and if necessary they can be recorded in this table-view block of fields. For each Importer, click the Add row button to create a new row.	
Name	Indicate the name(s) of the other Importer(s), (i.e. the Downstream user(s) under REACH). Click the	Entity reference field

	<p>Link button to select the Supplier and establish the link. If the desired Supplier is not present in your database, click the New button. It will trigger the opening of the Legal entity creation dialogue.</p> <p>The Importer is created and simultaneously linked to the Substance or Mixture dataset. To complete the information of this newly created Legal entity, click the Goto button.</p> <p>The modifications will be automatically updated by clicking the Save button. The Back button will lead back to section Suppliers. The link can be deleted by clicking the Delete button.</p>	
Agreement	<p>Insert the agreement document. Click the Attachment button and the green Plus button from the context menu appearing. Specify the path and the name of the file to be inserted and indicate any remarks if appropriate in the Properties window.</p>	Single file attachment
Other importers		

1.2.1 LOCATION OF MANUFACTURING PLANT(S)

Purpose

Detailed information on the location and contacts of each manufacturing plant (address, region, phone, email, etc) must be provided in this document, by referencing a SITE entity in the 'Site' field.

In case of more than one manufacturing sites, a separate document for each of them must be created in this section.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Sites		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p> <p>The flag system can be used in case of joint submission of information or if there is more than one manufacturer of the same substance and certain infrastructure/facilities are shared.</p> <p>Caution: The flags are set for all sites altogether. There is no possibility to filter out only one Legal entity site from an export file, a print-out or a Dossier.</p>	Confidentiality
Site	<p>Add as many repeatable blocks as necessary to list all production and/or /use locations.</p> <p>Site: Click the Link button to select the Site and establish the link. If the desired Site is not present in your database, click the 'Create' button. It will trigger the opening of the Legal entity site creation dialogue. The Legal entity site is created and simultaneously linked to the</p>	Entity reference field

	<p>Substance or Mixture dataset. To complete the information of this newly created Site, click the Goto button.</p> <p>The modifications will be automatically updated by clicking the Save button. The Back button will lead back to section Sites. The link can be deleted by clicking the Delete button.</p> <p>Caution: To delete only the link to the Site information click the Delete button located near the Site field. To delete all information on the Site, click the Delete button located at repeatable block level.</p>	
Remark	A remark field to enter additional information on the Site.	Text area
Manufacture / own use(s)		Header 1
Related manufacture / own use	<p>Click the Linkbutton to select the relates manufacture / own use and establish the link to the Site.</p> <p>Note: in case of a Distributor only, no manufacture / own use should be linked to the Site.</p>	Endpoint reference list
Related mixture/product		Header 1
Specify to which mixture/product(s) it applies:		Endpoint reference list

1.3 Identity, taxonomy and phylogeny of the microorganism – Endpoint study record

Purpose

This endpoint study record should be used for reporting data on the microorganism identity, including Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) information and raw sequencing data (e.g. FASTQ files).

In the area of plant protection products, Commission Regulation (EU) No 283/2013, as amended by Commission Regulation (EU) 1439/2022, also recommends the most appropriate molecular analytical methods to be used to characterize the micro-organism. The WGS-based data analysis can provide information to unequivocally assign taxonomic identification of the strains, as well as on the characterization of their potential functional traits of concern (e.g. virulence factors, resistance to antimicrobials of clinical relevance for humans and animals, production of known toxic metabolites).

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.GenomicCharacterisationMicroorganism		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Background		Header 1
Background information	Use this field to include any background information, if required, or any relevant introductory remarks on the study summary. Leave field empty if not applicable. Do	Text

	<p>not include information for which specific fields are provided.</p> <p>Example: This field can be used for summarising the pipeline followed to characterise the micro-organism using genomic methods, e.g. WGS.</p>	
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test Material – common block "	Header 2
Sample preparation		Header 2
Culture conditions	Describe the type of culture and culture conditions for the microorganism prior to the extraction of genetic material, if applicable (e.g. pure culture, monosporic culture).	Text
Genetic material extraction procedure	Describe the protocol / method used to extract DNA (with chromosomal and extra-chromosomal elements) or RNA (e.g. for viruses).	Text
Library preparation	Describe the library construction method for sequencing, e.g. DNA fragmentation method and selection of fragments, addition of adapters... Specify the manufacturer’s instructions followed, including version number, and describe any deviations from that method.	Text
Sequencing and Quality Control		Header 2
Sequencing platform / instrument	Indicate the sequencing platform / instrument used for sequencing, including the technology used (e.g. Sequencing by Synthesis, Pyrosequencing, Nanopore...), the company and the device. Further details about the method can be provided in field 'Details on sequencing method'	Text
Read type	Select the type of reads generated by the instrument.	List (picklist with remarks) sup.
Details on sequencing method	Provide any further details about the sequencing strategy and any base-calling method, where applicable.	Text
Trimming, adapter removal, and filtering strategy	Describe the strategy followed for trimming, removing adapters and filtering, including software, version and parameters used.	Text
Quality control method	Describe the method for quality control, including software, version and parameters used.	Text
Assembly		Header 2

Type	Indicate the method used for the assembly.	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
De-novo assembly (if applicable)		Header 3	
Assembly strategy	Describe the strategy followed for the assembly, including software, version and parameters used.	Text	
Post-assembly strategy	If post-assembly processing is carried out, describe the approach followed, including software, version and parameters used.	Text	
Genome annotation	If genome annotation is carried out, describe the approach followed, including software, version and parameters used. Database(s), version (where applicable) and/or date of accession should be indicated.	Text	
Reference-based mapping (if applicable)		Header 3	
Reference genome	Indicate the reference genome(s) / database(s) used for the mapping and justify this choice.	Text	
Mapping strategy	Describe the approach followed for mapping to the reference genome, including software, version and parameters used.	Text	
Taxonomic identification		Header 2	
Taxonomic identification strategy	Describe the strategy followed for the taxonomic identification of the microorganism, including software, version and parameters used.	Text	
Detection of contamination		Header 2	
Contamination detection strategy	Describe the strategy followed for detection of contamination, including software, version and parameters used.	Text	
Identification of traits of concern		Header 2	
Genetic modifications	Describe the methodology (e.g. alignment strategy) and sequences used for the detection of genetic modifications, including reference genome used, alignment software and parameters.	Text	
AMR genes	Described the strategy followed to identify genes related to antimicrobial resistance, including databases, software, version and/or accession date.	Text	
Toxigenicity and pathogenicity	Described the strategy followed to identify genes related to toxigenicity and pathogenicity (e.g. production of toxins, invasion and adhesion factors, participation in metabolic pathways involved toxigenicity, etc), including databases, software, version and/or accession date.	Text	

Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Sequencing and quality control		Header 2
Raw sequencing data	<p>Attach here the files containing raw sequencing data. Accepted formats are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fastq (*.fastq.gz; *.fq.gz) - for assembled genomes: fasta (*.fasta; *.fna; *.fa; *.fasta.gz; *.fna.gz; *.fa.gz) <p>Important note: one single file in compliance with the data formats listed above should always be submitted. In case of more contigs deriving from <i>de novo</i> assembly, the submission require one continuous file (that can be FASTA or one of the other options listed above).</p>	Attachment (multiple)
Raw reads quality control (before filtering and trimming)	Include data on the raw reads (before filtering and trimming).	Header 3
Total reads		Numeric (integer)
Average read length		Numeric (decimal)
% bases Q_≥ 20		Numeric (decimal)
% bases Q_≥ 30		Numeric (decimal)
% GC		Numeric (decimal)
Remarks		Text
Processed reads quality control (after filtering and trimming)	Include data on the processed reads (after filtering and trimming).	Header 3
Total reads		Numeric (integer)
Average read length		Numeric (decimal)
% bases Q_≥ 20		Numeric (decimal)
% bases Q_≥ 30		Numeric (decimal)

% GC		Numeric (decimal)
Remarks		Text
Assembly		Header 2
Genome size	Indicate the genome size from the assembly.	Numeric (integer)
Coverage	For de-novo assembly, indicate the % of reference genome covered by the assembly. For reference-based mapping, indicate the coverage at >5x depth.	Numeric (decimal)
Gene annotations		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Type of genes / elements		List (picklist)
Total number		Numeric (integer)
Remarks		Text
Gene annotations		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Additional details on assembly and gene annotation		Text
De-novo assembly (if applicable)		Header 3
Number of contigs		Numeric (integer)
Total contig length		Numeric (integer)
N50		Numeric (integer)
Longest contig length		Numeric (integer)
Mean contig length		Numeric (integer)
Remarks	E.g. if size not +/- expected length	Text
Reference-based mapping (if applicable)		Header 3
% reads mapped		Numeric (decimal)

Median read depth		Numeric (decimal)
Taxonomic identification		Header 2
Organism type		List (picklist)
Species		Text
Strain		Text
TaxID	Indicate NCBI's Tax ID for the organism.	Numeric (integer)
Identity to reference genome	Indicate ANI for bacteria, ANI or % identity for fungi	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Phylogenetic tree	Attach here the phylogenetic tree	Image upload
Additional details on taxonomic identification		Text
Contamination		Header 2
% contamination		Numeric (decimal)
Organism identified		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Organism		Text
% total reads		Numeric (decimal)
Remarks		Text
Organism identified		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Additional details on contamination		Text
Traits of concern		Header 2
Genetic modifications		Header 3
Genetic modifications detected		List (picklist)
List of genetic modifications		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Type	Select the type of genetic modification	List (picklist)
Start	Indicate the start position of the genetic modification	Numeric (integer)

End	Indicate the end position of the genetic modification	Numeric (integer)
Strand	Indicate the strand	List (picklist)
Genetic element type	Select the type of genetic element(s) or feature(s) (e.g. gene, CDS, regulatory element...) affected by the genetic modification. Picklist values are based on the feature key definitions of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) https://www.insdc.org/submitting-standards/feature-table/ . If none of the key features is applicable, please select "other" and indicate the genetic element. You can provide further information in the remarks field.	List (picklist) sup. with remarks)
Genetic element name	Indicate the name of the genetic element (e.g. gene name) affected by the genetic modification, if applicable	Text
Remarks	Indicate any additional information or annotations regarding the genetic modification or the genetic element affected	Text
List of genetic modifications		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Graphical description		Image upload
Additional details on genetic modifications		Text
AMR genes		Header 3
AMR genes detected		List (picklist)
List of genes		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Gene name		Text
Accession number		Text
Database		Text
Function		Text
% identity		Numeric (decimal)
% length covered		Numeric (decimal)
Gene mobile	Indicate if there is a correlation with mobile genetic elements and provide a justification in the remarks field.	List (picklist) sup. with remarks)
List of genes		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Dendrogram	Link here a dendrogram with related species or strains for which the presence of AMR is known.	Image upload

Additional details on AMR genes		Text
Toxigenicity and pathogenicity		Header 3
Genes linked to toxigenicity and pathogenicity detected		List (picklist)
List of genes		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Gene cluster	Indicate if the gene belongs to any specific cluster, group of category e.g. for secondary metabolites	Text (255 char.)
Gene name		Text
Accession number		Text
Database		Text
Function		Text
% identity		Numeric (decimal)
% length covered		Numeric (decimal)
List of genes		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Dendrogram	Link here a dendrogram with related species or strains for which the toxigenicity and pathogenicity are known.	Image upload
Additional details on genes linked to toxigenicity and pathogenicity		Text
Any other information on results incl. tables	Any other information on results incl. tables – common block	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Overall remarks, attachments – common block The form in Appendix A of EFSA, 2021 (https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6506) should be duly completed and signed by the applicants at the time of submission, and attached to this document.	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block	Header 1

Link to Supporting material:

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), 2024. EFSA statement on the requirements for whole genome sequence analysis of micro-organisms intentionally used in the food chain. *EFSA Journal*, 22(8), e8912. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2024.8912>

1.4 Specification of the microbial pest control agent as manufactured - Flexible record

Purpose

This flexible record must be used to report information on the composition of the representative batches, of the proposed technical specification and the proposed reference specification including the minimum purity of the active substance, maximum levels of impurities and minimum and maximum levels of additives (if applicable).

One document should be created/completed for each type of composition: one for each batch analysed, one for each technical specification related with a manufacturing site/source and one for the (proposed) reference specification (when relevant).

In the case of renewal applications, to provide the reference specification of the previous assessment, if available to the applicant, a document with the type of composition "Reference specification" should be created. In this document the applicant should indicate where the reference specification is located e.g. DAR/Month/Year in the 'Description' field.

For each 'Type of composition' (i.e. batch composition, technical specification and reference specification) the designated table sections 'constituents', 'impurities' and 'additives' must be completed.

Notes:

- If the active substance is manufactured as a technical concentrate (TK) two separated documents should be created/completed to report the composition of the technical concentrate and composition in the theoretical dry weight material.
- All impurities reported in this document should also be included in the 'Impurities' document under Section 1.4.6 of the product dataset, where additional details can be provided, including the identity and maximum content of chemical impurities present in the MPCA as manufactured which are relevant due to undesirable toxicological, ecotoxicological or environmental properties, as well as any metabolites of concern produced by the microorganism that occur as impurities in the manufacturing batch.
- The most appropriate microbial unit (e.g. CFU/g) should be selected when reporting the concentration of the active substance.
- Information and data on contaminating microorganisms should be provided in the batch analysis under Section 1.4.3 'Analytical profile of batches'. Under the same Section, separate documents should be prepared for reporting the data on contaminating organisms present in the MPCP.
- If data from analysis of PPP batches are reported (e.g. for active substances that are micro-organisms) then a justification should be provided why the batch analysis of the active substance as manufactured was not possible.
- Where data on industrial scale production are not available, a justification shall be provided.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.SubstanceComposition		
Name	Instructions	Type
General Information		Header 1
Name	Indicate a name representative of the composition.	Text
Type of composition	Select the type of composition as appropriate. For pesticide dossier the type of composition should be ' legal entity composition of the substance ', that	Open list

	<p>refers to a composition specific to the party carrying out the application/notification/registration.</p> <p>NOTE: When reporting the batch composition, select 'other:' and indicate "<u>batch composition</u>"</p>	
State / form	<p>Indicate the physical state and form of the active substance as manufactured. The picklist is not exhaustive but aims to reflect states and forms that may influence the properties of the substance.</p> <p>If none of pre-defined picklist items appropriately describe your composition, select 'other:'. A text field is then activated next to the list field in which you can enter the state and form of the composition. If multiple options apply, please create a separate composition for each.</p>	Open list
Description	<p>Include in this field, as appropriate, additional information on the active substance as manufactured. For a complex substance, the description should enable the understanding of the process that led to the particular composition. Free-text templates are available to support the user in providing a suitable description.</p> <p>When providing the reference specification of the previous assessment, include in this field where the reference specification is located e.g. DAR/Month/Year.</p>	Text template
Justification for deviations	<p>Provide in this field, if relevant, the justification for deviating from agreed conventions when reporting the composition. Such deviations can for example relate to the definitions of substance types (e.g. mono-constituent substance), or the level to which a composition has been described in terms of separate constituents, impurities and additives.</p>	Text area
Attached description / justification	<p>Attach supporting information to describe the composition, e.g. schematics for relevant chemical reactions or process steps that take place in the generation of the composition.</p>	
Attached document	<p>Upload a file by clicking the upload icon.</p> <p>Documents with confidential material should not be uploaded in this field.</p>	Single file attachment
Remarks	<p>Provide information about the contents of the attached document.</p>	Text
Related composition(s)		Header 2
Related composition	<p>Use this field only when the type of composition is "reference specification", in order to link the technical specification(s) used to derive the reference specification.</p> <p>Related compositions in other datasets or dossiers should be referred to textually in the field 'Reference to related composition(s)'</p>	Endpoint reference list
Reference to related composition(s)	<p>Use this field only when the type of composition is "reference specification", in order to describe the</p>	Multi-line text

	relation with the technical specification(s) from other dossiers, if applicable.	
Degree of purity		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
	For specification documents: Report the proposed minimum purity of the active substance as manufactured. For batch documents: Report the content of the pure active substance measured in the batch analysed. For providing only a single numeric value; enter the value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For the microbial active substance: report the proposed minimum purity using the most appropriate microbial unit (e.g. CFU/kg)	Range with open list (Decimal)
Constituents	This part is a repeatable block subsection enabling to report the identity and the content of the active substance in the composition. It is a repeatable block which allows the reporting of more than one constituent of the active substance if needed (e.g. in case the active substance is a defined mixture of two or more isolates, e.g. in case of bacteriophages). Click the "Plus" button to open the repeatable block. If the active substance is a mixture then all components of this mixture should be reported here with their proposed level of specification (or measured level in case of batch analysis results) using the repeatable block i.e. one row per component.	Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Reference substance	Assign here the reference substance that identifies the constituent. Click the "Arrow" button to access a linked reference substance and modify it as appropriate. Click the Link button to link/change the reference substance. If the desired reference substance is not present in your database, click the New button at the bottom of the Query window and insert the information of the reference substance in the available fields. For further information on reference substances, see chapter 10 of 'Functionalities of IUCLID', in the left pane of the Help system window.	Entity reference field

	Where relevant detailed information on all components such as condensates, culture medium, etc. must be provided	
Typical concentration	<p>When the type of composition is 'Technical' or 'Reference specification', the (proposed) minimum content of the active substance in the technical material should be reported.</p> <p>For 'batch composition' the measured amount of the active substance in the relevant (individual) batches is to be reported.</p> <p>Note: scientific notation can be used, 5e7= 50000000</p> <p>! For the microbial active substance: report the concentration using the most appropriate microbial unit (e.g. CFU/kg)</p>	Half-bounded with open list (Decimal)
Concentration range	<p>Use this field to report a concentration range.</p> <p>! For the microbial active substance: report the concentration using the most appropriate microbial unit (e.g. CFU/kg)</p>	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks	Provide additional information on the specification of purity of the active substance as manufactured.	Text area
Impurities		Header 1
	<p>This part is a repeatable block subsection enabling to report the identity and the content of each impurity in the composition. Click the Plus button to open the repeatable block. If the active substance as manufactured contains more than one impurity, add a new block to describe each impurity.</p> <p>For microorganisms used as active substance, the condensates and culture media must be listed in this section.</p> <p>Note: All impurities reported in this document should also be included in the 'Impurities' document (section 1.4.3 'Impurities' of the Product dataset) in which more details can be provided.</p>	
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Reference substance	<p>Assign here the reference substance that identifies the impurity. Click the Arrow button to access a linked reference substance and modify it as appropriate. Click the Link button to link/change the reference substance. If the desired reference substance is not present in your database, click the New button at the bottom of the Query window and insert the information of the reference substance in the available fields.</p> <p>For further information on reference substances, see chapter 10 of 'Functionalities of IUCLID', in the left pane of the Help system window.</p>	Entity reference field

Typical concentration	<p>When the Type of composition is 'technical specification' and 'reference specification' the (proposed) maximum content of the impurities in the technical material or technical concentrate should be reported.</p> <p>For "batch composition" the measured amount of the impurities in the relevant (individual) batches should be reported.</p>	Half-bounded with open list (Decimal)
Concentration range	<p>Use this field when you need to report a concentration range (e.g. for technical concentrates, plants extracts etc.).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In case of technical concentrate, the minimum and maximum content of the active substance in the technical concentrate should be reported. 	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks	Provide additional information about the impurity, as relevant.	Text area
This impurity is considered relevant for the classification and labelling of the substance	Select the checkbox to indicate that the impurity has an impact on the classification and labelling of the substance.	Check box
Additives		Header 1
	<p>This part is a repeatable block subsection enabling to provide detail on all additives of the active substance as manufactured. Click the Plus button to open the repeatable block.</p> <p>If the active substance as manufactured contains more than one additive, add a new block to describe each additive.</p>	
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see:</p> <p>"User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Reference substance	<p>Assign here the reference substance that identifies the additive. Click the Arrow button to access a linked reference substance and modify it as appropriate. Click the Link button to link/change the reference substance. If the desired reference substance is not present in your database, click the New button at the bottom of the Query window and insert the information of the reference substance in the available fields.</p> <p>For further information on reference substances, see chapter 10 of 'Functionalities of IUCLID', in the left pane of the Help system window.</p>	Entity reference field
Typical concentration	Use this field to report the exact measured value of the additive for the "batch composition", if applicable.	Half-bounded with open list (Decimal)
Concentration range	The minimum and maximum content of each additive in the technical and/or reference specification type of composition should be reported.	Range with open list (Decimal)

Function	Indicate the function of the additive in the active substance as manufactured. Ensure to follow regulatory guidance on what constitutes an additive.	Open list
Details of function in composition	Provide further information related to the function of the additive in the active substance as manufactured. In particular, if selecting a less specific entry in the previous 'Function' field, it is recommended to include more details on the function in this field.	Text area
Remarks	Provide additional information about the additive, as relevant.	Text area
This additive is considered relevant for the classification and labelling of the substance	Select the checkbox to indicate that the additive has an impact on the classification and labelling of the substance.	Check box
Characterisation of nanoforms	This section is not relevant for pesticides	Header 1
Characterisation of polymers	This section is not relevant for pesticides	Header 1

1.4.1 (CF. 1.4) CONTENT OF THE ACTIVE SUBSTANCE

1.4.2 (CF. 1.4) IDENTITY AND QUANTIFICATION OF ADDITIVES, RELEVANT CONTAMINATING MICROORGANISMS AND RELEVANT IMPURITIES

1.4.2.1 (Cf. 1.4) Identity and quantification of additives

1.4.2.2 (Cf. 1.4) Identity and content of relevant contaminating microorganisms

1.4.2.3 (Cf. 1.4) Identity and quantification of relevant impurities

1.4.3 ANALYTICAL PROFILE OF BATCHES - ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to **collect the outcome of all the 5-batch analysis (5BAs) submitted for the active substance**, to sum up all the technical aspects and lead to a conclusion on the specifications. All relevant endpoint study records detailing the 5-batch analysis must be linked in the dedicated field 'Link to relevant study record(s)' of the endpoint summary.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.AnalyticalProfBatches		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality

Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	All relevant endpoint study records detailing the 5-batch analysis must be linked in this field.	Link to document (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
		Text (rich-text area)
Description of key information (confidential)	Summarise the results for the analysis of batches and indicate if supporting data was provided to further justify the technical specification (not published).	Text (rich-text area)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

1.4.3 ANALYTICAL PROFILE OF BATCHES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

An endpoint study record for **each manufacturing plant** and/or **for each 5-batch analysis** (5BA) should be created. All standard fields common to endpoint study records should be fully completed, including the data source linking the study report.

Importantly, the 'Results and discussion' > 'Analytical profile of representative batches' section should be fully completed, including:

- Link to the Manufacturing site entity, including address, contact details, etc.
- One entry per batch within the repeatable table 'Substance composition analysis', providing all the batch specific data and linking the corresponding 'Substance composition' document for the batch (type = 'batch composition') as described in [Section 1.4](#).
- Quality control (QC) data for the same manufacturing site, including quantitative information for each of the analysed substances (average, min, max, SD). More than one quality control dataset can be provided, if applicable.
- Link to the 'Substance composition' document for the proposed technical specification (type = "technical specification", see [Section 1.4](#)) derived from the batch analysis and QC data reported in this document.

Where data on industrial scale production are not available, a justification shall be provided.

This document should present information and data on the content of contaminating microorganisms detected in the batches. Separate documents should be created to report batches on the active substance and batches on the product.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AnalyticalProfileOfBatches		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Any other information on		Header 2

materials and methods incl. tables		
	<p>In this field, you can enter any information on materials and methods, for which no distinct field is available, or transfer free text from other databases.</p> <p>You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format. You can also upload any htm or html document.</p>	Text (rich-text area)
Results and discussion		Header 1
Analytical profile of representative batches	<p>Provide in this section the information related to the batch analysis performed. Select the substance composition records which describe the analytical profile of each batch analysed, which must include the pure active substance, impurities, and additives.</p> <p>Where an active substance is produced in different plants, the batch analysis should be provided for each plant separately in different study records.</p>	Header 2
Manufacturing site	Link here the site entity corresponding to the manufacturing plant/site where the batch analysis and quality control data has been produced.	Link to document (single)
Substance composition analysis	<p>Create one entry per batch used in the analysis. At least 5 entries should be provided.</p> <p>This block should be used for providing all the batch specific data and linking the corresponding 'Substance composition' document for the batch (type = 'batch composition') as described in Section 1.4.</p>	Block of fields
Batch number	Indicate the batch number.	Text
Date of manufacture	Indicate the date of manufacture of the batch.	Date
Batch size	Indicate the size of the batch.	Numeric
Type of production	Indicate the type of production/manufacturing of the batch.	List
Batch composition	Select the substance composition document which describes the batch.	Link to document (single)
Remarks	If necessary, provide any additional information related to the batch analysis.	Text
Quality control (QC) data	<p>This block of fields could be used for reporting Quality control (QC) data for the same manufacturing site, including quantitative information for each of the analysed substances (average, min, max, SD).</p> <p>More than one quality control dataset can be provided, if applicable.</p>	Block of fields
Number of batches	Indicate the number of batches analysed for quality control.	Numeric

Date (start)	Indicate the beginning of the production period of the batches used for quality control data.	Date
Date (end)	Indicate the end of the production period of the batches used for quality control data.	Date
Units	Indicate the units in which QC data are reported in the table below.	List
QC data		Block of fields
	Set confidentiality and regulatory programme flags.	Confidentiality
Component	Assign here the reference substance that identifies the component analysed.	Link to document
Avg	Indicate the average concentration of the component in the batches analysed. The units should be consistent for all components in the block and correspond to the selection in the "Units" field above.	Numeric
Min	Indicate the minimum concentration of the component in the batches analysed. The units should be consistent for all components in the block and correspond to the selection in the "Units" field above.	Numeric
Max	Indicate the maximum concentration of the component in the batches analysed. The units should be consistent for all components in the block and correspond to the selection in the "Units" field above.	Numeric
SD	Indicate the standard deviation for the concentration of the component in the batches analysed. The units should be consistent for all components in the block and correspond to the selection in the "Units" field above.	Numeric
Technical specification	Select the substance composition document which describes the proposed technical specification (including min level of the active substance and maximum level of the impurities) based on the batch analysis and/or supporting information (e.g. QC data) reported above.	Link to document (single)
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

1.5 Information on manufacturing process and control measures for the active substance

1.5.1 PRODUCTION AND QUALITY CONTROL

Purpose

To describe the method of manufacture (synthesis pathway) of the active substance. For each manufacturing plant, describe the purity of the starting materials, chemical pathways and identity of impurities present in the final product as well as the identity of impurities present in the final product.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Manufacturer_EU_PPP		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Related compositions	Link to one or more compositions of the substance can be made which will then display the corresponding name(s). This link enables to transparently identify which composition of the substance is relevant for which use during its life cycle (from manufacture to service life).	Endpoint reference list
Description of key information		Header 1
	Describe the manufacturing process e.g. chemical pathways involved. Where the required information is provided for a pilot plant production system, that information shall again be provided once industrial scale production methods and procedures have stabilised. Where available, industrial scale data shall be provided before approval under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009. Where data on industrial scale production are not available, a justification shall be provided. For microorganisms describe how the micro-organism is produced in bulk for all the steps of the manufacturing process. Describe starting materials, culture media, fermentation process, purification, batch or continuous process etc. Description of the manufacturing process, Flowcharts can be uploaded as images in the Attached background material section.	Rich text area
Quality Control	Describe the quality control criteria and steps in the production process. Indicate techniques to ensure a uniform product. Quantitative Information on impurities should be reported the Substance Composition document.	Rich text area
Additional information		Header 1

	State the manufacturing plant if separate documents are provided for each manufacturing plant	Rich text area
Document J	<p>The original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions. If a file is uploaded under this field, (a) confidentiality claim(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.</p> <p>The completed "IUCLID templates for PPP Risk Assessment - Template 1.1 - Template for presentation the assessment for the equivalence of batches" (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4557366) must be included in Document J however, all relevant IUCLID documents including this information should also be completed.</p> <p>For MRL applications this document should be provided only upon request.</p> <p>For this reason, analytical methods for impurities which are not toxicologically relevant should be reported in Doc J.</p>	Single file attachment
Sanitised Document J	Document J must be uploaded here in its public (non-confidential) version. The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised. Save for the elements blackened, if applicable, content and layout-wise the public version must be fully identical to the confidential version. Upon conclusion of the confidentiality assessment, if applicable, a revised public version removing the redactions relating to confidentiality requests that were rejected in part or in full must be uploaded here.	Single file attachment
Attached background material	<p>Additional background material can be uploaded here, use remarks to indicate the contents of the uploaded files.</p> <p>The original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions. If a file is uploaded under this field (a) confidentiality claim(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.</p>	
Attached confidential document	Upload supporting material (e.g. Excel files) as described in regulatory guidance. Click the upload icon. As appropriate, enter any additional information, e.g. language. The file name is displayed after uploading the document.	Single file attachment

	The original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions. If a file is uploaded under this field (a) confidentiality claim(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.	
Attached (sanitised) documents for publication	A non-confidential version of any submitted background material must be uploaded here. These will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised. Save for the elements blackened, if applicable, content and layout-wise the public version must be fully identical with the confidential version. Upon conclusion of the confidentiality assessment, if applicable, a revised non-confidential version removing the redactions relating to confidentiality requests that were rejected in part or in full must be uploaded here.	Attachments list
Remarks	As appropriate, include remarks, e.g. a short description of the content of the attached document if the file name is not self-explanatory.	Text

Links to supporting material:

Transparency Regulation: Practical Arrangements

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/corporate/pub/tr-practical-arrangements>

1.5.2 RECOMMENDED METHODS AND PRECAUTIONS CONCERNING HANDLING, STORAGE, TRANSPORT OR FIRE

Purpose

This document should cover:

- **Recommended methods and precautions** (e.g., protective clothing, equipment).
- **Destruction or decontamination procedures** (e.g., chemical methods, autoclaving, etc).
- **Emergency measures** (e.g., spill containment, area decontamination, disposal of damaged packaging, protection of emergency workers and bystanders).

Supporting documents:

- **Safety datasheets** should be referenced to substantiate the information provided.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.ProtectionMeasures		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality

Instructions for use	Not relevant for pesticides: Instructions for use must be described in the Good Agricultural Practice (GAP) document	Header 1
Measures to protect humans, animals and the environment		Header 1
Recommended methods and precautions concerning storage of active substance/product; shelf-life of product	<p>Substance: The field is used to identify all methods and precautions concerning the storage of an active substance.</p> <p>Product: The field is used to identify all methods and precautions concerning the storage of a product, including the shelf life of a product. The shelf life of product under normal conditions of storage should be reported.</p>	Rich text area
Recommended methods and precautions concerning handling and transport	<p>Describe all methods and precautions concerning handling and transport.</p> <p>Detailed handling procedures for the storage, at both warehouse and user level of plant protection products must be provided</p> <p>Where appropriate, the nature and characteristics of protective clothing and equipment proposed shall be provided. The data provided shall be sufficient to evaluate the suitability and effectiveness under realistic conditions of use (for example field or glasshouse circumstances)</p>	Text area
Recommended methods and precautions concerning fire; in case of fire nature of reaction products, combustion gases etc.	The field is used to identify all methods and precautions concerning fire, and all possible consequences of it. Where available, information on combustion products shall be provided	Text area
Particulars of likely direct or indirect adverse effects	The field is used to identify all direct or indirect adverse effects.	Rich text area
First aid instructions, antidotes	Not relevant for pesticides: Report information on poisoning and treatment in the Medical data document (Section 5.1 Medical data or Section 5.1.4 Direct observation, e.g. clinical cases).	Text area
Emergency measures to protect environment in case of accident	<p>Provide information on Emergency measures in the case of an accident and detailed procedures to be followed in the event of an emergency, whether arising during transport, storage or use</p> <p>This could include containment of spillages, decontamination of areas, vehicles and buildings, disposal of damaged packaging, absorbents and other materials, protection of emergency workers and residents, including bystanders</p>	Text area

	In the case of microorganisms, Information on procedures for rendering the microorganism harmless in the environment (e.g. water or soil) in case of an accident must be provided	
Control measures of repellents or poison included in the product, to prevent action against non-target organisms (relevant for products only)	Select relevant value(s) from the picklist	Multi list select
Control measures of repellents or poison included in the product, to prevent action against non-target organisms (relevant for products only)	The field is used to identify all measures that could be taken to prevent action against non-target organisms when using the product.	Rich text area
Procedures, if any, for cleaning application equipment (relevant for products only)	The field is used to provide procedures for cleaning the equipment or machinery used for the application of the product. If there is no need to use any additional equipment, please indicate it clearly. Washing and cleaning of protective equipment should also be described (where relevant). The effectiveness of cleaning procedures shall be described in detail.	Text area
Possibility of destruction or decontamination following release in or on the following:		Header 1
Air	Describe possibility of destruction or decontamination following release in the air. Release to air is not relevant for micro-organisms	Text area
Water, including drinking water	Describe possibility of destruction or decontamination following release in or on the water, including drinking water.	Text area
Soil	Describe possibility of destruction or decontamination following release in or on the soil.	Text area
Procedures for waste management of active substance/product, and if appropriate, its packaging:	Procedures for destruction and decontamination shall be developed for both small quantities (user level) and large quantities (warehouse level).	Header 1

<p>Possibility of reuse or recycling</p>	<p>Substance: The field is used to identify possibility of reuse or recycling of the active substance and to describe relevant procedures for industry or professional users.</p> <p>Product: The field is used to identify possibility of reuse or recycling of the product and its packaging and to describe relevant procedures for industry, trained professional, professional users and non-professional users</p> <p>Procedures to preclude or minimise the generation of waste or leftovers shall be provided.</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Neutralisation procedure and possibility of neutralisation of effects</p>	<p>Neutralisation procedures (such as by reaction with other substances to form less toxic compounds) for use in the event of accidental spillages shall be described, where such procedures can be applied</p> <p>Methods to dispose safely of the micro-organism or, where necessary, to kill it prior to disposal, and methods to dispose of contaminated packaging and contaminated materials, must be fully described</p> <p>Substance: The field is used to identify possibility of neutralisation of effects caused by the active substance and to describe relevant procedures for industry or professional users.</p> <p>Product: The field is used to identify possibility of neutralisation of effects caused by the product and its packaging and to describe relevant procedures for industry, trained professional, professional users and non-professional users.</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Conditions for controlled discharge including leachate qualities on disposal</p>	<p>Substance: The field is used to describe conditions for controlled discharge of the active substance, including leachate qualities on disposal. Detailed description of all relevant procedures for industry or professional users should be done.</p> <p>Product: The field is used to describe conditions for controlled discharge of the product, including leachate qualities on disposal. Detailed description of all relevant procedures for industry, trained professional, professional users and non-professional users, should be done.</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Conditions for controlled incineration</p>	<p>If controlled incineration is not the preferred method of disposal, full information on the alternative method of safe disposal used shall be provided (in the other fields in this section)</p> <p>Substance: The field is used to describe conditions for controlled incineration of the active substance. Detailed description of all relevant procedures for industry or professional users should be done.</p> <p>Product: The field is used to describe conditions for controlled incineration of the product. Detailed description of all relevant procedures for industry, trained professional, professional users and non-professional users, should be done.</p>	<p>Text area</p>

Instructions for safe disposal of the product and its packaging for different groups of users (relevant for biocidal products only)	Not relevant for pesticides	Rich text area
Additional information		Header 1
Reference	<p>Indicate the bibliographic reference of the study report or publication used to support any or all of the points above. Provide general information such as Title, Author, Year, Bibliographic source, Testing Facility, Report Number, Study number, Report date etc., as requested in the core template for literature search. Always enter the primary reference in the first block of fields or sort it to the first position, if there are more than one reference to be cited. Copy this block of fields for specifying any other references related to this record (e.g. report of a preliminary study or other documentation). If results of a study report have been published, indicate the full citation of that publication(s) in addition to the reference of the original study.</p> <p>A sanitised version of the report must be uploaded in the literature reference for publication, the original version can be included if it differs from the sanitised version</p> <p>Safety datasheets in the form of literature references can be added as references in this field</p>	Literature reference list

Links to supporting material:

Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control)
<http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/75/2011-01-06>

1.5.3 (CF. 1.5.2) PROCEDURES FOR DESTRUCTION OR DECONTAMINATION

2. Biological properties of the microorganism

Purpose

Use this document to provide information on:

- Origin and isolation source
- Occurrence
- History of use
- Ecology and life cycle of the micro-organism
- Growth requirements
- Infectivity to the target organism
- Relationship to known human pathogens and to pathogens to non-target organisms
- Genetic stability and factors affecting it
- Information on metabolites of concern (see [instructions](#) in the introduction)
- Presence of transferable antimicrobial resistance genes

Please note that the mode of action on the target organism and host range should be reported in **Section 3.1** – Function and target organism)

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.BioPropertiesMicro		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/user-guide-submission-confidentiality-requests.pdf	Confidentiality
Biological properties of the micro-organism		Header 1
General information on the micro-organism		Header 2
	Familiarity (availability of relevant knowledge) of the microorganism not covered by the sections below. If the microorganism is genetically modified, the type of modification should be provided.	Text template
Type of micro-organisms		List (picklist)
Strain characteristics		List multi. (multi-select list with remarks)
Reference	Data source (Literature reference) – common block Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above. See also Literature search at the end of the table.	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Historical background	Not relevant for PPP dossiers – see next section Historical uses	Header 3
		Text template

Taxonomic level	Not relevant for PPP dossiers – see next section Historical uses	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Reference	Not relevant for PPP dossiers – see next section Historical uses	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Historical uses		Header 3
	<p><u>2.1.3 History of use</u></p> <p>Previous and current known uses of the micro-organism (e.g. research, commercial, uses evaluated for recommending the Qualified Presumption of Safety status). Include both plant protection and other uses (e.g. uses and/or assessments under other regulatory frameworks, bioremediation, uses in food and feed).</p> <p>Provide information at the most relevant taxonomic level (e.g. strain, species, genus), and according to the valid and accepted taxonomic criteria applicable at the time of the submission of the application.</p>	Text template
Taxonomic level	Select the taxonomic level of the information provided above and provide a justification of the choice of taxonomic level in the remarks field	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
QPS status	Select the Qualified Presumption of Safety Status https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1146566 . Qualifications from in the QPS list can be reported in the remarks	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Reference	<u>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</u> Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above. See also Literature search at the end of the table.	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Origin, natural occurrence and geographical distribution		Header 3
	<p><u>2.1.1 Origin and isolation source</u></p> <p><u>2.1.2 Occurrence</u></p> <p>The geographical location and environmental compartment (e.g. substrate, host organisms), from which the micro-organism was isolated, shall be stated. The method of isolation and the selection procedure of the microorganism shall be reported.</p> <p>The geographical distribution of the micro-organism shall be described.</p> <p>The environmental compartment(s) where the micro-organism is already expected to occur shall be described (e.g. soil, water, rhizosphere, phyllosphere, host organism).</p>	Text template

	<p>When relevant, food or feed commodities where the micro-organism is already expected to occur shall be described.</p> <p>The information referred to in this point shall be provided at the most relevant highest taxonomic level (e.g. strain, species, genus), and the choice of the relevant highest taxonomic level shall be justified.</p>		
Occurrence in water	<p>Indicate the occurrence in water selecting the appropriate value from the picklist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In strain under evaluation - in strain under evaluation - in closely related species - in organisms of the same genus - no 	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Occurrence in soil	<p>Indicate the occurrence in soil selecting the appropriate value from the picklist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In strain under evaluation - in strain under evaluation - in closely related species - in organisms of the same genus - no 	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Occurrence in rhizosphere	<p>Indicate the occurrence in rhizosphere selecting the appropriate value from the picklist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In strain under evaluation - in strain under evaluation - in closely related species - in organisms of the same genus - no 	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Occurrence in phyllosphere	<p>Indicate the occurrence in phyllosphere selecting the appropriate value from the picklist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In strain under evaluation - in strain under evaluation - in closely related species - in organisms of the same genus - no 	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Occurrence in host organisms	<p>Indicate the occurrence in host organisms selecting the appropriate value from the picklist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In strain under evaluation - in strain under evaluation - in closely related species - in organisms of the same genus - no 	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Occurrence in food or feed	<p>Indicate the occurrence in food or feed selecting the appropriate value from the picklist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In strain under evaluation - in strain under evaluation - in closely related species - in organisms of the same genus - no 	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Food or feed matrix	<p>When relevant, food or feed commodities where the micro-organism is already expected to occur shall be described.</p>	List (multi-select list remarks)	multi. with

Reference	<p>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</p> <p>Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above.</p> <p>See also Literature search at the end of the table.</p>	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Development stages / life cycle of the microorganism		Header 2
	<p><u>2.2 Ecology and life cycle of the micro-organism</u></p> <p>The known life cycle(s) of the micro-organism, its lifestyle(s) (e.g. parasitic, saprophytic, endophytic, pathogenic) and its ecological niche(s) shall be described, along with all forms that may occur and the type of reproduction.</p> <p>For bacteriophages, information shall be provided on, if applicable, lysogenic and lytic properties.</p> <p>For fungi and bacteria, information shall be provided, if applicable, on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - external conditions for resting stages, information on resistance of spores against adverse environmental conditions, survival time of the spores and conditions for germination, and/or - formation of biofilm. 	Text template
Life cycle	<p>Select from the picklist the relevant entry(ies) describing the life cycle of the microorganism under assessment, and add remarks, if any.</p>	List multi. (multi-select list with remarks)
Reference	<p>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</p> <p>Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above.</p> <p>See also Literature search at the end of the table.</p>	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Relationships to known plant or animal or human pathogens		Header 2
	<p><u>2.6 Relationship to known human pathogens and to pathogens to non-target organisms</u></p> <p>Where the microorganism is closely related to any known pathogens to humans, animals, crops or other non- target species, the applicant shall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - list the pathogens and the type of known diseases caused, - describe the known virulence factors belonging to the pathogens, - describe the known virulence factors belonging to the micro-organism, which is the active substance, 	Text template

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - describe the phylogenetic relationship between the micro-organism and the related pathogens identified, - describe the way or means to distinguish the active micro-organism from pathogenic species. 	
Related known pathogens to	<p>Indicate relationship to known plant or human or animal pathogens selecting the appropriate value from the picklist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in strain under evaluation - in closely related species - in organisms of the same genus - no 	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Phylogenic tree	<p>Upload a picture of the phylogenetic tree of the microorganism.</p> <p>The scale of the phylogenetic tree shall be selected to include relevant strains and species (e.g. in case of use of read-across among related strains or species to address data requirements). Superseded names of included micro-organisms or taxonomic groupings may be indicated in the phylogenetic tree.</p>	Image upload
Reference	<p>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</p> <p>Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above.</p> <p>See also Literature search at the end of the table.</p>	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Genetic stability and factors affecting it		Header 2
	<p><u>2.7. Genetic stability and factors affecting it</u></p> <p>Where the microorganism is a non-virulent variant of a plant pathogen virus, the likelihood of regaining virulence through mutation after application under the proposed conditions of use shall be reported, including the information on measures that can be taken to reduce the likelihood of this occurrence and the effectiveness of such measures.</p>	Text template
Non-virulent virus variant	<p>[Relevant for <u>viruses</u> only]</p> <p>Select yes if the micro-organism is a non-virulent variant of a plant pathogen.</p> <p>If yes is selected, the likelihood of regaining virulence through mutation after application under the proposed conditions of use shall be reported, including the information on measures that can be taken to reduce the likelihood of this occurrence and the effectiveness of such measures in the remarks field.</p>	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 32,000 char.)
Reference	<p>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</p> <p>Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above.</p> <p>See also Literature search at the end of the table.</p>	Link to lit. reference (multiple)

<p>Information on the production of relevant metabolites and toxins</p>	<p>Instructions on how to report information on metabolites of (potential) concern are reported in the introduction of this manual, subsection 'Information on secondary metabolites'.</p>	<p>Header 2</p>
	<p><u>2.8 Information on metabolites of concern</u></p> <p>A summary and conclusion of the assessment performed by the applicant on the secondary metabolites must be included in this field.</p> <p>The applicant shall identify under this point the metabolites of concern produced by the micro-organism, including a summary of the information submitted under data requirements points 5.5.1, 8.8.1, 6.1, 7.2.1 and 7.2.2 used to identify or to exclude metabolites as being of concern.</p> <p>All metabolites of potential concern should be listed in the Flexible Summary Metabolites in the in the <u>Section 1.4.1</u> of the product dataset.</p> <p>The evidence for exclusion of metabolite production should be reported in this field.</p> <p>Note: If Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) data are used to verify whether specific metabolite(s) of (potential) concern can be produced by the active substance, this information should be reported in this field. When WGS confirms that the gene(s) required to produce such metabolite(s) is/are absent, a targeted literature search for this/these metabolite(s) is not required, as its/their non-production has been demonstrated and no further information is needed.</p>	<p>Text template</p>
<p>Absence of genes for secondary metabolite production</p>	<p>Indicate (Y/N) the absence of gene(s) required for the production of the identified metabolite(s) of potential concern.</p> <p>Where genomic sequence data is available this should be reported in <u>Section 1.3</u> 'Identity, taxonomy and phylogeny of the microorganism' of the active substance dataset</p>	<p>List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)</p>
<p>Metabolites of potential concern identified</p>	<p>Indicate whether metabolites of potential concern were identified selecting the appropriate entry from the picklist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in strain under evaluation - in closely related species - in organisms of the same genus - no 	<p>List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)</p>
<p>Reference</p>	<p><u>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</u></p> <p>Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above.</p> <p>See also <u>Literature search</u> at the end of the table.</p>	<p>Link to lit. reference (multiple)</p>
<p>Production and resistance to antibiotics and other</p>		<p>Header 2</p>

antimicrobial agents		
	<p><u>2.9 Presence of transferable antimicrobial resistance genes</u></p> <p>Where the microorganism is a bacterium, information on any resistance to relevant antimicrobial agents shall be reported at strain level.</p> <p>Information on whether the antimicrobial resistance genes are acquired, transferable and functional shall be reported.</p> <p>Where genomic sequence data is available this should be reported in Section 1.3 'Identity, taxonomy and phylogeny of the micro-organism'</p>	Text template
Presence of antimicrobial resistance genes		List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Presence of transferable antimicrobial resistance genes	The information provided shall be sufficient to perform an evaluation as to the risks for human and animal health due to a possible transfer of relevant antimicrobial resistance genes.	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Reference	<p>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</p> <p>Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above.</p> <p>See also Literature search at the end of the table.</p>	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Robustness to environmental factors		Header 2
	<p><u>2.4 Growth requirements</u></p> <p>The conditions required for growth and proliferation of the microorganism shall be described (e.g. host, nutrients, pH, osmotic potential, humidity).</p>	Text template Display: Basic
Temperature range for growth (°C)	The minimum, optimum and maximum temperature required for growth and proliferation shall be reported.	Numeric range (decimal)
Generation time	Report the generation time under favourable growth conditions	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Reference	<p>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</p> <p>Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above.</p> <p>See also Literature search at the end of the table.</p>	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Further information on the microorganism		Header 2

	Any further relevant information.	Text template
Taxonomic level	Select the taxonomic level of the information provided above and provide a justification of the choice of taxonomic level in the remarks field	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Reference	Data source (Literature reference) – common block Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above. See also Literature search at the end of the table.	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Effectiveness against target organisms	Not relevant for PPP dossiers – This information should be reported in section 3.1 Function and target organism	Header 1
Infectiveness, dispersal and colonisation ability	Not relevant for PPP dossiers	Header 2
		Text template
Infectivity to the target organism	<u>2.5 Infectivity to the target organism</u> In case any pathogenic mode(s) of action on the target organism is described in Section 3.1 [<i>Mode of action on the target organism and host range</i>], virulence factors and (if applicable) environmental factors affecting them shall be indicated and described. The results of any relevant experimental studies and/or data/information from the existing literature at the relevant taxonomic level shall be reported.	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Reference	Data source (Literature reference) – common block Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above. See also Literature search at the end of the table.	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Methods to prevent loss of virulence of seed stock of the microorganism	Not relevant for PPP dossiers	Header 2
		Text (rich-text area)
Reference	Data source (Literature reference) – common block Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above. See also Literature search at the end of the table.	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Measures necessary to protect humans,	Not relevant for PPP dossiers Information on Precautions and Methods in case of accidents should be reported in Section 4.1 Procedures	Header 1

animals and the environment	doe cleaning and decontaminating of application equipment	
Monitoring plan to be used for the active microorganism including handling, storage, transport and use	Not relevant for PPP dossiers	Header 2
		Text (rich-text area)
Reference	<p>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</p> <p>Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above.</p> <p>See also Literature search at the end of the table.</p>	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Classification & Labelling of the micro-organism (for biocidal products)	Not relevant for PPP dossiers	Header 1
Relevant risk group specified in Article 2 of Directive 2000/54/EC		Header 2
		List (picklist)
Biological properties of the micro-organism in the biocidal product	Not relevant for PPP dossiers	Header 1
		Text template
Reference	<p>Data source (Literature reference) – common block</p> <p>Link to relevant Literature Reference entities to support the descriptions of the biological properties reported above.</p> <p>See also Literature search at the end of the table.</p>	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Supporting literature searches (if relevant)		Block of fields (repeatable) Start

Literature search	When collecting evidence for specific biological properties the method for searching, retrieving, and assessing studies for relevance and reliability should be presented. Note: For each biological properties section a separate literature search document should be completed, the literature search document should be named according to the section where the literature references were cited	Link endpoint (single) to
Remarks	Provide any additional remarks on the literature search, i.e. which section(s) of biological properties is addressed by the literature search	Text (2,000 char.)
Supporting literature searches (if relevant)		Block of fields (repeatable) End

Links to supporting material:

Directive 2000/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 September 2000 on the protection of workers from risks related to exposure to biological agents at work (seventh individual directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC) <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2000/54/2020-06-24>

Guidance on the Risk Assessment Of Metabolites Produced by Microorganisms Used As Plant Protection Active Substances. SANCO/2020/12258 Rev. 1 21 March 2024 https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/ffdf09b5-77a5-45b5-95f9-b16272f7535a_en

Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/1637>

EFSA Qualified presumption of safety (QPS) <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/qualified-presumption-safety-qps>

2.1 (Cf. 2) Origin and isolation source, occurrence and history of use

2.2 (Cf. 2) Ecology and life cycle of the microorganism

2.3 (Cf. 3.1) Mode of action on the target organism and host range

2.4 (Cf. 2) Growth requirements

2.5 (Cf. 2) Infectivity to the target organism

2.6 (Cf. 2) Relationship to known human pathogens and to pathogens to non-target organisms

2.7 (Cf. 2) Genetic stability and factors affecting it

2.8 (Cf. 2 and product dataset 1.4.1) Information on metabolites of concern

2.9 (Cf. 2) Presence of transferable antimicrobial resistance genes

3. Further information

3.1 Function and target organism - Endpoint summary

Only **one document** should be created for this endpoint summary. It must provide a **high-level overview** of all information reported in **Section 3.2**, covering the data from:

- The generic endpoint study record.
- Any other endpoint study record created to include information from specific experimental studies (if available).

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.EffectivenessAgainstTargetOrganisms		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Description of Key information	Provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here. The summary could include, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the test type - the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) - the test organism - the exposure duration - other contextual information on the origin of the key value 	
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

3.1 Function and target organism - Endpoint study record

Two separate endpoint study records should be created under this section.

A **mandatory document** must be created to provide **generic information** on:

- Function and mode of action.
- Target organisms.
- Products or objects to be protected.
- General effectiveness, including resistance.

Key instructions:

- Use endpoint: "effects on harmful organisms".
- Set adequacy of study: "supporting study".
- Complete all relevant fields, even if no experimental data is available.
- Link sources via the Literature Reference entity (type: "publication" or "other").

Additional endpoint study records should be created if experimental studies are performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.EffectivenessAgainstTargetOrganisms		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1

Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	
General information		Header 1
Background information	<p>Use this field to include any background information, if required, or any relevant introductory remark. Leave field empty if not applicable. Do not include information for which specific fields are provided.</p> <p>PURPOSE OF THIS TEMPLATE:</p> <p>This template can be used for recording general information on the effectiveness of an active substance, a plant protection product or a biocidal product, together with its active substances (as required by the relevant legislation).</p> <p>For products, efficacy studies should be reported using the corresponding template 'Efficacy data'. For active substances, the effectiveness achieved or claimed should be briefly described in this template. If required or sensible such description can be supported by including summary table(s) which give an overview of relevant efficacy studies performed with a product or products.</p> <p>As appropriate, the general information can be provided in one record or in several individual records. For instance, one record may be sensible if several target organisms, but same function and product type are addressed. Separate records may be sensible for addressing different types of target organisms and functions.</p> <p>Note that this template focuses primarily on biocides. In purpose additional pieces of information may have to be provided. Consult the programme-specific guidance on the</p>	Multi-line text
Pest / target organisms to be controlled		Header 2
Target organisms	Specify the target organism(s) to be controlled. Repeat this block of fields as necessary. Due to the great number of possible target organisms this picklist is not exhaustive. If the species name is not listed, choose an appropriate superior term (e.g. 'Acaridae:') and specify by entering free text in the related field. If organism is not listed at all, choose 'other:' and enter the name or several names in a row in the related text field.	
Scientific name	<p>Select appropriate scientific name from picklist. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. See also instructions on this block of fields.</p> <p>Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for target organism if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses. If scientific name is not available in the picklist, select "other" and refer to EPPO lists available at https://gd.eppo.int/</p>	Open list with remarks

Common name	Select appropriate common name from picklist. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. See also instructions on this block of fields. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field. EPPO codes for common name relevant to plant protection products can be retrieved at https://gd.eppo.int/ .	Open list with remarks
Developmental stage of target pest	Indicate the developmental stage of the target organism. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. If not applicable, leave field empty. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for the developmental stage if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses.	Open list with remarks
Developmental stage of target plant	Indicate the developmental stage of the target organism. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. If not applicable, leave field empty.	Multi select open list with remarks
Target organisms		
Products, organisms or objects to be protected / under study		Header 2
Organisms (to be protected) or treated materials	Describe and specify the organism(s) or materials(s) / object(s) to be protected, e.g. human, pets, farm animals, fur- and wool-bearing animals, plants, plant products, seeds, storage goods, drinking water, hard surface material, porous surface.	Multi-line text
Information on intended use and application		Header 2
Function addressed	Indicate the function of the substance. Multiple selection is possible for indicating additional functions provided they relate to the same product type indicated in the next field. However, it may be sensible or required according to legislation-specific guidance to use separate records for each function. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for the function if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses.	Multi select open list with remarks
Product type	Indicate the product type in which the active substance is intended to be included or which is envisaged for the product. In case of multiple product types use separate records for each of them. Note that only product types related to EU BPD are listed. For other legislations, choose 'other:' and specify in the related text field.	Open list

Field of use envisaged / User	If the use conditions are fully described in a GAP document in the dossier, it is sufficient to make reference to the GAP document which describes the use. IUCLID document name and UUID. If this is provided additional information on the use of the product already described in the GAP document does not need to be provided	Text area
Information on application of product		Header 2
Method of application	For the product, indicate the method of application. Multiple selection is possible for indicating more than one method. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for the method of application if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses, e.g. 'VII.1 (EU BPD)'. Reference to use description document is sufficient. Alternatively, see Field of use envisaged / User	Multi select open list with remarks (2000)
Details on application	See Field of use envisaged / User	Text template
General information on effectiveness		Header 2
Effects on target organisms	The effects on the target organisms required for the claimed efficacy should be described and specified if possible for each use and method of application if these have different effects, including any effect-concentration dependencies or the possible existence of a threshold concentration of the active substance. Refer to the instructions given in the relevant guidance documents (e.g. EU BPD TNsG, SANCO and EPPO standards). In case of a submission of an active substance the effectiveness achieved or claimed should be briefly described. If required or sensible such description can be supported by including summary table(s) which give an overview of relevant efficacy studies performed with a product or products. Upload predefined table(s) in the rich text field 'Overall remarks'. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). To show possible differences, the use, i.e. product type and method of application of the product(s) envisaged should also be given. For products, efficacy studies should be reported using the corresponding template 'Efficacy data'.	Text area
Mode of action	Indicate the principles of the mode of action for the function indicated in above field, e.g. 'acute toxin: contact poison'. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for the mode of action if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses, e.g. 'III.1.2 (EU BPD)'. For plant	Open list with remarks

	protection products mode of action, FRAC, HRAC and IRAC codes can be reported.	
Details on mode of action	For the function indicated in above field, indicate the principles of the mode of action; e.g. 'contact poison' or 'stomach poison'. Briefly describe the biochemical and physiological mechanisms, e.g. 'cholinesterase inhibition' and the biochemical pathway and specify any time delay between application and effect. Use the freetext template as appropriate (delete/add elements). For further instructions refer to the relevant guidance documents.	Text template
(Possible) Occurrence of resistance	Indicate whether resistance can possibly develop including cross-resistance. As appropriate include an appraisal of the information gained from the efficacy studies.	Text area
Management strategies to avoid resistance	Describe any appropriate management strategies towards the minimization of the development of resistance.	Text area
Any other known limitations and management strategies	As applicable describe any other known limitations and relevant management strategies towards them.	Text area
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Details on results		Text area
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

EPPO (2017) EPPO Global Database. Database available online: <https://gd.eppo.int>

EPPO database on PP1 standards <https://pp1.eppo.int/>

3.2 (Cf. product dataset, 3.1) Field of use envisaged

3.3 (Cf. product dataset, 3.1) Crops or products protected or treated

3.4 (Cf. 3.1) Information on possible development of resistance in the target organism(s)

3.5 Literature data – Flexible record

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide a description of the methodology used for the search for all relevant data from scientific peer reviewed open literature.

In accordance with Art 8(5) of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009, the summary dossier shall include “Scientific peer-reviewed open literature, as determined by the Authority, on the active substance and its relevant metabolites dealing with side-effects on health, the environment and non-target species and published within the last 10 years before the date of submission of the dossier shall be added by the applicant to the dossier” (both in case of chemical and microbial active substance).

Link to all Literature Reference entities that were retrieved from the literature search and are considered relevant and reliable after the full text screening step should be included in the field “Link to relevant studies”. An appropriate Endpoint Study Record should be completed for each relevant study and the literature reference included in the data source section).

For literature searches on **secondary metabolites** refer to the dedicated subsection in the introduction of this manual.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.LiteratureSearch		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: “User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests” available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant studies	Link to all Literature Reference entities that were retrieved from the literature search and are considered relevant and reliable after the full text screening step. An appropriate Endpoint Study Record should be completed for each relevant study and the literature reference included in the data source section.	Header 1
Literature reference(s)		Literature reference list
Description of key information	Summary of all relevant data from the scientific peer reviewed open literature on the active substance, metabolites and breakdown or reaction products and plant protection products containing the active substance and dealing with side-effects on health, the environment and non-target species	Rich text area

Overall summary of the literature search	<p>Summary of the methodology used to retrieve relevant studies on side-effects on health, the environment and non-target species.</p> <p>Report the criteria used to classify the references as being clearly non-relevant (e.g. not related to pesticides).</p> <p>Report the criteria used to assess the reliability of the studies.</p>	Rich text area
Search strategy	Indicate how the literature search was carried out.	Header 1
Bibliographic databases used in the literature review and search results	A description each of the search strategies used in the literature review	
Online search service	<p>Select the database/source where the search was performed. Use other to indicate a database/source that is not included in the list. The remarks field should contain the justification for selecting the database/source.</p> <p>More information on databases/sources is provided in the supporting materials below</p>	Open list with remarks
Date of search	Provide the date when the search was performed using the database.	Date
Time window of the literature search	The period covered in the literature search e.g. 2010 to 2020	Text
Search string(s) used	<p>The search strings used to retrieve the records e.g.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ts= (Beauveria bassiana OR B. bassiana) 2. ts=(Beauveria bassiana OR B. bassiana) AND (secondary metabolite* OR toxin*) 3. ts=(Beauveria bassiana OR B. bassiana) AND (Antimicrobial resist*) 	Multi-line text
Filters	Indicate if filters were applied in the search. If yes is selected the filters applied must be described	Closed list with remarks
Limits	Indicate if any limits were applied in the search, for example only studies in English. If yes is the limits applied must be described	Closed list with remarks
Number of hits	The number of hits for the search in each database/source	Integer
Number of hits after refinement	The number of hits after refinement, if applicable	Integer
Number of hits after duplicate removal	The number of hits after duplicate removal	Integer

Evaluation of the review		Header 1
Records retrieved	The number of records retrieved when the results for the searches above where combined	Integer
Records after removal of duplicates	Total number of summary records retrieved after removing duplicates from all database searches	Integer
Records after rapid assessment	Report the number of records retained after title/abstract screening	Integer
Records after detailed assessment	Report the number of records retained after full text screening	Integer
Reliable studies	Report the number of records retained after the reliability assessment	Integer
Evaluated studies	Number of studies included in the dossier, reported in an endpoint study record and used as supporting information. These studies should be listed in the Literature reference(s) field and the number should be the same.	Integer
Publications excluded from the risk assessment after detailed assessment of full-text documents	For each of the studies excluded on the basis of relevance or reliability link to the Literature Reference entity and describe the reason for exclusion.	
Literature reference	Link a reference to the excluded publication.	Literature reference list
Exclusion reason	Reason for not including publication in dossier (based on relevance and reliability criteria).	Multi-line text
Publications excluded from the risk assessment after detailed assessment of full-text documents	For each of the studies excluded on the basis of relevance or reliability link to the Literature Reference entity and describe the reason for exclusion	
Additional information		Header 1
Additional information	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Overall remarks, attachments – common block".</p> <p>Any other information needed to interpret the results for the literature research.</p> <p>The bibliographic results of literature searches can be uploaded here in RIS format or as an Excel table containing bibliographic information.</p>	Rich text area

	<p>Upload supporting files e.g. bibliographic metadata.</p> <p>Indicate here criteria for selected studies: a) Studies that provide data for establishing or refining risk assessment parameters. (b) Studies relevant for the data requirement but in the opinion of the applicant provide only supplementary information c) Studies for which relevance cannot be clearly determined.</p>	
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Link to supporting material:

Submission of scientific peer-reviewed open literature for the approval of pesticide active substances under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009.
<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/j.efsa.2011.2092>

Further guidance on performing and presenting the literature search
<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/action/downloadSupplement?doi=10.2903%2Fj.efsa.2011.2092&file=efs22092-sup-0001-Appendix.pdf>

Inventory of Sources of Scientific Evidence Relevant to EFSA's Risk
<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.2903/sp.efsa.2014.EN-593>

Technical Manual for Performing Electronic Literature Searches in Food and Feed Safety
<http://www.syreaf.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/Technical-Manual-for-Performing-Electronic-Literature-Searches-in-Food-and-Feed-Safety.pdf>

Additional considerations:

The applicant must ensure that terms and conditions asserted by any copyright holder of publications or information submitted to EFSA are fully satisfied. The applicant should consult with copyright licensing authorities (i.e. at national level) for guidance on purchasing copyright licenses to reproduce any publications provided to EFSA. The applicant remains solely responsible and liable for obtaining all necessary authorizations and rights to use, reproduce and share the publications provided to EFSA.

4. Analytical methods

4. Analytical methods – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide a summary of the analytical methods submitted together with the most relevant information and link to the individual analytical methods study reports. A tabulated format is most advisable.

For each group of analytical methods please provide a separate summary:

- Methods for the analysis of the active substance as manufactured
- Methods for risk assessment
- Methods for post-approval control and monitoring purposes, if applicable

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.AnalyticalMethods		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Cross-reference: ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AnalyticalMethods
Description of key information	Provide an assessment of the suitability of the proposed methods for enforcement and risk assessment. Note: Further information on residue definitions and LOQs can be provided in Proposed residue definitions document and Proposed maximum residue levels document in the Residues Section	
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block " Attached (sanitised) documents for publication: The file " Template 4.1 - Template for the overview table for analytical methods for risk assessment" (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4556992) shall be uploaded here.	Header 1

Links to supporting documents

OECD (2007). Guidance Document on Pesticide Residue Analytical Methods. Environment, Health and Safety Publications. Series on Testing and Assessment No. 72 and Series on Pesticides No. 39. (ENV/JM/MONO(2007)17)
[http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono\(2007\)17&doclanguage=en](http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono(2007)17&doclanguage=en)

Guidance Document on Pesticide Analytical Methods for Risk Assessment and Post-approval Control and Monitoring Purposes (SANTE/2020/12830, Rev.1)

https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-03/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_res_mrl_guidelines-2020-12830.pdf

EU Guidance document: Technical Active Substance and Plant protection products: Guidance for generating and reporting methods of analysis in support of pre- and post-registration data requirements for Annex (Section 4) of Regulation (EU) No 283/2013 and Annex (Section 5) of Regulation (EU) No 284/2013 (SANCO/3030/99 rev.5)

https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-03/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_phys-chem-ana_3030.pdf

Technical Guideline on the Evaluation of Extraction Efficiency of Residue Analytical Methods (SANTE/2017/10632)

https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-05/pesticides_mrl_guidelines_wrkdoc_2017-10632.pdf

4. Analytical methods – Endpoint study record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report analytical methods used for the generation of pre-approval data and required for post-approval control and monitoring purposes. Descriptions of methods must be provided and include details of equipment, materials and conditions used. On request, the following must be provided: (a) analytical standards of the purified active substance; (b) samples of the active substance as manufactured; (c) analytical standards of relevant metabolites and all other components included in all monitoring residue definitions; (d) samples of reference substances for the relevant impurities. Where possible, the standards referred to in points (a) and (c) shall be made commercially available and, on request, the distributing company shall be named.

Provide all relevant validation data, including matrix effects, description of calibration procedure, calibration data, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), recovery (individual data and mean) and repeatability, data providing the selectivity and specificity of the method, stability of standards and extracts, confirmation data (if required), independent laboratory validation data (if required), extraction efficiency of solvents used in methods for food and feed of plant and animal origin.

It is recommended to use the cross-reference feature in endpoint study records to cross link to a specific analytical method endpoint study record used in the study.

Note: In order to facilitate further extraction of the analytical method(s) related to analysis of the **impurities** (other than relevant impurities) in a Confidential report¹⁸ all analytical methods for significant impurities must have 'Methods for significant impurities' in the '**Endpoint**' field (under 'administrative data' block). The documents should be duly filled in, including all the dedicated structured fields for the Materials and methods and Results sections.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AnalyticalMethods		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Background		Header 1
Background information	Use this field to include any background information, if required, or any relevant introductory remarks on the study summary. Leave field empty if not	Multi-line text

¹⁸ To replace Document J, once applicable to microbial dossiers

	<p>applicable. Do not include information for which specific fields are provided. For instance, include any background information on the test substance in fields on 'Test materials'.</p> <p>PURPOSE OF THIS TEMPLATE:</p> <p>This template can be used for summarising analytical methods for determining a given substance in various matrices. Depending on the requirements of the relevant legislation, methods for the following matrices may have to be recorded: soil, sediment, suspended particulates, air, water (including drinking water), animal and human body fluids and tissues, plants, plant products, food and feeding stuffs, formulated product, other.</p>	
Method class	Indicate the method classes reported in this document.	Picklist
Materials and methods	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Material and methods – common block"</p> <p>Guideline: different guidelines apply for the technical material and for residues. Select the applicable test guideline based on the appropriate scenario.</p>	Header 1
Matrix / medium	<p>Indicate the medium (e.g. plants, high oil content, egg, soil, groundwater) for which the analytical method is described. In the supplementary remarks field, you can add explanations as appropriate.</p> <p>Note: The picklist is not descriptive as to whether analytical methods have to be submitted for each of the matrices provided in the picklist. If the methods for several matrices can be summarised in one record, you can copy this field for indicating the respective matrices.</p>	Multi select open list with remarks
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Analytical (primary) method		Header 2
Instrument / detector	<p>Indicate the instrument / detector used for the quantitative analysis including the type of detector, e.g. 'HPLC-UV'. Multiple selection is possible if more than one method needs to be specified. Give any further details in field 'Details on analytical data collection method'.</p> <p>Note: If a residue analytical method is recorded, the instrument/detector used for the so-called data collection or data-gathering method should be specified here. Data collection method is the analytical method used to collect quantitative residue data by analysing the analyte(s) in the matrices. This method can be identical with or differ from the so-called enforcement method which has to be recorded under the heading 'Enforcement method (if applicable)'. Enforcement method is a validated analytical method which can be applied by the regulatory agency for enforcing the proposed</p>	Multi select open list

	tolerance, i.e. maximum residue limits (MRL) for pesticides.	
Residue method	Indicate if the method detects multiple analytes. Further details can be provided in the remarks.	Picklist
Extraction and clean-up	Indicate the method used for extraction and clean-up. For major deviations or different methods, select other and provide remarks.	
Flow diagram	Provide an image of the analytical method steps	image
Further details on analytical method	<p>Briefly describe further details on the principles of the method used to detect the analytes (to be specified, e.g. 'parent compound', 'parent and transformation products' or 'transformation product:') in matrices. Use free text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. For example, add specific parameters in the case of inorganic chemicals. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.</p> <p>Note: If a residue analytical method is recorded, the details for the so-called data collection or data-gathering method should be specified here. As to the terms 'data collection method' and 'enforcement method' see help text for field 'Instrument / detector'.</p> <p>Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p>	Text template
Enforcement method (if applicable)	This section should be completed if Enforcement has been selected in the Method Class field. Provide information only where it differs from the information provided in the 'Principles of the analytical methods section'.	Header 2
Instrument detector / for enforcement method	<p>If no enforcement method is proposed or required, ignore this field. An enforcement method is a validated analytical method which can be applied by the regulatory agency for enforcing the proposed tolerance, i.e. maximum residue limits (MRL) for pesticides. If such a method is proposed indicate the instrument / detector used in the enforcement method.</p> <p>Multiple selection is possible if more than one method needs to be specified. Give any further details in field 'Details on data enforcement method'.</p>	Multi select open list
Residue method	Indicate if the method detects multiple analytes. Further details can be provided in the remarks.	picklist
Extraction and clean-up	Indicate the method used for extraction and clean-up. For major deviations or different methods, select other and provide remarks.	picklist
Flow diagram	Provide an image of the analytical method steps	image
Further details on enforcement method	Briefly describe further details on the principles of the method used to detect the analytes (to be specified, e.g. "parent compound", "parent and transformation products" or "transformation product:") in	Text template

	<p>matrices. Use free text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. For example, add specific parameters in the case of inorganic chemicals. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.</p> <p>Note: If a residue analytical method is recorded, the details for the so-called data collection or data-gathering method should be specified here. As to the terms "data collection method" and "enforcement method" see help text for field "Instrument / detector".</p> <p>Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p>	
Confirmatory method (if applicable)	<p>This section should be completed if Confirmatory has been selected in the Method Class field.</p> <p>Provide information only where it differs from the information provided in the 'Principles of the analytical methods section'.</p>	Header 2
Instrument / detector for confirmatory method	<p>'If not applicable, ignore this field. If a confirmatory method was used (i.e. applying techniques to demonstrate specificity in case the original method is not highly specific), indicate the instrument / detector used.</p> <p>Note: Not all picklist items may be relevant for a confirmatory technique. Multiple selection is possible if more than one method needs to be specified.</p> <p>Give any further details in field "Details on data confirmatory method".'</p>	Multi select open list
Residue method	<p>Indicate if the method detects multiple analytes. Further details can be provided in the remarks.</p>	picklist
Extraction and clean-up	<p>Indicate the method used for extraction and clean-up. For major deviations or different methods, select other and provide remarks.</p>	picklist
Suitability of the method for confirmation	<p>Indicate the method type used to confirm correct analyte identity and quantification.</p>	picklist
Further details on confirmatory method	<p>Briefly describe further details on the principles of the confirmatory method if any.</p> <p>Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p>	Multi-line text
Independent Laboratory Validation – ILV (if applicable)	<p>This section should be completed for primary monitoring methods for food of plant and animal origin. ILV for drinking or ground water should be also submitted for enforcement methods.</p>	Header 2
Instrument/detector	<p>Indicate the instrument / detector used for the quantitative analysis of the parent compound / transformation products including the type of detector, e.g. 'HPLC-UV'. Multiple selection is possible if more than one method needs to be</p>	Multiselect open list

	<p>specified. Give any further details in field 'Details on analytical data collection method'.</p> <p>Note: If a residue analytical method is recorded, the instrument/detector used for the so-called data collection or data-gathering method should be specified here. Data collection method is the analytical method used to collect quantitative residue data by analysing the analyte(s) in the matrices. This method can be identical with or differ from the so-called enforcement method which has to be recorded under the heading 'Enforcement method (if applicable)'. Enforcement method is a validated analytical method which can be applied by the regulatory agency for enforcing the proposed tolerance, i.e. maximum residue limits (MRL) for pesticides.</p>	
Residue method	Indicate if the method detects multiple analytes. Further details can be provided in the remarks.	picklist
Extraction and clean-up	Indicate the method used for extraction and clean-up. For major deviations or different methods, select other and provide remarks.	picklist
Flow diagram	Provide an image of the analytical method steps	image
Details on ILV	<p>Briefly describe further details on the principles of the ILV method if any.</p> <p>Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p>	Multi-line text
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion	Report the results for the method described in the 'Principles of the analytical methods section'.	Header 1
Results using analytical (primary) method		Header 2
Recovery	Complete the template for the evaluated recovery with the following information	Text template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Indicate the matrix the analyte was extracted from	text
MRM/ parent m/z	Report the m/z value of the parent (precursor) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
MRM/fragment m/z	Report the m/z value of the fragment (product) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
Fortification level	Report the fortification levels at which repeatability was evaluated	Numeric
Number replicates	Number of determinations (n) per concentration level	Numeric
Range recovery (%)	Report lowest and highest values of the recovery	Numeric range

Mean recovery (%)	Report mean value of recovery	Numeric range
RSD (%)	Report recovery relative standard deviation	numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
Additional details on recovery results	Report any additional detail not covered by the other fields, if any.	text
Repeatability	Complete the template for the evaluated repeatability with the following information	Template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Indicate the matrix the analyte was extracted from	text
Number replicates	Report number of replicates	Numeric
Mean content	Report mean concentration of the analyte	Numeric
RSD_R (%)	Report reproducibility relative standard deviation	Numeric
RSD_r (%)	Report repeatability relative standard deviation	Numeric
Horrat value	Report Horrat value	Numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
LOQ/LOD	Complete the template for the determined LOQ/LOD with the following information	template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Short description of the matrix tested	text
Limit of quantification	Enter the limit of quantification (LOQ)	numeric
Limit of detection	Enter the limit of detection (LOD), if relevant and validated	numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
Calibration	Complete the template for the calibration with the following information	template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Standards	Describe the standards used in the calibration	Picklist
Matrix	Short description of the matrix tested	text
MRM/ parent m/z	Report the m/z value of the parent (precursor) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
MRM/ fragment m/z	Report the m/z value of the fragment (product) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
Calibration range	Report lowest and highest value of calibration values	Numeric range
Calibration equation	Report the calibration equation	text
Correlation coefficient (r)	Report the value of the correlation coefficient	numeric
Correlation coefficient (r²)	Report the value of the correlation coefficient	numeric
Number replicates	Indicate the number of replicates	numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text

Matrix effects (%)	Report the matrix effect (100 * peak area or slope (matrix)/ peak area or slope (solvent) – 100)	Numeric
Matrix effects remarks	Provide additional information on the Matrix effects, further information should be provided if matrix effects exceed 20%	text
Additional details on analytical (primary) method	Provide additional information on the results of the primary method. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	text
Results using enforcement method (if applicable)		Header 2
Recovery	Complete the template for the evaluated recovery with the following information.	Text template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Indicate the matrix the analyte was extracted from	text
MRM/ parent m/z	Report the m/z value of the parent (precursor) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
MRM/ fragment m/z	Report the m/z value of the fragment (product) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
Fortification level	Report the fortification levels at which repeatability was evaluated	Numeric
Number replicates	Number of determinations (n) per concentration level	Numeric
Range recovery (%)	Report lowest and highest value of the range recovery	Numeric range
Mean recovery (%)	Report mean value of the recovery	Numeric range
RSD(%)	Report recovery relative standard deviation	numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
Additional details on recovery results	Report any additional detail not covered by the other fields, if any.	text
Repeatability	Complete the template for the evaluated repeatability with the following information	Template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Indicate the matrix the analyte was extracted from	text
Number replicates	Report number of replicates	Numeric
Mean content	Report mean concentration of the analyte	Numeric
RSD_R (%)	Report reproducibility relative standard deviation	Numeric
RSD_r (%)	Report repeatability relative standard deviation	Numeric
Horrat value	Report Horrat value	Numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text

LOQ/LOD	Complete the template for the determined LOQ/LOD with the following information	template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Short description of the matrix tested	text
Limit of quantification	Enter the limit of quantification (LOQ)	numeric
Limit of detection	Enter the limit of detection (LOD), if relevant and validated	numeric
Remarks	Report and relevant remarks if any.	text
Calibration	Complete the template for the calibration with the following information	template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Standards	Describe the standards used in the calibration	Picklist
Matrix	Short description of the matrix tested	text
MRM/ parent m/z	Report the m/z value of the parent (precursor) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
MRM/ fragment m/z	Report the m/z value of the fragment (product) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
Calibration range	Report lowest and highest calibration values	Numeric range
Calibration equation	Report calibration equation	text
Correlation coefficient (r)	Report the value of the correlation coefficient	numeric
Correlation coefficient (r2)	Report the value of the correlation coefficient	numeric
Number replicates	Report number of replicates	numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
Matrix effects (%)	Report the matrix effect (100 * peak area or slope (matrix)/ peak area or slope (solvent) – 100)	Numeric
Matrix effects remarks	Provide additional information on the Matrix effects, further information should be provided if matrix effects exceed 20%	text
Additional details on enforcement method	Provide additional information on the results of the enforcement method. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	text
Results using confirmatory method (if applicable)	If not applicable, ignore this field. If applicable (as for enforcement methods), present the results of the confirmation (whether it is simultaneous to the primary detection or by an independent analytical technique) in terms of whether or not it was conducted according to guideline specifications.	Header 2
Recovery	Complete the template for the evaluated recovery with the following information.	template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Indicate the matrix the analyte was extracted from	text

MRM/ parent m/z	Report the m/z value of the parent (precursor) ion of the mass transition monitored. For confirmation simultaneous to primary detection, discuss whether enough number of qualifier ions/mass transitions were monitored according to guideline specifications.	Numeric
MRM/ fragment m/z	Report the m/z value of the fragment (product) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
Fortification level	Report the fortification levels at which repeatability was evaluated. Repeatability should be evaluated at least at the level of the respective LOQ of the primary method.	Numeric
Number replicates	Number of determinations (n) per concentration level	Numeric
Range recovery (%)	Report lower and highest values of recovery	Numeric range
Mean recovery (%)	Report mean value of recovery	Numeric range
RSD (%)	Report recovery relative standard deviation	numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
Repeatability	Complete the template for the evaluated repeatability with the following information	Template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Indicate the matrix the analyte was extracted from	text
Number replicates	Report number of replicates	Numeric
Mean content	Report mean concentration of the analyte	Numeric
RSD_R (%)	Report reproducibility relative standard deviation	Numeric
RSD_r (%)	Report repeatability relative standard deviation	Numeric
Horrat value	Report Horrat value	Numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
LOQ/LOD	For confirmation method this template (table) is not relevant.	template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Indicate the matrix the analyte was extracted from	text
Limit of quantification	Enter the limit of quantification (LOQ)	numeric
Limit of detection	Enter the limit of detection (LOD), if relevant and validated	numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	test
Calibration	Complete the template for the calibration with the following information	template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Standards	Describe the standards used in the calibration	Picklist
Matrix	Short description of the matrix tested	text

MRM/ parent m/z	Report the m/z value of the parent (precursor) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
MRM/ fragment m/z	Report the m/z value of the fragment (product) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
Calibration range	Report lowest and highest values of calibration values	Numeric range
Calibration equation	Report calibration equation	text
Correlation coefficient (r)	Report the value of the correlation coefficient	numeric
Correlation coefficient (r2)	Report the value of the correlation coefficient	numeric
Number replicates	Indicate the number of replicates	numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
Matrix effects (%)	Report the matrix effect (100 * peak area or slope (matrix)/ peak area or slope (solvent) – 100)	Numeric
Matrix effects remarks	Provide additional information on the Matrix effects, further information should be provided if matrix effects exceed 20%	text
Additional details on confirmatory method	Provide additional information on the results of the confirmatory method. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	text
Independent laboratory validation (if applicable)	If not applicable, ignore this field. If applicable (as for enforcement methods), discuss the independent laboratory validation (ILV) in terms of whether or not it was conducted according to guideline specifications. Discuss any method modifications that may impact the analyses of the residues (e.g., altered LOQ) that are suggested by the independent laboratory.	Header 2
Recovery	Complete the template for the evaluated recovery with the following information.	text template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Indicate the matrix the analyte was extracted from	text
MRM/ parent m/z	Report the m/z value of the parent (precursor) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
MRM/ fragment m/z	Report the m/z value of the fragment (product) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
Fortification level	Report the fortification levels at which repeatability was evaluated.	Numeric
Number replicates	Number of determinations (n) per concentration level	Numeric
Range recovery (%)	Report lowest and highest values of the recovery	Numeric range
Mean recovery (%)	Report mean value of recovery	Numeric range
RSD (%)	Report recovery relative standard deviation	numeric

Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
Repeatability	Complete the template for the evaluated repeatability with the following information	Template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Indicate the matrix the analyte was extracted from	text
Number replicates	Report number of replicates	Numeric
Mean content	Report mean concentration of the analyte	Numeric
RSD_R (%)	Report reproducibility relative standard deviation	Numeric
RSD_r (%)	Report repeatability relative standard deviation	Numeric
Horrat value	Report Horrat value	Numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
LOQ/LOD	Complete the template for the determined LOQ/LOD with the following information	template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Matrix	Short description of the matrix tested	text
Limit of quantification	Enter the limit of quantification (LOQ). It should confirm the LOQ of the primary method.	numeric
Limit of detection	Enter the limit of detection (LOD), if relevant and validated	numeric
Remarks	Report and relevant remarks if any.	test
Calibration	Complete the template for the calibration with the following information	template
Analyte	Link the reference substance of the analyte	
Standards	Describe the standards used in the calibration	Picklist
Matrix	Short description of the matrix tested	text
MRM/ parent m/z	Report the m/z value of the parent (precursor) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
MRM/ fragment m/z	Report the m/z value of the fragment (product) ion of the mass transition monitored	Numeric
Calibration range	Report lowest and highest value of calibration values	Numeric range
Calibration equation	Report the calibration equation	text
Correlation coefficient (r)	Report the value of the correlation coefficient	numeric
Correlation coefficient (r²)	Report the value of the correlation coefficient	numeric
Number replicates	Indicate the number of replicates	numeric
Remarks	Report relevant remarks if any.	text
Matrix effects (%)	Report the matrix effect (100* peak area or slope (matrix)/peak area or slope (solvent) – 100)	numeric
Matrix effects remarks	Provide additional information on the Matrix effects, further information should be provided if matrix effects exceed 20%.	text

Additional details on independent laboratory validation	Use this field to detail any differences between the primary method and the ILV method. If this is reported in a separate study, the ILV study should be cross-referenced to this study.	picklist
Remarks	Provide additional information on the results of the ILV not covered in the previous fields.	text
Any other information on results tables	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Any other information on results incl. tables – common block"</p> <p>Provide here the results of the evaluation of extraction efficiency according to SANTE/2017/10632. Rev. 5.</p> <p>Extraction efficiency should be evaluated for all plant matrix groups or animal commodities for which residue analytical methods are required (pre- and post-registration).</p> <p>As a first step, the evaluation of extraction efficiency should be done with radiolabelled material. If not available for the matrix group where the crop(s) of interest belong(s), cross-validation studies should be performed and detailed results provided as indicated in the extraction efficiency technical guideline SANTE/2017/10632.</p> <p>Enter any details (including tables) that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. If this is reported in a separate study, the evaluation of extraction efficiency should be cross-referenced to this study and ideally, the main conclusions with a conclusive justification reported here.</p>	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

OECD Guidance document on pesticide residue analytical methods
[http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono\(2007\)17&doclanguage=en](http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono(2007)17&doclanguage=en)

Technical Active Substance and Plant protection products: Guidance for generating and reporting methods of analysis in support of pre- and post-registration data requirements for Annex (Section 4) of Regulation (EU) No 283/2013 and Annex (Section 5) of Regulation (EU) No 284/2013. https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-03/pesticides_ppp_app_proc_guide_phys-chem-ana_3030.pdf

Technical Guideline on the Evaluation of Extraction Efficiency of Residue Analytical Methods – SANTE 2017/10632 rev.5, 11 May 2023 https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-05/pesticides_mrl_guidelines_wrkdoc_2017-10632.pdf

Residue analytical methods for risk assessment and post-approval control and monitoring purposes (SANTE/2020/12830 Rev 2). https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-04/pesticides_mrl_guidelines_2020-12830.pdf

Principles of analytical methods

Instrument / detector

✓ HPLC-UV

Details on analytical method

Method REM 138.12

Homogenized plant samples are extracted with acetonitrile. Fatty coextracts are removed by partitioning into hexane. The analytes are cleaned up subsequently by solid phase extraction on a C-18 cartridge, reextraction into hexane-diethyl ether and a second solid phase extraction step on a silica cartridge. Active substance is eluted in a fraction and determined by HPLC on a 2-column switching system with UV-detection.

Results and discussion

Recovery results and characteristics of analytical method

Recovery results

Please refer to the table below for more details.

Characteristics of analytical method

COMPOUND (ANALYTE): Active substance

- Equipment ID: HPLC-UV
- Limit of quantitation (LOQ): 0.02 mg/kg for grain, 0.1 mg/kg for straw and green plant material
- Accuracy / precision: all mean recoveries of the individual fortifications levels as well as the overall mean recoveries are within the range of 70 - 110%
- Repeatability: all the relative standard deviations are less than 20%
- Linearity: not reported
- Specificity: The control chromatograms generally have no peaks above the chromatographic background and the spiked sample chromatograms contain only the analyte peak of interest.

4.1 (CF. 4) METHODS FOR THE ANALYSIS OF THE MPCA AS MANUFACTURED

4.2 (CF. 4) METHODS TO DETERMINE THE DENSITY OF THE MICROORGANISM AND QUANTIFY RESIDUES

5. Effects on Human Health

Introduction

When compiling the dossier for active substances **and their metabolites**, applicants should consult programme-specific guidance under Commission Communication on list of test methods and guidance documents for active substances available at [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52023XC0609\(02\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52023XC0609(02))¹⁹.

For mammalian toxicology studies it is recommended to present the results in a tabular format.

The following templates should be used when compiling documents in this section:

Template name and link	Information
Template 5.1 Template for presentation of results in tabular format for mammalian toxicology studies	This word file contains the template for presentation of results in tabular format for mammalian toxicology studies, replacing the appendix F of the EFSA administrative guidance on submission of dossiers and assessment reports for the peer-review of pesticide active substances (EFSA, 2019). The template shall be used when compiling tables in the "Any other information on results incl. tables" field in the relevant endpoint study record(s) .

In cases where **read-across** from a supporting source substance (structural analogue or surrogate) is proposed for metabolites or impurities, the information shall be provided in the IUCLID section corresponding to the endpoint study record of the target substance. In the endpoint of the target substance the following sections should be filled in:

- **Administrative data:** endpoint, adequacy of the study, justification (read-across templates) and cross-reference (to the endpoint study record of the source substance)
- **Test material:** specify here the material that is the target of the read-across.
- The **results** shall always be reported in the target record even if they may be identical to the source endpoint study record if read-across is truly one-to-one. However, there may be differences between the source and target chemicals, which influence the numerical result (e.g. molecular weight).
- **Applicant's summary and conclusion:** the information should reflect the target material.

Applicants are also reminded to:

1. ensure that an **endpoint study summary** is **always created** for each endpoint/properties assessed across all datasets in the dossier (e.g. active substance AND metabolites).
2. if an endpoint study summary does not allow for the **reporting of multiple species** in a single document, create separate endpoint study summaries for each species to ensure that all relevant data are captured
3. Similarly, if an endpoint study summary does not allow for the **reporting of studies with different durations** in a single document, applicants should create separate endpoint study summaries for each study duration to ensure that all relevant data are captured.
4. compile all the relevant data regarding key endpoints for assessment and **link to the summary** only those studies from which the endpoints are derived (i.e., if additional

¹⁹ Communication from the Commission concerning Part B of the Annex to Commission Regulation (EU) No 283/2013 setting out the data requirements for active substances in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market. OJ C 202, 9.6.2023, pagg. 14–24

studies are provided but not used to derive the final key endpoints, they do not need to be linked).

5. flag always which **results are "key"** (i.e. used to derive the final endpoints for assessment) and which are not in the endpoint study records when available.
6. select always a justification for **data waiving** when a data waiving is proposed. If the option "other:" is selected, provide a brief justification (no more than 255 char) in the box and do not only refer to the remarks section. The remarks can be used to provide additional details on the justification.

5. Effects on Human health – Flexible summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to report toxicological reference values. These are the Acceptable operator exposure level (AOEL), Acceptable daily intake (ADI), Acute reference dose (ARfD) and Acute Acceptable operator Exposure Level (AAOEL) values derived for the active substance and, if applicable, its metabolite(s).

Note: Instructions for compiling this flexible record are applicable to active substances and metabolites.

When specific reference values are allocated for metabolites, data should be reported in the flexible record created under the relevant metabolite dataset. Otherwise, data can be reported in the flexible record under the active substance dataset.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ToxRefValues		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	Provide a summary of the most relevant information used to derive the key values for the assessment. This field should be also used to provide information on the toxicological reference values of the metabolites, if applicable.	Rich text area
Human health hazard characteristics		Header 1
AOEL (Acceptable operator exposure level)		Header 2
Not allocated	Check the box if an AOEL is not necessary for the application	Check box
Justification	Justification for the non-derivation of an AOEL	Text
AOEL	Report the AOEL value and select the relevant units	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Population	Select the relevant population	Multi-picklist

Assessment body	Select the relevant assessment body	Picklist
Study retained	Type of study used to derive the AOEL (species and duration)	Multi select open list with remarks
Route of original study	Route of exposure in the study used to derive the AOEL	Closed list
Oral absorption value (%)	Oral absorption value derived from the toxicokinetic studies expressed as a percentage	Decimal
Overall uncertainty factor (UF)	The overall assessment factor is the product of all the assessment factors used. The default UF is 100 (10 for intraspecies differences and 10 for interspecies differences).	Text
Justification of the overall UF	Justification for the uncertainty factor applied considering intra/inter species extrapolation. Please detail if additional UF are applied e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UF for dose response relationship i.e. consideration should be given to the uncertainties in the dose descriptor as the surrogate for the true no-adverse-effect-level. - For instance, in case the starting point for AOEL derivation is a LOAEL instead of a NOAEL, the uncertainty factor should be between 2 and 10. However, by using the BMD approach instead of NOAEL/LOAEL approach there would be not need to apply an additional UF in this case. - UF for differences in duration of exposure i.e. need to be considered taking into account that, in general, the experimental dose descriptor will decrease with increasing exposure times and that other and more serious adverse effects may appear with increasing exposure times. - UF for the quality of the whole database i.e. may be applied to compensate for the potential remaining uncertainties during AAOEL derivation. In that case, it should be considered issues related to completeness and consistency of the available data and issues related to reliability of alternative data if those have been used. - e.g. In case some studies are missing, additional UF can be added. - UF for remaining uncertainties. In that case, the assessment factor should where relevant be applied and justified on a case-by-case basis. 	Multi-line text
Dose descriptor starting point	Critical endpoint value, type (e.g. NOAEL, BMDL05), value and units	Open list
Value	Report the numerical value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Critical endpoint	Link to the critical endpoint study record	Reference
Justification and comments	Provide additional information related to the derivation of this specific toxicological reference value.	Rich text area

ADI (Acceptable daily intake)		Header 2
Not allocated	Check the box if an ADI is not necessary for the application	Check box
Justification	Justification for the non-derivation of an ADI	Text
ADI	Report the ADI value and select the relevant units Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Population	Select the relevant population	Multi-Picklist
Assessment body	Select the relevant assessment body	Picklist
Study retained	Type of study used to derive the ADI (species and duration)	Multi select open list with remarks
Route of original study	Route of exposure in the study used to derive the ADI. It should be by default: oral.	Closed list
Overall uncertainty factor (UF)	<p>The overall assessment factor is the product of all the assessment factors used.</p> <p>The default UF is 100 (10 for intraspecies differences and 10 for interspecies differences).</p> <p>Please detail if additional UF are applied e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UF for dose response relationship i.e. consideration should be given to the uncertainties in the dose descriptor as the surrogate for the true no-adverse-effect-level. For instance, in case the starting point for AOEL derivation is a LOAEL instead of a NOAEL, the uncertainty factor should be between 2 and 10. - UF for differences in duration of exposure i.e. need to be considered taking into account that, in general, the experimental NOAEL will decrease with increasing exposure times and that other and more serious adverse effects may appear with increasing exposure times. - UF for the quality of the whole database, i.e. may be applied to compensate for the potential remaining uncertainties during AOEL derivation. In that case, it should be considered issues related to completeness and consistency of the available data and issues related to reliability of alternative data if those have been used. e.g. In case some studies are missing, additional UF can be added. - UF for remaining uncertainties. In that case, the assessment factor should where relevant be applied and justified on a case-by-case basis. 	Text
Justification of the overall UF	Justification for the uncertainty factor applied considering intra/inter species extrapolation	Multi-line text
Dose descriptor starting point	Critical endpoint value, type (e.g. NOAEL, BMDL05), value and units	Open list

Value	Report the numerical value	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Critical endpoint	Link to the critical endpoint study record	Reference
Justification and comments	Provide additional information related to the derivation of this specific toxicological reference value.	Rich text area
ARfD (Acute reference dose)		Header 2
Not allocated	Check the box if an ARfD is not necessary for the application	Check box
Justification	Justification for the non-derivation of an ARFD	Text
ARfD	Report the ARfD value and select the relevant units Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Population	Select the relevant population	Multi-picklist
Assessment body	Select the relevant assessment body.	Picklist
Study retained	Type of study used to derive the ARfD (species and duration)	Multi select open list with remarks
Route of original study	Route of exposure in the study used to derive the ARfD. It should be by default: oral.	Closed list
Overall uncertainty factor (UF)	The overall assessment factor is the product of all the assessment factors used. The default UF is 100 (10 for intraspecies differences and 10 for interspecies differences).	Text
Justification of the overall UF	Please detail if additional UF are applied e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UF for dose response relationship i.e. consideration should be given to the uncertainties in the dose descriptor as the surrogate for the true no-adverse-effect-level. For instance, in case the starting point for ARfD derivation is a LOAEL instead of a NOAEL, the uncertainty factor should be between 2 and 10. However, by using the BMD approach instead of NOAEL/LOAEL approach there would be not need to apply an additional UF in this case. - UF for differences in duration of exposure i.e. need to be considered taking into account that, in general, the experimental dose descriptor will decrease with increasing exposure times and that other and more serious adverse effects may appear with increasing exposure times. - UF for the quality of the whole database, i.e. may be applied to compensate for the potential remaining uncertainties during ARfD derivation. In that case, it should be considered issues related to completeness and consistency of the available data and issues related to reliability of alternative data if those have been used. e.g. In case some studies are missing, additional UF can be added. 	Multi-line text

	<p>- UF for remaining uncertainties. In that case, the assessment factor should where relevant be applied and justified on a case-by-case basis.</p> <p>Justification for the uncertainty factor applied considering intra/inter species extrapolation</p>	
Dose descriptor starting point	Critical endpoint value, type (e.g. NOAEL, BMDL05), value and units	Open list
Value	Report the numerical value	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Critical endpoint	Link to the critical endpoint study record	Reference
Justification and comments	Provide additional information related to the derivation of this specific toxicological reference value.	Rich text area
AAOEL (Acute acceptable operator exposure level)		Header 2
Not allocated	<p>Select the box if an AAOEL is not necessary for the application.</p> <p>It should be ticked for each toxicological reference value.</p>	Check box
Justification	Justification for the non-derivation of an AAOEL	Text
AAOEL	Report the AAOEL and if they are available select the relevant units.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Population	Select the relevant population.	Multi-picklist
Assessment body	Select the relevant assessment body.	Picklist
Study retained	Type of study used to derive the AAOEL (species and duration)	Multi select open list with remarks
Route of original study	Route of exposure in the study used to derive the AAOEL	Closed list
Oral absorption value (%)	Oral absorption value derived from the toxicokinetic studies expressed as a percentage	Decimal
Overall uncertainty factor (UF)	<p>The overall assessment factor is the product of all the assessment factors used.</p> <p>The default UF is 100 (10 for intraspecies differences and 10 for interspecies differences).</p>	Text
Justification of the overall UF	<p>Justification for the uncertainty factor applied considering intra/inter species extrapolation.</p> <p>Please detail if additional UF are applied e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UF for dose response relationship i.e. consideration should be given to the uncertainties in the dose descriptor as the surrogate for the true no-adverse-effect-level. <p>For instance, in case the starting point for AAOEL derivation is a LOAEL instead of a NOAEL, the uncertainty factor should be between 2 and 10.</p>	Multi-line text

	<p>However, by using the BMD approach instead of NOAEL/LOAEL approach there would be not need to apply an additional UF in this case.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UF for differences in duration of exposure i.e. need to be considered taking into account that, in general, the experimental dose descriptor will decrease with increasing exposure times and that other and more serious adverse effects may appear with increasing exposure times. - UF for the quality of the whole database i.e. may be applied to compensate for the potential remaining uncertainties during AAOEL derivation. In that case, it should be considered issues related to completeness and consistency of the available data and issues related to reliability of alternative data if those have been used. <p>e.g. In case some studies are missing, additional UF can be added.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UF for remaining uncertainties. In that case, the assessment factor should where relevant be applied and justified on a case-by-case basis. 	
Dose descriptor starting point	Critical endpoint value, type (e.g. NOAEL, BMDL05), value and units	Open list
Value	Report the numerical value	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Critical endpoint	Link to the critical endpoint study record	Reference
Justification and comments	Provide additional information related to the derivation of this specific toxicological reference value.	Rich text area
Other reference values		Header 2
Not allocated	Select if the derivation of the reference dose is not necessary.	Checkbox
Justification	Justify the non-derivation of the reference dose.	Text
Reference value descriptor	Select the relevant reference value. Refer to EFSA Glossary for further information (https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/glossary-taxonomy-terms).	Picklist
Value	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Quantity
Population	Select the relevant population.	Multi-picklist
Assessment body	Select the relevant assessment body.	Picklist
Overall uncertainty factor (UF)	The overall assessment factor is the product of all the assessment factors used. The default UF is 100 (10 for intraspecies differences and 10 for interspecies differences). Please detail if additional UF are applied e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UF for dose response relationship i.e. consideration should be given to the uncertainties in the 	Text

	dose descriptor as the surrogate for the true no-adverse-effect-level. For instance, in case the starting point for AOEL derivation is a LOAEL instead of a NOAEL, the uncertainty factor should be between 2 and 10. - UF for differences in duration of exposure i.e. need to be considered taking into account that, in general, the experimental NOAEL will decrease with increasing exposure times and that other and more serious adverse effects may appear with increasing exposure times. - UF for the quality of the whole database i.e. may be applied to compensate for the potential remaining uncertainties during AOEL derivation. In that case, it should be considered issues related to completeness and consistency of the available data and issues related to reliability of alternative data if those have been used. e.g. In case some studies are missing, additional UF can be added. - UF for remaining uncertainties. In that case, the assessment factor should where relevant be applied and justified on a case-by-case basis. Refer to the Scientific Opinion (EFSA, 2012) Guidance on selected default values to be used by the EFSA Scientific Committee, Scientific Panels and Units in the absence of actual measured data: https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2012 .	
Justification of the overall UF		text
Critical endpoint	Link to the critical endpoint study record	Reference
Justification and comments	Explain the choice of the study(ies) retained for the reference value setting; of the starting point chosen, etc.	Rich text
Reference to EFSA Opinion	Link to the relevant EFSA Output/Opinion in case the critical endpoint is not available (e.g., TTC, MOE)	Link to lit. reference (multiple)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

OECD (2010) "Guidance for the Derivation of an Acute Reference Dose" OECD Series on testing and assessment, No. 124, 08-Jun-2010
[http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono\(2010\)15&doclanguage=en](http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono(2010)15&doclanguage=en)

Guidance for the setting of an acute reference dose (ARfD)
https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-10/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_tox_acute-ref-dose.pdf

Guidance for the setting and application of acceptable operator exposure levels (AOELS)
https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-10/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_tox_accpt-exp-levs-2006.pdf

Guidance on selected default values to be used by the EFSA Scientific Committee, Scientific Panels and Units in the absence of actual measured data
<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2012.2579>

Update: use of the benchmark dose approach in risk assessment
<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7584>

5.1 Medical data

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide a summary of any available information on symptoms of infection or pathogenicity caused by the microbial active substance, drawn from medical reports or from case reports entered in the endpoint study records in subsections 5.1.1 - 5.1.4 (including a summary of information on the effectiveness of first aid and therapeutic measures).

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ExposureRelatedObservationsHumans		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in "Administrative data summary – common block" Provide brief description of relevant studies and effects. For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited; new active substance, - no detrimental effects on health in manufacturing personnel 	Header 1
Justification for classification or non-classification		Header 1
	The available information should be compared against the classification criteria and the reasons for fulfilling or not fulfilling the classification criteria should be presented.	Rich Text
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block " Provide additional information related to the potential effects on human health of the micro-organism, including consideration of its pathogenic potential, its ability to infect and its toxicological effects.	Header 1

5.1.1 THERAPEUTIC AND FIRST AID MEASURES

Purpose

The peer-reviewed published literature on the microorganism or closely related members of the taxonomic group and relating to clinical cases of infections in humans shall be submitted together with reports of any follow-up studies undertaken.

Such reports shall, where available, contain complete descriptions of the nature, level and duration of exposure, as well as the clinical symptoms observed, first aid and therapeutic measures applied and measurements and observations made, as well as follow up studies undertaken.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.DirectObservationsClinicalCases		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block " For microorganisms, direct observations and clinical cases should be considered as supporting information.	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1

Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Study type	Select type of medical data.	Open list with remarks
Endpoint addressed	<p>If the study recorded gives useful information on one or several of the classic endpoints, select the endpoint(s) addressed from the picklist.</p> <p>Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify.</p> <p>NOTE: The list of endpoints provided is a generic list. Some endpoints may not be applicable for the type of study summarised in this record.</p>	Multi select open list
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Method		Header 2
Type of population	<p>Indicate whether subjects of the general population and/or from an occupational environment were investigated. If 'Other' is selected, please include additional details in the free text box.</p> <p>If two independent studies are reported by the same report, use two separate records.</p>	Multi select open list
Subjects	Describe the subject(s) examined based on the freetext template (delete/add elements as appropriate). As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Ethical approval	Where ethical approval is required, indicate whether and what kind of consent was received from the persons studied. Include details in the supplementary remarks field. If 'not applicable' or 'no' is selected, give reasoning as appropriate in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Route of exposure	Indicate the route of exposure. Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify.	Multi select open list with remarks
Reason of exposure	Indicate the reason of exposure e.g. intentional or occupational unintentional.	Open list
Exposure assessment	Indicate whether the exposure was measured or estimated.	Closed list with remarks
Details on exposure	<p>Describe type and incidence of exposure including quantitative data if available, i.e. state if single or multiple exposure, duration, exposure concentrations (if inhalation), amount of chemical or micro-organisms ingested, dermal contact etc. Include methods of analysis if data available.</p> <p>If exposure was estimated, describe how this was done, if available.</p>	Text area
Examinations	Indicate type of examinations performed and at what time after start of exposure. Use freetext template (delete/add elements as appropriate). As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template

Medical treatment	Indicate if and what medical treatment exposed / intoxicated persons received.	Text area
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Clinical signs	Describe any relevant signs and symptoms observed.	Text area
Results of examinations	Describe the results of examinations based on freetext template (delete/add elements as appropriate). As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Effectivity of medical treatment	Indicate whether and during what time intoxicated persons responded to medical treatment.	Text area
Outcome of incidence	Describe the clinical manifestation of signs and symptoms, partial or total recovery after what time etc. If reported, give data on any follow-up examinations.	Text area
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

5.1.2 MEDICAL SURVEILLANCE

Purpose

Available reports of occupational health surveillance programmes, supported with detailed information on the design of the programme and on exposure to the active must be submitted. Such reports should, where feasible, include data relevant to the mechanism of action of the active and report of adverse health effects, including allergenic responses to chemicals in humans. These reports shall, where available, include data from persons exposed in manufacturing plants or after application of the active (e.g. in efficacy trials).

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.HealthSurveillanceData		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Study type	<p>Select the appropriate study type. Optionally, include details in the supplementary remarks field. Definitions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biological effect monitoring: involves the measurement of a biological change that is non-adverse and reversible (in contrast to medical monitoring), e.g. liver toxicity biomarkers (i.e. activity of aminotransferase and other enzymes). ▪ Biological exposure monitoring: measurement of biomarkers to assess the exposure from dietary, environmental or occupational sources. Biomarkers of exposure include either the measurement of levels of chemical agents and their metabolites in body fluids, tissue, cells or excreta, or the measurement of biological responses such as cytogenetic and reversible physiological changes in the exposed individuals. ▪ Health record from industry: a review of medical records and occupational exposure. ▪ Health record, other: any other review of medical history and records (e.g. exposed non-occupational). ▪ Medical monitoring: aims to measure early signs and symptoms of adverse effects for preventive reasons. ▪ Medical screening: method for detecting disease or body dysfunction before an individual would normally seek medical care. Aim: early diagnosis and treatment. ▪ Other: any other type of study or information, e.g. self-reported symptoms. 	Open list with remarks
Endpoint addressed	<p>If the study recorded gives useful information on one or several of the classic endpoints, select the endpoint(s) addressed from the picklist. Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify.</p> <p>NOTE: The list of endpoints provided is a generic list. Some endpoints may not be applicable for the type of study summarised in this record.</p>	Multi select open list
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Method		Header 2
Type of population	Indicate whether subjects of the general population and/or from an occupational environment were	Multi select open list

	investigated. If 'Other' is selected, please include additional details in the free text box. If two independent studies are reported by the same report, use two separate records.	
Ethical approval	Where ethical approval is required, indicate whether and what kind of consent was received from the persons studied. Include details in the supplementary remarks field. If 'not applicable' or 'no' is selected, give reasoning as appropriate in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Details on study design	Include detailed information on the design of the health surveillance programme and exposure to the substance in question and to other chemicals. Include or attach tables as appropriate.	Text area
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Results	Describe the results of the health surveillance study. In addition, include or attach tables and/or an excerpt from the study report.	Text area
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

5.1.3 INFORMATION ON SENSITISATION/ALLERGENICITY

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide available reports from the peer-reviewed published literature on the microorganism or closely related members of the taxonomic group and relating to sensitisation in humans.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SensitisationData		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block " For micro-organisms, direct observations and clinical cases should be considered as supporting information.	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OECD 406 - Method B.42 Skin sensitisation: Local lymph node assay (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008). - Method B.6 Skin sensitisation (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008). - OECD 429 - OECD 442A + 442B. - US EPA OPPTS 885.3400 hypersensitivity Incidents 	Header 1
Type of sensitisation studied	Indicate whether respiratory and/or skin sensitisation was studied.	Multi select open list
Study type	Select type of medical data.	Open list with remarks
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Method		Header 2
Type of population	Indicate whether subjects of the general population and/or from an occupational environment were investigated. If 'Other' is selected, please include additional details in the free text box. If two independent studies are reported by the same report, use two separate records.	Multi select open list
Ethical approval	Where ethical approval is required, indicate whether and what kind of consent was received from the persons studied. Include details in the supplementary remarks field. If 'not applicable' or 'no' is selected, give reasoning as appropriate in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Subjects	Describe the subject(s) examined based on the freetext template (delete/add elements as appropriate). As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Clinical history	Describe the clinical history of the subject(s) examined based on the freetext template (delete/add elements as appropriate). As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Controls	Indicate control or reference group or other comparison group and application of control/reference substances	Text area

Route of administration	Indicate the route of administration.	Open list
Details on study design	Describe the test design, i.e. type of test(s) used, method of application and the examinations performed. Select freetext template for the respective type of sensitisation investigated and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Results of examinations	Describe the results of examinations based on freetext template (delete/add elements as appropriate). As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

5.1.4 DIRECT OBSERVATION

Purpose

Where available, reports from studies with humans, such as tests on toxicokinetics and metabolism, or tests on skin irritation or skin sensitisation, shall be submitted. In general, the reference values shall be based on animal studies, but if appropriate scientifically valid and ethically generated human data are available and show that humans are more sensitive and lead to lower regulatory limit values, these data shall take precedence over animal data.

This document can also be used to report Dislodgeable Foliar Residues studies cited in operator exposure assessments.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ExposureRelatedObservationsOther		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Type of study / information	Briefly indicate the type of information (which does not fit into any of the specific chapter.)	Multi-line text
Endpoint addressed	If the study recorded gives useful information on one or several of the classic endpoints, select the endpoint(s) addressed from the picklist.	Multi select open list

	Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. NOTE: The list of endpoints provided is a generic list. Some endpoints may not be applicable for the type of study summarised in this record.	
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Method		Header 2
Ethical approval	Where ethical approval is required, indicate whether and what kind of consent was received from the persons studied. Include details in the supplementary remarks field. If 'not applicable' or 'no' is selected, give reasoning as appropriate.	Open list with remarks
Details on study design	Describe the study design including any relevant information from a study report, publication or other source. Include or attach tables or excerpts from study report as appropriate.	Text area
Exposure assessment	Indicate whether the exposure was measured or estimated. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details in the following freetext field.	Closed list with remarks
Details on exposure	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Explanations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ TYPE OF EXPOSURE: Characterise type of exposure including information on manufacturing / processing / use as applicable. If available, describe special exposure situations / workplaces. ▪ TYPE OF EXPOSURE MEASUREMENT: Indicate relevant predefined type(s); delete those being not applicable. ▪ EXPOSURE LEVELS: Give exposure level(s) reported (with units) or insert/attach table, for several exposure conditions and levels. ▪ EXPOSURE PERIOD: Describe when subjects were exposed and duration of exposure, i.e., hours, hours per day, days, days per week, weeks, months, years, person years, other. ▪ POSTEXPOSURE PERIOD: State period of time elapsed between last exposure/first examination or time study was conducted. ▪ DESCRIPTION / DELINEATION OF EXPOSURE GROUPS / CATEGORIES: If several exposure groups (e.g. different concentrations or durations) are analysed, identify the exposure groups or categories, number of subjects within each group, sex, other categorical descriptions, etc. 	Text template
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2

methods incl. tables		
Results and discussion		Header 1
Results	Provide exposure data as available and describe any relevant outcome of the study. If appropriate present the data in tabular form and/or attach excerpt(s) from the study report.	Text area
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

5.2 Assessment on potential infectivity and pathogenicity of the micro-organism to humans

Purpose

This document is to be used to consolidate all available information on infectivity and pathogenicity of the microorganism to humans using a weight of evidence (WoE) approach, as described in [EFSA Scientific Committee, 2017](#). The objective is to reach a robust conclusion either to exclude infectivity and pathogenicity or to identify specific data requirements needed to complete the assessment.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.PathogenicityInfectivityHumans		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Assessment of potential infectivity and pathogenicity of the microorganism to humans	Scientific Opinion on the guidance on the use of the weight of evidence approach in scientific assessments. EFSA Scientific Committee, Hardy, A, Benford, D, Halldorsson, T, Jeger, MJ, Knutsen, HK, More, S, Naegeli, H, Noteborn, H, Ockleford, C, Ricci, A, Rychen, G, Schlatter, JR, Silano, V, Solecki, R, Turck, D, Benfenati, E, Chaudhry, QM, Craig, P, Frampton, G, Greiner, M, Hart, A, Hogstrand, C, Lambre, C, Luttik, R, Makowski, D, Siani, A, Wahlstroem, H, Aguilera, J, Dorne, J-L, Fernandez	Header 1

	Dumont, A, Hempen, M, Valtueña Martínez, S, Martino, L, Smeraldi, C, Terron, A, Georgiadis, N and Younes, M, 2017 EFSA Journal 2017;15(8):4971, 69 pp. First published: 03 August 2017 https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4971	
	Conclude on potential infectivity and pathogenicity based on the lines of evidence presented below.	Text (rich-text area)
Assembling evidence	Link to any literature searches for evidence on pathogenicity of infectivity.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Weighing evidence		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Description of key conclusion for the study	Include consideration of the relevance and reliability of the study	Text
Identified uncertainties		Text
Link to relevant study record	Link to the endpoint study describing the supporting evidence.	Link to endpoint (single)
Weighing evidence		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Integrating evidence		Header 2
Opportunistic infection	Indicate whether there is evidence of opportunistic infection in immunocompromised persons	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Absence of infectivity	Record the finding that infectivity has been ruled out for the microorganism.	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Absence of pathogenicity	Record the finding that pathogenicity has been ruled out for the microorganism.	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

EFSA Scientific Committee, Hardy, A, Benford, D, Halldorsson, T, Jeger, MJ, Knutsen, HK, More, S, Naegeli, H, Noteborn, H, Ockleford, C, Ricci, A, Rychen, G, Schlatter, JR, Silano, V, Solecki, R, Turck, D, Benfenati, E, Chaudhry, QM, Craig, P, Frampton, G, Greiner, M, Hart, A, Hogstrand, C, Lambre, C, Luttik, R, Makowski, D, Siani, A, Wahlstroem, H, Aguilera, J, Dorne, J-L, Fernandez Dumont, A, Hempen, M, Valtueña Martínez, S, Martino, L, Smeraldi, C, Terron, A, Georgiadis, N and Younes, M, 2017. Scientific Opinion on the guidance on the use of the weight of evidence approach in scientific assessments. EFSA Journal 2017;15(8):4971, 69 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4971>

5.3 Infectivity and pathogenicity studies on the microorganism

5.3.1 INFECTIVITY AND PATHOGENICITY

Purpose

Infectivity and pathogenicity studies with the microorganisms are only needed when infectivity and pathogenicity of the microorganism to humans cannot be excluded based on the body of knowledge on the microorganism and as reported in **Section 5.2**.

This document is to be used to provide summary information of the most relevant study(-ies) in which the relative hazards associated with the different routes of exposure have been investigated in test mammals. The information generated through acute toxicity, pathogenicity and infectiveness testing is of particular value in assessing hazards likely to arise in accident situations and consumer risks due to exposure to possible residues.

All signs of infection and/or pathogenicity and a clearance assessment should be included.

The document should contain the information needed to be reported according to the list of end points for acute oral, dermal and inhalation toxicity (SANCO/12592/2012-rev. 2, 22 March 2019).

If acute oral toxicity is assessed for a metabolite create a summary for the metabolite, in the relevant dataset.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.AcuteToxicity		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	Provide a brief description of toxicity studies and effects.	Rich text area
Key value for assessment		Header 1
Acute toxicity: via oral route		Header 2
Link to relevant study records	Follow instructions reported in "Administrative data" Common block for endpoint summaries. The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the robust study summary is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score, duration of the study, whether or not the study is GLP).	Header 3
Endpoint conclusion	Note: In case of acute studies with micro-organisms, less severe but still adverse effects are also considered during the assessment.	Header 3
Dose descriptor	LD ₅₀ should usually be chosen. However, if the acute toxicity was established by determining the discriminating dose, that should be chosen.	
Effect level	Select the qualifier according to the key value: - if none specifically apply, leave the field empty. - if the effect level is based on "no effect seen" at the highest tested concentration, the qualifier ">" should be used and the highest tested concentration should be reported. When	

	<p>there is no effect observed at the highest tested concentration, and when such concentration is above the test limit dose, then it can be assumed in the further assessment process that no hazard has been identified.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - if effects have been observed at the lowest tested concentration and you are not able to extrapolate an adequate dose descriptor, use the qualifier "<". <p>Nevertheless, note that the reporting of such an effect concentration may be difficult to use appropriately in further processing of the value. As a consequence, if you can justify the extrapolation of the value to one of the proposed dose descriptors, you may do so in your assessment and explain your method in the field "Additional information". The following units should only be used in the case of microbial active substances: - cells - CFU (colony-forming unit) - ITU (International Toxic Unit) - IU (International Unit) - OB (occlusion bodies) - spores</p>	
Acute toxicity: via dermal route		Header 2
Link to relevant study records	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Endpoint summary block for relevant study record"</p> <p>The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the robust study summary is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score, duration of the study, whether or not the study is GLP.</p>	Header 3
Endpoint conclusion	<p>Note: In case of acute studies with microorganisms, less severe but still adverse effects are also considered during the assessment.</p>	Header 3
Dose descriptor	<p>LD50 should usually be chosen. However, if the acute toxicity was established by determining the discriminating dose, that should be chosen.</p>	
Effect level	<p>Select the qualifier according to the key value:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - if none specifically apply, leave the field empty. - if the effect level is based on "no effect seen" at the highest tested concentration, the qualifier ">" should be used and the highest tested concentration should be reported. When there is no effect observed at the highest tested concentration, and when such concentration is above the test limit dose, then it can be assumed in the further assessment process that no hazard has been identified. - if effects have been observed at the lowest tested concentration and you are not able to extrapolate an adequate dose descriptor, use the qualifier "<". <p>Nevertheless, note that the reporting of such an effect concentration may be difficult to use appropriately in further processing of the value. As a consequence, if you can justify the extrapolation of the value to one of the proposed dose descriptors, you may do so in your assessment and explain your method in the field "Additional information".</p> <p>The following units should only be used in the case of microbial active substances: - cells - CFU (colony-</p>	

	forming unit) - ITU (International Toxic Unit) - IU (International Unit) - OB (occlusion bodies) – spores (or other relevant units).	
Acute toxicity: via inhalation route		Header 2
Link to relevant study records	Follow instructions reported in “Endpoint summary block for relevant study record” The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the robust study summary is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score), duration of the study, whether or not the study is GLP.	Header 3
Endpoint conclusion	Note: In case of acute studies with microorganisms, less severe but still adverse effects are also considered during the assessment.	Header 3
Dose descriptor	LC50 should usually be chosen. However, if the acute toxicity was established by determining the discriminating concentration, that should be chosen.	
Effect level	Select the qualifier according to the key value: - if none specifically apply, leave the field empty. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - if none specifically apply, leave the field empty. - if the effect level is based on “no effect seen” at the highest tested concentration, the qualifier “>” should be used and the highest tested concentration should be reported. When there is no effect observed at the highest tested concentration, and when such concentration is above the test limit dose, then it can be assumed in the further assessment process that no hazard has been identified. - if effects have been observed at the lowest tested concentration and you are not able to extrapolate an adequate dose descriptor, use the qualifier “<”. <p>Nevertheless, note that the reporting of such an effect concentration may be difficult to use appropriately in further processing of the value. As a consequence, if you can justify the extrapolation of the value to one of the proposed dose descriptors, you may do so in your assessment and explain your method in the field “Additional information”.</p> <p>The following units should only be used in the case of microbial active substances: - cells - CFU (colony-forming unit) - ITU (International Toxic Unit) - IU (International Unit) - OB (occlusion bodies) – spores, or other relevant units.</p>	
Physical form	Indicate in what physical form the test material was administered.	Open list
Justification for classification or non-classification	Not relevant for microorganisms.	Header 1
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in “ Additional information – common block ”	Header 1

	Provide additional information related to the endpoint, for example: Rat LD50 oral Rat LC50 inhalation Rat LD50 intraperitoneal/subcutaneous	
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5.3.1.1 Oral infectivity and pathogenicity

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide information on the oral toxicity of the active substance/the plant protection product or metabolites.

The oral infectivity and pathogenicity following a single exposure to the micro-organism must be reported.

A study in test animals in accordance with relevant guidelines shall be performed, unless the applicant can demonstrate absence of oral infectivity and pathogenicity based on a weight of evidence approach as set out in point 5.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AcuteToxicityOral		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Material and methods – common block"</p> <p>Applicable test guideline:</p> <p>Method B.1 bis Acute oral toxicity - fixed dose procedure (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008).</p> <p>Method B.1 tris Acute oral toxicity - Acute toxic class method (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008).</p> <p>OECD Test Guideline 420: Acute oral toxicity: fixed dose procedure</p> <p>OECD Test Guideline 423: Acute oral toxicity: acute toxic class method</p> <p>OECD Test Guideline 425: Acute oral toxicity: up-and-down procedure</p> <p>Microbial Pesticide Test Guidelines: US EPA OPPTS 885.3050 Acute Oral Toxicity/Pathogenicity</p> <p>Are relevant for this endpoint Information on the version and date of the guideline used and/or any other specifics can be entered in the next field 'Version / remarks'.</p>	Header 1
Test type	<p>If possible, indicate whether the acute toxic class method, fixed dose procedure, up-and-down procedure or standard acute method was used. The latter method should not be used any more. However, it may apply to existing studies. If neither of these test types applies, either leave field empty or use 'other:'.</p> <p>Note: This field may be redundant with the information</p>	Open list

	given in field 'Guideline',but is considered useful for searching reasons.	
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	Closed list
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Test animals	Follow instructions reported in " Test animals – common block " Species: Select name of species. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify. NOTE: Human data should be reported in an appropriate subsection of section 'Basic information' It can be useful to document, in the section on acute toxicity, that human data are provided by creating a record and referring to the human data in field 'Cross-reference'. This could be relevant if lack of animal experiments is defended by the availability of data on experience with human exposure.	Header 2
Administration / exposure		Header 2
Route of administration	Select as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.	Open list
Vehicle	Select 'unchanged (no vehicle)' if none was used or select vehicle used if any. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field. Note that some of the vehicles provided in this list are used for specific routes of administration only.	Open list with remarks
Details on oral exposure	Indicate details of oral exposure. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Doses	Include the doses including unit administered to the test animals (in CFU/ml or CFU/kg bw). As appropriate include notes in parentheses, e.g. '(male)'.	Multi-line text
No. of animals per sex per dose	Enter value or specify according to dose if different number of animals per dose, e.g. '10 (controls), 5 (in dose groups)'. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, also include a detailed table on the animal assignment in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined table(s) if any or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). Note: Specific tables may be required.	Multi-line text
Control animals	Indicate whether concurrent control group was used.	Open list with remarks
Details on study design	Include any further details on the study design, i.e. observation period, frequency of observations/weighing, necropsy of survivors and other examinations performed. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Statistics	Indicate the method of calculating the LD50 or other.	Multi-line text
High dose level used	Where a test method offers flexibility in the study design, for example in relation to the choice of dose levels, the chosen study design shall ensure that the data generated are adequate for hazard identification and risk assessment. To this end, testing shall be performed at appropriately	

	high dose levels. If dose (concentration) selection is limited by the physicochemical properties or biological effects of the test substance, justification shall be provided.	
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block ". Verification that each enumeration method is sufficiently sensitive to serve as a useful quantitative assay, for the micro-organism in tissues, organs, and body fluids.	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Preliminary study	Summarise evidence of toxicity and mortality of any preliminary sighting study.	Multi-line text
Effect levels	Provide the LD50 with confidence limits if available and/or other effect levels reported. Copy this field block for each effect level. If both sexes were tested at each dose level, then the combined effect level should be stated. Where there are significant differences in response between the sexes, include the effect levels for both. If the test was conducted according to the fixed dose procedure, include the discriminating dose, i.e. the highest out of the four fixed dose levels which can be administered without causing compound-related mortality (including human kills). If no LD50 or other endpoint available from picklist is reported, but only a dose level, specify this dose using 'other' and indicate the effects observed in subfield 'Remarks on result'.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Sex	Select from drop-down list.	Closed list
Dose descriptor	Select the relevant dose descriptor from drop-down list, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects. If a fixed dose procedure was used, select 'discriminating dose', i.e. the dose causing evident toxicity but not mortality. With the up-and-down procedure an 'approximate LD50' may be derived. Where no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used, the upper or lower dose level for the relevant dose descriptor can be reported as appropriate with relevant qualifier, e.g. LD50 >10 or LD50 <10. An additional explanation may be given in field 'Remarks on result', e.g. 'not determinable due to absence of adverse toxic effects'.	Open list with remarks
Effect level	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the	Open list with remarks

	<p>relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification.</p> <p>Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.</p>	
95% CL	<p>For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if available.</p> <p>Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.</p>	Range (Decimal)
Remarks on result	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Effect levels		
Mortality	In the case of a fixed dose study, summarise evidence of toxicity and mortality of any preliminary sighting study at the fixed doses administered.	Multi-line text
Clinical signs	<p>Briefly describe significant effects found, including the numbers of animals showing signs, time of onset, duration of the major clinical signs and time when most animals recovered. Do not dwell on effects that are most likely due to agonal death. Focus on any important findings, i.e. compound-related or suspected related effects. In case particular effects are considered control-related e.g. because of abnormal control values, this should be specifically addressed.</p> <p>Note if there was a reference point (e.g. NOAELs) for clinical findings.</p> <p>If the fixed dose method was used, indicate if animals appeared to recover completely and state if there were no obvious substance-related signs of toxicity.</p>	Multi-line text
Body weight	Briefly describe whether animals gained or lost weight. Indicate if body weight loss was greater than 10%.	PickListWith Remarks2000
Gross pathology	Briefly describe whether there were any treatment related effects. Do not stress effects due to agonal death.	Multi-line text
Other findings	<p>The following should be reported for studies with microorganisms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clearance estimates (numeration of the micro-organism/toxin in the relevant tissues/organs/body fluids at different time points) - Infectivity/persistence findings (numeration and findings in affected organs/tissues, if any) 	Text template
Additional information about applicability domain and	Follow instructions reported in "Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block"	Header 2

reliability of (Q)SAR predictions		
Any other information on results incl. tables)	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block " Attached document: Detailed results in the different dose groups can be reported in Appendix F format either as an attachment and in the 'Any other information on results incl. tables'	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Results and discussion

Preliminary study
None

Effect levels + New item 📄 Import file v

#	Key result	Sex	Dose descriptor	Effect level	Based on	95% CL	Remarks on result	Actions
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	male/female	LD50	1829 mg/kg bw	test mat.	None	None	
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	male	LD50	1392 mg/kg bw	test mat.	None	None	
3	<input type="checkbox"/>	female	LD50	2271 mg/kg bw	test mat.	None	other:	

Mortality
No mortality was recorded in either sex at 500 mg/kg bw. At 2000 mg/kg bw 4/5 males and 1/5 females were found dead at days 8 and 9 of the observation period. At 5000 mg/kg bw all the animals died during the first two days after treatment with the exception of one male that died on the ninth day

Clinical signs
✓ other: The following symptoms were reported: dyspnea, exophthalmos and hunched body position. In addition, sedation was reported on the sixth day after treatment in the animals that received 2000 mg/kg bw. Sedation was also reported from the days of administrati

Body weight
None

Gross pathology
The autopsy of the animals received 500 mg/kg bw and the survivors of the 2000 mg/kg bw dose group did not show any treatment related changes. Dilatation, hemorrhage or liquid content of the intestinal tract were reported in the 4 dead males and one female at 2000 mg/kg bw and in one male and one female at 5000 mg/kg bw. Reddish or discolored lungs with oedema were seen in 4 males and 1 female at 2000 mg/kg bw and in 4 males and 3 females at 5000 mg/kg bw. Soft liver was reported in one male and one female at 2000 mg/kg bw. Thymic hemorrhage was reported in four males and four females at the highest dose.

5.3.1.2 Intratracheal / intranasal infectivity and pathogenicity

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide information on the inhalation toxicity of the active substance/the plant protection product or metabolites.

The intratracheal/ intranasal infectivity and pathogenicity following a single exposure to the microorganism must be reported. Expert judgement may support the evaluation on which of the two exposure routes is the most appropriate to be investigated, based on biological properties of the micro-organism and available information described in points 5.1 and 5.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439. A study in test animals in accordance with relevant guidelines must be performed, unless the applicant can demonstrate absence of intratracheal/ intranasal infectivity and pathogenicity based on a weight of evidence approach as set out in point 5.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AcuteToxicityInhalation		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1

Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guideline: Microbial Pesticide Test Guidelines: US EPA OPPTS 885.3150 Acute Pulmonary Toxicity/Pathogenicity	Header 1
Test type	If possible, indicate which method was used in the study. If neither of these test types applies, either leave field empty or use 'other':. Note: This field may be redundant with the information given in field 'Guideline', but is considered useful for searching reasons.	Open list
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	Closed list
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Test animals	Follow instructions reported in " Test animals – common block " Select name of species. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify. NOTE: Human data should be reported in an appropriate subsection of section 'Basic information'. It can be useful to document, in the section on acute toxicity, that human data are provided by creating a record and referring to the human data in field 'Cross-reference'. This could be relevant if lack of animal experiments is defended by the availability of data on experience with human exposure. Sex: Provide rationale for use of females (if applicable), in field 'Details on test animals and environment conditions'.	Header 2
Administration / exposure		Header 2
Route of administration	Specify the route of administration by indicating in what physical form the test material was administered. In case of intratracheal administration, specify it under 'Type of inhalation'.	Open list
Type of inhalation exposure	Indicate type of inhalation exposure, e.g. 'nose only'. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks subfield. In case of intratracheal administration, select other and report this in the 'remarks' field.	Open list with remarks
Vehicle	Select the vehicle used. If not available from picklist, select 'other'.	Open list with remarks
Mass median aerodynamic diameter (MMAD)	Specify the particle size distribution in terms of mass median aerodynamic diameter (MMAD). Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Geometric standard deviation (GSD)	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)

	This field can be used for giving an additional information by selecting 'other:' or selecting a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. 'not measured/tested' or 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field.	
Remark on MMAD/GSD	Enter any remarks related to the mass median aerodynamic diameter.	Multi-line text
Details on inhalation exposure	Indicate details of inhalation exposure. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt (i.e. diagram as pdf/jpeg etc.) from the study report.	Text template
Analytical verification of test atmosphere concentrations	Indicate whether the test atmosphere concentrations and the particle size were analytically verified. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, include a short description on the method of analysis in the supplementary remarks field. State whether the analytical data indicated that the difference between nominal and actual concentrations was acceptable. If any problems occurred, then they should be reported in more detail. If this could have affected the veracity or conclusions of the study, discuss this in field 'Rationale for reliability incl. deficiencies'.	Closed list with remarks
Duration of exposure	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with closed list (Decimal)
Remarks on duration	Enter any remarks related to the recorded value as appropriate.	Text
Concentrations	Provide rationale for the selection of the starting concentration. Include the nominal concentrations the test animals were exposed to, e.g. '100, 500, 2500 and 20000 ppmV(gas)' or '0.5, 2.0, 10, 20 mg/L air (dust/mist)'. For micro-organisms (CFU/L air or other relevant units should be used) As appropriate include notes in parentheses, e.g. '(male)'. For robust study summaries, also provide the analytical concentrations in the results table (see field 'Mortality').	Multi-line text
No. of animals per sex per dose	Enter number or state numbers for different groups if varying, e.g. '10 (controls), 5 (in test groups)'. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, also include a detailed table on the animal assignment in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). Note: Specific tables may be required.	Multi-line text
Control animals	Indicate whether concurrent control group was used.	Open list with remarks
Details on study design	Include any further details on the study design, i.e. observation period, frequency of observations/weighing, necropsy of survivors and other examinations performed. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template

Statistics	Indicate the method of calculating the category. LC50 or other, if applicable.	Multi-line text
High dose level used	Where a test method offers flexibility in the study design, for example in relation to the choice of dose levels, the chosen study design shall ensure that the data generated are adequate for hazard identification and risk assessment. To this end, testing shall be performed at appropriately high dose levels. If dose (concentration) selection is limited by the physicochemical properties or biological effects of the test substance, justification shall be provided.	
Justification for deviation from the high dose level	Provide a justification for deviating from the high dose level.	Text template
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block ". Information on the test atmosphere characteristics can be provided e.g. Nominal concentration and Temperature For microorganisms: Verification that each enumeration method is sufficiently sensitive to serve as a useful quantitative assay for the MPCA tissues, organs, and body fluids should be reported.	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Preliminary study	Summarise evidence of toxicity and mortality of any preliminary sighting study (if performed).	Multi-line text
Effect levels	Provide the LC50 with confidence limits if available and/or other effect levels reported. Copy this field block for each effect level. If both sexes were tested at each dose level, then the combined effect level should be stated. Where there are significant differences in response between the sexes, include the effect levels for both. If no LC50 or other endpoint available from picklist is reported, but only a concentration level, specify this concentration using 'other' and indicate the effects observed in subfield 'Remarks on result'.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment.	Check box
Sex	Select from drop-down list.	Closed list
Dose descriptor	Select the relevant dose descriptor from drop-down list, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects. If a fixed dose concentration was used, select 'discriminating conc.', i.e. the dose causing evident toxicity but not mortality. Where no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used, the upper or lower dose level for the relevant dose descriptor can be reported as appropriate with relevant qualifier, e.g. LC50 >10 mg/m ³ air or LC50 <10 mg/m ³ air.	Open list with remarks

	For microorganisms (CFU/L air or other relevant units should be used) An additional explanation may be given in field 'Remarks on result', e.g. 'not determinable due to absence of adverse toxic effects'.	
Effect level	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
95% CL	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant available. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Exp. duration	Enter numeric value. If exposure cannot be described by a single (integer) number, calculate hours and minutes reported to a decimal number, preferably based on the unit 'h (hour)', e.g. 4.15 h for 4 h, 9 min.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results where required and in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:'	Open list with remarks (2000)
Effect levels		
Mortality	Summarise evidence of toxicity and mortality of any preliminary sighting study.	Multi-line text
Clinical signs	Choose the corresponding clinical sign and briefly describe significant effects found, including the numbers of animals showing signs, time of onset, duration of the major clinical signs and time when most animals recovered. (For non TG 433 inhalation studies, do not dwell on effects that are most likely due to agonal death.) Focus on any important findings, i.e. compound-related or suspected related effects. In case particular effects are considered control-related e.g. because of abnormal control values, this should be specifically addressed. If another clinical sign should be reported, choose option – other: and mention the sign as contained in the comprehensive Clinical sign lexicon provided as Table 2 in the publication by Sewell F. et al. (2015), "A global	Open list with remarks

	initiative to refine acute inhalation studies through the use of 'evident toxicity' as and endpoint: Towards adoption of the Fixed Concentration Procedure", Regul Toxicol Pharmacol, Vol. 73, pp. 770-779. Note if there was a reference point (e.g. NOAELs) for clinical findings.	
Body weight	Briefly describe whether animals gained or lost weight. Indicate if body weight loss was greater than 10%.	Text template
Gross pathology	Briefly describe whether there were any treatment related effects. Do not stress effects due to agonal death.	Multi-line text
Other findings	For microorganism studies report results related to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clearance estimates, notably in the lungs (numeration of the micro-organism/toxin in the relevant tissues/organs/body fluids at different time points) - Infectivity/persistence findings (numeration of micro-organism and findings in affected organs/tissues, if any) 	Text template
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables)	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

5.3.1.3 Intravenous / intraperitoneal or subcutaneous single exposure

Purpose:

The intraperitoneal/subcutaneous test is considered a highly sensitive assay to elicit in particular infectiveness. The subcutaneous injection may be preferred if the maximum growth temperature is lower than 37 °C as the micro-organism may in this case be more likely to cause infections in the skin rather than deep tissue. Intravenous and intraperitoneal injection studies are unrealistic exposure routes and should only be performed if justified, e.g. if unexpected adverse effects occur in the acute oral or intratracheal study.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SpecificInvestigations		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
	Applicable test guideline:	

	<p>Microbial Pesticide Test Guidelines: US EPA OPPTS 885.3200 Microbial pesticide test guidelines. Acute Injection Toxicity/Pathogenicity US EPA OPPTS 885.3650 Reproductive/fertility effects</p> <p>Note: Acute intraperitoneal/subcutaneous study is always <i>in vivo</i>.</p>	
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Test animals	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Test animals – common block"</p> <p>Select name of species. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.</p> <p>NOTE: Human data should be reported in an appropriate subsection of section 'Basic information'. It can be useful to document, in the section on acute toxicity, that human data are provided by creating a record and referring to the human data in field 'Cross-reference'. This could be relevant if lack of animal experiments is defended by the availability of data on experience with human exposure.</p>	Header 2
Administration / exposure		Header 2
Route of administration	Specify the route of administration by indicating in what physical form the test material was administered.	Open list
Vehicle	Select the vehicle used. If not available from picklist, select 'other'.	Open list with remarks
Details on exposure	Select freetext template for the respective type of study and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Analytical verification of doses or concentrations	Indicate whether the doses or concentrations were analytically verified.	Closed list with remarks
Details on analytical verification of doses or concentrations	<p>For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, include a short description on the method of analysis in the supplementary remarks field. If any problems occurred in any of these procedures, then they should be reported in more detail. If this could have affected the veracity or conclusions of the study, discuss this in field 'Rationale for reliability incl. deficiencies'.</p> <p>Further route-dependent information to be included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For oral studies: State whether the analytical data indicated that the variance between nominal and actual dosage (if diet is route of administration) or concentrations (for drinking water study) was acceptable. If diet is the route of administration, briefly record when and at what dose levels the dosage analyses were made and include the results (range of values) of (i) Homogeneity analysis, (ii) Stability analysis and (iii) Concentration analysis. It may be appropriate to include 	Text

	<p>a cross-reference to another study in which stability analysis was performed and reported. If so, a justification should also be included briefly explaining the rationale of referring to another study.</p> <p>- For inhalation studies: State whether the analytical data indicated that the variance between nominal and actual concentrations was acceptable.</p> <p>- For dermal studies: State whether the analytical data indicated that the variance between nominal and actual concentrations of the test substance in the vehicle was acceptable.</p>	
Duration of treatment / exposure	Indicate duration in days, weeks or months, e.g. '28 days' or '18 months'.	Multi-line text
Frequency of treatment	Indicate the frequency of the administration of doses to the test animals (e.g., 'daily, 7 days each week'). Use of non-standard dosing regime (e.g. a five-day per week regime) should be justified.	Multi-line text
Post exposure period	Indicate observation period (in days, weeks, months) after last exposure to the test material. Specify, if there are differences for treatment and recovery groups or other individual groups.	Multi-line text
Doses / concentrations	Indicate the dose or concentration levels applied and the basis of quantity used. Copy this block of fields for each numeric value and to record values on a different basis, i.e. mg/kg bw/day (nominal), mg/kg bw/day (actual dose received), mg/kg diet, mg/L drinking water, mg/kg bw (total dose), ppm, CFU/kg bw/day if applicable. Conversion of the dose / conc. values to the relevant unit used for the effect levels may be required.	
Dose / conc.	Enter numeric value	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to dose / concentration values.	Multi-line text
Doses / concentrations		
No. of animals per sex per dose	Enter number or state numbers for different groups if varying, e.g. '10 (controls), 5 (in test groups)'. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, also include a detailed table on the animal assignment in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). Note: Specific tables may be required.	Multi-line text
Control animals	Indicate whether concurrent control group was used.	Open list with remarks
Details on study design	Include any further details on the study design, i.e. observation period, frequency of observations/weighing, necropsy of survivors and other examinations performed. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template

Examinations		Header 2
Examinations	Include details on the examinations performed.	Text area
Positive control	Briefly describe the positive control data cited, and its acceptability for use with the current study. Criteria for acceptability include the positive demonstration of sensitivity of the test methods to detect changes in the measured parameters.	Multi-line text
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block ". Information on the test atmosphere characteristics can be provided e.g. Nominal concentration and Temperature For micro-organisms: Verification that each enumeration method is sufficiently sensitive to serve as a useful quantitative assay for the MPCA tissues, organs, and body fluids should be reported	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Details on results	For microorganisms report <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Number of animals at the start of the test. (ii) Time of death of individual animals. (iii) Number of animals displaying other signs of toxicity and pathogenicity. (iv) Description of toxic and pathogenic effects. (v) Expression of the dose levels with the appropriate unit for the microorganism under consideration (vi) Body weights at different time points. (vii) Necropsy findings. (viii) Pathology findings. (ix) Micro-organism enumeration from tissues, organs, and body fluids (at different time points), and methods used, and sensitivities and limits of detection (to address infectivity and clearance estimate). 	Text area
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block ".	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables)	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block ".	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block ".	Header 1

Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1
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5.3.2 CELL CULTURE STUDY

Purpose:

This information must be reported for intracellular replicating microorganisms, such as viruses, viroids or specific bacteria and protozoa, unless it is clearly demonstrated that the microorganism does not replicate in warm-blooded organisms. A cell culture study shall be performed in human cell or tissue cultures of different organs. Selection can be based on expected target organs after infection. If human cell or tissue cultures of specific organs are not available, other mammal cell and tissue cultures can be used. For viruses, the ability to interact with the human genome is a key consideration.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.CellCultureStudy		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guideline: US EPA OPPTS 885.3500 Cell Culture.	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Administration / exposure		Header 2
Cell cultures	Indicate one or more cell cultures used in the study e.g. Human W138. Justifications for the selection of the cell lines should be provided in the remarks field	Multi select closed list with remarks
Plating conditions	Describe the number of cells per plate, time when the plates were exposed to the virus. Number of cells in each group of plates and the culture mediums added to the groups of plates should be reported.	Text area
Incubation conditions	Describe the conditions used to incubate the plates e.g. temperature.	Text area
Doses / concentrations	Indicate the dose/Titres or concentration levels applied to the cell cultures and the units of quantity used. The remarks field can be used to justify the dosing level or provide additional information on the doses/Titre applied.	
Dose / conc.	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to dose / concentration values.	Multi-line text
Assays	Indicate the biological assays used in the cell culture study. Create a new row for each assay type	

Assay type	Select assay type e.g. nucleic acid assay or select 'other' and indicate the assay used in the cell culture study.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Link analytical method	Link to the description of the assay from the analytical methods section.	Endpoint reference list
Remarks	Provide additional information on the assay/s used in the study	Multi-line text
Assays		
Controls	Indicate the controls used in the study e.g untreated (negative) control, control with inactivated microorganism, vehicle control, positive control.	Multi-line text
Other treatments	Describe any treatments used in the study, e.g. treatment for diseases not caused by the test substance. Test animals or plants with a history of disease are not to be used for microbial pesticide testing. The feed must be antibiotic free. For MPCAs where test organisms have been treated with some agent or manipulated by some system to prevent or control infectious diseases not caused by the test substance, a full description of such treatment or manipulation must be reported. Such description should include: (A) Identification of the test organisms affected and the disease organism involved. (B) The nature and severity of the disease. (C) The date of onset and duration of the disease. (D) The nature of the treatment or manipulation used to control or eliminate the disease, and the dates of such actions. (E) The outcome of the treatments in relation to the disease and to the test results.	Text area
Details on study design	Give additional details on the study design. To support automatic report generation an excerpt from the study report is recommended.	Text area
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Cytopathic effects	Indicate whether cytopathic effects were observed in the cell monolayers. For viruses, the appearance of cytopathic effect should be described in the remarks in such a way that virus-induced cell destruction is differentiated from nonspecific effects.	Open list with remarks (2000)
TCID50	If cytopathic effects are observed report the Fifty-percent tissue culture infective dose	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)

Results of assays		
Sample type	Indicate whether the measurement was taken from culture fluid or intracellular fluid	Open list with remarks
Time point	Indicate the time post inoculation when the sample was taken	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Material detected	Indicate whether the result shows the presence of nucleic acids, proteins or other infection markers	Open list with remarks
Detected	Check the box if the material could be detected	Check box
Quantity	Report the quantitative result of the assay (where quantifiable)	Range with open list (Decimal)
Statistics	List parameters that were analysed and the statistical methods used; include a statement that the Reviewer considers the analyses to be appropriate. If inappropriate, provide alternative/rationale.	Multi-line text
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

5.4 (Cf. 5.3.1.3) Specific infectivity and pathogenicity studies on the microorganism

5.5 Information and toxicity studies on metabolites

5.5.1 INFORMATION AND TOXICITY OF METABOLITES

Purpose

Summary to conclude on the toxicity of metabolites based on literature search in order to identify metabolites of concern for human and animal health and/or to conclude on exclusion of metabolites as being of concern.

All the metabolites of potential concern should be listed, providing further information to demonstrate whether they are of concern or not.

Identified metabolites of concern to be reported in *Flexible_Summary.Metabolites & Other Substance for Assessment* dataset (see instructions above).

FLEXIBLE.SUMMARY_InformationToxicityMetabolites

Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Description of key information	<p>This document is for Metabolites of Concern for Human Health</p> <p>See SANCO/2020/12258 Guidance on the risk assessment of metabolites produced by micro-organisms used as plant protection active substances.</p> <p>Stage 1 and Stage 2 the collection of basic information from literature should be reported in the Biological Properties document (Section 2 of the active substance dataset).</p> <p>This document should be used to report the results of targeted literature searches for all metabolites of potential concern in order to identify 'Metabolites of Concern'.</p> <p>If the identity is known, a complete list of metabolites of potential concern should be listed in the 'Information on Metabolites' document and for the metabolites of concern the experimental data should be provided in the linked datasets.</p> <p>Provide additional information from the metabolite specific literature searches which cannot be reported in the repeatable block below.</p>	Header 1
		Text (rich-text area)
Metabolites		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Link to metabolite		Link to entity (single)
Link to Literature Search		Link to endpoint (single)
Hazardous effect observed in toxicological studies	<p>If the picklist value 'no' is selected provide the justification in the remarks field. No further information is required in this table.</p> <p>If the picklist value 'yes' is selected complete all the information required in the table.</p>	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Conditions	Describe the conditions under which the microorganism produces the metabolite.	Text (2,000 char.)

LOQ of method	Any available information about the LOQ of the method used to determine/quantify the metabolite.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Expected quantities	Any available information about the expected quantities.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Regulation mechanism	Any available information on the mechanism by which the microorganism regulates the production of the metabolite must be provided.	Text (2,000 char.)
Mode of action	Any available information on the influence of the produced metabolites on the microorganism's mode of action against the target organism(s) must be provided.	Text (2,000 char.)
Sufficient body of knowledge	Is there enough published literature to assume that a literature search would provide sufficient information on metabolite production? Make reference to the literature search included in the 'Link to Literature Search' in the table when justifying the selection of 'yes' or 'no' in the remarks field.	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Nature of observed toxic effect	Indicate any observed toxic effect(s) of the metabolite. Multiple choices are possible.	List multi (multi-select list)
Relevant antimicrobial activity	The checkbox should be ticked if the metabolite shows any relevant antimicrobial activity	Check box
Remarks	Provide any other information to support the classification of this metabolite as 'of concern'.	Text (2,000 char.)
Metabolites		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Step 5: Is the genus of the strain under evaluation well studied?		Header 2
	Literature data. Is the microorganism well studied? (see step 5.1 of SANCO/2020/12258) Provide a further an evaluation of the body of knowledge from the scientific literatures presented above. Is there sufficient information to conclude on the metabolites of concern? As a matter of principle, it is highly recommended to the applicant to conduct the search beyond the normally requested period of 10 years before the application, in order to gather all the possible relevant scientific literature to support the risk assessment.	Text (rich-text area)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

Link to supporting material:

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

Guidance on the risk assessment of metabolites produced by micro-organisms used as plant protection active substances. SANCO/2020/12258 Rev. 1
https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/ffdf09b5-77a5-45b5-95f9-b16272f7535a_en

5.5.2 (CF. METABOLITE DATASET, 5) ADDITIONAL TOXICITY STUDIES ON METABOLITES OF CONCERN

Studies carried out with metabolites of (potential) concern should be reported in the dataset of each relevant metabolite.

Supporting material:

European Commission draft guidance document Guidance for the setting of an acute reference dose (ARfD) (7199/VI/99)

ECHA Guidance on the application of the CLP criteria. Guidance to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures

EFSA Guidance on the use of the Threshold of Toxicological Concern approach in food safety assessment (EFSA Journal 2019;17(6):5708)

OECD Series on Testing and Assessment No. 124, Guidance for the Derivation of an Acute Reference Dose. (ENV/JM/MONO(2010)15)

5.6 Additional toxicological information – Endpoint summary

Purpose

Provide a summary of additional studies investigating chronic mammalian toxicity, pathogenicity and infectiveness, carcinogenicity and reproductive toxicity (if available). Provide only the most relevant details.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.AdditionalToxicologicalInformation		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study records	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Cross-reference: ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD. AdditionalToxicologicalInformation
Description of key information	Provide a brief description of additional toxicological studies and effects.	Text (rich-text area)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block ". Provide additional information related to the endpoint, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An overview summary table with conclusion on the toxicological profile of metabolites (i.e. genotoxicity and general toxicity) found as residues in crops and/or livestock and/or in groundwater. 	Header 1

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Supplementary studies on the active substance (State which study was performed and in what species and the outcome, if applicable also the NOAEL and LOAEL.) ▪ Endocrine disrupting properties (State which study was performed and in what species and the outcome, if applicable also the NOAEL and LOAEL.) ▪ Studies performed on metabolites or impurities. Especially the acute toxicity and genotoxicity should be highlighted. Present other parameters if more examined. <p>If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty. See <i>IUCLID templates for PPP Risk Assessment - Template 5.4 - Template summary table on the assessment of the toxicological profile of metabolites</i> [http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4557353]"</p>	
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5.6 Additional toxicological information – Endpoint study record

Purpose

Under IUCLID if a metabolite is entered in the Metabolites Information document as a substance, a dataset is created and the study should be reported in this dataset if the test material is the metabolite. See instructions on secondary metabolites in the dedicated section in the introduction.

This endpoint study record should be used for those studies where not specific IUCLID document can be used.

As example, comparative *in vitro* metabolism studies should be currently reported by using this template.

In certain cases, it can be necessary to carry out supplementary studies to further clarify the adverse human effects.

In particular, if results from earlier studies indicate that the micro-organism may cause long-term health effects, studies on chronic toxicity, pathogenicity and infectiveness, carcinogenicity and reproductive toxicity must be carried out. Furthermore, where a toxin is produced, kinetic studies must be performed.

Studies required must be designed on an individual basis, in the light of the particular parameters to be investigated and the objectives to be achieved. Before performing such studies, the applicant shall seek agreement of the competent authorities on the type of study to be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AdditionalToxicologicalInformation		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Type of study / information	Indicate the type of information provided in this record and include any relevant information in fields 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables', 'Any other information on results incl. tables' and/or 'Overall remarks' as appropriate.	Multi-line text

	Note: Include only information that does not fit into any of the specific chapters. Use chapter 'Specific investigations: other studies' for studies on behavioural effects, biochemical or cellular interactions, chemobiokinetics general studies, cytotoxicity, endocrine system modulation, hematotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, mechanistic studies, methaemoglobinaemia, nephrotoxicity, phototoxicity, respiratory irritation, splenic toxicity, or toxicogenomics.	
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

6. Residues in or on treated articles, food and feed

Data on residues must be provided, unless:

- based on a weight of evidence approach concerning the information submitted in accordance with Sections 2, 3, 5 and 7 of Regulation (EU) 2022/1439, it can be justified that possible metabolites of concern identified are not hazardous to humans as a result of the intended use,
- it is possible to conclude, through estimation of consumer exposure to residues of metabolites for which a hazard to human health was identified that the risk for consumers is acceptable, or
- the micro-organism is a virus.

General note on instructions for section 6: please follow the instructions for the common blocks reported in the relevant chapter of this manual, **unless specific instructions are provided.**

6.1 Estimation of consumer exposure to residues

This document is to be used to summarize qualitative or semi-quantitative information on consumer exposure to residues of metabolites of potential concern. The objective is to determine whether such residues pose any risk to human or animal health and to classify metabolites as either not of concern (no further assessment required) or of concern.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ExpectedExposure		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	Optional text box to specify any issue related to the exposure assessment that could not be reported in the following tables. Make reference to the risk assessment residue definition reported in the Proposed residue definitions document, the toxicological reference values reported in the Toxicological reference values document and Processing/peeling factors reporting in the Nature and magnitude of residues in processed commodities document. When estimating the exposure, it shall be born in mind that the risk assessment has to take into account the residue definition established for risk assessment. Describe if relevant, the possible presence of pesticide residues arising from sources other than current plant protection uses of active substances (for example use	Rich text area

	<p>of active substances resulting in common metabolites, use as biocide or veterinary drug), and how their aggregate exposure shall be taken into account.</p> <p>Describe the method and results, if cumulative exposure to more than one active substance has been performed.</p> <p>If different exposure scenario are performed in the dossier, this should be reflected in different endpoint summaries. Please create on endpoint summary per scenario. Similarly, if both TMDI and IEDI are calculated to assess the chronic exposure, this should be reported in separate documents.</p> <p>Use this field to report the input values used to perform the chronic and acute risk assessments. The input values should be reported in a table (use the function create table in the rich text area). Please do not use merged cells in the table (see example below).</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Commodity</th> <th>Input value for chronic RA</th> <th>Comment</th> <th>Input value for acute RA</th> <th>Comment</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Commodity	Input value for chronic RA	Comment	Input value for acute RA	Comment																										
Commodity	Input value for chronic RA	Comment	Input value for acute RA	Comment																												
Exposure from dietary sources	Summarize results from PRIMO such as TMDI/IEDI (% ADI), IESTI (% ARfD) indicating the uses under consideration (e.g. representatives and/or MRLs) and highlighting whether a risk for consumer is expected.	Header 2																														
Model	Select PRIMO version (e.g. "PRIMo 3.1") if 'other' is selected provide details in the remarks	Open list with remarks																														
Food domain	Specify the food domain/class of the substance	Picklist with remarks																														
Residue definition(s) for risk assessment	Specify the compound(s), e.g., parent + metabolite(s), that are considered in the present exposure assessment.	Text																														
Toxicological reference values	Please select the document (from the mammalian toxicology section) where are reported the toxicological reference values (ADI and ARfD) relevant for this risk assessment.	Endpoint reference field																														
Chronic exposure		Header 3																														
Exposure assumption	Specify if TMDI or IEDI calculations.	Pick list with remarks																														
Assumptions	Specify the scenario under assessment and the assumptions taken for the chronic exposure calculations: e.g. if possible exposure from other sources were considered such as non-EU PPP compounds (e.g. biocide or veterinary drug), other	Multi-line text																														

	active substances resulting in common metabolites; if residues from rotational crops were considered; if Codex MRLs were considered; if any risk mitigation measures are applied; if other non-standard factors affecting the calculation are applied.	
Toxicological reference value (ADI) (converted)	[Only if needed]: If the TRV taken from the TRV document can directly be considered without conversion, this field is not relevant. If there is a need to convert the TRV to match with the expression of the RD RA (e.g. if the tRV is expressed for the variant but the RD RA is expressed as acid), please report the converted value of the TRV here and explain the rational for the conversion (incl. the factors used).	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Total exposure (absolute value)	Please report the absolute value of the highest calculated chronic exposures among all surveys/populations.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Total exposure (% of ADI)	Please report the value of the highest calculated chronic (among all surveys/populations) as % of ADI.	Decimal
Survey	Please report the name of the survey/population for which the highest chronic exposure was identified. This information is available in PRIMo excel file.	Open list with remarks
Contribution of commodities		Block of fields (repeatable block)
Commodity - chronic exposure	Commodities of plant and animal origin available for the PRIMo calculations (to assess the chronic exposure):	Open list
Chronic exposure from this commodity (absolute value)	Please report the absolute value of the chronic exposure due to the above mentioned commodity (highest calculated chronic exposures among all surveys/populations).	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Chronic exposure from this commodity (% of ADI)	Please report the value of the highest calculated chronic (among all surveys/populations) as % of ADI. Please report the value of the chronic exposure due to the above mentioned commodity as % of ADI (highest calculated chronic exposures among all surveys/populations).	Decimal
Population / Survey	Please report the name of the survey/population for which the highest chronic exposure was identified. This information is available in PRIMo excel file.	Open list with remarks
Acute exposure		Header 3
Assumptions	Specify the scenario under assessment and the assumptions taken for the acute exposure calculations: e.g., if possible exposure from other sources were considered such as non-EU PPP compounds (e.g. biocide or veterinary drug), other active substances resulting in common metabolites; if residues from rotational crops were considered; if Codex MRLs were considered; if any risk mitigation measures are applied; if other non-standard factors affecting the calculation are applied.	Multi-line text
Toxicological reference	[Only if needed]: If the TRV taken from the TRV document can directly be considered without conversion, this field is not	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)

value (ARfD) (converted)	relevant. If there is a need to convert the TRV to match with the expression of the RD RA (e.g., if the tRV is expressed for the variant but the RD RA is expressed as acid), please report the converted value of the TRV here and explain the rationale for the conversion (incl. the factors used).	
Commodity - acute exposure	Commodities of plant and animal origin for which an acute exposure can be calculated in PRIMo:	Open list
Exposure (absolute value)	Please report the absolute value of the acute exposure calculated for the commodity(ies) under assessment. Please report the highest IESTI.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Exposure (% of ARfD)	Please report the acute exposure as % of ARfD calculated for the commodity(ies) under assessment. Please report the highest IESTI	Decimal
Exposure from other sources (drinking water)		Header 2
	Exposure from other sources (drinking water). Please report in the Table the additional contribution to consumer intake through drinking water resulting from groundwater metabolites expected to be present above 0.75 µg/L. Indicate any metabolites included in the exposure assessment. Report PEC _{gw} or make reference to the information reported in Estimation of concentrations in ground water. Please use the recommended formats, available on knowledge junction [cf. residue Template 6.1 (http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621833), Table 6.9]. Please repeat the tables as much as necessary.	Rich text area
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block " Please upload here the PRIMo calculation. In case different scenarios are assessed, please repeat the block as much as necessary and explain the different scenarios in the remark field. An empty template of the PRIMo file is available on knowledge junction (Residue Template 6.6 : PRIMo rev.3.: http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1137758]. The uploaded file should not contain confidential material.	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

FAO Manual (FAO, 2016): <http://www.fao.org/3/i5452e/i5452e.pdf>

6.2 Further information required

6.2.1 STORAGE STABILITY OF RESIDUES – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide a summary overview of the demonstrated freezer storage stability period per compound per matrix and to conclude whether the storage stability of residues in matrices of plant and animal origin was sufficiently elucidated in the context of the present application.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.StabilityResiduesCommodities		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Study name / type	Provide here the link to the most relevant study (or studies) from which the key value(s) for the storage stability of residues is/are derived.	Endpoint reference list
Results		Read-only
Description of key information		Header 1
	Please make a statement as to whether the storage stability of residues in matrices of plant and animal origin was sufficiently elucidated in the context of the present application (according to the relevant data requirements and OECD test guidelines 506) and highlight data gap(s) and the non-standard uncertainty(ies), if any. Respective detailed parameters on the available key studies used for risk assessment should be reported in the detailed blocks below (one repeatable block for "storage stability - plant" and one repeatable block for "storage stability - animal").	Rich text area
Storage stability - plant	Repeat this block to create one row per key result (e.g. one row for each combination stability matrix/compound(s) covered with the most critical storage stability conditions).	Block of fields (Repeatable)
Category	Select the matrix to which the key results apply (e.g. commodities with "high water content"). Category defined according to OECD TG 506.	Open list with remarks
Commodity	Indicate the commodity(ies) tested in the study (multi-selection is possible). Select from the list of commodities of plant and animal origin to which MRLs apply according to Annex I of Reg. (EC) No 396/2005. Tested commodities can also be feed items (e.g. forage) or processed food product (e.g. grapefruit juice).	Multi select open list with remarks

Compound(s) covered	Indicate which compound(s) were tested for storage stability. If parent and metabolites were tested independently, please report it in different rows. If the sum of parent and metabolites was tested for stability, please specify it in this field.	Text
Substance(s)	Link (cross reference) to the substance(s) indicated in the above field.	Entity reference list
Temperature (°C)	Indicate the temperature tested in the study in degrees Celcius (e.g. -18°C).	Decimal
Tested period (length of the study)	Enter the entire period (as number) for which stability of the compounds was tested. The preferred reporting unit is months (m). Enter data using one decimal point, e.g. 244 days would be 3.8 months using an average of 30.4 days per month. If the period is lower than one month, report in full days. Example: If the study investigated storage stability for 24 months but residues are only stable for 12 months, please report 24 months in the present field.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Demonstrated stability period	Enter the period (as number) for which stability of the compounds was demonstrated. The preferred reporting format for storage stability is months (m). Enter data using one decimal point, e.g. 244days would be 3.8 months using an average of 30.4 days per month. If stability is lower than one month, report in full days.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Remarks	Add here any relevant information on the preparation of the samples and/or on any specific storage conditions for which stability has been shown. Examples for additional comments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mode of fortification, e.g. whole commodity or homogenised; - Analysis of fortified samples or samples from metabolism studies with incurred residues; - For specific cases, e.g. stability of sum of compounds sharing common moiety, use the same field to explain. 	Multi-line text
Storage stability animal	Repeat this block to create one row per key result (e.g. one row for each combination animal commodity(ies)/compound(s) covered with the most critical storage stability conditions). Fields and instruction are the same as for storage stability in plant matrices.	Block of fields (Repeatable)
Category	Select category from the list	Open list with remarks
Commodity	Commodity(ies) covered by the stability study(ies). Indicate the commodity(ies) tested in the study (multi-selection is possible). Select from the list of commodities of animal origin.	Multi select open list with remarks
Compound(s) covered	Indicate which compound(s) were tested for storage stability. If parent and metabolites were tested independently, please report it in different rows. If the sum of parent and metabolites was tested for stability, please specify it in this field.	Text
Substance(s)	Link (cross reference) to the substance(s) indicated in the above field.	Entity reference list
Temperature (°C)	Indicate the temperature tested in the study in degrees Celcius (e.g. -18°C).	Decimal

Tested period (length of the study)	Enter the entire period (as number) for which stability of the compounds was tested. The preferred reporting unit is months (m). Enter data using one decimal point, e.g. 244 days would be 3.8 months using an average of 30.4 days per month. If the period is lower than one month, report in full days. Example: If the study investigated storage stability for 24 months but residues are only stable for 12 months, please report 24 months in the present field.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Demonstrated stability period	Enter the period (as number) for which stability of the compounds was demonstrated. The preferred reporting format for storage stability is months (m). Enter data using one decimal point, e.g. 244 days would be 3.8 months using an average of 30.4 days per month. If stability is lower than one month, report in full days.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Remarks	Please report the same text as for stability in plant for the similar field.	Multi-line text
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

6.2.1 STORAGE STABILITY OF RESIDUES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

The aim of these studies is to demonstrate the time period for which stability has been shown in representative commodities from crops, by extrapolation to processed fractions derived from crops, and products of animal origin.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.StabilityOfResiduesInStoredCommod		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Product type	Indicate the product type addressed by the information entered in this record.	List
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Radiolabelling	Indicate if labelled or non-labelled test material was used. Generally, stability studies are carried out with non-labelled test material. In this case, please indicate "No" in this field. In the rare cases where the commodities used for stability study were obtained from metabolism studies using radiolabelled material, please indicate "Yes" in this field.	Open list with remarks
Study design		Header 2
Test commodity(ies)	To select the commodity(ies) tested in the study. In the context PPP applications, preferably use the picklists of commodities of plant and animal origin to which MRLs apply according to Annex I of Reg. (EC) No 396/2005.	Multi select open list
Details on stored commodities	Provide detailed description of commodities / matrices stored (whether raw or processed).	Text area

Storage temperature	Specify the storage temperature.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Duration of storage	Specify the total duration of the storage.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Other storage conditions	Specify the freezer type and additional storage conditions, e.g. dark or potential control condition including any special storage conditions, e.g. stabilizer added, humidity control, acid or base, temperature, lighting, container types/size, commodity form (extract/macerate/etc.), sample sizes/weight(s), duration, etc. You can choose the corresponding picklist item and give an explanation in the supplementary remarks field. . You can choose the corresponding picklist item and give an explanation in the supplementary remarks field.	Multi select closed list with remarks (2000)
Sampling and analytical methodology		Header 2
Details on sample collection	Include details on sampling time (age of raw commodity in days at each sampling time), number of samples/replicates. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Details on sample handling and preparation	Studies may be either performed on samples from treated crops or animals with incurred residues or by fortification experiments. In the latter case, aliquots of prepared control samples shall be spiked with a known amount of chemical before storage under normal storage conditions. Include details on the sample handling and preparation. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. The following information should be addressed: Handling and shipping of commodities, any preparation done prior to extraction (e.g. homogenised samples). It should be clear whether samples contain incurred residues or if samples were spiked/fortified with the active substance/metabolites; whether samples were homogenised or not. Use "insert existing templates" and delete/add elements as appropriate. E.g. <i>RAC</i> samples were homogenized and fortified with <i>test material</i> at about <i>X</i> mg/kg.	Text template
Details on analytical methodology	Provide details on the analytical method, i.e. describe methods fully or reference them if previously submitted. The method and its validation should be reported in Section 4 of the dossier 'Analytical methods', using a specific study record. Please cross-refer to the analytical methods and its validation using the "cross reference" block (see instructions in common block) Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate, or upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').	Text template

Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Residue data	<u>Specify the residue level of each analyte determined for a given commodity. Copy this block of fields for recording the results of multiple samplings, i.e. for each tested commodity at each storage period.</u>	
Test commodity	Select the tested commodity for which results are reported in this block. In the context PPP applications, preferably use the picklists of commodities of plant and animal origin to which MRLs apply according to Annex I of Reg. (EC) No 396/2005.	Open list
Other details on test commodity	As appropriate, provide details on the test commodity analysed.	Multi-line text
Fortification date (day 0)	Enter the date when the sample was fortified and put into storage (day 0)	Date
Storage removal date (day X)	Enter the date when the stored sample was removed from storage for analysis (day X)	Date
Sample ID	Provide the code of the sample if any.	Text
Sample description	Include a description of the sample.	Text
Storage period	Enter the storage period. This value should correspond to the difference between fortification and storage removal dates.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Fortification rate / spike level of stored sample	Enter the fortification level for the sample.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Analyte measured	Specify residue level of each analyte determined for a given commodity sample at a given storage period. Copy this block of fields for recording the results for multiple analytes (if any). If only one analyte (e.g. parent compound) is analysed in the study, there is no need to repeat this block.	
Analyte identity	Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name for indicating the identity (i.e. CAS number, CAS name,	Entity reference field

	<p>IUPAC name, SMILES code, molecular formula, structural formula etc.). If not available in the inventory, create a new one.</p> <p>Once stored in the Substances Inventory a reference substance can be re-used in the data set.</p> <p>Depending on the user interface of the software used the identity of the reference substance may only be displayed in a shortened form (e.g. comprising the CAS and IUPAC name), with a link for navigating to the actual record containing the reference substance information.</p> <p>If several compounds are directly analysed together by the analytical method (e.g. a common moiety method), a specific reference substance (being directly a sum of analytes) should be created and referred to. In this case, the results can be directly reported for the sum of compounds. In case of isomers please specify if the analyte measured is the sum of isomers (without distinction of isomers) or if specific isomer(s) were analysed separately. A corresponding reference substance may need to be created.</p>	
Extraction date	Enter the date of extraction.	Date
Analysis date	Enter the date of extraction.	Date
Method ID	Identify the analytical method that was used to obtain this result. This should cross-reference with the method(s) described in the method portion of this template).	Text
Residue level	<p>Enter the result as measured (i.e. based on the measured analyte) as concentration and % spiking level, without re-calculation and correction for storage stability.</p> <p><u>Copy this block of fields for recording the results of multiple analytical repetitions, and report the mean of analytical repetitions after the repeated blocks.</u></p>	
Analysed sample ID	Report the sample number/ID that was measured.	Text
Residue level	Report the measured level of the residue mentioned afore.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Residue level (% of nominal spiking level)	Enter the percentage of the nominal spiking level for the residue level determined in freezer storage stability sample as compared with the fortification level provided above.	Decimal
Mean residue level	Enter the mean residue level from the repeated analytical repetitions, determined in freezer storage stability sample including unit.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)

Mean residue level (% of nominal spiking level)	Enter the mean percentage of the nominal spiking level from the repeated analytical repetitions, for the residue level determined in freezer storage stability sample.	Decimal
Procedural recovery	Enter the result of the procedural recoveries for the given commodity at a given storage period. <u>Copy this block of fields for recording the results of multiple analytical repetitions, and report the mean of analytical repetitions after the repeated blocks.</u>	Block of fields (Repeatable)
Control Sample ID	Report the control sample number/ID that was used to measure the procedural recovery.	Text
Procedural recovery control (%)	Enter the percentage of the procedural recovery determined in freezer storage stability control sample.	Decimal
Mean procedural recovery control (%)	Enter the mean percentage, from the repeated analytical repetitions, of the procedural recovery for freshly spiked control sample.	Decimal
Storage stability of residues (Sample Integrity)	Briefly describe the conditions, which residues of [parent and/or metabolites] appeared to be [stable or [decreased or increased] by [percentage]]. <u>Example:</u> The residue of [parent and/or metabolites] decreased slowly with time. After [x months] of storage it amounted to [XX]% of the initial value and after [y months] of storage it amounted to [YY]% of the initial value Please make one statement per commodity. (Optional) Provide graph of residue stability in matrix as applicable as percent recovery over time, in an attachment (in the block below).	Text area
Transformation products	Indicate whether transformation products occurred and were identified in this study. If yes, provide information on the identified transformation products in following block of fields. Any further details can be entered in field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'.	Closed list with remarks
Identity of transformation products	Use this repeatable block of fields for specifying the transformation products found and their parent compound(s).	
No.	select a consecutive number for each transformation product from drop-down list if more than one transformation product is entered. If the same substance is identified by more than one identifiers (e.g. by CAS name and Common name), make sure that the same number is allocated to these entries.	Closed list
Reference substance	Indicate the identity of the compound (transformation product or test substance) using an appropriate identifier, e.g. CAS number, CAS name, IUPAC name. Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name. If not available in the inventory, create a new one.	Entity reference field

Parent compound(s)	<p>If the compound is a transformation product, link to the identity of the substance that is characterised as the parent of this transformation product. Link to multiple parent substances if applicable.</p> <p>Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name. If not available in the inventory, create a new one.</p>	Entity reference field
Maximum occurrence (%)	Indicate the maximum occurrence of the transformation product in %.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables		Header 2
	<p>In this field, you can enter any other remarks on the results. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format.</p> <p>NB: According to OECD 506 guidance correction for day zero recovery and/or procedural recovery is not recommended.</p> <p>Other formats can be used provided that all information requested in OECD TG 506 is reported and that they are readable by the system.</p>	Rich text area
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in "Overall remarks, attachments – common block"	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in "Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block"	Header 1
Conclusions	The assessment and conclusion of the applicant should be reported here.	Text area
Executive summary	<p>Briefly summarise the relevant aspects of the study(ies) including the conclusions reached. If a specific format is prescribed, copy it from the corresponding document.</p> <p><u>Example:</u></p> <p>Samples of [ground or whole crop/matrix] were fortified with [analytes] at a level of [fortification level] and put into storage at [temperature]. At intervals of [xx, yy, and zz] months, stored samples and freshly fortified samples were analyzed for residues of [list analytes].</p> <p>At each storage interval, [analytes] were determined using Method [Method ID], a [describe method]. Acceptable [method validation and] concurrent</p>	Rich text area

	<p>recoveries were reported for [matrices] samples at fortification levels of [xx] mg/kg (ppm), thus validating the method. The limit of quantitation (LOQ) was [xx] ppm per analyte for [matrices].</p> <p>Under these conditions, residues of [active ingredient and metabolites (if applicable)] were stable {or [decreased or increased] by [percentage]} in [crop/matrix] for [duration of time].</p>	
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6.2.2 MAGNITUDE OF RESIDUES IN PLANTS AND ROTATIONAL CROPS – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Endpoint summary for “PRIMARY CROPS”

Purpose

To provide a summary overview of the residue levels of all components of monitoring (MO) and risk assessment (RA) residue definitions (RD) in the relevant commodities for the critical GAP(s), to summarize risk assessment values and the MRL proposals and to conclude whether the magnitude of residues in plant (primary crops) was sufficiently elucidated in the context of the present dossier.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.MagnitudeResiduesPlants		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: “User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests” available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	<p>Enter a short description of the most relevant endpoint data.</p> <p>Only information on studies for primary crops should be described here. Information on rotational crops should be reported in a separate endpoint summary record.</p> <p>Please make a statement whether the magnitude of residues in plant (primary crops) was sufficiently elucidated in the context of the present dossier (according to the relevant data requirements and to OECD TG No 509) and highlight data gap(s) and the non-standard uncertainty(ies), if any. Respective detailed parameters on the available key trials used for risk assessment should be reported in the repeatable blocks below.</p>	Rich text area
Endpoint	From the picklist select the relevant endpoint addressed by this summary. Here: “residue in crops (field trials)”.	Closed list with remarks

	Separate endpoint summary records should be created for primary crops and rotational crops.	
Residue definition monitoring	Specify the residue definition for monitoring the residue level is based upon. If there are more than one relevant RD-Mo in the dossier, one endpoint summary per RD should be created.	Text area
Residue definition Risk Assessment	Specify the residue definition for risk assessment the residue level is based upon. If there are more than one relevant RD in the dossier, one endpoint summary per RD should be created.	Text area
Relevant GAPs	Enter the GAP(s) covered by the key residues results and key values reported in the present document. Create one new line for each relevant GAP.	Block of fields (repeatable)
GAP name	Enter the names of the GAP(s) covered by the key residues results and key values reported in the present document. The name of the GAP should be the same as the name given to the GAP document in the product dataset (Crop_zone.001).	Text area
Remark	Any remark on the reported GAP. The GAP name should be explicit (Crop_zone.numbering). Use this fields for any additional information.	Text area
Relevant GAPs		
Summary of key residues data selected from the supervised residue trials	Use this block to report the key residue results selected from the available residue trial studies. Repeat the block for each selected value and link each value to a study record.	Block of fields
Commodity	Select the raw agricultural commodity on which the relevant residue trial was performed. If the residue trial was performed on commodity A (e.g. Apples) to derive endpoints on commodity B (e.g. Pears), please report commodity A (e.g. Apples) in this field. The codes and names of raw agricultural commodities contained in the picklist are extracted from Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005.	Open list
Relevant GAP	Select the GAP, for which the selected key residue data is relevant. Pick-up the GAP name from the proposed list (refer to the GAP names defined in the block "Relevant GAPs"). Please note that this is a single link. Therefore, if a key residue data is relevant for more than one GAP, the line should be repeated for each GAP.	Linked to repeatable entry

Residue levels: RD MO	Report here the relevant result from supervised residue trial for the commodity (RAC), e.g. for wheat grain, expressed according to the residue definition for monitoring. Result should be expressed as mg/kg. The residue values below LOQ shall be indicated using the remark field.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Residue levels: RD RA	Report here the relevant result from supervised residue trial for the RAC, e.g. for wheat grain, expressed according to the residue definition for risk assessment. Result should be expressed as mg/kg. If RD-RA = RD-Mo, repeat the same value as for RD-Mo, or let this cell empty.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Plant back interval (PBI)	Not relevant for primary crops. If the endpoint selected is "residue in crops (field trials)", this field does not appear.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Study name / type	Specify from which study record the key value was selected.	Endpoint reference list
Remark	Enter any specific information on the rationale for selecting the values (e.g. PHI, calculation according to RDs...). In this field it is also possible to report the Sample ID from which the reported key values were identified. This information can better clarify the origin of the results when several samples are analysed in the same study record.	Text area
Summary of key residues data selected from the supervised residue trials		
Variability factors	Repeat this block to list each single variability factor study relevant for the assessment of the respective commodity(ies).	Block of fields (repeatable)
Commodity	Select the raw agricultural commodity name on which Variability Factor is derived. Please note that this is a single link. Therefore, if a Variability Factor is relevant for more than one commodity (and GAP), the line should be repeated for each commodity/GAP. The codes and names of raw agricultural commodities contained in the picklist, are extracted from Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005.	Open list
Relevant GAP	Select the GAP, for which the Variability Factor is relevant. Pick-up the GAP name from the proposed list (refer to the GAP names defined in the block "Relevant GAPS"). If a Variability Factor is relevant for more than one GAP, the line should be repeated for each GAP.	Linked to repeatable entry
Variability factor	Enter the empirical Variability factor derived for the commodity and GAP under assessment.	Numeric (decimal)

Residue definition	Specify the residue definition the variability factor is based upon. In case of deviating residue definitions for monitoring and risk assessment, report values individually in different blocks.	Text area
Study name / type	Provide here the link to the relevant study(ies) used to derive the Variability factor.	Endpoint reference list
Variability factor		
Endpoints derived from key residue data	Repeat this block for each relevant commodity/GAP under assessment.	Block of fields (repeatable)
Commodity for which MRL and risk assessment values are derived	<p>Select the raw agricultural commodity on which endpoints (MRL and risk assessment values) are derived.</p> <p>If residue trials were performed on commodity A (e.g. Apples) to derive endpoints on commodity B (e.g. Pears), please report commodity B (e.g. Pears) in this field.</p> <p>The codes and names of raw agricultural commodities contained in the picklist are extracted from Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005.</p> <p>This is a single choice. Therefore, if endpoints are relevant for more than one commodity/GAP, the line should be repeated for each GAP/commodity.</p> <p>The picklist also contains relevant feed items, to be selected when residue trials provide data on residues in feed items, used to derive STMR, HR and CF for feed items. For feed items not listed, select `Other` and specify.</p>	Open list
Relevant GAP	<p>Select the GAP, for which the endpoints (MRL and risk assessment values) are relevant. Pick-up the GAP name from the proposed list (refer to the GAP names defined in the block "Relevant GAPs").</p> <p>This is a single link. Therefore, if endpoints are relevant for more than one commodity/GAP, the line should be repeated for each GAP/commodity.</p>	Linked to repeatable entry
Highest residue RD-RA	Enter the supervised trials highest residue value (HR) [default unit is mg/kg] according to the residue definition for risk assessment.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
STMR RD-RA	Enter the supervised trials median residue value (STMR) [default unit is mg/kg] according to the residue definition for risk assessment.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Highest residue RD-Mo	Enter the supervised trials highest residue value (HR) [default unit is mg/kg] according to the residue definition for monitoring.	Numeric (decimal including unit)

STMR RD-Mo	Enter supervised trails median residue value (STMR) [default unit is mg/kg] according to the residue definition for monitoring.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Plant back interval (PBI)	Not relevant for primary crops. If the endpoint selected is "residue in crops (field trials)", this field does not appear.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Conversion factor	If RD for RA differ from RD for monitoring insert here the median conversion factor (CF) derived from the reported residue trials using the following formula: CF= [residue concentration] according to RD-RA / [residue concentration] according RD-MO To derive the median CF, user need to derive single CF for each pair of results (RD-RA/RD-MO) individually and then to calculate the median of the series of values.	Decimal
MRL derived	Enter the MRL derived from the relevant GAP, from the submitted residue trials listed above. Not mandatory for commodities exclusively used as feed items (e.g. wheat straw).	Numeric (decimal including unit)
MRL at LOQ?	Tick this check box if the MRL derived correspond to the LOQ for enforcement.	Check box
MRL is Provisional	Indicate if the proposed MRL and risk assessment values are provisional (yes or no) and clarify the reason in the additional remark field which appears after selection yes or no.	Closed list with remarks (2000)
Remarks	Specify whether a sufficient number of GAP compliant residue trials is available to support the GAP. For primary crops: confirmation that the trials support the GAP. Use this field for any other remarks that is not covered by the above fields. If the results reported in the above blocks refer to single trial results for pulp (e.g. orange pulp), this should be specified here in the remarks: e.g. "detailed results and risk assessment values derived from pulp". In such a case, no MRL needs to be derived.	Text area
Endpoints derived from key residue data		
Additional information		Header 1
	Use this field to add any additional useful text on this section. If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.	Rich text area

Attached background material	Add any additional document that support the above key results (e.g. calculation tables, graphs).	
Attached confidential document	The original file only needs to be attached here if it differs from the file in Attached (sanitised) documents for publication.	Single file attachment
Attached (sanitised) documents for publication	<p>Add any additional document that support the above key results (e.g. calculation tables, graphs).</p> <p>In support of the MRLs calculated for plant commodities, please also attach here the OECD calculator Excel, available for single and multiple data sets here: https://www.oecd.org/env/ehs/pesticides-biocides/oecdmaximumresiduelimitcalculator.htm.</p> <p>If additional calculators (e.g. Kruskal-Wallis.xls to compare dataset) were used in the assessment, they should also be uploaded here</p> <p>The uploaded file should not contain confidential material.</p>	Attachments list
Remarks		Text

Endpoint summary for “ROTATIONAL CROPS”

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide a summary overview of the residue levels of all components of monitoring (MO) and risk assessment (RA) residue definitions (RD) in the relevant rotational crops at various plant back intervals (PBI) covering the maximum soil concentration expected for the active substance (and its soil metabolites) for the use pattern on primary crop under assessment, to summarize risk assessment values and the MRL proposals (if relevant) and to conclude whether the magnitude of residues in rotational crops was sufficiently elucidated in the context of the present dossier and whether restrictions in crop rotation are required.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.MagnitudeResiduesPlants		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: “User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests” available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	<p>Enter a short description of the most relevant endpoint data.</p> <p>Only information on studies for rotational crops should be described here. Information on primary crops should be reported in a separate endpoint summary record.</p>	Rich text area

	<p>Please make a statement whether the magnitude of residues in plant (rotational crops) was sufficiently elucidated in the context of the present dossier (according to the relevant data requirements and to OECD TG No 509) and highlight data gap(s) and the non-standard uncertainty(ies), if any.</p> <p>If rotational crops residue trials are available, please report the detailed results in the repeatable blocks below.</p>	
Endpoint	<p>From the picklist select the relevant endpoint addressed by this summary. Here: "residues in rotational crops (limited field studies)".</p> <p>Separate endpoint summary records should be created for primary crops and rotational crops.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Residue definition monitoring	<p>Specify the residue definition for monitoring the residue level is based upon. If there are more than one relevant RD-Mo in the dossier, one endpoint summary per RD should be created.</p>	Text area
Residue definition Risk Assessment	<p>Specify the residue definition for risk assessment the residue level is based upon. If the RD-RA for rotational crops is different than for primary crops, please make sure this is reflected in this field. If there are more than one relevant RD in the dossier, one endpoint summary per RD should be created.</p>	Text area
Relevant GAPs	<p>Enter the GAP(s) covered by the available rotational crops field trials reported in the present document.</p> <p>Create one new line for each relevant GAP.</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)
GAP name	<p>Enter the names of the GAP(s) covered by the available rotational crops field trials reported in the present document.</p> <p>The name of the GAP should be the same as the name given to the GAP document in the product dataset (Crop_zone.001).</p>	Text area
Remark	<p>Any remark on the reported GAP. The GAP name should be explicit (Crop_zone.numbering). Use this fields for any additional information.</p>	Text area
Summary of key residues data selected from the supervised residue trials	<p>Use this block to report the key residue results selected from the available rotational field trial studies.</p> <p>Repeat the block for each selected value and link each value to a study record.</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)
Commodity	<p>Select the agricultural commodity investigated in the rotational crop trial, i.e. the following crop that is planted after soil aging.</p> <p>If bare soil was treated and aged and then planted</p>	Open list

	<p>with commodity A (e.g. sugar beet root), please report commodity A (e.g. sugar beet root) in this field.</p> <p>The codes and names of raw agricultural commodities contained in the picklist are extracted from Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005.</p>	
Relevant GAP	<p>Select the critical GAP covered by the key residue data reported in this block. Pick-up the GAP name from the proposed list (refer to the GAP names defined in the block "Relevant GAPs").</p> <p>Please note that this is a single link. Therefore, if a key residue data is supporting for more than one GAP, make sure to report the critical GAP relevant for rotational crops.</p>	Linked to repeatable entry
Residue levels: RD MO	<p>Report here the relevant result from rotational crop field trial for the commodity (RAC), e.g. sugar beet root, expressed according to the residue definition for monitoring. Result should be expressed as mg/kg.</p> <p>The residue values below LOQ shall be indicated using the remark field.</p>	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Residue levels: RD RA	<p>Report here the relevant result from rotational crop field trial for the commodity (RAC), e.g. sugar beet root, expressed according to the residue definition for risk assessment. Result should be expressed as mg/kg. If RD-RA = RD-Mo, repeat the same value as for RD-Mo, or let this cell empty.</p>	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Plant back interval (PBI)	<p>This field appears only if the endpoint selected is "residues in rotational crops (limited field studies)".</p> <p>For rotational crops trials, specify at which PBI (typically 30d, 120d of 365d) the residue results are considered. PBI is reported in days (d).</p>	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Study name / type	<p>Specify from which study record the key value was selected.</p>	Endpoint reference list
Remark	<p>Enter any specific information on the rationale for selecting the values (e.g. calculation according to RDs...). Possibility to also report the Sample ID(s) from which the reported key values were identified.</p>	Text area
Summary of key residues data selected from the supervised residue trials		
Variability factors	<p>Not expected to be reported under rotational crops endpoint. If a variability factor is derived from the available data, please report it under the endpoint "residue in crops (field trials)".</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)
Endpoints derived from key residue data	<p>Use this block only if MRL and RA value above the LOQ are proposed or derived in the present application. Repeat the block for each crop groups where significant residues in rotational crops have been reported.</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)

<p>Commodity for which MRL and risk assessment values are derived</p>	<p>This is a single choice.</p> <p>For rotational crops, endpoints are usually derived for an entire crop group (e.g. leafy crops).</p> <p>For pragmatic reason, it is not required to repeat this line for commodity. In this case, only select the representative commodity of the crops (on which trials were performed), e.g. sugar beet root (for root crops) or lettuce (for leafy crops)...</p> <p>The picklist also contains relevant feed items, to be selected when residue are expected from rotational crops in feed items and if STMR, HR and CF are proposed for feed items. For feed items not listed, select `Other` and specify.</p>	<p>Open list</p>
<p>Relevant GAP</p>	<p>Select the critical GAP for rotational crops covered by reported endpoints (MRL and risk assessment values). Pick-up the GAP name from the proposed list (refer to the GAP names defined in the block "Relevant Gaps").</p> <p>Please note that this is a single link. Therefore, if a key residue data is supporting for more than one GAP, make sure to report the critical GAP relevant for rotational crops.</p>	<p>Linked to repeatable entry</p>
<p>Highest residue RD-RA</p>	<p>Enter the supervised trials highest residue value (HR) [default unit is mg/kg] according to the residue definition for risk assessment.</p>	<p>Numeric (decimal including unit)</p>
<p>STMR RD-RA</p>	<p>Enter the supervised trials median residue value (STMR) [default unit is mg/kg] according to the residue definition for risk assessment.</p>	<p>Numeric (decimal including unit)</p>
<p>Highest residue RD-Mo</p>	<p>Enter the supervised trials highest residue value (HR) [default unit is mg/kg] according to the residue definition for monitoring.</p>	<p>Numeric (decimal including unit)</p>
<p>STMR RD-Mo</p>	<p>Enter supervised trails median residue value (STMR) [default unit is mg/kg] according to the residue definition for monitoring.</p>	<p>Numeric (decimal including unit)</p>
<p>Plant back interval (PBI)</p>	<p>This field appears only if the endpoint selected is "residues in rotational crops (limited field studies)".</p> <p>For rotational crops trials, specify at which PBI (typically 30d, 120d or 365d) the residue results are considered. PBI is reported in days (d).</p>	<p>Numeric (decimal including unit)</p>
<p>Conversion factor</p>	<p>If RD for RA differ from RD for monitoring insert here the median conversion factor (CF) derived from the reported residue trials using the following formula:</p> $CF = \frac{[\text{residue concentration}] \text{ according to RD-RA}}{[\text{residue concentration}] \text{ according RD-MO}}$ <p>To derive the median CF, user need to derive single CF for each pair of results (RD-RA/RD-MO) individually and then to calculate the median of the series of values.</p>	<p>Decimal</p>

MRL derived	<p>Enter the MRL derived to cover residues expected from rotational crops, based on the critical GAP and the residue trials listed above.</p> <p>Not mandatory for commodities exclusively used as feed items (e.g. wheat straw).</p> <p>Not mandatory if MRLs are not proposed for rotational crops.</p>	Numeric (decimal including unit)
MRL at LOQ?	Tick this check box if the MRL derived correspond to the LOQ for enforcement.	Check box
MRL is Provisional	Indicate if the proposed MRL and risk assessment values are provisional (yes or no) and clarify the reason in the additional remark field which appears after selection yes or no.	Closed list with remarks (2000)
Remarks	<p>Specify whether a sufficient number of rotational field residue trials is available to support the critical GAP considered for this assessment.</p> <p>Use this field for any other remarks that is not covered by the above fields.</p>	Text area
Endpoints derived from key residue data		
Additional information		Header 1
	Use this field to add any additional useful text on this section. If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.	Rich text area
Attached background material	Add any additional document that support the above key results (e.g. calculation tables, graphs).	
Attached confidential document	The original file only needs to be attached here if it differs from the file in Attached (sanitised) documents for publication.	Single file attachment
Attached (sanitised) documents for publication	<p>Add any additional document that support the above key results (e.g. calculation tables, graphs).</p> <p>In support of the MRLs calculated for plant commodities, please also attach here the OECD calculator Excel, available for single and multiple data sets here: https://www.oecd.org/env/ehs/pesticides-biocides/oecdmaximumresiduelimitcalculator.htm.</p> <p>If additional calculators (e.g. Kruskal-Wallis.xls to compare dataset) were used in the assessment, they should also be uploaded here</p> <p>The uploaded file should not contain confidential material.</p>	Attachments list
Remarks		Text

6.2.2 MAGNITUDE OF RESIDUES IN PLANTS AND IN ROTATIONAL CROPS – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

Primary crops: Magnitude of residue trials in plants shall allow to quantify the highest likely residue levels of all components of the different residue definitions in treated crops at harvest or outloading from store, in accordance with the proposed GAP, and, to determine, where appropriate, the decline rate of plant protection product residues in plants.

Rotational crops: Magnitude of residue trials in rotational crops shall permit an evaluation of the magnitude of residues in rotational crops, to decide on restrictions in crop rotation, provide information for assessing the overall relevancy of the residues for dietary risk assessment and to decide on the necessity of MRLs for rotational crops.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ResiduesInRotationalCrops		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Trial design and site description	<p>This section contains detailed information of supervised residue trials (primary crops or rotational crops depending on the endpoint selected at the beginning of the document).</p> <p>This part is divided into 3 main blocks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trial - Plot - Application <p>These blocks should then be linked using the function "block reference".</p>	Header 2
Trial	<p>This block of fields should be repeated for each trial. If one trial contain several plots, this should be reflected using the appropriate block below. Several plots can refer to the same trial using the function "block reference".</p> <p>Note: For still one year of transition (2025-2026), applicants can still opt for reporting the detailed residue trial information directly in the Excel file Residues trial table to be attached in the field "Attached sanitized documents".</p> <p>However, it is highly recommended to already use the structured fields of the OHT as available here.</p> <p>An empty Excel file to report Residues trials is available on the 'knowledge junction' [cf. residue Template 6.3 (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621117)]. The uploaded file should not contain confidential material.</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)

Type of trial	For residues in crops (field trials) (primary crops studies) indicate the type of trial, i.e. decline trial, harvest trial, reverse decline trial, post-harvest trial, seed treatment trial, or other: This field is not displayed for rotational crops trials.	
Type of crop	For crop rotation studies only: indicate whether the crop information entered in this field block refers to the primary crop or the rotational crop. If the initial application is made on bare soil, select "rotational" and report here the information on the following crop in the respective fields below. If the initial application is made on real crops (not on bare soil), select "primary" and report here the information on the crop on which the application was made. Then create another block with the same Trial ID No, select "rotational" and report the information on the following crop. This field is not displayed for primary crop residue trials.	
Trial ID no.	Define the trial specific and unequivocal identification code. For example, Company Internal Code.	Text
Crop	Enter the EPPO name of crop, see EPPO Plant Protection Thesaurus. at http://eppt.eppo.org using the available picklist. Note: this field is intended to report the crop used in the residue trial using the EPPO codes. Users are asked to find the best match in the available picklist. For the specific case of post-harvest treatment please use the sub-group "3HARVO harvested crops (treatment of)".	Open list with remarks
Crop variety	Specify the crop variety used in the trial, e.g. blood orange.	Text
Replant no. (1, 2)	List the consecutive numbers of the replanting. i.e. 1st crop replant = 1, 2nd crop replant = 2.	Integer
Date of planting	Enter the date of planting.	Date
Date of seeding	Enter the date of seeding.	Date
Date of flowering (beginning)	Enter the date of the beginning of flowering.	Date
Date of flowering (end)	Enter the date of the end of flowering.	Date
Date of harvest (beginning)	Enter the date of the beginning of harvest. This is just the starting date, please note that specific dates for each samples are expected to be recorded in the appropriate block "sampling and samples" in the results section.	Date
Date of harvest (end)	Enter the date of the end of harvest. This is just the ending date, please note that specific dates for each samples are expected to be recorded in the	Date

	appropriate block "sampling and samples" in the results section.	
Other details on test crops	Include other details on test crops.	Text area
Crop plant back interval	For rotational crop only: specify the time between application and planting (in days). This field is not displayed for primary crop residue trials.	Text
Crop information / history	All cultural information pertaining to planting, culture and trial-history of primary crop(s) or rotational crops, planting dates, rainfall and irrigation (accumulated from application), temperature data.	Text template
Geographic location and soil characteristics		Header 4
Test site type	Select the type of test site or test facility where the crops were grown, normally 'greenhouse', 'growth chamber' or 'outdoor test plot' for crop study or 'field site' for crop rotation study. If not listed, select 'other:' and specify.	Open list
Geographic location	Trial specific information.	Text
Trial deviation	List any deviations which may impact the trial results or study conclusions.	Text
Year	Indicate the year in which the first GLP data are collected in trial. Trial may extend over several years.	Integer
Country or territory	Select the country or the territory of the test site. The names of countries and territories are those prevailing at OECD for names used in lists available on the OECD website or in an OECD document. The codes mentioned between square brackets correspond to the 2-letter ISO codes.	Open list
Geographic region	Select the geographic region of the country.	Closed list
State/Province	Select the state/province as applicable depending on the selected country or territory.	Open list
County	Indicate the county as applicable.	Text
City	Indicate the city and the postal code as applicable.	Text
Postal code	Indicate the postal code as applicable.	Text
GPS coordinates	Provide the GPS coordinates as applicable. Use any of the following units and formats to specify the latitude and longitude: sexagesimal degree (degrees, minutes, and seconds): e.g. 50° 26' 46" N 80° 58' 56" W degrees and decimal minutes: e.g. 50° 26.767' N 80° 58.933' W decimal degrees: e.g. 50.446° N 80.982° W	Text

Soil characterization	Describe the soil type.	Multi-line text
Environmental conditions	Describe environmental conditions information which are not described in other sections in detail, e.g. abnormal weather conditions, soil properties, any other environmental effect that might have had an impact on the results observed in this study.	Multi-line text
Other details on test site	Describe details on testing environment information which are not described in other sections in detail, including crop and pesticide history on the trial site for the three years preceding the study, rationale for selection of trial site, location of test and control sites (as appropriate attach map of test plots indicating their location, topography, and location and size of control plots in relation to test plots), environmental conditions experienced during the course of the study (i.e., temperature, rainfall, sunlight), and soil characteristics (not required for materials applied to foliage) at the testing site such as soil type, % sand, % silt, % clay, % organic matter, cation exchange capacity and pH. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate or upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').	Text template
Trial		
Plot description		Header 2
Plot	This block of fields can be repeated to cover each plot (treated and control). Each plot should be linked to a given trial, using the Trial ID No (as a block reference/ link to a repeatable entry). Several plots can refer to the same trial. The report of control plots is not mandatory if control plots are negative. However, if positive findings are found for control plots, it is recommended to report them.	Block of fields (repeatable)
Trial ID	Use the block reference function (link to a repeatable entry) to link the plot to an unequivocal Trial ID No identification code. The trials ID should be created before in the above block.	Link to a repeatable entry
Plot ID	Define the plot specific and unequivocal identification code.	Text
Control plot	Specify if the reported plot is a control plot or a treated plot. If it is a treated plot, select "no"; if it is a control plot, select "yes"). N.B. control plot ID only need to be created if detailed results of control plot need to be reported (i.e. if there are positive control to be reported). If all control samples are negative, there is no need to create any control plot IDs.	Closed list

Plot description	Describe plot any useful specific information which are not described in other sections in detail, e.g. plot size or area, row spacing, plant spacing, plants/area, crop height, seeding rates, number of seeds/area, leaf wall area (LWA, applicable for high crops only), etc.	Multi-line text
Plot		
Application		Header 2
Application	This block of fields can be repeated to cover each application performed on a given plot. The applications should be numbered following the chronologic order of the application pattern. Each application should be linked to a given treated plot, using the Plot ID No (link to a repeatable entry).	Block of fields (repeatable)
Plot ID No.	Use the block reference function (link to a repeatable entry) to link the application to an unequivocal Plot ID No. The Plot ID should be created before in the above block.	Link to a repeatable entry
Application no. (1, 2)	State the consecutive number of the applications. i.e. 1st crop replant = 1, 2nd crop replant = 2. In the case of seed treatment, the sowing of the seeds is the first application.	Closed list
Bare soil	For crop rotational studies only: indicate if the application was on bare soil (yes) or not (no).	Closed list
Growth stage code (BBCH) at application	Enter the code of the BBCH-scale system or an intervall of two codes separated by "-" eg. 99 or 99-99.	Text
Growth stage description at application	Enter the description of the growth stage at application.	Text
Plant row distance	Enter the plant row distance.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Crown height during application	Enter the crown height during application. For non-tree crops report total treated plant height.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Leaf wall area	Enter the leaf wall area during application.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Date of application	Enter the date of application.	Date
Application target	Using the available picklist, specify how the product is applied (e.g. on soil, on foliage/plant, post-harvest...). This information is complementary to the method of application.	Open list with remarks
Method of application	Select the treatment/application method used in the residue trial. The picklist is based on the EPPO list (https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/). If no EPPO code is available to describe the method of application, select 'other:' from the picklist and	Open list

	<p>describe the method of application in the remarks. Examples for methods of application with no EPPO codes are listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bait treatment - basal bark treatment - dabbing/rubbing - [local treatment] - incorporation into compost - material incorporation or impregnation - [no class] - paint - [local treatment] - paste guns for volatile substances - pressure treatment - prune/wound treatment - [local treatment] - soil bed solarization <p>The remarks field can be also used to provide further details on the EPPO code selected to describe the method of application.</p> <p>Examples for further specification of some EPPO codes are listed below:</p> <p>Circulating water application (3CWATM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - hydroponic/aquaponic water treatment <p>Fogging (3FOGGM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mechanical fogging - thermal fogging <p>Fumigating (3FUMIM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fumigation: enclosed spaces - fumigation: vacuum chamber - gassing <p>Injecting (3INJEM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stem injection <p>Placing (3PLACM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - doseable matrix dispensers for volatile substances - retrievable active dispensers for volatile substances - retrievable passive dispensers for volatile substances - non retrievable active dispensers for volatile substances - non retrievable passive dispensers for volatile substances 	
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	<p>Spraying (3SPRYM):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - air assisted broadcast spraying - high volume spraying - low volume spraying - ultra low volume spraying - application in overhead irrigation water - banded spraying - spot treatment (spraying) <p>Spreading (3SPRDM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - granules application in row - granules application overall <p>If different application methods are foreseen in the same experiment (e.g. seed treatment followed by foliar broadcast), two application (#1 and #2) should be created and linked to the same plot.</p>	
Seeding rate	Enter the seeding rate, in case of seed treatments only.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Thousand grain weight	Enter the thousand grain weight in case of seed treatments for small grains.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Remarks	Any additional useful remark not captured in the above fields can be reported here.	Multi-line text
Test material information	Select the appropriate TMI record. The test material should be a mixture. The mixture needs to be created in a separate document and be able in the repository. A link to the relevant mixture (TMI) should then be created (it is also possible to copy an existing TMI record, edit it and store it as new TMI).	Entity reference field
Adjuvant added	Indicate the additive type, additive name, content added in spray volume (%), actual additive amount.	Multi-line text
Amount of water used in spray application	Indicate the amount of water used in spray application and specify the unit.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Related substance information	<p>Each component should be cross referenced to a 'Real' Substance definition in IUCLID.</p> <p>In the context of active substance assessment (new active or renewal) of in an MRL application, it is only mandatory to report the active substance under assessment.</p>	Entity reference field
Applied amount a.i. (actual)	State the actual application rate, anticipated/targeted use rate (label rate) of the active ingredient. The application rate refers the active ingredient and specify the unit.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)

Application		
Other details on application	Include any other details on the application pattern that is not already captured in the above blocks. (e.g. the application rate per meter height of crown).	Text
Sampling		Header 2
Details on sample collection	Include any useful details on sampling time which are not reported in detail in the structured fields.	Text template
Details on sample handling and preparation	<p>Details on sample handling and preparation which are not reported in detail in the structure fields.</p> <p>Describe all storage intervals between sampling in the field and analysis in the laboratory, and cross-reference to storage stability study, as applicable. The conditions of handling and storing the samples (e.g. chopped, homogenised, as extracts) at all stages between sampling and analysis should be described.</p>	Text template
Further details on study design	Include any further relevant details on the study design. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables		Header 2
	<p>In this field, you can enter any information on materials and methods, for which no distinct field is available, or transfer free text from other databases. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format. You can also upload any htm or html document.</p> <p>Note: One rich text editor field each is provided for the MATERIALS AND METHODS and RESULTS section. In addition the fields 'Overall remarks' and 'Executive summary' allow rich text entry.</p>	Rich text area
Results and discussion		Header 1
Storage stability of residues (Sample integrity)	<p>Provide storage stability data for all analysed components of the residue, including conditions and length of storage of samples following receipt in laboratory and conditions and length of storage of extracts prior to identification of residues (Note: Handling, pre-shipping storage and shipping procedures for harvested samples to be described in field 'Details on sampling and analytical method').</p> <p>As appropriate, upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p>	Text area

	Note: Specific tables may be required. Consult the programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD HPVC, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) thereof.	
Storage stability studies	Enter cross reference to all storage stability studies relevant.	Entity reference field
Control plot results	<p>Select the relevant statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If all controls are <LOQ, select option one and specify the value of the LOQ in remark. - If there are few positive controls (>LOQ) but this is not expected to have an impact on the validity of the results, select option 2 and provide a justification why no impact on the results is expected in remark. - If controls are generally <LOQ, with few exceptions, select option three, and report detailed results only of those positive control plots in the summary of residues. <p>For substances where positive controls in most of the trials (e.g. naturally occurring compounds), select option four and report detailed results from control plots in the summary of residues.</p>	Closed list with remark
Summary of residues		Header 2
Sampling and samples	This block of fields can be repeated to cover each sampling and should be linked to a given treated plot, using the Plot ID No.	Block of fields (repeatable)
Plot ID No	Use the block reference function (link to a repeatable entry) to link the sampling information to an unequivocal Plot ID No. The Plot ID should be created before in the above block.	Link to a repeatable entry
Sampling ID No	Unequivocal sample identification.	Text
Sampling timing	Provide any information regarding the timing of the sampling, e.g. relation to application events, days after last application, etc.	Open list with remarks
Sampling interval	Enter number of days for specified sampling timing.	Integer
Growth stage code (BBCH) at sampling	Enter the code of the BBCH-scale system or an interval of two codes separated by "-" e.g. 99 or 99-99.	Text
Growth stage description at sampling	Enter the code of the BBCH-scale system and a description of the growth stage at application.	Text
Date of sampling	Enter the date of sampling.	Date
Sampling information	Description of sampling method, special remark (e.g. cabbage was harvested according to agricultural practice, 1st set of outer leaves were removed), sample handling (e.g. samples were frozen within 24 hours).	Multi-line text

	If applicable for the crop in question, information on number of trees/vines/crops sampled and number of units within a sample need to be provided.	
Sampled material / commodity (Field RAC sample) code	<p>Specify the sampled material / commodity (field RAC sample). Raw agricultural commodity (RAC) means the product in or nearly in its natural state intended for sale or consumption without further processing, or for processing into food for sale to the consumer. It includes irradiated primary food commodities and products after removal of certain parts of the plant. The term RAC means the same as "primary food commodity" or "primary feed commodity".</p> <p>The codes and names of raw agricultural commodities contained in the picklist are extracted from the Codex Classification of Foods and Animal Feeds, issued by the Joint FAO/WHO Food Standards Programme. The following Classes and Types are included with all their groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Class A Primary Food Commodities of Plant Origin; -Type 1 Fruits; -Type 2 Vegetables; -Type 3 Grasses; -Type 4 Nuts and seeds; Type 5 Herbs and spices (Codes starting with FB, FC, FI, FP, FS, FT, GC, GS, HH, HS, SB, SO, TN, VA, VB, VC, VD, VL, VO, VP, VR and VS) - Class C Primary Feed Commodities; Type 11 Primary feed commodities of plant origin (Codes starting with AL, AF, AM, AS and AV). <p>The field should be empty, if no appropriate Sampled material / commodity could be found in the Codex Classification of Foods and Animal Feeds.</p>	Open list
Sampling and samples		
Residue levels	<p>Specify residue level of each analyte determined for this sampling instance. Copy this block of fields for recording the results of repetitions and for multiple analytes.</p> <p>This block of fields can be repeated for recording the results of repetitions and for multiple analytes and should be linked to a given sample, using the sampling ID No.</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)
Sample ID No.	Use the block reference function (link to a repeatable entry) to link these results to an unequivocal Sample ID No. The Sample ID should be created before in the above block.	Link to repeatable entry
Analyte identity	<p>Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name for indicating the identity (i.e. CAS number, CAS name, IUPAC name, SMILES code, molecular formula, structural formula etc.). If not available in the inventory, create a new one.</p> <p>Once stored in the Substances Inventory a reference substance can be re-used in the data set.</p>	Entity reference field

	Depending on the user interface of the software used the identity of the reference substance may only be displayed in a shortened form (e.g. comprising the CAS and IUPAC name), with a link for navigating to the actual record containing the reference substance information.	
Method ID	Identify the analytical method that was used to obtain this result.	Link to repeatable entry
Extraction date	Enter the date of extraction.	Date
Analysis date	Enter the date of analysis.	Date
Recovery (%)	State the average recovery value that was obtained from concurrent recovery experiments for this analyte in the matrix or, if analytical results were corrected, the percentage value used for the correction of the respective sample results. Correction of results refers both to quantitative consideration of the general method performance (typically via mean percentage of procedural recovery results) and of compensation for specific matrix effects. This allows a reversal of analytical results corrected with the recovery, where needed (e.g. for older studies where the results were corrected).	Decimal
Correction by recovery	Indicate whether the correction by recovery was done.	Closed list
Reference portion	Specify for which part of plant or commodity the residue is calculated. Information on the sample preparation for analytical samples (peel/flesh separation, stone/pit removal, soaking for dry commodities, homogenisation) should be provided. For citrus fruits, stone fruits and tropical fruits also weight distribution between peel/flesh, flesh/stone, peel/stone/flesh needs to be recorded and provided.	Multi-line text
Residue level (measured)	Enter the result as measured (i.e. based on the measured analyte), without re-calculation and correction for storage stability. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Calculated analyte identity	Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name for indicating the identity (i.e. CAS number, CAS name, IUPAC name, SMILES code, molecular formula, structural formula etc.). If not available in the inventory, create a new one. Once stored in the Substances Inventory a reference substance can be re-used in the data set. Depending on the user interface of the software used the identity of the reference substance may only be displayed in a	Entity reference field

	shortened form (e.g. comprising the CAS and IUPAC name), with a link for navigating to the actual record containing the reference substance information.	
Residue level (calculated)	<p>Enter the result expressed as the calculated analyte (e.g. acid expressed as carboxylic ester), without correction for storage stability or recovery.</p> <p>Note: Depending on the relevant regulation corrected data may be provided in addition, but not instead of measured data. This refers also to data which are corrected for recovery.</p> <p>Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.</p>	Range with open list (Decimal)
Residue level (calculated and corrected)	<p>Enter the result expressed as the calculated analyte (e.g. acid expressed as carboxylic ester), after correction for recovery.</p> <p>Depending on the relevant regulation corrected data may be provided in addition, but not instead of measured data. This refers also to data which are corrected for recovery.</p> <p>Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.</p>	Range with open list (Decimal)
Residue levels		
Remarks	Report any general information on the overall residue results (e.g. deviations to GDs).	Text
Any other information on results incl. tables		Header 2
	In this field, you can enter any other remarks on results. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format.	Rich text area
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in "Overall remarks, attachments - common block"	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion		Header 1
Interpretation of results	Select applicable conclusion from the picklist.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Conclusions	The assessment and conclusion of the applicant should be reported here.	Text area

<p>Executive summary</p>	<p>The assessment and conclusion of the applicant should be reported here.</p> <p>Briefly summarise the relevant aspects of the study(ies) including the conclusions reached. If a specific format is prescribed, copy it from the corresponding document or upload it if provided as htm or html document.</p> <p>Example for supervised residue trials on primary crops:</p> <p>[Number] field trials for [active ingredient] on [crop(s)] were conducted in [country] during the [year] growing season.</p> <p>At each trial location, [describe timing and method of application; formulation used, rate, treatment interval and seasonal application rates of [xx] g ai/ha]. An adjuvant [was or was not] added to the spray mixture for all applications. [Crops] were harvested at a preharvest interval (PHI) of [xx] days. In [one] trial, samples were collected at different time intervals (PHIs of x, xx, xxx days) to monitor residue decline.</p> <p>All samples were maintained frozen at the testing facility, during shipping to the laboratory, and were stored frozen until analysis. The maximum storage interval for samples between harvest and analysis was [xx] days/months. Residues of [active ingredient] have been shown to be stable in [crops] for up to [xx] days under frozen conditions. Adequate storage stability data are therefore available to support the storage conditions and intervals for samples in the current trials.</p> <p>Samples in the current study were analyzed using Method [Method ID], a [describe method] to determine residues of [list analytes]. Acceptable [method validation and] concurrent recoveries were reported for [matrices] samples at fortification levels of [xx] mg/kg, thus validating the method. The limit of quantitation (LOQ) was [xx] per analyte for [matrices].</p> <p>Individual sample (and per-trial average) residues in [matrix] ranged from [xx] mg/kg to [yy] mg/kg. [Include for each matrix and/or variation in use pattern in the study]. Residue decline data show that residues of [active ingredient/metabolite] [increase/decrease/are unchanged/are too variable to assess decline] in [commodities] with increasing PHIs.</p> <p>Example for rotational crop field trials:</p> <p>[Number] field trials for [active ingredient] on [crop(s)] as rotational crops were conducted in [country] during the [year] growing season.</p> <p>At each trial location, [describe timing and method of application (specify bare soil or primary crop);</p>	<p>Rich text area</p>
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	<p>formulation used, rate, treatment interval and seasonal application rates of [xx] g ai/ha). An adjuvant [was or was not] added to the spray mixture for all applications. [Describe growth/maintenance of primary crop, if applicable]. [Crops] were planted into treated plots at plant-back intervals (PBIs) of [xx, yy, and zz] days. Crops were harvested at maturity and prepared for residue analysis.</p> <p>All samples were maintained frozen at the testing facility, shipped and stored frozen until analysis. The maximum storage duration for samples between harvest and analysis was [xx] days/months. Residues of [active ingredient] have been shown to be stable in [crops] for up to [xx] days under frozen conditions. Adequate storage stability data are therefore available to support the storage conditions and intervals for samples in the current trials.</p> <p>Samples in the current study were analyzed using Method [Method ID], a [describe method] to determine residues of [list analytes]. Acceptable [method validation and] concurrent recoveries were reported for [matrices] samples at fortification levels of [xx] mg/kg, thus validating the method. The limit of quantitation (LOQ) was [xx] mg/kg per analyte for [matrices].</p> <p>The results from these trials show that quantifiable residues of [list analytes] are not expected to occur at PBIs greater than [xx] days. At a PBI of [yy] days, individual sample residues ranged from [xx] ppm to [yy] ppm (Crop 1), [xx] ppm to [yy] ppm (Crop 2), and [xx] ppm to [yy] ppm (Crop 3). [Address other PBIs as needed.]</p>	
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6.2.3 MAGNITUDE OF THE RESIDUES IN PROCESSED COMMODITIES – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

Purpose of document on the effects of processing on the nature of residues: To provide a summary on the nature of the active substance/metabolites under standard hydrolysis study and to conclude whether or not breakdown or reaction products arise from residues in the raw agricultural commodity (RAC) during processing, which may require a separate risk assessment.

Purpose of document on the effects of processing on the magnitude of residues: To provide an overview on the quantitative distribution of residues in various processed commodities (PC) and the derived processing factors (PF). Pesticide residues to be measured in processing studies are determined by the residue definition which is derived from studies on the nature of the residue in processing and/or in plant and livestock.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.NatureMagnitudeResiduesProcessedCommodities		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1

	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see:</p> <p>"User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	<p>Please make a statement whether:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the nature of residues in processed commodities was sufficiently investigated in the context of the present dossier (according to current data requirements and OECD Guideline No 507) and highlight data gap(s) and the non-standard uncertainty(ies), if any. Please also clarify if the reported conclusions on stability/non stability of the residues under hydrolytic conditions refer to the parent compound only and/or to any relevant metabolites found in plant and animals. In the latter case, please create the endpoint summary in the metabolite data set and specify the metabolites covered by this conclusion. 2) the magnitude of residues in processed commodities was sufficiently investigated in the context of the present dossier (according to current data requirements and to OECD Guideline No 508) and highlight data gap(s) and the non-standard uncertainty(ies), if any. <p>Key results used for the risk assessment should be reported in the detailed tables below.</p>	Rich text area
Nature of residues in processed commodities	<p>Summarise the results from standard hydrolysis studies.</p> <p>Repeat this block to create one row per key result (e.g. one row for each hydrolytic condition investigated by the study/ies).</p>	Block of fields (Repeatable)
Relevant studies	Provide here the link to the most relevant study(ies) from which the key results for nature of residues in processed commodities.	Endpoint reference list
Conditions	<p>Select the standard hydrolysis conditions (e.g. sterilisation) for which a conclusion can be derived.</p> <p>Picklist values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - baking, brewing and boiling (60 min, 100°C, pH 5) - pasteurisation (20 min, 90°C, pH 4) - sterilisation (20 min, 120°C, pH 6) - other: 	Multi select open list with remarks (2000)
Stable	Select a statement whether the residues are stable or not when undergoing hydrolytic conditions mentioned above. Please use the field "remark" to further specify the conclusion (e.g. if the answer is "no", please	Closed list with remarks (2000)

	specify which are the main degradation products expected, e.g. if the answer is "inconclusive", please specify the eventual data gaps).	
Nature of residues in processed commodities		
Processing factors	<p>Repeat this block to create one box per combination raw agricultural commodity (RAC)/processed commodity (PC) for which processing factors could be derived.</p> <p>This section can also be used to capture the distribution of residues in peel/pulp by derivation of process factor pulp/RAC.</p>	Block of fields (Repeatable)
Relevant studies	Provide here the link to the study from where is derived the processing factor reported in this line.	Endpoint reference list
Type of application	Specify how the RAC samples were obtained. If the RAC sample come from field trials specify the type of treatment (pre-, post- or pre- and post-harvest treatment). If the samples where spiked, select "spiked sample".	Closed list
Processed fraction (PF sample)	<p>Specify the processed fraction for which the processing factor is derived (e.g. apple juice), using the available picklist. If not available in the picklist, select 'other:' and specify.</p> <p>Note: the available picklist provides the FoodEx2 code for processed commodities. Processed fraction can be found in the hierarchical picklist starting from RAC (e.g. apple juice pasteurized).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 0100000 - Fruits, fresh or frozen; tree nuts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0110000 - Citrus fruits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 0130000 - Pome fruits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0130010 - Apples <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0130010 - Apples, fruit, canned (FoodEx2: A01N0) 0130010 - Apples, fruit, cooked (from jelly) (FoodEx2: A039MFF28.A0BA1) 0130010 - Apples, fruit, dried (FoodEx2: A01MC) 0130010 - Apples, jelly (FoodEx2: A16FC#FD4.A01D.J) 0130010 - Apples, juice (FoodEx2: A039MFF10.A06HR) 0130010 - Apples, juice, clarified (FoodEx2: A039MFF10.A07X0) 0130010 - Apples, juice, clarified, pasteurised (FoodEx2: A039MFF10.A07X0SF28.A07HV) 0130010 - Apples, juice, pasteurised (FoodEx2: A039MFF10.A06HRSF28.A07HV) 0130010 - Apples, pomace, dry (FoodEx2: A0BJ0) 0130010 - Apples, pomace, wet (FoodEx2: A0BJR) 0130010 - Apples, puree (FoodEx2: A010J#F27.A01D.J) 	Open list
Residue definition Monitoring - RAC	Specify the residue definition for monitoring the residue level in the raw agricultural commodity is based upon.	Text area
Residue definition Monitoring - PC	Specify the residue definition for monitoring the residue level in the processed commodity is based upon.	Text area
Processing factor: RD MO	<p>The processing factor (PF) for monitoring is derived following this formula:</p> $\frac{[\text{residue concentration in Processed Com}]}{[\text{residue concentration in RAC}] \text{RD Mo}}$	Numeric range (decimal)
Residue definition Risk Assessment - RAC	Specify the residue definition for risk assessment the residue level in the raw agricultural commodity is based upon.	Text area

Residue definition Risk Assessment - PC	Specify the residue definition for risk assessment the residue level in the processed commodity is based upon.	Text area
Processing factor: RD RA	The processing factor (PF) for risk assessment is derived following this formula: [residue concentration in Processed Com]RD RA / [residue concentration in RAC]RD RA	Numeric range (decimal)
Conversion factor	Enter the value resulting from the following ratio: [residue concentration in Processed Com]RD RA / [residue concentration in Processed Com]RD Mo	Numeric range (decimal)
Is PF acceptable?	If PF derived is not acceptable, select "no" or "indicative", and clarify the reason in the remark field below.	Close list
Remarks	Please enter any additional remark for the processing factor, for example if the processing factor is tentative.	Text area
Sample ID	Optional entry: allow to specify the Sample ID from which the reported key values were identified. This field is not mandatory but might be useful to ensure a clear link between the reported processing factor and the original results of the study record.	Text area
Processing factors		
Remarks	Please enter any additional general remark regarding all processing factors reported above.	Text area
Endpoints derived from key PF data		Block of fields (Repeatable)
Processed fraction (PF sample)	Specify the processed fraction for which the processing factor is derived (e.g. apple juice), using the available picklist. If not available in the picklist, select 'other:' and specify. Note: the available picklist provides the FoodEx2 code for processed commodities. Processed fraction can be found in the hierarchical picklist starting from RAC (e.g. apple juice pasteurized). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 0100000 - Fruits, fresh or frozen; tree nuts <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0110000 - Citrus fruits <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0130000 - Pome fruits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0130010 - Apples <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0130010 - Apples, fruit, canned (FoodEx2: A01N0) 0130010 - Apples, fruit, cooked (from jelly) (FoodEx2: A039M#F28.A0BA1) 0130010 - Apples, fruit, dried (FoodEx2: A01M0) 0130010 - Apples, jelly (FoodEx2: A16FC#F04.A01D.J) 0130010 - Apples, juice (FoodEx2: A039M#F10.A06HR) 0130010 - Apples, juice, clarified (FoodEx2: A039M#F10.A07X0) 0130010 - Apples, juice, clarified, pasteurised (FoodEx2: A039M#F10.A07X0SF28.A07HV) <li style="background-color: yellow;">0130010 - Apples, juice, pasteurised (FoodEx2: A039M#F10.A06HRSF28.A07HV) 0130010 - Apples, pomace, dry (FoodEx2: A0B.J0) 0130010 - Apples, pomace, wet (FoodEx2: A0B.JR) 0130010 - Apples, puree (FoodEx2: A01QJ#F27.A01D.J) 	Open list
Residue definition Monitoring - RAC	Specify the residue definition for monitoring the residue level in the raw agricultural commodity is based upon.	Text area
Residue definition Monitoring - PC	Specify the residue definition for monitoring the residue level in the processed commodity is based upon.	Text area

Median Processing factor: RD MO	The processing factor (PF) for monitoring is derived following this formula: [residue concentration in Processed Com]RD MO / [residue concentration in RAC]RD Mo	Numeric range (decimal)
Residue definition Risk Assessment - RAC	Specify the residue definition for risk assessment the residue level in the raw agricultural commodity is based upon.	Text area
Residue definition Risk Assessment - PC	Specify the residue definition for risk assessment the residue level in the processed commodity is based upon.	Text area
Median Processing factor: RD RA	The processing factor (PF) for risk assessment is derived following this formula: [residue concentration in Processed Com]RD RA / [residue concentration in RAC]RD RA	Numeric range (decimal)
Median Conversion factor	Enter the value resulting from the following ratio: [residue concentration in Processed Com]RD RA / [residue concentration in Processed Com]RD Mo	Numeric range (decimal)
Is median PF reliable?	If the median PF derived is not reliable (e.g. not derived from a sufficient number of trials), select "no" or "indicative", and clarify the reason in the remark field below.	Close list
Type of application	Specify how the RAC samples were obtained. If the RAC sample come from field trials specify the type of treatment (pre-, post- or pre- and post-harvest treatment). If the samples where spiked, select "spiked sample".	Close list
Remarks	Please enter any additional specific remark on the median factor reported in this line.	Text area
Endpoints derived from key PF data		
Remarks	Please enter any additional general remark regarding the median processing factors reported above.	Text area
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information - common block "	Header 1

6.2.3 MAGNITUDE OF THE RESIDUES IN PROCESSED COMMODITIES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

Studies concerning the effects of processing on the magnitude of residues in processed commodities to determine the quantitative distribution of residues in the various processed commodities used as food or feed, to estimate processing factors and to allow a more realistic estimation of dietary intake of residues.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.MagnitudeResidInProcessedComm		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data - common block "	Header 1

	Note: Select relevant endpoint from picklist: magnitude of residues in processed commodities	
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Trial design and site description		Header 2
Spiked samples	<p>If the raw agricultural commodities samples (RAC samples) are spiked, and not taken from field experiments, select "yes". In this case, information on the field phase is not requested (see below).</p> <p>For spiked samples, please report any additional information on the spiking in remark.</p>	Closed list
Trial	These sections are relevant if RAC samples were not spiked (see above).	Block of fields (repeatable)
Plot description	These sections are essential to describe how the RAC samples were obtained before undergoing food processing.	Header 2
Application		Header 2
Sampling	<p>If RAC samples are obtained from a field residue trial, this section can be duplicated from the study record created with OHT 85-5.</p> <p>If not available, please report the essential field phase information necessary to understand how the RAC samples were obtained (trials, plots, applications and sampling). It is in particular essential to know which crop (and crop variety) was used, which method of application were tested and how the samples were obtained.</p> <p>See all detailed instructions how to fill these blocks in section 6.3 (Magnitude of residues in plants – Endpoint study record).</p> <p>Note: For still one year of transition (2025-2026), applicants can still opt for reporting the detailed processing trial information directly in the Excel file Processing trials table to be attached in the field "Attached sanitized documents".</p> <p>However, it is highly recommended to already use the structured fields of the OHT as available here.</p> <p>An empty Excel file to report Residues in Processed commodities is available on the 'knowledge junction' [cf. residue Template 6.5 (http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621130)]. The uploaded file should not contain confidential material.</p>	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Storage stability of		Text area

residues (Sample integrity)	See detailed instructions how to fill these fields in section 6.3 (Magnitude of residues in plants – Endpoint study record).	
Storage stability studies		Entity reference field
Control plot results		Closed list with remark
Summary of residues		Header 2
Sampling and samples	<p>This block of fields can be repeated to cover each sampling. The same block is used for RAC samples and processed samples.</p> <p>The RAC samples should be linked to a given treated plot, using the Plot ID No.</p> <p>The processed samples should be linked to a RAC sample (created in the present table).</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)
Plot ID No	Only for RAC samples: Use the block reference function (link to a repeatable entry) to link the sampling information to an unequivocal Plot ID No. The Plot ID should be created before in the above block.	Link to a repeatable entry
Sample ID No	Unequivocal sample identification.	Text
Processed commodity	<p>Indicate if sample is the results of processing and represents a processed commodity (yes or no).</p> <p>If the sample is a RAC sample, say "no".</p> <p>If the sample is a processed sample, say "yes".</p> <p>Depending on this entry, the respective fields of the present blocks will be available or not.</p> <p>For example, if the answer is "no" (i.e. RAC sample), the field "processing information" will not be available.</p> <p>For example, if the answer is "yes" (i.e. processed sample), the field "sampling timing" will not be available.</p>	Closed list
RAC sample ID	Only for processed samples: Please define the sample ID of the raw agricultural commodity (RAC sample ID) from which it was taken. The sample ID of the RAC and its characteristic should be defined separately (create another line for the RAC sample).	Text
Processing information	Only for processed samples: Description of processing method(s). Processed fraction: Special attention should be given to, but not limited to, processing order, pressures, temperatures, and the corresponding yield-weights of each fraction. Processed fraction handling (e.g. samples were frozen within 24 hours after processing). A description of the process method is necessary and the use of flow chart diagrams is helpful.	Text
Date of processing	Only for processed samples: Enter the date of processing.	Date

<p>Processed fraction (PF sample)</p>	<p>Only for processed samples: Use the available picklist to specify the processed fraction to which the residue data summarised in this refer. If not available in the picklist, select 'other:' and specify.</p> <p>Note: the available picklist provides the FoodEx2 code for processed commodities. Processed fraction can be found in the hierarchical picklist starting from RAC (e.g. apple juice pasteurized).</p>	<p>Open list</p>
<p>Sampling timing</p>	<p>Only for RAC samples: Provide any information regarding the timing of the sampling, e.g. relation to application events, days after last application, etc.</p>	<p>Open list with remarks</p>
<p>Sampling interval</p>	<p>Only for RAC samples: Enter number of days for specified sampling timing.</p>	<p>Integer</p>
<p>Growth stage code (BBCH) at sampling</p>	<p>Only for RAC samples: Enter the code of the BBCH-scale system or an interval of two codes separated by "-" eg. 99 or 99-99.</p>	<p>Text</p>
<p>Growth stage description at sampling</p>	<p>Only for RAC samples: Enter the code of the BBCH-scale system and a description of the growth stage at application.</p>	<p>Text</p>
<p>Date of sampling</p>	<p>Enter the date of sampling.</p>	<p>Date</p>
<p>Sampling information</p>	<p>Description of sampling method, special remark (e.g. cabbage was harvested according to agricultural practice, 1st set of outer leaves were removed), sample handling (e.g. samples were frozen within 24 hours).</p> <p>If applicable for the crop in question, information on number of trees/vines/crops sampled and number of units within a sample need to be provided.</p>	<p>Multi-line text</p>
<p>Sampled material/commodity (Field RAC sample) code</p>	<p>Only for RAC samples: Specify the sampled material / commodity (field RAC sample). Raw agricultural commodity (RAC) means the product in or nearly in its natural state intended for sale or consumption without further processing, or for processing into food for sale to the consumer. It includes irradiated primary food commodities and products after removal of certain parts of the plant. The term RAC means the same as "primary food commodity" or "primary feed commodity".</p> <p>The codes and names of raw agricultural commodities contained in the picklist are extracted from the Codex Classification of Foods and Animal Feeds, issued by the Joint FAO/WHO Food Standards Programme. The following Classes and Types are included with all their groups:</p> <p>- Class A Primary Food Commodities of Plant Origin; - Type 1 Fruits; -Type 2 Vegetables; -Type 3 Grasses; - Type 4 Nuts and seeds; Type 5 Herbs and spices (Codes starting with FB, FC, FI, FP, FS, FT, GC, GS, HH, HS, SB, SO, TN, VA, VB, VC, VD, VL, VO, VP, VR and VS)</p>	<p>Open list</p>

	<p>- Class C Primary Feed Commodities; Type 11 Primary feed commodities of plant origin (Codes starting with AL, AF, AM, AS and AV).</p> <p>The field should be empty, if no appropriate Sampled material / commodity could be found in the Codex Classification of Foods and Animal Feeds.</p>	
Sampling and samples		
Residue levels	<p>Specify residue level of each analyte determined for this sampling instance. Copy this block of fields for recording the results of repetitions and for multiple analytes.</p> <p>This block of fields can be repeated for recording the results of repetitions and for multiple analytes and should be linked to a given sample, using the sampling ID No.</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)
Sample ID No.	Use the block reference function (link to a repeatable entry) to link these results to an unequivocal Sample ID No. The Sample ID should be created before in the above block.	Link to repeatable entry
Analyte identity	<p>Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name for indicating the identity (i.e. CAS number, CAS name, IUPAC name, SMILES code, molecular formula, structural formula etc.). If not available in the inventory, create a new one.</p> <p>Once stored in the Substances Inventory a reference substance can be re-used in the data set.</p> <p>Depending on the user interface of the software used the identity of the reference substance may only be displayed in a shortened form (e.g. comprising the CAS and IUPAC name), with a link for navigating to the actual record containing the reference substance information.</p>	Entity reference field
Method ID	Identify the analytical method that was used to obtain this result.	Link to repeatable entry
Extraction date	Enter the date of extraction.	Date
Analysis date	Enter the date of analysis.	Date
Recovery (%)	State the average recovery value that was obtained from concurrent recovery experiments for this analyte in the matrix or, if analytical results were corrected, the percentage value used for the correction of the respective sample results. Correction of results refers both to quantitative consideration of the general method performance (typically via mean percentage of procedural recovery results) and of compensation for specific matrix effects. This allows a reversal of analytical results corrected with the recovery, where	Decimal

	needed (e.g. for older studies were the results were corrected).	
Correction by recovery	Indicate whether the correction by recovery was done.	Closed list
Reference portion	Specify for which part of plant or commodity the residue is calculated. Information on the sample preparation for analytical samples (peel/flesh separation, stone/pit removal, soaking for dry commodities, homogenisation) should be provided. For citrus fruits, stone fruits and tropical fruits also weight distribution between peel/flesh, flesh/stone, peel/stone/flesh needs to be recorded and provided.	Multi-line text
Residue level (measured)	Enter the result as measured (i.e. based on the measured analyte), without re-calculation and correction for storage stability. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Calculated analyte identity	Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name for indicating the identity (i.e. CAS number, CAS name, IUPAC name, SMILES code, molecular formula, structural formula etc.). If not available in the inventory, create a new one. Once stored in the Substances Inventory a reference substance can be re-used in the data set. Depending on the user interface of the software used the identity of the reference substance may only be displayed in a shortened form (e.g. comprising the CAS and IUPAC name), with a link for navigating to the actual record containing the reference substance information.	Entity reference field
Residue level (calculated)	Enter the result expressed as the calculated analyte (e.g. acid expressed as carboxylic ester), without correction for storage stability or recovery. Note: Depending on the relevant regulation corrected data may be provided in addition, but not instead of measured data. This refers also to data which are corrected for recovery. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Residue level (calculated and corrected)	Enter the result expressed as the calculated analyte (e.g. acid expressed as carboxylic ester), after correction for recovery. Depending on the relevant regulation corrected data may be provided in addition, but not instead of measured data. This refers also to data which are corrected for recovery.	Range with open list (Decimal)

	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	
Residue levels		
Remarks	Report any general information on the overall residue results (e.g. deviations to GDs).	Text
Any other information on results incl. tables		Header 2
	In this field, you can enter any other remarks on results. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format.	Rich text area
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in "Overall remarks, attachments – common block"	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion		Header 1
Conclusions	The assessment and conclusion of the applicant should be reported here.	Text area
Executive summary	<p>Briefly summarise the relevant aspects of the study including the conclusions reached.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>[crop] field trial for [active ingredient] was conducted in [country, location] during the [year] growing season. [Active ingredient, % ai, formulation type] was applied to [crop] at [rate of application (xx g ai/ha)] and harvested xx days after final treatment. The [RAC samples] were processed into [processed food/feed fractions] using [simulated commercial practices].</p> <p>All samples were frozen at the testing facility and remained frozen during shipping and storage prior to processing and analysis. The maximum storage interval for samples was [xx] days/months [specify period from harvest to processing and from processing to analysis]. Storage conditions and durations are supported by studies showing that residues of [active ingredient] are stable in [crops/processed commodities] for up to [xx] days under frozen conditions.</p> <p>Samples in the current study were analyzed using Method [Method ID], a [describe method] method to determine residues of [list analytes]. Acceptable [method validation and] concurrent recoveries were reported for [matrices] samples at fortification levels of [xx] mg/kg, thus validating the method. The limit</p>	Rich text area

	<p>of quantitation (LOQ) was [xx] mg/kg per analyte for [matrices].</p> <p>A comparison of the residues in the raw agricultural commodity (RAC) with those in each processed fraction resulted in processing factors of [processing factors] for [processed fractions], respectively. These processing factors [conform/did not conform] with the theoretical concentration factors.</p>	
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6.2.4 FEEDING STUDIES – FLEXIBLE SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide a summary overview of the residue levels of all components in products of animal origin which result from residues in feed.

Information on the relevant animal matrix for the calculated animal burdens in order to summarise the risk assessment values and the proposals for MRLs and to determine whether the magnitude of residues in products of animal origin has been sufficiently elucidated in the context of the present dossier.

Note 1: Feeding studies shall be provided where metabolism studies indicate that residues at levels of above 0,01 mg/kg may occur in edible animal tissue, milk, eggs or fish, taking into account the residue levels in potential feeding stuffs, obtained at the 1 × dose rate, calculated on the dry weight basis. Feeding studies shall not be required where intake is below 0,004 mg/kg bw/day, except in cases where the residue, that is to say the active substance, its metabolites or breakdown products, as defined in the residue definition for risk assessment, tends to accumulate.

Note 2: this document is also relevant to report dietary burden for different fish species and MRL proposal for fish and fish products.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.ResiduesInLivestock					
Name	Instructions				Type
Administrative data					Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .				
Description of the key information	Use this field to report the input values used to calculate the median and max dietary burden. The input values should be reported in a table (use the function create table in the rich text area). Please do not use merged cells in the table (see example below).				Rich text area
	Feed commodity	Input value for median DB	Comment	Input value for maximum DB	Comment

	<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>													
Key value for assessment		Header 1												
Dietary burden	<p>Provide here the results of the calculated livestock dietary burden for each relevant species (one new item per species). Repeat the block for each species. The dietary burden results reported here are the ones used to derive the MRL and risk assessment values in animal commodities that are reported in the second part of the present document. This document is also relevant for fish and fish products.</p>	Block of fields (Repeatable)												
RD (plant/feed) RA	Provide the plant risk assessment residue definition (valid for all plants including feed and processed feed item) for which this dietary burden is calculated.	Multi-line text												
Animal species	<p>Select the animal species, which the calculated dietary burden refers to. The picklist contains also relevant fish species, to be used if an assessment of residues levels in fish and fish products is performed.</p>	Closed list												
Median dietary burden	Report the Median dietary burden (mg/kg bw per day) calculated for the selected animal species.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)												
Maximal dietary burden	Report the Maximal dietary burden (mg/kg bw per day) calculated for the selected animal species.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)												
Median dietary burden	Report the Median dietary burden (mg/kg dry matter) calculated for the selected animal species.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)												
Maximal dietary burden	Report the Maximal dietary burden (mg/kg dry matter) calculated for the selected animal species.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)												
Trigger exceeded?	Conclude ("Yes" or "No") whether the trigger value is exceeded according to the relevant data requirement.	Closed list												
Remarks	Additional remarks on the calculated dietary burden result for the given species.	Text area												
Summary of residues data from feeding studies	<p>Expected key information: MRL derived, median and highest residue levels (STMR and HR) for each animal matrix (i.e. muscle, fat, liver, kidney, milk, eggs, etc.) based on the results of the feeding studies and comparison with dietary burden calculations. MRL and risk assessment values reported here are derived from the dietary burden results reported above. Repeat the block for each animal tissue.</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)												
Link to relevant study record(s)	Link to the relevant study record.	Endpoint reference list												
Commodity(ies) for which MRL and risk assessment values are derived	<p>Please select from the picklist the commodity(ies) of animal origin for which MRL and risk assessment values are derived in this block.</p> <p>In case the same MRL and RA values risk assessment values are derived for different commodities, a multi-selection is possible (e.g. sheep and goat muscles).</p>	Multiselect open list												

	The picklist contains also relevant commodities for fish products, to be selected if MRLs are proposed on fish and fish products.	
Highest residue RD-RA	Enter the highest residue according to the residue definition for risk assessment. [default unit "mg/kg"]	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
STMR RD-RA	Enter supervised trails median residue value according to the residue definition for risk assessment. [default unit "mg/kg"]	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Highest residue RD-Mo	Enter the highest residue according to the residue definition for monitoring. [default unit "mg/kg"]	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
STMR RD-Mo	Enter supervised trails median residue value according to the residue definition for monitoring. [default unit "mg/kg"]	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
MRL derived	This field refers to the MRL which is derived from the dietary burden reported in the present document. MRL is always expressed according to the residue definition for monitoring [default unit "mg/kg"]. All MRLs should be listed as basis for the decision on the MRL proposal to be reported in the summary report MRL.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
MRL at LOQ?	Tick this check box if the MRL derived correspond to the LOQ for enforcement.	Check box
Provisional	If proposed MRL and risk assessment values are provisional ("yes"), clarify the reason in the additional remark field.	Closed list with remarks (2000)
Remarks	This field can be used to report any further additional remark regarding the calculated MRL and risk assessment values, that could not be reported in the above table.	Text area
Conversion factor (CF)	Conversion factor between enforcement and risk assessment derived from the results of the feeding study.	Decimal
Additional information		Header 1
	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block " Provide additional information related to the endpoint, for example: - information on the potential data gaps - relevance of the results for the risk assessment	Rich text area

6.2.4 FEEDING STUDIES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

Residues in Livestock studies are conducted in order to quantify levels of residues in meat, milk, eggs and edible meat by-products (e.g. fat, liver, kidney), following the use of a pesticide product on feed plant commodities. The studies are conducted according to OECD TG 505 and provide data on the quantitative transfer of residues, i.e. factor between residue level in the diet and residue levels in edible commodities (milk, eggs, tissues).

Residues in Livestock studies are typically conducted in ruminants (cattle) and poultry (laying hen). In general, the results of cattle feeding studies may be extrapolated to other domestic animals (ruminants, horses, pigs, rabbits and others) and laying hen feeding studies to other

types of poultry (turkey, goose, duck and others). Please create one Endpoint study record per feeding study. Extrapolations should be specified in the endpoint summary above.

If feeding studies are not required in the context of the present application, please specify

NB: If you used a metabolism study as a proxy to conclude that residues exceeding the LOQ are expected in some matrices or if the calculated intakes indicate that existing MRLs have to be changed, additional calculations based on the livestock feeding study data have to be performed in order to set/update the MRL values for products of animal origin.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ResiduesInLivestock		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block " Note: Select relevant endpoint from picklist, here: "Residues in livestock".	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Background information	Use this field to include any background information, if required, or any relevant introductory remarks on the study summary. Leave field empty if not applicable. Do not include information for which specific fields are provided. For instance, include any background information on the test substance in fields on 'Test materials'.	Multi-line text
Product type	Indicate the product type addressed by the information entered in this record.	Open list with remarks
Type of study	Indicate the type of study in terms of exposure source. Select either 'livestock feeding', 'direct animal treatment', 'livestock feeding and direct animal treatment', 'animal premise treatment' or 'other:' (specify). In the supplementary remarks field, you can add explanations as appropriate. Most frequent options in the context EU PPP assessments: "livestock feeding".	Open list
Test guideline	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Block of fields (repeatable)
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Test animals		Header 2
Species	Select name of species. Multiple selection is possible, but it is strongly recommended to use separate records for each animal species studied. You can include a cross-reference, in field 'Same study also described in chapter:', to the record where the methodology is described in detail.	Multi select open list
Details on housing conditions and test animals	Include details on housing conditions and test animals. Use free text template and delete/add elements as appropriate, or upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). The following information should be addressed: HOUSING / HOLDING AREA: Describe the test facilities, i.e. animal housing including size of	Text template

	enclosures, individual vs. group housing, food and water containers, temperature, lighting, and waste handling. TEST ANIMALS: Include information on breed, age, weight, stage of development, health status and condition of test animals.	
Details on dietary regime	Include details on dietary regime. Use free text template and delete/add elements as appropriate, upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). The following information should be addressed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Composition of diet: Describe the diet of animals during acclimation and the dosing period regarding: (1) Types of feed (e.g., corn grain, layers mash, alfalfa pellets) and liquids; (2) Quantities provided (i.e., specific amounts or ad libitum). - Feed consumption: Report the feed consumption (dry weight for ruminants) on an individual or treatment group basis throughout the study. - Water: Report water consumption - Acclimation period: specify 	Text template
Administration / exposure		Header 2
Treatment type (route of exposure)	Select the treatment type used which determines the primary route of exposure in the study. Multiple selection is possible if, in specific situations, direct application of a product to livestock was studied in addition to exposure through feeding of treated crops. Most frequent options in the context EU PPP assessments: Oral: "capsule" or "applied on feed"	Multi select open list
Frequency of dosing	The frequency of application / dosing if the test material is not incorporated into the total diet or feed. Note: Reporting of the dates of the initial and final doses/applications may also be required. Consult the programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD HPVC, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) thereof.	Multi-line text
Dosing duration	Indicate the total length of the dosing period (e.g. 20 days).	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Doses / concentrations	Indicate the dose rates (feeding levels) as "mg/kg bw per day" (also possible mg/kg diet, mg/animal/day). If diet is the route of administration, the level of the test material in the total diet may be reported in parts per million (mg/kg feed) (dry weight basis for ruminants).	Block of fields (repeatable)
Dose / conc.	Enter numeric value with unit (recommended "mg/kg bw/day").	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to dose / concentration values, e.g. feeding level.	Multi-line text
Details on dosing	Include further details on the preparation of dose and the dosing regimen. If diet is the route of administration, use free text template (delete/add	Text template

	<p>elements as appropriate) or formulate otherwise or upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>PREPARATION OF DOSE: Describe the method of preparation of the dose (mixing with feed or concentrate ration, gelatine capsule, bolus, etc.). Indicate the date of dose preparation and storage conditions prior to its administration. RATIONALE FOR SELECTION OF DOSE LEVELS: Briefly describe, i.e. Level of intake expected, Exaggerated levels. Provide justification for other than the recommended dosing scheme.</p> <p>ANALYSIS OF SPIKED FEED: Describe the method used to analyse spiked feeds and the results of such analyses. If the methodology is described in chapter 'Analytical methods', you can include a cross-reference to that record in the block 'Cross-reference'.</p> <p>DOSING REGIME: Using an appropriate predefined table indicate the dosing regimen used.</p>	
No. of animals per dose group	Report the number of animals per dose group, e.g. "3 cows per feeding level".	Multi-line text
Control animals	Indicate whether and what type of concurrent control groups were used. Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify.	Multi select open list with remarks
Further details on study design		Header 2
Further details on study design	Include any further relevant details on the study design.	Text area
Details on sampling and analytical methods	<p>Include details on the sampling, handling and preparation of samples and the analytical methodology applied. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate, or upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>The following information should be addressed:</p> <p>IN-LIFE SAMPLING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Milk / eggs collected: Explain the collection of milk and eggs with any deviations from normal practice explained. Note compositing or pooling of samples; no pooling of milk from animals within a dosage group. - Amount of milk and number of eggs produced during normal production: Provide data as indicated. - Urine, faeces, cage wash collected: For feed-through pesticides, include data on urine, feces and cage wash. 	Text template

	<p>POST-SLAUGHTER SAMPLING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mode of sacrifice: Describe - Interval from last dose or treatment to sacrifice: Describe the time interval in hours or days between time of sacrifice and administration of last dose or application of final treatment. Give an explanation of intervals longer than 24 hours and consideration of their effect on residues. - Tissue harvested and their weights: Indicate the tissues taken after sacrifice, their type (e.g., thigh muscle, omental fat, etc.), and their weights. - Specification of and combining of samples from different animals: Indicate if pooling was done (usually acceptable for poultry, but not ruminants). <p>SAMPLE HANDLING AND PREPARATION: Describe the handling of tissues, eggs and milk between sample collection and storage addressing at least following items:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sample preparation prior to storage: e.g., chopping - Containers - Storage temperature - Length of storage: Include dates of collection, shipping, analysis, etc. - Mode of shipping, if applicable: <p>ANALYTICAL METHODOLOGY</p> <p>The method and its validation should be reported in Section 4 of the dossier 'Analytical methods', using a specific study record. Please cross-refer to the analytical methods and its validation using the "cross reference" block (see instructions in common block). If the study record referred to was duly compiled and contain the data on method validation, further information is not required in the present document. In the study record created for this method (and its validation) in Section 4 of the dossier, the following information is expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description of instrumentation, equipment and reagents used: Give a detailed description of the analytical method employed to measure residues and listing of which chemical species were measured (parent pesticide, metabolites). If the methodology is described in chapter 'Analytical methods', you can include a cross-reference to that record in the block 'Cross-reference'. - Extraction schemes: state 'see graphic attached' if a figure is attached in field 'Illustration' 	
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	<p>(picture/graph)' in 'Overall remarks, attachments'.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description of extraction and fractionation of radioactivity in each matrix - Chromatographic and spectroscopic behaviour of radioactive residues in extracts of animal matrices, parent, metabolites, and reference standards - The LOQ for all animal matrices analysed and, if available, the LOD and a description of how the LOQ and LOD were determined. 	
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block".</p>	Header 2
	<p>In this field, you can enter any information on materials and methods, for which no distinct field is available, or transfer free text from other databases. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format. You can also upload any htm or html document.</p>	Rich text area
Results and discussion		Header 1
Storage stability	<p>Provide storage stability data showing the behavior of residues as a function of time in tissues, milk, and eggs. Where samples were not analysed within 30 days, provide evidence showing that the storage did not affect the results of the study. Typically, reference should be made to Section 6.1 where storage stability data showing the behaviour of residues as a function of time in tissues, milk, and eggs have been reported. By reference to the endpoint summary on storage stability (Section 6.1), please specify whether the conditions of storage of the samples of the present studies are covered by the most limiting storage conditions for which stability of the relevant residues has been demonstrated.</p>	Text area
Residue data	<p><u>Enter a consecutive sampling number and specify the matrix / tissue sampled, sampling time and dose/feeding level. In a nested repeatable block, multiple analytes and repetitions can be recorded with the residue levels.</u></p> <p><u>Copy this block of fields for each different sampling instance.</u></p>	Block of fields (repeatable)
Animal No.	<p><u>Results should be associated to each animal individually.</u></p> <p><u>Therefore, please enter here the Animal No to which the following results correspond. For example, if three different goats were used in a lactating goat feeding</u></p>	Multi select closed list

	study, please indicate if the block refers to Animal #1, Animal #2 or Animal #3. Although multiple numbers can be selected, this function should not be used.	
Feeding level	Specify the feeding level, typically 1, 2 or 3.	Integer
Dose (mg/kg bw)	Specify the dose in mg/kg bw.	Decimal
Matrix / tissue sampled	Select the matrix / tissue analysed from the drop-down list. Further details can be entered as free text in the related supplementary text field, for instance the animal number. If not listed, select 'other:' and specify.	Open list with remarks
Sampling date	Report the days after the first dose or the actual date in ISO 8601 format (e.g. 2021-05-22).	Text
Sampling time	Report phase of the day the sampling took place, for milk/egg sampling.	Open list
Slaughter interval	Report time between last dose and sacrifice, for tissue.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Additional information on the sampling procedure	Report any additional information regarding the sampling procedure, if applicable.	Multi-line text
Analyte measured	Specify residue level of each analyte determined for this sampling instance. Copy this block of fields only if there is a need for recording the results for multiple analytes. If only one analyte (e.g. parent compound) was analysed in the study, no need to repeat this block.	Block of fields (repeatable)
Analyte identity	Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name for indicating the identity (i.e. CAS number, CAS name, IUPAC name, SMILES code, molecular formula, structural formula etc.). If not available in the inventory, create a new one. Once stored in the Substances Inventory a reference substance can be re-used in the data set. Depending on the user interface of the software used the identity of the reference substance may only be displayed in a shortened form (e.g. comprising the CAS and IUPAC name), with a link for navigating to the actual record containing the reference substance information. If several compounds are directly analysed together by the analytical method (e.g. a common moiety method), a specific reference substance (being directly a sum of analytes) should be created and referred to. In this case, the results can be directly reported for the sum of compounds. In case of isomers please specify if the analyte measured is the sum of isomers (without distinction of isomers) or if specific isomer(s) were analysed	Entity reference field

	separately. A corresponding reference substance may need to be created.	
Residue level	<p>Enter the result as measured (i.e. based on the measured analyte), without re-calculation and correction for storage stability.</p> <p>Copy this block of fields for recording the results of analytical repetitions. The mean calculated from all analytical repetitions should be reported after this repeatable block.</p>	Block of fields (repeatable)
Analysed sample ID	Report the sample number/ID that was measured.	Text
Residue level	Report the measured level of the residue mentioned afore. [Typical unit : "mg/kg"]	Range with open list (Decimal)
Mean residue level	Enter the mean residue level of the replicates data provided above [Typical unit : "mg/kg"]	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Remarks	Enter any additional information, e.g. the storage stability factor and how it was used in cases the residue level is based on a corrected value. Also correction by recovery if any can be indicated.	Text
Total / mean	<p>Specify the total (mean) of the relevant analytes reported above. Typically: sum of the parent compound and relevant metabolite(s), if for instance this calculated result is in line with the residue definition.</p> <p>If only one analyte (e.g. parent compound) was analysed in the study, please ignore this field..</p>	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Recoveries	Provide recovery percentages (all values, not just averages or ranges) for the test substance and/or its metabolites for tissues, milk, and eggs fortified with these compounds. If the method is described in another record, you can include a reference to that method description using the 'Cross-reference' feature. As appropriate, upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').	Text area
Depuration	Provide the results of depuration studies, if any. If a separate depuration study was done, you can include a reference to that record using the 'Cross-reference' feature. As appropriate, upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').	Text area
Residue transfer	Outline the conclusion reached as to whether residues of the pesticide transfer from feed items, direct application to meat, milk and eggs. If so, discuss the extent of transfer. Indicate the time needed to reach a plateau level in eggs and milk, respectively. The results can be summarized in a table (the preferable format) showing either the ranges or maximum residues in type each of sample for each feeding level. As appropriate, upload predefined table(s), if any, in rich text field 'Any other information on results incl.	Text area

	tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').	
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables		Header 2
	In this field, you can enter any other remarks on results. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format.	Rich text area
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in "Overall remarks, attachments – common block"	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in "Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block"	Header 1
Conclusions	Enter any conclusions if applicable in addition to the information given in fields 'Key results' and 'Interpretation of results' (if any).	Text area
Executive summary	<p>Briefly summarise the relevant aspects of the study including the conclusions reached. Example: [Active ingredient] was administered [method of administration] to [number and breed] of [animal] for [duration] consecutive days. Dosing was made at [list dosing levels in mg/kg feed]. [Report details on depuration study, if applicable.]</p> <p>Milk/egg samples were collected twice daily [provide details on sampling method]. Animals were sacrificed on Day xx within [xx] hours of last dose. Tissue samples of [liver, kidney, muscle, and fat] were taken from each sacrificed animal. All samples were maintained frozen at the testing facility, during shipping to the laboratory and were stored frozen until analysis. The maximum storage interval for samples between collection and analysis was [xx] days/months. Residues of [active ingredient] have been shown to be stable in [livestock matrices] for up to [xx] days under frozen conditions. Adequate storage stability data are therefore available to support the storage conditions and intervals for samples in the current study.</p> <p>Samples in the current study were analysed using Method [Method ID], a [describe method] to determine residues of [list analytes]. Acceptable [method validation and] concurrent recoveries were reported for [matrices] samples at fortification levels</p>	Rich text area

	<p>of [xx] ppm, thus validating the method. The limit of quantitation (LOQ) was [xx] ppm per analyte for [matrices].</p> <p>Following a pre-slaughter interval of [xx] hours, individual sample residues ranged from xx ppm to yy ppm [list matrices and residue levels]. [Describe, qualitatively and quantitatively, the relationship between residue levels and dosing levels for the matrices addressed in the study.] Depuration results indicated that residues of [analytes(s)] will [describe depuration results, noting especially matrices where there appears to be little reduction of residues with time.]</p>	
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6.2.5 PROPOSED RESIDUE DEFINITIONS

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide a summary overview on the residue definitions for commodities of plant and animal origin as derived on the basis of available metabolism studies in plant, livestock and processed commodities; and to provide conclusions on which compounds are to be included in the residue definitions for enforcement and risk assessment. In this endpoint summary, you should also highlight the provisional (i.e. tentative) residue definitions and their relevant data gaps.

NOTE: Only one summary per dataset should be created. If different residue definitions are proposed for different crops or different types of use, they should be reported in the repeatable blocks.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ResidueFood		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see:</p> <p>"User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	Optional text box to specify any particular issue related to the residue definitions, that could not be reported in the following tables.	Rich text area
Food / feed of plant origin residue definition risk assessment	Use the repeatable block to create as many rows as necessary to reflect the residue definition(s) for risk assessment for each combination "crop group/metabolism group/treatment type/provisional or not". Please make sure that a residue definition for risk assessment is proposed for all combinations that are relevant for this application	Block of fields (repeatable)
Crop group	Indicate if the residue definition covers primary crops and/or processed commodities and/or rotational crops. Please make sure that a residue definition for risk assessment is proposed for each item of the	Multi select closed list with remarks

	picklist, unless not required (e.g. not relevant for rotational crops)	
Metabolism group	If the residue definition is for primary crops or rotational crops, then select the metabolism group(s) for which the RD is applicable (from list OECD list Crops and Crop Groups for Purposes of Metabolism in Crops Studies)	Multi select open list with remarks
Treatment type	Indicate the type(s) of treatment for which the RD is applicable (e.g. seed treatment or foliar application)	Multi select open list with remarks
Residue definition risk assessment	Write here the full name of the residue definition for risk assessment; please use the exact wording in line with the current standards (e.g. sum of parent and metabolite 01, expressed as parent).	Multi-line text
Residue definition risk assessment components	Select the substance(s) (parent and/or metabolites/breakdown products) that is/are part of the residue definition written above	Entity reference list
Provisional	Indicate if the residue definition for risk assessment is provisional, if yes a remark field will open where the data gaps should be reported. Please note that if there is a data gap, the RD should be considered provisional.	Closed list with remarks (2000)
Remarks	Any additional remarks regarding the proposed RD for risk assessment (e.g. common RD with other substances, RD1 associated with tox references value of compound 1, RD2 associated with tox references value of compound 2...).	Multi-line text
Food / feed of plant origin residue definition for monitoring	Use the repeatable block to create as many rows as necessary to reflect the residue definition(s) for monitoring for each combination "metabolism group/provisional or not". Please note that for monitoring RD, no distinction be made between primary and rotational crops.	Block of fields (repeatable)
Commodity type	Indicate if the residue definition for monitoring is proposed for raw commodities (unprocessed) and/or for processed commodities. If the residue definition is for processed commodities, indicate the type of process (baking/brewing/boiling, pasteurisation, sterilisation) covered by the residue definition in the remarks. If the same monitoring residue definition is proposed for raw and processed commodities, both items can be selected to report the same residue definition in the same line.	Multi select open list with remarks
Metabolism group	Select the metabolism group(s) for which the RD is applicable (from list OECD list Crops and Crop Groups for Purposes of Metabolism in Crops Studies)	Multi select open list with remarks
Residue definition monitoring	Write here the full name of the residue definition for monitoring; please use the exact wording in line with the current standards (e.g. sum of parent and metabolite 01, expressed as parent).	Multi-line text
Residue definition monitoring components	Select the substance(s) (parent and/or metabolites/breakdown products) that is/are part of the residue definition written above	Entity reference list
Monitoring residue	Limit of quantification (LOQ) for the residue definition for monitoring and enforcement	Decimal

definition LOQ (mg/kg)		
Provisional	Indicate if the residue definition for monitoring is provisional, if yes describe a remark field will open where the data gap(s) should be reported. Please note that if there is a data gap, the RD should be considered provisional.	Closed list with remarks (2000)
Remarks	Any additional remarks regarding the proposed RD monitoring (e.g. common RD with other substance(s)...))	Multi-line text
Validated method	Indicate if a validated method for Monitoring (including inter-laboratory validation ILV) is available for the proposed residue definition.	Check box
Link to validated method	Link to the study describing method for monitoring and its validation	Endpoint reference field
Food / feed of plant origin residue definition for monitoring		
Food of animal origin residue definition risk assessment	Use the repeatable block to create as many rows as necessary to reflect the residue definition(s) for risk assessment for each combination "animal commodity/provisional or not".	
Animal	Select the animal group(s) (e.g ruminants) for which the proposed residue definition is applicable. If the same residue definition is applicable to several animals (e.g. ruminants and pigs), multi-selection feature can be used.	Open list with remarks
Commodity	Select the animal product(s) (e.g. liver or eggs) for which the proposed residue definition is applicable. Please make sure that a residue definition for risk assessment is proposed for each item of the picklist. If the same residue definition is applicable to several commodities (e.g. r all tissues of ruminants and pigs), multi-selection feature can be used.	Multi select open list with remarks
Residue definition risk assessment	Write here the full name of the residue definition for risk assessment; please use the exact wording in line with the current standards (e.g. sum of parent and metabolite 01, expressed as parent).	Multi-line text
Residue definition risk assessment components	Select the substance(s) (parent and/or metabolites/breakdown products) that is/are part of the residue definition written above	Entity reference list
Provisional	Indicate if the residue definition for risk assessment is provisional, if yes a remark field will open where the data gaps should be reported. Please note that if there is a data gap, the RD should be considered provisional.	Closed list with remarks (2000)
Remarks	Any additional remarks regarding the proposed RD for risk assessment (e.g. common RD with other substances, RD1 associated with tox references value of compound 1, RD2 associated with tox references value of compound 2...).	Multi-line text
Food of animal origin residue definition monitoring	Use the repeatable block to create as many rows as necessary to reflect the residue definition(s) for monitoring for each combination "animal commodity/provisional or not".	Block of fields (repeatable)

Animal	Select the animal group(s) (e.g. ruminants) for which the proposed residue definition is applicable. If the same residue definition is applicable to several animals (e.g. ruminants and pigs), multi-selection feature can be used.	Open list
Commodity	Select the animal product(s) (e.g. liver or eggs) for which the proposed residue definition is applicable. If the same residue definition is applicable to several commodities (e.g. r all tissues of ruminants and pigs), multi-selection feature can be used.	Multi select open list with remarks
Processing	Indicate if the monitoring residue definition is also relevant for processed commodities and indicate the type of processed commodity(ies) in the remarks.	Closed list with remarks (2000)
Residue definition monitoring	Write here the full name of the residue definition for risk assessment; please use the exact wording in line with the current standards (e.g. sum of parent and metabolite 01, expressed as parent).	Multi-line text
Residue definition monitoring components	Select the substance(s) (parent and/or metabolites/breakdown products) that is/are part of the residue definition written above	Entity reference list
Monitoring residue definition LOQ (mg/kg)	Limit of quantification (LOQ) for the residue definition for monitoring and enforcement	Decimal
Provisional	Indicate if the residue definition for monitoring is provisional, if yes describe a remark field will open where the data gap(s) should be reported. Please note that if there is a data gap, the RD should be considered provisional.	Closed list with remarks (2000)
Remarks	Any additional remarks regarding the proposed RD monitoring (e.g. common RD with other substance(s)...))	Multi-line text
Validated method	Indicate if a validated method for Monitoring (including inter-laboratory validation ILV) is available for the proposed residue definition.	Check box
Link to validated method	Link to the study describing method for monitoring and its validation	Endpoint reference field
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

6.2.6 PROPOSED MAXIMUM RESIDUE LEVELS

Purpose:

This document is to be used to provide a summary overview on the proposed MRLs for commodities of plant and animal origin as derived on the basis of supervised residue field trials (for plants) or from livestock feeding studies (for animal commodities). In this endpoint summary, you should also highlight the tentative/indicative MRLs and their relevant data gaps, indicate the proposed extrapolations and discuss the eventual non-standard uncertainty.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.MRLProposal		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).	Confidentiality

	For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	
Description of key information		Header 1
	Optional text box to specify any particular issue related to the proposed MRL(s), that could not be reported in the following table.	Rich text area
Maximum residue level	Use the repeatable block to create as many rows as necessary to report each MRL proposed in this application. Please report only one MRL proposal per combination "commodity/residue definition for monitoring". If for a given plant commodity, different MRLs could be derived in section 6.3 (based different GAPs), please only report the MRL to be proposed for inclusion in the Regulation (i.e. highest MRL for which no safety concerns are identified). Also note that only MRLs fully supported by data are expected to be reported in this table. A MRL proposal should be linked to a GAP, to at least one commodity and to a residue definition for monitoring (RD MO). If more than one RD MO are derived for this active substance, please propose one MRL per RD MO.	
Rationale for MRL proposal	Please indicate the reason why a new MRL is proposed, by choosing one or more rationale(s). Repeat this action for each MRL proposed in this table. Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - if an MRL on wheat grain is directly derived from a GAP on wheat, please select "use on primary crop". - If an MRL on commodity of animal origin is derived because the GAP on wheat leads to a significant increase of the dietary burden, please select "increase of the livestock dietary burden". - If the purpose of the MRL application is to delete an MRL, please select "other" and explain the rationale for lowering MRL at the LOQ in the remark field, e.g. "a risk for consumer is identified with the existing MRL, therefore it is propose to lower the MRL at the LOQ" 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Critical GAP	This entry refers to the critical GAP(s), on which the MRL proposal is based. Please note that cross-link to GAP is not possible. Therefore, the exact name of the GAP document as reported in the product dataset should be reported in the text box. If rationale for the MRL proposal is "use on primary crop", please enter the document name/s of the corresponding GAP document/s from the product dataset in the text box. The corresponding GAP is/are the critical GAP(s), on which the MRL proposal is based. In case of several GAPs for the same commodity/crop (e.g. SEU, NEU, indoor, third countries) only the GAP resulting in the highest MRL proposal (not leading to consumer safety concerns) should be reported here. If the MRL proposal is based on a combined dataset linked to several GAPs, all these GAP should be	MultiLine Text (2000)

	reported here. If rationale for MRL proposal is “residue in rotational crops from soil uptake”, report here the GAP leading to highest residue in soil.	
Commodity	The picklist contain all commodities of plant and animal origin to which MRLs apply according to Annex I of Reg. (EC) No 396/2005, plus products or part of products exclusively used for animal feed production. Indicate the commodity(ies) for which MRL is/are derived. Please repeat this block for each MRL. In case of extrapolation with similar MRL for different commodities, the extrapolated commodities can be selected using the multi-selection (e.g. apples, pears, quinces).	Multi select open list
MRL proposal	This field refers to the MRL proposal (in mg/kg) in the commodity(ie)y of plant or animal origin. In case of multiple GAPs, the highest MRL (expressed on RD for monitoring) and not leading to consumer safety concerns should be inserted here. Only MRLs fully supported by data are expected to be reported in this table. Therefore, provisional MRLs are not expected to be reported in this table.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Residue definition monitoring	Enter the monitoring residue definition relevant for the selected commodities of plant or animal origin. This is the residue definition on which the MRL is derived.	Multi-line text
MRL at LOQ	Tick this box to indicate if the MRL is proposed at the enforcement LOQ (equivalent to symbol * in the EU MRL database).	Check box
Remarks	Any additional remarks linked to the MRL derived.	Multi-line text
Maximum residue level		
Additional information	<p>Follow instructions reported in “Additional information – common block”</p> <p>Provide any additional information related to the MRL proposal(s), e.g., cases were MRL proposal are based on results from other crops.</p> <p>In support of the MRLs proposed for plant commodities, please attach here the OECD calculator Excel file, available on https://www.oecd.org/env/ehs/pesticides-biocides/oecdmaximumresiduelimitcalculator.htm, including the residue values used to derive the MRL proposal(s). The MRLs proposed for animal commodities, should be justified by the Animal Calculator Excel, which is uploaded in the endpoint summary of Section 6.4 (Feeding studies). The uploaded file should not contain confidential material.</p> <p>Upload this information into the Attached (sanitised) documents for publication field</p>	Header 1

Maximum residue level + New item 📄 Import file ▼

#	Rationale for MRL propo...	Critical GAP	Commodity	MRL proposal	Residue definition m...	MRL at LOQ
1	use on primary crop	Citrus_SEU.002 UUID752403c0- ee82-4c0c- a195-2e1c158951e 1	✓ 0110050 - Mandarins (0100000 - Fruits, fresh or frozen; tree nuts > 0110000 - Citrus fruits > 0110050 - Mandarins)	2 mg/kg	parent	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.2.7 EFFECT ON THE RESIDUE LEVEL IN POLLEN AND BEE PRODUCTS – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide a summary overview on the transfer of residues into pollen and bee products when active substance is applied on melliferous crop according to the intended/critical use pattern and whether any adverse risk to bee health was observed in the context of the present dossier.

Please report the key results on the residue levels in pollen and bee products for human consumption resulting from residues taken up by honeybees from crops at blossom.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.SupplementaryStudies		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	Please make a statement whether the magnitude residues in bee products was sufficiently investigated (according the current data requirements and to the latest version of the Technical Guideline SANTE/11956/2016) in the context of the present dossier and highlight data gap(s) and the non-standard uncertainty(ies), if any. Please report here the type of the experimental study according to the latest version of the Technical Guideline SANTE/11956/2016 (e.g., experimental studies via syrup feeding, field residue trials or tunnel trials), which was designed with an objective to determine the inadvertent residue in honey arising from pesticide use, in order to allow a dietary risk assessment and to establish scientifically-based MRLs. The relevance of results should be discussed in relation to the proposed uses of the plant protection product, including a critical appraisal of the study and its results. In particular the following points must be addressed:	Rich text area

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A residue at or above the LOQ (a value of 0.05 mg/kg or lower is favoured) in control samples - Adverse effects on health of the honeybees - MRL proposal and risk assessment values <p>If studies reported in this summary are not guideline or GLP compliant, if deviation from guidance are observed (e.g. not validated analytical method), please report it here.</p>	
Residue definition for monitoring	Specify the residue definition for monitoring in honey and bee products for which residue levels are reported.	Text
Residue definition for risk assessment	Specify the residue definition for risk assessment in honey and bee products for which residue levels are reported.	Text
Summary of key residues data selected	Use this block to report the key residue results selected from the available studies. Repeat the block for each selected value and link each value to a study record.	Repeatables Table
Matrix	Select the matrix from the drop-down list (typically "honey").	Open list
Residue level: RD-Mo	Report here the relevant result from available trial expressed according to the residue definition for monitoring. Result should be expressed as mg/kg.	Decimal including unit
Residue level: RD-RA	Report here the relevant result from available trial expressed according to the residue definition for risk assessment. Result should be expressed as mg/kg. If RD-RA = RD-Mo, repeat the same value as for RD-Mo, or let this cell empty.	Decimal including unit
Study name / type	Specify from which study record the key value was selected.	Endpoint reference list
Remark	Enter any specific information on the rationale for selecting the values. Possibility to also report the Sample ID(s) from which the reported key values were identified.	Text
Summary of key residues data selected		
Key results	Use this block of fields to report the key values (median, highest residues) per matrix according to the relevant residue definition(s).	Repeatables Table
Matrix	Select the matrix from the drop-down list (typically "honey").	Open list
Highest residue RD-RA	Enter the highest residue according to the residue definition for risk assessment.	Decimal including unit
STMR RD-RA	Enter the supervised trials median residue value according to the residue definition for risk assessment.	Decimal including unit
Highest residue RD-Mo	Enter the highest residue according to the residue definition for monitoring.	Decimal including unit
STMR RD-Mo	Enter supervised trials median residue value according to the residue definition for monitoring.	Decimal including unit
Conversion factor	Enter the conversion factor (residue definition for monitoring/risk assessment) derived from the available trials.	Decimal
MRL derived	Enter the MRL derived from the key residue values.	Decimal including unit

Remarks	Specify whether data is available to support the proposed MRL.	Text
Key results		
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

6.2.7 EFFECT ON THE RESIDUE LEVEL IN POLLEN AND BEE PRODUCTS – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to be used to report studies to determine the residue in pollen and bee products for human consumption resulting from residues taken up by honeybees from crops at blossom.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ResiduesProcessedCommodities		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Endpoint	Select relevant endpoint from picklist: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - residues in honey - residue in nectar - residues in pollen - residues in other bee products <p>If the MRL application is done to request an MRL in honey, the relevant endpoint to be selected is "residue in honey". If residues in flowers/upper part of the plant or nectar are used to support an MRL in honey, the relevant point is also "residue in honey" because the overall purpose is to derive an MRL in honey.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test guideline	Indicate according to which test guideline the study was conducted. (<p>If no test guideline was explicitly followed, but the methodology used is equivalent or similar to a specific guideline, you can indicate so in the 'Qualifier' subfield preceding the field 'Guideline'. Copy this block of fields for specifying more than one guideline (e.g. US EPA in addition to OECD guideline).</p>	
Guideline	There are two options referring to the same guideline "Residue Levels in honey SANTE/11956/2016 rev. 9" and "Technical Guidelines for determining the magnitude of pesticide residues in honey and setting Maximum Residues Levels in honey". <p>If the study was performed according to this guideline, by convention please select "Residue Levels in honey SANTE/11956/2016 rev. 9".</p>	Open list
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Study design	Please report the study design in the proposed structure below.	Header 2
Study type	Use the picklist to define the study type (field trials, syrup feeding tests, tunnel trials).	Open list with remarks

	<p>If different types of study are reported in the same study report, please create one study record per study type.</p> <p>If residues trials are performed to analyse residues in flowers/upper part of the plant or nectar, to support an MRL in honey, these trials should be considered as "field trials", specifying in the remark field "residues in nectar/flowers are measured".</p> <p>If trials are performed as rotational crops trials (measuring residues in honey or any other matrices), these trials should be considered as "field trials", specifying in the remark field "rotational crops".</p>	
Number of trials	Report the number of trials available in the study.	Numeric (integer)
Trial parameters	Use this block of fields to report detailed parameters for each trial.	
Trial number	Assign consecutive numbers to each trial (e.g. 1, 2, 3) and report the parameters for each trial below.	Closed list with remarks
Trials site	Only relevant for tunnel and field trials. Specify the trial site (e.g. geographical location). Specify: Country – Region - City – Postal code	Text area
Duration of trial	Indicate the duration of the trials using the appropriate unit. For honey trials, the duration goes from the day when the honeybee colony is exposed to the a.s. (e.g. the colony is fed with treated syrup or placed in the treated tunnel/field) until honey sample collection. For crop field trials, the duration goes from the treatment day until (flower/upper part of the plant or nectar) sample collection.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Tunnel size/ Field size	For syrup or tunnel trials, report here the tunnel size. For field trials, report here the field size. Size should be reported in m ² or in hectares.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Method of application/ administration	For syrup trials: Please provide information on administration of the test substance, such as number of days of administration of the spiked feeding solution, volume of the feeding solution. The concentration level should be reported in the specific field below. For tunnel and field trials: Describe how the test substance is applied and the crops used in the study (report the mode of application, the growth stage of the crops at application...). The number of applications and the application rate should be reported in the specific fields below.	Text area
Dose/ concentration	For syrup trials only: Indicate the dose or concentration levels applied and the basis of quantity used. Conversion of the dose / conc. values to the relevant unit used for the effect levels may be required. Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Number of applications	For tunnel and field trials only. Report the number of individual applications.	Numeric (integer)

Application rate (active ingredient) (actual)	For tunnel and field trials only: Report the actual application rate of the active ingredient (if more than one application is performed, the single rate per application should be reported here).	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to dose / concentration values, e.g. feeding level that could not be reported in the above fields. For field trials performed as rotation crops trials, please report here the additional relevant parameters: application on bare soil or not, Plant back interval (PBI), type of soil...	Text area
Trial parameters		
Additional study design details	Provide additional information on the study to assess compliance with guidelines and reliability/reproducibility of the results. Text prompts are provided for each study design. For syrup feeding test: Percentage of sugar in feeding solution For tunnel trials: Details on control plot Distance between trial sites (km) For field trials: Details on control plot No flowering crops within a 2 to 3 km radius? (500 m radius in the case of less-attractive flowering crops compared to the treated crop). Distance between trial sites (km) Details on pollen traps and methods to determine honey source	Text template
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block " In this field, you can enter any information on materials and methods, for which no distinct field is available, or transfer free text from other databases. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document.	Header 2
		Rich text area
Results and discussion		Header 1
Colony health	Report a general statement on colony health observations taken during the study.	Text area
Honey sample size	Report the sizes of the samples used in the study. A range of values is expected to cover the size of all the relevant samples used in the study.	Range with closed list (Decimal)
Storage of samples	Report the number of days the samples were stored for. As only one value can be reported to cover the storage conditions of all the relevant samples used in	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)

	the study, please report the max storage length from all samples.	
Percentage water content in honey	For field studies report the % water content to demonstrate that the honey has reached commercial maturity. A range of values is expected to cover all the relevant samples used in the study.	Range (Decimal)
Residue data	Specify residue level of each analyte determined for this sampling instance. Copy this block of fields for recording the results of repetitions (each trial) and for multiple analytes.	
Trial number	Refer to the trial number defined in material and methods. (e.g. for trial #1 defined in material and methods, report #1 in this field and report the results corresponding to trial #1 in this block of fields). Several lines can be created for the same trial, to report data from different samples and/or for different analytes.	Closed list
Analysed sample ID	Report the sample number/ID that was measured.	Text area
Result type	Specify if the results correspond to the treated sample or the control sample. Results for the treated samples are mandatory. Results for the control samples are mandatory if above LOQ. If control samples remain below LOQ, this can be included as a general statement in the field "remarks" of the present block.	Closed list with remarks
Matrix sampled	Select the matrix analysed from the drop-down list. 	Open list with remarks
Analyte identity	Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name for indicating the identity (i.e. CAS number, CAS name, IUPAC name, SMILES code, molecular formula, structural formula etc.). If not available in the inventory, create a new one. Once stored in the Substances Inventory a reference substance can be re-used in the data set. Depending on the user interface of the software used the identity of the reference substance may only be displayed in a shortened form (e.g. comprising the	Entity reference field

	CAS and IUPAC name), with a link for navigating to the actual record containing the reference substance information.	
Residue level	Report the measured level of the residue trial mentioned afore using the relevant unit (typically "mg/kg").	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks	Enter any additional information, e.g. the storage stability factor and how it was used in cases the residue level is based on a corrected value. Also correction by recovery if any can be indicated. If control samples remain below LOQ, this could be included as a general statement in this field.	Text area
Residue data		
Any other information on results incl. tables	Discuss and evaluate the reported measurements and the relevance of results in relation to the proposed uses of the PPP, including a critical appraisal of the study and its results. The results of the study can be also presented in a table format. In particular the following points must be addressed: - a residue at or above the LOQ (a value of 0.05 mg/kg or lower is favoured) in control samples. - MRL proposal, with reasoning, and derived risk assessment values.	Header 2
		Rich text area
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in "Overall remarks, attachments – common block"	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion		Header 1
Conclusions	The assessment and conclusion of the applicant should be reported here.	Text area
Executive summary	Briefly summarise the relevant aspects of the study including the conclusions reached. In case new compounds have been identified in bee product, which are not included in the risk assessment residue definition in plant commodities please report this information here. Example: In case of field test/tunnel test: The residue trials for the determination of residues of [test substance] in [bee product] from [name crop] were conducted in [country, location] during the [year] growing season. [Active ingredient, % ai, formulation type] was applied to [crop] at [rate of application (xx g ai/ha)] under [specify trial conditions (field/tunnel)]. In case of syrup feeding study: [residue of concern] was administered via syrup [application method] to bees for [duration] consecutive days. Dosing was made at [list dosing levels in mg/kg feed]. [Bee product] samples were collected at [conditions of sampled product (maturity, water content (%) etc.)] at [crop growth stage].	Rich text area

	<p>Residues of [active substance/metabolites] were present at the level of [xx] mg/kg in control samples of [bee product]/not present in control samples of [bee product] above the LOQ of [xx] mg/kg in control samples.</p> <p>In [bee product] the residues of [active substance/metabolites] were present at the level of [xx] mg/kg.</p> <p>All samples were frozen at the testing facility and remained frozen during shipping and storage prior to processing and analysis. The maximum storage interval for samples was [xx] days/months [specify period from harvest to processing and from processing to analysis]. Storage conditions and durations are supported by studies showing that residues of [active ingredient] are stable in [crops/processed commodities] for up to [xx] days under frozen conditions.</p> <p>Samples in the current study were analyzed using Method [Method ID], a [describe method] method to determine residues of [list analytes]. Acceptable [method validation and] concurrent recoveries were reported for [matrices] samples at fortification levels of [xx] mg/kg, thus validating the method. The limit of quantitation (LOQ) was [xx] mg/kg per analyte for [matrices].</p>	
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6.2.8 OTHER STUDIES – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.AdditionalInformationOnResiduesInFoodAndFeedingstuffs		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)	<p>Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.</p> <p>The study(ies) giving rise to the highest concern should be chosen. The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the study record is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score), type of study (e.g. duration, experimental design, observed effects), whether or not the study is GLP. Please provide your rationale for the selection of the relevant study record in the field "Additional information".</p>	Header 1

Description of key information		Header 1
	If all key information is provided in the linked study records, this field can be left empty. In case there is no linked study record, or in case you want to point to specific information in the linked study record, provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here.	Rich text area
Additional information	Provide a brief description of additional study(ies) and of the key conclusions derived from this/these study(ies). Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

6.2.8 OTHER STUDIES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

Use this section to report any study that does not fit into other specific endpoints study records or endpoints study summaries of the Section 6 (e.g. specific studies used to refine the consumer risk assessment such studies on variability factors).

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AdditionalInfoOnResiduesInFood		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block " Note: Select from picklist 'additional information on residue chemistry'	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Note: "Product type" field is not mandatory. The product type is already reported in Section 3.2 (Effect on harmful organism, function, mode of action and possible resistance). This field is optional.	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables		Header 2
	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block " In this field, you can enter any information on materials and methods, for which no distinct field is available, or transfer free text from other databases.	Rich text area

	You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format. You can also upload any htm or html document. Note: One rich text editor field each is provided for the MATERIALS AND METHODS and RESULTS section. In addition, the fields 'Overall remarks' and 'Executive summary' allow rich text entry.	
Results and discussion		Header 1
Details on results	Provide any other relevant details if not entered in the specific "Description" fields for the examined parameters.	Text area
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	In this field, you can enter any other remarks on results. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format. Note: One rich text editor field each is provided for the MATERIALS AND METHODS and RESULTS section. In addition, the fields 'Overall remarks' and 'Executive summary' allow rich text entry.	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in "Overall remarks, attachments – common block"	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in "Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block"	Header 1

7. Environmental occurrence of the microorganism, including fate and behaviour of metabolites of concern

7. Environmental occurrence of the microorganism, including fate and behaviour of metabolites of concern – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarize information from a range of different studies to conclude on the fate and behaviour in soil, water and air.

This document is to be used to summarise information on the occurrence of the microbial active substance in relevant environmental compartments (e.g., soil, surface water), focussing on the strain/isolate under evaluation; information on the natural occurrence of related organisms (e.g., species level) should be reported in Section 2 (biological properties document).

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.EnvironmentalFateAndPathways		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Description of key information	Description of key information: Enter a short description of the most relevant endpoint data. The short description could include for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the test guideline used, - the test organism, - the exposure duration, - the contextual information of the origin of the value, - qualitative characterization of some properties Group the main findings from the relevant endpoint level summaries and provide conclusions on the available information for the hazard assessment.	
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block " Data analysis file (calculation of parameters) can be uploaded in Attached (sanitised) documents for publication, the original file should be uploaded in Attached document only if it differs from the sanitised version	Header 1

7.1 Environmental occurrence of the microorganism

7.1.1 PREDICTED ENVIRONMENTAL DENSITY OF THE MICROORGANISM

Purpose

This document is to be used to report predicted environmental density/concentration for microorganisms and its metabolites following treatment with the plant protection product containing that microorganism under the proposed conditions of use.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EstConcOtherRoutes		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Link to relevant summary record(s)		Header 1
Summaries used as input parameters	Select the most relevant summary(ies) used to predict environmental concentrations.	Endpoint reference list
Description of key information		Header 1
	Indicate the route of exposure and conclude on the predicted environmental concentration for the route/s.	Rich text area
PEC from other routes of exposure		Header 1
PEC other routes		
Use description	Select the GAP document/s for the use	Endpoint reference list
Parent metabolite /	Indicate if the PEDs/PECs are reported for the microorganism (select "parent") or the metabolite.	Closed list
Substance	Select the substance for which the PEDs/PECs are reported.	Entity reference field
Route of exposure	Describe the route of exposure	Multi-line text
Method of calculation	Report the model or method of calculation	Text area
PEC	Report the value of the predicted environmental concentration or predicted environmental density.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)

PEC other routes		
Additional information	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Additional information – common block"</p> <p>Reports on how the PEC/PED were calculated can be uploaded in the attached documents.</p>	Header 1

Supporting information:

EFSA Guidance document on clustering and ranking of emissions of active substances of plant protection products and transformation products of these active substances from protected crops (greenhouses and crops grown under cover) to relevant environmental compartments, Section 2 (EFSA Journal 2014;12(3):3615)

EU Working document to the Environmental Safety Evaluation of Microbial Biocontrol Agents, section 3.1.2 (SANCO/12117/2012)

EFSA Guidance document for predicting environmental concentrations of active substances of plant protection products and transformation products of these active substances in soil, section 2.7 'Applicability of the tiered assessment scheme for microbial actives substances' (EFSA Journal 2017;15(10):4982)

EU Working document to the Environmental Safety Evaluation of Microbial Biocontrol Agents, section 3.2.1 (SANCO/12117/2012)

7.1.1.1 (Cf. 7.1.1) Soil

7.1.1.2 (Cf. 7.1.1) Water

7.1.2 (CF. 8) EXPOSURE TO MICROORGANISMS KNOWN TO BE PATHOGENIC EITHER FOR PLANTS OR FOR OTHER ORGANISMS

7.1.3 QUALITATIVE EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT OF THE MICROORGANISM

Purpose

This document is to be used to record environmental qualitative exposure assessment, including links to relevant environmental and ecotoxicological studies and using weight of evidence (WoE) approach as described in [EFSA Scientific Committee, 2017](#).

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EnvironmentQualitativeExposureAssessment		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Qualitative exposure assessment of the microorganism	<p>Scientific Opinion on the guidance on the use of the weight of evidence approach in scientific assessments.</p> <p>EFSA Scientific Committee, Hardy, A, Benford, D, Halldorsson, T, Jeger, MJ, Knutsen, HK, More, S, Naegeli, H, Noteborn, H, Ockleford, C, Ricci, A, Rychen, G, Schlatter, JR, Silano, V, Solecki, R, Turck, D, Benfenati, E, Chaudhry, QM, Craig, P,</p>	Header 1

	Frampton, G, Greiner, M, Hart, A, Hogstrand, C, Lambre, C, Luttik, R, Makowski, D, Siani, A, Wahlstroem, H, Aguilera, J, Dorne, J-L, Fernandez Dumont, A, Hempen, M, Valtueña Martínez, S, Martino, L, Smeraldi, C, Terron, A, Georgiadis, N and Younes, M, 2017 EFSA Journal 2017; 15(8):4971, 69 pp. First published: 03 August 2017 https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4971	
	Conclude on environmental exposure based on the lines of evidence presented below.	Text (rich-text area)
Assembling evidence	Link to any literature searches for evidence to support the qualitative exposure assessment in the environment.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Weighing evidence		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Description of key conclusion for the study	Include consideration of the relevance and reliability of the study	Text (32,768 char.)
Identified uncertainties		Text (32,768 char.)
Link to relevant study record	Link to the endpoint study describing the supporting evidence.	Link to endpoint (single)
Weighing evidence		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Integrating evidence		Header 2
Potential risk for identified non-target organisms	Indicate whether there is evidence of risk for non-target organisms	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Non-target organisms	Where effects on non-target organisms are observed indicate the species group	List multi. (multi-select list)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

EFSA Scientific Committee, Hardy, A, Benford, D, Halldorsson, T, Jeger, MJ, Knutsen, HK, More, S, Naegeli, H, Noteborn, H, Ockleford, C, Ricci, A, Rychen, G, Schlatter, JR, Silano, V, Solecki, R, Turck, D, Benfenati, E, Chaudhry, QM, Craig, P, Frampton, G, Greiner, M, Hart, A, Hogstrand, C, Lambre, C, Luttik, R, Makowski, D, Siani, A, Wahlstroem, H, Aguilera, J, Dorne, J-L, Fernandez Dumont, A, Hempen, M, Valtueña Martínez, S, Martino, L, Smeraldi, C, Terron, A, Georgiadis, N and Younes, M, 2017. Scientific Opinion on the guidance on the use of the weight of evidence approach in scientific assessments. EFSA Journal 2017;15(8):4971, 69 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4971>

7.1.4 EXPERIMENTAL EXPOSURE DATA OF THE MICROORGANISM

7.1.4.1 Experimental exposure data soil – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise experimental data on density of microorganisms in the soil.

If under consideration of the information provided under points 7.1.1, 7.1.2, 7.1.3 and 7.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 1439/2022 a potential risk is identified for humans or non-target organism(s) or information is not sufficient to conclude about it, the population density of the microorganism shall be determined in relevant environmental compartment(s) (e.g. soil, water, plant surfaces).

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ExpressionInSoil		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Use the Confidentiality flag and/or the Regulatory purpose flag to filter out data in subsequent operations such as exporting, printing or dossier creation. A justification is required when the confidentiality flag is set.	Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment. The study(ies) giving rise to the highest concern should be chosen. The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the study record is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score), type of study (e.g. duration, experimental design, observed effects), whether or not the study is GLP. Please provide your rationale for the selection of the relevant study record in the field "Additional information".	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
	If all key information is provided in the linked study records, this field can be left empty. In case there is no linked study record, or in case you want to point to specific information in the linked study record, provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here. The summary could include, for example: - the test type	Text (rich-text area)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) - the test organism - the exposure duration - other contextual information on the origin of the key value 	
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

7.1.4.1 Experimental exposure data soil – Endpoint Study Record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report experimental data on density of microorganisms in the soil.

If under consideration of the information provided under points 7.1.1, 7.1.2, 7.1.3 and 7.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 1439/2022 a potential risk is identified for humans or non-target organism(s) or information is not sufficient to conclude about it, the population density of the microorganism shall be determined in relevant environmental compartment(s) (e.g. soil, water, plant surfaces).

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ExpressionInATerrestrialEnvironment		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Study design		Header 2
Soil properties	Repeat this block of fields for each different soil used as indicated by the Soil No. Enter soil type as cited in the study report and the respective soil properties.	Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Soil no.	Select a consecutive soil number from drop-down list if more than one soil types were used.	List (picklist)
Soil type	Select from drop-down list.	List (picklist)
% Clay	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
% Silt	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
% Sand	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range	Numeric range (decimal)

	use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	
% Org. C	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
pH	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
CEC	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Bulk density (g/cm³)	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
% Moisture content	Moisture content of the soil (at pF 2 or at Maximum Water Holding Capacity). Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
Soil properties		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Duration of test (contact time)	Specify duration of test in terms of contact time. Repeat block for each soil type. If different test runs have different durations, enter lower and upper value in respective subfields.	Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Soil No.	Select a consecutive soil number from drop-down list if more than one soil types were used.	List (picklist)
Duration	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Duration of test (contact time)		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Initial test substance concentration	Specify the initial test concentration applied. If different concentrations were used in different test runs, copy this block of fields accordingly. If a range of concentrations is reported, include the lower and upper values in the numeric range field. If appropriate copy this block of fields for indicating	Block of fields (repeatable) Start

	different parameters, the initial concentration is based on (e.g. COD and test substance).	
Soil No.	Select a consecutive soil number from drop-down list if more than one soil types were used.	List (picklist)
Initial conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Based on	From drop-down list, select the parameter on which the initial concentration is based.	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Initial test substance concentration		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
	In this field, you can enter any information on materials and methods, for which no distinct field is available, or transfer free text from other databases. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format. You can also upload any htm or html document. Note: One rich text editor field each is provided for the MATERIALS AND METHODS and RESULTS section. In addition, the fields 'Overall remarks' and 'Executive summary' allow rich text entry.	Text (rich-text area)
Results and discussion		Header 1
Detection of microorganism	For each soil/sediment type, indicate the microorganism detection levels for each time point.	Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose. Consult any programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) on how to use this field.	Check box
Test system no.	Select a consecutive soil/sediment number from drop-down list if more than one soil types were used.	List (picklist)
Sampling date		Date
Microorganism detected		List (picklist)

Quantification	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
St. dev.	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal)
Sampling time	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other:' 	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Detection of microorganism		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

7.1.4.2 Experimental exposure data water – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the experimental data on density of microorganisms in water.

If under consideration of the information provided under points 7.1.1, 7.1.2, 7.1.3 and 7.2 of Part B of the Annex to Reg 283/2013 a potential risk is identified for humans or non-target organism(s) or information is not sufficient to conclude about it, the population density of the microorganism shall be determined in relevant environmental compartment(s) (e.g. soil, water, plant surfaces).

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ExpressionInWater		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Use the Confidentiality flag and/or the Regulatory purpose flag to filter out data in subsequent operations such as exporting, printing or dossier creation. A justification is required when the confidentiality flag is set.	Header 1

	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality Display: Basic
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment. The study(ies) giving rise to the highest concern should be chosen. The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the study record is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score), type of study (e.g. duration, experimental design, observed effects), whether or not the study is GLP. Please provide your rationale for the selection of the relevant study record in the field "Additional information".	Link to endpoint (multiple) Display: Basic
Description of key information		Header 1
	If all key information is provided in the linked study records, this field can be left empty. In case there is no linked study record, or in case you want to point to specific information in the linked study record, provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here. The summary could include, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the test type - the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) - the test organism - the exposure duration - other contextual information on the origin of the key value 	Text (rich-text area) Display: Basic
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

7.1.4.2 Experimental exposure data water – Endpoint Study Record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report experimental data on density of microorganisms in water.

If under consideration of the information provided under points 7.1.1, 7.1.2, 7.1.3 and 7.2 of Part B of the Annex to Reg 283/2013 a potential risk is identified for humans or non-target organism(s) or information is not sufficient to conclude about it, the population density of the microorganism shall be determined in relevant environmental compartment(s) (e.g. soil, water, plant surfaces).

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ExpressionInAFreshwaterEnvironment

Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Study design		Header 2
Test system properties	Repeat this block of fields for each different water/sediment used as indicated by the water/sediment sample number. Enter water/sediment type as cited in the study report and the respective water/sediment properties.	Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Test system no.	Select a consecutive water/sediment sample number from drop-down list if more than one water/sediment types were used.	List (picklist)
Test system	Select from drop-down list.	List (picklist) Display: Basic
Temperature (°C)	Report the temperature in degrees Centigrade. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
Oxygen conditions	Indicate whether test was performed under aerobic or anaerobic conditions. Include any explanations in the supplementary remarks field as appropriate.	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
pH	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
Nutrients	Indicate any nutrients detected or added to the water / sediment.	Text (2,000 char.)
Sunlight	Indicate if the test system was exposed to sunlight.	List (picklist)
Hardness	Report the hardness to the water in the test system.	Numeric range (decimal)
Test system properties		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Duration of test (contact time)	Specify duration of test in terms of contact time. Repeat block for each water/sediment type. If different test runs have different durations, enter lower and upper value in respective subfields.	Block of fields (repeatable) Start

Test system no.	Select a consecutive water/sediment number from drop-down list if more than one soil types were used.	List (picklist)
Duration	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Duration of test (contact time)		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Initial test substance concentration	Specify the initial test concentration applied. If different concentrations were used in different test runs, copy this block of fields accordingly. If a range of concentrations is reported, include the lower and upper values in the numeric range field. If appropriate copy this block of fields for indicating different parameters the initial concentration is based on (e.g. COD and test substance).	Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Test system no.	Select a consecutive soil number from drop-down list if more than one soil types were used.	List (picklist)
Initial conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Based on	From drop-down list, select the parameter on which the initial concentration is based.	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Initial test substance concentration		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
	In this field, you can enter any information on materials and methods, for which no distinct field is available, or transfer free text from other databases. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format. You can also upload any htm or html document. Note: One rich text editor field each is provided for the MATERIALS AND METHODS and RESULTS section. In addition, the fields 'Overall remarks' and 'Executive summary' allow rich text entry.	Text (rich-text area)

Results and discussion		Header 1
Detection of microorganism	For each water/sediment type, indicate the microorganism detection levels for each time point.	Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose. Consult any programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme) on how to use this field.	Check box
Test system no.	Select a consecutive water/sediment number from drop-down list if more than one soil types were used.	List (picklist)
Sampling date		Date
Microorganism detected		List (picklist)
Quantification	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
St. dev.	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal)
Sampling time	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other' 	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Detection of microorganism		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1

Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1
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7.2 (Cf. metabolite dataset, 7) Fate and behaviour of metabolite(s) of concern

7.3 Additional information on environmental fate and behaviour – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information on higher tier and non-experimental studies which are not listed in the test guidelines of the other IUCLID documents in the Fate and Behavior section of a dataset.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.AdditionalInformationOnEnvironmentalFateAndBehaviour		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint
Description of key information		Header 1
	Indicate the pH value used to define DegT50 value indicated in the summary in case multiple endpoint summaries are created for different DegT50 values. If all key information is provided in the linked study records, this field can be left empty. In case there is no linked study record, or in case you want to point to specific information in the linked study record, provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here. The summary could include, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the test type - the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) - the test organism - the exposure duration - other contextual information on the origin of the key value 	Rich text area
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

7.3 Additional information on environmental fate and behaviour – Endpoint study record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report higher tier and non-experimental studies which are not listed in the test guidelines of the other IUCLID documents in the Fate and Behavior section of a dataset.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AdditionalInformationOnEnvironmentalFateAndBehaviour		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

8. Ecotoxicological studies

Note: Regulation (EU) No **283/2013** (data requirements) and the Document **PAFF-PPL-October 2023-Doc.A.07.01** (explanatory notes) should be consulted when compiling this section of the dossier and the specific subsections (e.g. for compilation of chronic and/or acute effects on aquatic organisms).

Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries

List of harmonised endpoint summaries in ecotox section:

Document name	Substance Section	Product Section
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ToxicityToBirds	8.1.1	10.1
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ToxicityToOtherAboveGroundOrganisms	8.1.2	10.2
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.LongTermToxicityToFish	8.2.1.1	10.2.1.1
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ShortTermToxicityToFish	8.2.1.2	10.2.1.2
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.LongTermToxicityToAquaticInvertebrates	8.2.2.1	10.2.2.1
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ShortTermToxicityToAquaticInvertebrates	8.2.2.2	10.2.2.2
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.SedimentToxicity	8.2.2.3	10.2.2.3
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ToxicityToAquaticAlgae	8.2.3	10.2.3
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ToxicityPlants	8.2.4	10.2.4
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ToxicityToBees	8.3	10.3
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ToxicityToTerrestrialArthropodsOtherThanBees	8.4	10.4
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ToxicityToSoilArthropods	8.5.1	10.5.1
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ToxicityToSoilMacroorganismsExceptArthropods	8.5.2	10.5.2
ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.ToxicityToTerrestrialPlants	8.6	10.6

The following instructions are applicable to **all harmonised endpoint summaries** of the IUCLID section on Ecotoxicological studies as listed above.

Harmonised Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1

	<p>Provide and assessment of the relevance and reliability of the studies provided. Report the rationale for selecting the studies linked to this document considering factors such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the test type - the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) - the test organism - the exposure duration - other contextual information on the origin of the key value <p>If the key value reported below has been corrected, indicate why and the nature of the correction.</p> <p>If reporting e.g. a geometric mean of L(E)Cx/NOEC values for this endpoint provide an explanation on the origin and context of the value.</p> <p>If effects have been observed at the lowest tested concentration and you are not able to extrapolate an adequate dose descriptor justify the extrapolation of the value to one of the proposed dose descriptors and detail the method applied.</p> <p>Describe any remaining uncertainties which should be considered in the risk assessment, potential data gaps and the quality of the whole database for this endpoint.</p>	
Key value for assessment		Header 1
Key Value	<p>The type of Key value is reported e.g. Freshwater fish, Toxicity to bees acute oral or BCF (aquatic species).</p> <p>Depending on the endpoint <u>one or more</u> Key Values will need to be reported.</p>	Header 2
Link to relevant study record(s)	<p>In this field there is the option to link to one or more Endpoint Study Records. Do not link to all the submitted studies but only the ones relevant for setting the key value. The study(ies) giving rise to the highest concern should be chosen.</p>	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Dose descriptor	<p>Select the relevant dose descriptor for reporting the key value of the endpoint assessed e.g. NOEC, LD50</p>	List (picklist)
Effect concentration	<p>Select the qualifier according to the key value:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - if none specifically apply, leave the field empty. - if the effect concentration is based on "no effect seen" at the highest tested concentration, the qualifier ">" should be used and the highest tested concentration should be reported. When there is no effect observed at the highest tested concentration, and when such concentration is above the test limit dose, then it can be assumed in the further assessment process that no hazard has been identified. <p>Make sure to select the units from the correct section of the picklist.</p>	Numeric range (half bounded)

	<p>The upper units are suitable for chemicals and the lower units for microorganisms</p> <p>ng/kg food µg/kg food mg/kg food g/kg food mg/kg bw mg/kg bw/day</p> <p>microbial active substances</p> <p>cells/kg bw/day CFU/kg bw/day ITU/kg bw/day IU/kg bw/day OB/kg bw/day spores/kg bw/day</p>	
Higher tier testing	Depending on the regulatory context, you would either be expected to provide the key values from the higher tier testing in the fields "Dose descriptor" and "Effect concentration" above, or to provide the key findings of higher tier studies in this section, to complement the values provided above.	Header 2
Link to relevant study record(s)	In this field there is the option to link to one or more Endpoint Study Records. Do not link to all the submitted studies but only the ones describing higher tier studies. The study(ies) giving rise to the highest concern should be chosen.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Key information from higher tier testing	Provide information about higher tier testing (e.g. mesocosm, modelling or field studies for the different taxa). Information concerning the residue decline in potential food items can be described here.	Text (rich-text area)
Additional information		Header 1
	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Additional information – common block" Provide information related to the assessment of the endpoint, for example any endpoint specific information relevant for the interpretation of the results.</p> <p>This field can be used in cases where information in a tabular format is requested risk assessment guidance document. However, all IUCLID fields must be completed in the Endpoint Study Record and this field should not be used to save time by copying pasting from older documentation.</p> <p>If there is no additional information to be reported, this field may be left empty.</p>	Text (rich-text area)

Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Material and methods – common block"</p> <p>Applicable test guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ OECD Test Guideline 205: Avian Dietary Toxicity Test ▪ OECD Test Guideline 206: Avian Reproduction Test ▪ OECD Test Guideline No 223: Avian acute oral toxicity study ▪ OECD Test Guideline No 223: Avian acute oral toxicity study (updated version of July 2016) ▪ US EPA OCSPP 850.2100: Avian oral toxicity test ▪ US EPA OPPTS 885.4050 Avian Oral, Tier I ▪ US EPA OPPTS 885.4600 Avian Chronic Pathogenicity and Reproduction Test, Tier III ▪ US EPA OCSPP 850.2200: Avian dietary toxicity test. ▪ US EPA OCSPP 850.2300: Avian Reproduction Test 	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Dose method	Select as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.	Open list with remarks
Analytical monitoring	Indicate whether test substance was monitored in the test medium. If yes, specify in field 'Details on preparation and monitoring of diet'.	Closed list with remarks
Vehicle	Indicate whether a vehicle was used, e.g. to disperse/solubilise or facilitate mixing of test substance with feed.	Closed list with remarks
Details on preparation and analysis of diet	Indicate whether a vehicle was used, e.g. to disperse/solubilise or facilitate mixing of test substance with feed. Indicate details about diet preparation and homogeneity analysis of test material. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. In the case of OECD or similarly acknowledged guideline only items may be covered where deviations apply or where parameters are left open in the guideline, provided the respective regulatory programme allows so.	Text template
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	Open list
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design		Header 2
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	Closed list
Total exposure duration (if not single dose)	Select from drop-down list.	Unit measure with Closed

		List (Decimal)
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to the total exposure duration.	Text
Post exposure observation period	Indicate the post-observation period (with unit) during which 'clean' feed was administered.	Multi-line text
No. of animals per sex per dose and/or stage	Indicate the post-observation period (with unit) during which 'clean' feed was administered. Indicate number of animals used per dose group and/or stage. State if different numbers were used and reason why.	Multi-line text
Control animals	Indicate whether and what type of concurrent control groups were used. Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify.	Multi select open list with remarks
Nominal and measured doses / concentrations	List nominal and, if available, measured dose levels or test concentrations (with unit). Indicate if nominal or measured for bolus dose, etc. Provide range, median, mean, SD as applicable. As appropriate tabulate nominal vs. measured concentrations and refer to Table no. For micro-organisms, average achieved dose in colony forming units (cfu) also must be reported.	Multi-line text
Details on test conditions	Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
High Dose Level Used	Where a test method offers flexibility in the study design, for example in relation to the choice of dose levels, the chosen study design shall ensure that the data generated are adequate for hazard identification and risk assessment. To this end, testing shall be performed at appropriately high dose levels. If dose (concentration) selection is limited by the physicochemical properties or biological effects of the test substance, justification shall be provided.	Picklist
Examinations		Header 2
Details on examinations and observations	Indicate the time schedule and further details for all examinations and observations performed (use separate free-text field for reproductive parameters, if applicable). Also indicate the dose groups that were examined if not all. When tabulating parameters examined, refer to respective table no. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Details on reproductive parameters	For avian reproduction toxicity test, indicate the reproductive parameters examined. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template

Reference substance (positive control)	Indicate if a positive control was tested, i.e. a reference substance with known toxicity. If yes, include the identity of the substance(s) and the concentrations in the supplementary remarks field.	Closed list with remarks
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect levels	Report the LC ₅₀ , LD ₅₀ , NOEC or LOEC for appropriate parental and reproductive parameters depending on the study type. Copy this field block for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration (if not single dose)	Enter numeric value (not relevant for bolus dose) and unit.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect level	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Conc. / dose based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Basis for effect	Select effect parameter such as mortality, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. 'related to number of eggs or young surviving'.	Open list with remarks
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='.	Range (Decimal)

	both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other:'	Open list with remarks (2000)
Effect levels		
Repellency factors (if applicable)	If repellency was investigated, describe the repellency results including all repellency factors (RF) given in the study report, i.e. either for each bird (choice test) or for per test group (no-choice test). As appropriate include or attach a table.	Multi-line text
Mortality and sub-lethal effects	Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). Note: Specific tables may be required.	Text template
Effects on reproduction	For avian reproduction toxicity test, include data on reproduction during pre-treatment and treatment periods depending on the requirements of the test guideline used. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). Note: Specific tables may be required.	Text template
Results with reference substance (positive control)	If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Further details on results	For microorganisms, information on infectiveness and pathogenicity to birds must be reported.	Text area
Reported statistics and error estimates	Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed.	Multi-line text

Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS1/RM/44), 14.1 Birds

EFSA (2009) Guidance of EFSA - Risk assessment for birds and mammals. EFSA Journal 2009; 7(12):1438.

OECD series of testing and assessment Number 54. "Current approaches in the statistical analysis of ecotoxicity data: a guidance to application" [http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono\(2006\)18&doclanguage=en](http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono(2006)18&doclanguage=en)

EU Guidance Document on Terrestrial Ecotoxicology (SANCO/10329/2002 rev 2)

8.1.2 EFFECTS ON TERRESTRIAL VERTEBRATES - OTHER VERTEBRATES – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

A summary on potential infectivity and pathogenicity of the micro-organism to terrestrial vertebrates other than birds (e.g. mammals, reptiles, and amphibians) must be provided, based on the information already provided under Sections 1, 2, 3, 5 and 7 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439 and that information which may be retrieved from any other reliable source.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

8.1.2 EFFECTS ON TERRESTRIAL VERTEBRATE - OTHER VERTEBRATES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

Relevant pathogenicity/infectivity studies must be performed unless the applicant demonstrates, by following a weight of evidence approach, that pathogenicity/infectivity of the microorganism to non-target terrestrial vertebrates other than birds can be assessed based on the summary provided.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToOtherAboveGroundOrganisms		
Name	Instructions	Data type

Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis		Header 2
Analytical monitoring	Indicate whether test substance was monitored in the test solutions. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details on sampling and analytical methods in the corresponding free text fields.	Closed list with remarks
Details on sampling	Enter details on sampling regime and method. Use free text template as appropriate.	Text template
Details on analytical methods	If the amount of test material in the test solutions was monitored, enter any details on the analytical methods used. Use free text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Copy any subheading(s) under IDENTIFICATION AND QUANTIFICATION OF PARENT COMPOUND to include the respective information for transformation products.	Text template
Test substrate		Header 2
Vehicle	Indicate whether a vehicle was used, e.g. to disperse/solubilise or facilitate mixing of test substance with feed.	Closed list with remarks
Details on preparation and application of test substrate	PREPARATION AND APPLICATION OF TEST MATERIAL <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Method: ▪ Spray deposition (if applicable): ▪ Chemical name of vehicle (organic solvent, emulsifier or dispersant): ▪ Concentration of vehicle in test medium (stock solution and final test solution): ▪ Volume of test solution applied: 	Text template
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	Open list
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design		Header 2
Study type	Indicate the study type, i.e. laboratory study, extended laboratory study (e.g. with a more natural substrate), semi-field study (mimicking a near-natural environment with ambient climatic conditions) or field study (using natural populations).	Closed list

Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	Closed list
Total exposure duration	Select from drop-down list.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to the total exposure duration.	Text
Post exposure observation period	Indicate the post-observation period (with unit) during which 'clean' feed was administered.	Multi-line text
Study design		
Test conditions		Header 2
Test temperature	<p>Indicate test temperature values measured in the treatment and control vessels during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As applicable indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different temperatures were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies. Example: 20+/-1°C (adults), 25+/-1.5°C (larval exposure), 18+/-1°C (pupal development), 25+/-1°C (fecundity).</p> <p>Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.</p>	Text area
Humidity	<p>Indicate the relative humidity of the experimental room during the test measured in the treatment and control vessels. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As applicable indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different humidities were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies.</p> <p>Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.</p>	Text area
Photoperiod and lighting	<p>Indicate the photoperiod and lighting intensity in the experimental room during the test measured in the treatment and control vessels. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As applicable indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different lighting conditions were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies.</p> <p>Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.</p>	Text area
Details on test conditions	<p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.</p> <p>Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined table(s) if any or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>TEST SYSTEM</p>	Text area

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test container (material, size): - No. of organisms per container (treatment): - No. of replicates per treatment group: - No. of replicates per control: - No. of replicates per vehicle control: <p>OTHER TEST CONDITIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Photoperiod: - Light intensity: <p>EFFECT PARAMETERS MEASURED (with observation intervals if applicable):</p> <p>VEHICLE CONTROL PERFORMED: [yes/no]</p> <p>TEST CONCENTRATIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spacing factor for test concentrations: - Justification for using less concentrations than requested by guideline: - Range finding study - Test concentrations: - Results used to determine the conditions for the definitive study 	
Nominal and measured concentrations	List nominal and, if available, measured test concentrations (with unit). As appropriate tabulate nominal vs. measured concentrations and refer to Table No. (use predefined table if any).	Text area
Reference substance (positive control)	Indicate if a positive control was tested, i.e. a reference substance with known toxicity. If yes, include the identity of the substance(s) and the concentrations in the supplementary remarks field.	Closed list with remarks
Test conditions		
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1

Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal measured /	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	Closed list
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Basis for effect	Select effect parameter such as mortality, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:'	Open list with remarks (2000)

	Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.	
Effect concentrations		
Details on results	For microbial organisms, information on infectiveness and pathogenicity to terrestrial vertebrates other than birds must be reported.	Text template
Results with reference substance (positive control)	If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept and probit slope. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship.	Multi-line text
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

Effects on terrestrial vertebrates Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS 1/RM/44), 14.2 Small Mammals

OECD Guidance to the environmental safety evaluation of microbial biocontrol agents, Series on Pesticides No. 67 (ENV/JM/MONO(2012)1)

EFSA, 2009. Guidance of EFSA - Risk assessment for birds and mammals. EFSA Journal 2009; 7(12):1438.

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

EFSA, 2023. Guidance on the risk assessment for Birds and Mammals. *EFSA Journal* 2023; 21(2):7790, 300 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7790>. **Note:** This document has been issued by EFSA following the mandate by European Commission but its implementation is still pending on the agreement in the SCoPAFF.

EC (European Commission – DG Health and Consumer Protection), 2002. Guidance Document on Risk Assessment for Birds and Mammals under Council Directive 91/414/EEC. SANCO/4145/2000 – final 25 September 2002, pp 74. (https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-10/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_ecotox_ra_birds-mammals.pdf)

OECD series of testing and assessment Number 54. "Current approaches in the statistical analysis of ecotoxicity data: a guidance to application"

EU Guidance Document on Terrestrial Ecotoxicology (SANCO/10329/2002 rev 2)

8.2 Effects on aquatic organisms – Endpoint summary

Purpose

A summary on potential infectivity and pathogenicity of the microorganism to aquatic organisms must be provided, based on the information already provided under Sections 1, 2, 3, 5 and 7 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439 and that information which may be retrieved from any other reliable source.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.AquaticToxicity		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	If all key information is provided in the linked study records, this field can be left empty. In case there is no linked study record, or in case you want to point to specific information in the linked study record, provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here. The summary could include, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ the test type ▪ the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) ▪ the test organism ▪ the exposure duration ▪ other contextual information on the origin of the key value 	Text (rich-text area)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

	Provide additional information derivation that was not possible to capture in previous fields.	
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8.2.1 EFFECTS ON FISH

8.2.1.1 Chronic effects on fish – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details:

- Group: Specify fish species
- Time scale
- Toxicity, infectivity, and pathogenicity (endpoint, value or other description of effects)

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

8.2.1.1 Chronic effects on fish – Endpoint study record

Purpose

Relevant pathogenicity/infectivity studies must be performed unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

Where adverse effects are observed in such studies, further relevant studies (e.g. under representative conditions in accordance with the proposed conditions of use) shall be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.LongTermToxToFish		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: OPPTS 885.4700 Fish Life Cycle Studies, Tier III OECD Test Guideline 210: Fish, Early-Life Stage Toxicity Test US EPA protocol OCSPP 850.1500 Fish life cycle toxicity	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis	Follow instructions reported in " Sampling and analysis / Test solutions – common block (OHT: Aquatic Toxicity) "	Header 2
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	Open list

Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design	Follow instructions reported in " Study design – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) "	Header 2
Test conditions	Follow instructions reported in " Test conditions – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) " For microorganisms : In the “nominal and measured concentrations” field, the average achieved dose in cfu or relevant microbial unit must be reported.	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when “Type of information” is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion	For microorganisms: Details on results: Information on toxicity, infectiveness and pathogenicity to fish must be reported. Isolation, identification, and enumeration of microorganisms responsible for any observed pathogenic effects.	Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal measured /	Actual achieved dose in relevant units must be reported.	Closed list

	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Basis for effect	Select effect parameters such as inhibition of respiratory rate or growth inhibition, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Multi select open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Detailed results	See instructions reported in the " Dose response – common block ".	Header 2
Details on results	Any abnormal adverse or beneficial effects in treatment and/or control groups, including dates and times the effects were observed, should be reported. Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available, and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').	Text template
Results with reference substance	If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information.	Text template

(positive control)	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	
Reported statistics and error estimates	Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept and probit slope. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship.	Multi-line text
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS 1/RM/44), 11.1 Freshwater Fish

8.2.1.2 Acute effects on fish – Endpoint summary

Purpose

Summarise the information from the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details, including:

- The species tested;
- Time scale (exposure duration);
- The derived endpoint and the concentration.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

8.2.1.2 Acute effects on fish – Endpoint study record

Purpose

If needed, short-term pathogenicity/infectivity/toxicity studies should be performed unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ShortTermToxicityToFish		
Name	Instructions	Data type

Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: OECD Test Guideline 203: Fish, Acute Toxicity Test EPA OPPTS 885.4200 - Freshwater Fish Testing, Tier I (February 1996)	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis	Follow instructions reported in " Sampling and analysis / Test solutions – common block (OHT: Aquatic Toxicity) "	Header 2
Test organisms / cell line		Header 2
Test organisms (species)/ cell line	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	Open list
Details on test organisms / cell line	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design	Follow instructions reported in " Study design – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) "	Header 2
Test conditions	Follow instructions reported in " Test conditions – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) " For microorganisms : In the "nominal and measured concentrations" field, the average achieved dose in cfu or relevant unit must be reported.	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)

Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal measured /	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	Closed list
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Basis for effect	For acute fish test, select effect parameter such as mortality or visible abnormalities related to appearance and behaviour. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field. For fish embryo test, select indicators of mortality (or lethality): (i) coagulation of fertilised eggs, (ii) lack of somite formation, (iii) lack of detachment of the tail-bud from the yolk sac, and (iv) lack of heartbeat. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; ▪ giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or ▪ entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' 	Open list with remarks (2000)

	Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.	
Detailed results	See instructions reported in the " Dose response – common block ".	Header 2
Details on results	Information on toxicity, infectiveness and pathogenicity to fish must be reported.	Text template
Results with reference substance (positive control)	If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept and probit slope. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship.	Multi-line text
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting materials

OECD. Series on testing and assessment No 126. Short guidance on the threshold approach for acute fish toxicity. ENV/JM/MONO(2010)17

<https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/iccvam/suppdocs/feddocs/oecd/oecd-gd126.pdf>

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS 1/RM/44), 11.1 Freshwater Fish

EFSA PPR Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues), 2013. Guidance on tiered risk assessment for plant protection products for aquatic organisms in edge-of-field surface waters. EFSA Journal 2013;11(7):3290, 268 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2013.3290.

8.2.2 EFFECTS ON AQUATIC INVERTEBRATES

8.2.2.1 Chronic effects on aquatic invertebrates – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the information from the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details, including:

- The species tested;
- Time scale (exposure duration);
- The derived endpoint and the concentration.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

Links to supporting material

Guidance Document on Tiered Risk Assessment for Plant Protection products for Aquatic Organisms in Edge-of-field Surface Waters in the Context of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 (SANTE-2015-00080, 15 January 2015) <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/3290/10.2903/j.efsa.2013.3290>

8.2.2.1 Chronic effects on aquatic invertebrates – Endpoint study record

Purpose

Relevant pathogenicity/infectivity studies shall be performed unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

Where adverse effects are observed in such studies, further relevant studies (e.g. under representative conditions in accordance with the proposed conditions of use) must be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.LongTermToxicityToAquaInv		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: OECD Test Guideline 211: <i>Daphnia magna</i> Reproduction Test US EPA OCSPP 850.1350 Mysid Chronic Toxicity Test OECD Test Guideline 242: <i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i> Reproduction Test OECD Test Guideline 243: <i>Lymnaea stagnalis</i> Reproduction Test OECD Test Guideline 218: Sediment-Water Chironomid Toxicity Using Spiked Sediment	Header 1

	<p>OECD Test Guideline 219: Sediment-Water Chironomid Toxicity Using Spiked Water</p> <p>OECD Test Guideline 233: Sediment-Water Chironomid Life-Cycle Toxicity Test Using Spiked Water or Spiked Sediment</p> <p>OECD Test Guideline 225: Sediment-Water Lumbriculus Toxicity Test Using Spiked Sediment</p> <p>OPPTS 885.4650 Aquatic Invertebrate Range Testing, Tier III</p>	
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis	Follow instructions reported in " Sampling and analysis / Test solutions – common block (OHT: Aquatic Toxicity) "	Header 2
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	Open list
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design	Follow instructions reported in " Study design – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) "	Header 2
Test conditions	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Test conditions – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity)"</p> <p>For <u>microorganisms</u>: In the "nominal and measured concentrations" field, the average achieved dose in cfu or the relevant unit must be reported.</p>	Header 2
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)

Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal measured /	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	Closed list
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Basis for effect	Select effect parameter such as inhibition of respiratory rate or growth inhibition, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; ▪ giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or ▪ entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' <p>Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.</p>	Open list with remarks (2000)

Detailed results	See instructions reported in the " Dose response – common block ".	Header 2
Details on results	For micro-organisms : Information on toxicity, infectiveness and pathogenicity to freshwater invertebrates must be reported. Briefly summarize relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined table(s) if any or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').	Text template
Results with reference substance (positive control)	If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept and probit slope. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship.	Multi-line text
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material

Guidance Document on Tiered Risk Assessment for Plant Protection products for Aquatic Organisms in Edge-of-field Surface Waters in the Context of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 (SANTE-2015-00080, 15 January 2015) <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/329010.2903/j.efsa.2013.3290>

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS 1/RM/44), 10.1 Freshwater Invertebrates

8.2.2.2 Acute effects on aquatic invertebrates – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the information from the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details, including:

- The species tested;
- Time scale (exposure duration);
- The derived endpoint and the concentration.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

8.2.2.2 Acute effects on aquatic invertebrates – Endpoint study record

Purpose

If needed, short-term pathogenicity/infectivity/toxicity studies should be performed unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ShortTermToxicityToAquaInv		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: OECD Test Guideline 202: <i>Daphnia sp.</i> Acute Immobilisation Test US EPA OCSPP 850.1035 Mysid Acute Toxicity Test OECD Test Guideline 235: <i>Chironomus sp.</i> , Acute Immobilisation Test OPPTS 885.4240 Freshwater Aquatic Invertebrate Testing, Tier I	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis	Follow instructions reported in " Sampling and analysis / Test solutions – common block (OHT: Aquatic Toxicity) "	Header 2
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	Open list
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design	Follow instructions reported in " Study design – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) "	Header 2

Test conditions	Follow instructions reported in " Test conditions – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) " For microorganisms: Nominal and measured concentrations: Actual achieved dose in cfu or the relevant unit must be reported.	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block " A detailed description of the steps taken to determine micro-organism dissemination, replication, or survival in the test animal tissues, organs, or fluids.	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal / measured	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	Closed list
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further	Open list with remarks

		information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	
Basis for effect		Select effect parameter such as inhibition of respiratory rate or growth inhibition, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result		<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' <p>Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.</p>	Open list with remarks (2000)
Detailed results		See instructions reported in the " Dose response – common block ".	Header 2
Details on results		<p>For micro-organisms, information on toxicity, infectiveness and pathogenicity to freshwater invertebrates must be reported.</p> <p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available, and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>As appropriate also attach a figure with growth curves in field 'Attached background material'. Note: Specific tables may be required.</p>	Text template
Results with reference substance (positive control)		If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates		Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept and probit slope. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated	Multi-line text

	with the determination of concentration-response relationship.	
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

Guidance Document on Tiered Risk Assessment for Plant Protection products for Aquatic Organisms in Edge-of-field Surface Waters in the Context of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 (SANTE-2015-00080, 15 January 2015) <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/3290/10.2903/j.efsa.2013.3290>

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS 1/RM/44), 10.1 Freshwater Invertebrates

8.2.2.3 Aquatic sediment toxicity – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the information from the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details, including:

- The species tested;
- Time scale (exposure duration);
- The derived endpoint and the concentration.

Toxic effects expressed as LCx and ECx and/or NOEC/LOEC.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

8.2.2.3 Aquatic sediment toxicity – Endpoint study record

Purpose

In case there are indications of an accumulation of the purified active substance in aquatic sediment as a result of environmental fate studies or predictions, the impact on a sediment-dwelling organism shall be assessed by the determination of the chronic toxicity to *Chironomus riparius* or *Lumbriculus* spp. of the purified active substance. An appropriate alternative test species may be used where a recognised guideline is available.

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

The active substance shall be applied to either the water or the sediment phase of a water/sediment system and the test shall take account of the major route of exposure.

The EC10, EC20 and a NOEC of active substance in the overlying water and the sediment shall be reported in terms of mg substance/kg dry sediment and mg substance/L water.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SedimentToxicity		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis		Header 2
Analytical monitoring	Indicate whether test substance was monitored in the test solutions or suspensions. Include in the remarks which concentrations were monitored and how often or when during the testing period (frequency of monitoring). For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details on sampling and analytical methods in the corresponding freetext fields	Closed list with remarks
Details on sampling	If the concentration of test material was monitored, enter details on sampling. Use freetext template as appropriate and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Details on analytical methods	If the concentration of test material was monitored, enter any details on the analytical methods used. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Copy any subheading(s) for the different matrices as appropriate.	Text template
Test substrate		Header 2
Vehicle	Indicate whether vehicle was used to emulsify or mix the experimental test material to enhance its solubility. If yes, specify in field 'Details on sediment and application'.	Closed list with remarks
Details on sediment and application	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	Open list
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template

Study design		Header 2
Study type	Indicate the study type, i.e. laboratory study, extended laboratory study (e.g. with a more natural substrate), semi-field study (mimicking a near-natural environment with ambient climatic conditions) or field study (using natural populations).	Open list with remarks
Test type	Select the appropriate test type.	Open list
Water media type	Indicate whether organisms were tested in fresh-/salt- or brackish/estuarine water.	Open list with remarks
Type of sediment	Indicate whether natural or formulated sediment was used as substrate.	Closed list with remarks
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	Closed list
Exposure duration	Indicate the exposure duration and, if applicable, the related exposure phase. Copy this block of fields for different phases as appropriate.	
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Exposure phase	Select the related exposure phase, i.e. total exposure duration, larvae from first generation (P), reproduction phase, larvae from second generation (F1) or other: (specify). As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to the total exposure duration.	Text
Exposure duration		
Post exposure observation period	Indicate the post-observation period (with unit) if appropriate, e.g. in the case of a reproduction test.	Multi-line text
Test conditions	Follow instructions reported in " Test conditions – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2

Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal measured /	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	Closed list
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Basis for effect	Select effect parameter such as development, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. 'mean development rate, male and female midges pooled'.	Open list with remarks

<p>Remarks on result</p>	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; ▪ giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or ▪ entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' <p>Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.</p>	<p>Open list with remarks (2000)</p>
<p>Detailed results</p>	<p>See instructions reported in the "Dose response - common block".</p>	<p>Header 2</p>
<p>Details on results</p>	<p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Select freetext template for the respective type of study and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.</p> <p>Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). As appropriate also attach a figure with growth curves in field 'Attached background material'.</p> <p>Note: Specific tables may be required. Consult the programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD HPVC, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) thereof.</p>	<p>Text template</p>
<p>Results with reference substance (positive control)</p>	<p>If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p>	<p>Text template</p>
<p>Reported statistics and error estimates</p>	<p>Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept and probit slope. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship.</p>	<p>Multi-line text</p>
<p>Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of</p>	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions - common block"</p>	<p>Header 2</p>

(Q)SAR predictions		
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

OECD Guidelines for the testing of chemicals, Section 2 (Effects on biotic systems) https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/environment/oecd-guidelines-for-the-testing-of-chemicals-section-2-effects-on-biotic-systems_20745761

8.2.3 EFFECTS ON ALGAE – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated.

Provide only the most relevant details e.g:

Effects on algal growth, growth rate and capacity to recover.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

Links to supporting material:

Guidance Document on Tiered Risk Assessment for Plant Protection products for Aquatic Organisms in Edge-of-field Surface Waters in the Context of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 (SANTE-2015-00080, 15 January 2015) <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/329010.2903/j.efsa.2013.3290>

8.2.3 EFFECTS ON ALGAE – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

Relevant studies on pathogenic/infective effects on algae growth and growth rate must be performed if the microorganism is known to have an herbicidal mode of action or to be closely related to a plant pathogen, unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

Where adverse effects are observed in such studies, further relevant studies (e.g. under representative conditions in accordance with the proposed conditions of use) must be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToAquaticAlgae		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1

Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guideline: OECD Test Guideline 201: Algae growth inhibition test are relevant for this endpoint US EPA OCSPP 885.4300 Non target plant studies Tier I	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis	Follow instructions reported in "Sampling and analysis / Test solutions – common block (OHT: Aquatic Toxicity)"	Header 2
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	Open list
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design	Follow instructions reported in " Study design – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) "	Header 2
Test conditions	Follow instructions reported in " Test conditions – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) " For microorganisms : Nominal and measured concentrations: the average achieved dose and relevant units in cfu must be reported.	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)

95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal measured /	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	Closed list
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Basis for effect	Select effect parameter such as inhibition of respiratory rate or growth inhibition, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' <p>Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.</p>	Open list with remarks (2000)
Detailed results	See instructions reported in the " Dose response – common block ".	Header 2
Details on results	Information on effects on algal growth, growth rate and capacity to recover must be reported. Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any	Text template

	<p>other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available, and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>As appropriate also attach a figure with growth curves in field 'Attached background material'. Note: Specific tables may be required.</p>	
Results with reference substance (positive control)	Results with reference substance (positive control) - If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide EC50 data and other relevant information. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept and probit slope. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship. In addition, report the growth curves and the graphical presentation of the concentration-effect relationship.	Multi-line text
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS 1/RM/44), 9.1 Freshwater plants

8.2.4 EFFECTS ON AQUATIC MACROPHYTES – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the information from the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details, including:

- The species tested;
- The test guideline used;
- Time scale (exposure duration);

- The derived endpoint and the concentration.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

8.2.4 EFFECTS ON AQUATIC MACROPHYTES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

Relevant studies on pathogenic/infective effects on aquatic macrophytes shall be performed if the micro-organism is known to have an herbicidal mode of action, or to be closely related to a plant pathogen, unless the applicant demonstrates, no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

Where adverse effects are observed in such studies, further relevant studies (e.g. under representative conditions in accordance with the proposed conditions of use) must be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToAquaticPlant		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guideline: OECD Test Guideline 221 (2006): <i>Lemna sp.</i> Growth Inhibition Test ASTM E1913-04: Standard Guide for Conducting Static, Axenic, 14-Day Phytotoxicity Tests in Test Tubes with the Submersed Aquatic Macrophyte, <i>Myriophyllum sibiricum Komarov</i> OECD Test Guideline 238 (2014): Sediment-Free <i>Myriophyllum Spicatum</i> Toxicity Test OECD Test Guideline 239 (2014): Water-Sediment <i>Myriophyllum Spicatum</i> Toxicity Test OPPTS 885.4300 Nontarget Plant Studies, Tier I	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis	Follow instructions reported in " Sampling and analysis / Test solutions – common block (OHT: Aquatic Toxicity) "	Header 2
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	Open list
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design	Follow instructions reported in " Study design – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) "	Header 2

Test conditions	Follow instructions reported in " Test conditions – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity) " For micro-organisms: In the “nominal and measured concentrations” field, the average achieved dose in cfu must be reported.	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when “Type of information” is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal measured /	Actual achieved dose in relevant units must be reported. Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	Closed list
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further	Open list with remarks

	information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	
Basis for effect	Select effect parameters such as inhibition of respiratory rate or growth inhibition, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Multi select open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Detailed results	See instructions reported in the "Dose response – common block".	Header 2
Details on results	Any abnormal adverse or beneficial effects in treatment and/or control groups, including dates and times the effects were observed, should be reported. Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available, and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').	Text template
Results with reference substance (positive control)	If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept and probit slope. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship.	Multi-line text

Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

EU Guidance Document on Terrestrial Ecotoxicology (SANCO/10329/2002 rev 2) https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-10/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_ecotox_terrestrial.pdf

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS 1/RM/44), 9.1 Freshwater plants

EFSA PPR Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues), 2013. Guidance on tiered risk assessment for plant protection products for aquatic organisms in edge-of-field surface waters. EFSA Journal 2013;11(7):3290, 268 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2013.3290.

8.3 Effects on bees – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details, e.g.:

- Group: Specify species tested;
- Test type (laboratory/others);
- Dose;
- Exposure route/time-scale (hours, days, weeks);
- Toxicity (endpoint or other description of effects).

A summary on potential infectivity and pathogenicity of the microorganism to bees must be provided, based on the information already provided under Sections 1, 2, 3 and 7 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439 and on other information which may be retrieved from any other reliable source.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

Links to supporting material:

EU Guidance Document on Terrestrial Ecotoxicology (SANCO/10329/2002 rev 2) https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-10/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_ecotox_terrestrial.pdf

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

EFSA, 2013. Guidance on the risk assessment of plant protection products on bees (*Apis mellifera*, *Bombus* spp. and solitary bees) <http://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2013.3295>

EFSA, 2023. Revised guidance on the risk assessment of plant protection products on bees (*Apis mellifera*, *Bombus* spp. and solitary bees). *EFSA Journal* 2023; 21(5):7989, 133 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7989>. **Note:** This document has been issued by EFSA following the mandate by European Commission but its implementation is still pending on the agreement in the SCoPAFF.

Candolfi et al (2001). Guidance Document on Regulatory Testing and Risk Assessment Procedures for Plant Protection Products With Non-Target Arthropods: From the Escort 2 Workshop (European Standard Characteristics of Non-Target Arthropod Regulatory Testing). SETAC press, pp 46. ISBN 1-880611-52-x.

Candolfi et al, 2001. Guidance document on regulatory testing and risk assessment procedures for plant protection products with non-target arthropods. Report of the SETAC/ESCORT 2 Workshop, Wageningen, the Netherlands, and SETAC-Europe, Brussels, Belgium.

8.3 Effects on bees – Endpoint study record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report effects on bees.

Relevant pathogenicity/infectivity studies, including adult and larval stages, must be performed, unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

Where adverse effects are observed in such studies, further relevant studies (e.g. extended laboratory tests or field studies under representative conditions in accordance with the proposed conditions of use) must be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToBees		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ OECD Guideline 213 (Honeybees, Acute Oral Toxicity Test) ▪ OECD Guideline 214 (Honeybees, Acute Contact Toxicity Test) ▪ OECD Guideline 237 (Honey bee (<i>Apis mellifera</i>) Larval Toxicity Test, Single Exposure) ▪ OECD Guideline 245 (Honey Bee (<i>Apis mellifera</i> L.), Chronic Oral Toxicity Test (10-Day Feeding)) ▪ OECD Guideline 246 (Bumblebee, Acute Contact Toxicity Test) ▪ OECD Guideline 247 (Bumblebee, Acute Oral Toxicity Test) ▪ OECD Guidance Document No 75 (Guidance Document on the Honey Bee (<i>Apis mellifera</i> L.) Brood test Under Semi-field Conditions) 	Header 1

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ OECD Guidance Document No 239 (Guidance Document on Honey Bee Larval Toxicity Test following Repeated Exposure) ▪ OECD Guidance Document No 332 (Guidance document on honey bee (<i>Apis mellifera</i> L.) Homing flight test, using single oral exposure to sublethal doses of test chemical) ▪ EPA OPP 141-1 (Honey Bee Acute Contact Toxicity) ▪ EPA OPP 141-2 (Honey Bee Toxicity of Residues on Foliage) ▪ EPA OPP 141-5 (Field Testing for Pollinators) ▪ EPA OPPTS 850.3020 (Honey Bee Acute Contact Toxicity) ▪ EPA OPPTS 850.3030 (Honey Bee Toxicity of Residues on Foliage) ▪ EPA OPPTS 850.3040 (Field Testing for Pollinators) ▪ EPA OPPTS 885.4380 (Microbial Pesticide, Honey Bee Testing, Tier I) ▪ EPPO PP 1/170 (4) (Side-effects on honeybees) ▪ EU Method C.16 (Honeybees - Acute Oral Toxicity Test) ▪ EU Method C.17 (Honeybees - Acute Contact Toxicity Test) ▪ Method for honeybee brood feeding tests with insect growth-regulating insecticides by Oomen et al. (1992); The Oomen bee brood feeding test – revision of the method to current needs and developments by Luckmann J, Schmitzer S (2019). ▪ A method for a solitary bee (<i>Osmia</i> sp.) first tier acute contact and oral laboratory test: an update by Roessink et al. (2017); Progress on the <i>Osmia</i> acute oral test: findings of the ICCPR non-<i>Apis</i> subgroup solitary bee laboratory testing by Roessink et al. (2019). ▪ Summary of an ICPPR Non-<i>Apis</i> workshop – Subgroup higher tier (bumble bees and solitary bees) with recommendations for a semi-field experimental design by Knäbe et al. (2017); Higher tier bumble bees and solitary bees recommendations for a semi-field experimental design by Knäbe et al. (2019) ▪ Results of 2-Year Ring Testing of a Semifield Study Design to Investigate Potential Impacts of Plant Protection Products on the Solitary Bees <i>Osmia Bicornis</i> and <i>Osmia Cornuta</i> and a Proposal for a Suitable Test Design by Franke et al. (2021) 	
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Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis		Header 2
Analytical monitoring	Indicate whether test substance was monitored in the test solutions or suspensions. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details on sampling and analytical methods in the corresponding freetext fields.	List (picklist with remarks) sup.
Details on sampling	If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter details on sampling. Use freetext template as appropriate and delete/add elements as appropriate. Note: Indicate which concentrations were measured if not all. As applicable, provide information for soil, stock and/or spray solution.	Text template
Details on analytical methods	If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter any details on the analytical methods used. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Test substrate		Header 2
Application method	Select the method of application as appropriate. If not available from the picklist, select 'other:' and specify.	List (picklist)
Application rate	In case the application is done under field/semi-field conditions, indicate the application rate.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Vehicle	Indicate whether vehicle was used to emulsify or mix the experimental test material to enhance its solubility. If yes, specify in field 'Details on preparation and application of test substrate'.	List (picklist with remarks) sup.
Details on preparation and application of test substrate	Depending on the type of study, select appropriate freetext template (e.g. Honeybees: contact study) and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. Consult the programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD HPVC, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) thereof.	Text template
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	List (picklist)
Animal group	Indicate the animal group.	List (picklist)
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template

Study design		Header 2
Study type	Indicate the study type, i.e. laboratory study, semi-field study (mimicking a near-natural environment with ambient climatic conditions) or field study (using natural populations).	List (picklist) sup. with remarks
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	List (picklist)
Total exposure duration	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal)
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to the total exposure duration.	Text (255 char.)
Post exposure observation period	Indicate the post-observation period (with unit) if appropriate.	Text (2,000 char.)
Test conditions		Header 2
Test temperature	Indicate test temperature values measured in the treatment and control vessels during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As appropriate state the location and type of measurement (e.g. continuous monitoring). As applicable indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different temperatures were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies. Example: 20+/-1°C (adults), 25+/-1.5°C (larval exposure), 18+/-1°C (pupal development), 25+/-1°C (fecundity). Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text (2,000 char.)
Humidity	Indicate the relative humidity of the experimental room during the test measured in the treatment and control vessels. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As applicable indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different humidities were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text (2,000 char.)
Photoperiod and lighting	Indicate the photoperiod and lighting intensity and sources in the experimental room during the test measured in the treatment and control vessels. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As applicable, indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different lighting conditions were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text (2,000 char.)
Number of replicates	Indicate the number of organisms per treatment container/unit, the number of replicates per treatment group and the number of replicates per control group.	Text (2,000 char.)

Test system/structure	Indicate the type of structure in which the bees were kept during the exposure phase.	List sup.
Date of the test (beginning)	Enter the date of the beginning of the test.	Date
Date of the test (end)	Enter the date of the end of the test.	Date
Place of the test	Enter the place of the test as applicable (e.g. ZIP code, city and country).	Text (2,000 char.)
GPS coordinates	Provide the GPS coordinates as applicable. Use any of the following units and formats to specify the latitude and longitude: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sexagesimal degree (degrees, minutes, and seconds): e.g. 50° 26' 46" N 80° 58' 56" W - degrees and decimal minutes: e.g. 50° 26.767' N 80° 58.933' W - decimal degrees: e.g. 50.446° N 80.982° W 	Text (255 char.)
RFID tag information and performance	Provide information on the radio-frequency identification (RFID) tagging technology, such as supplier and performance of the RFID system.	Text (2,000 char.)
Details on test conditions	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. You can delete and add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Nominal and measured concentrations	List nominal and, if available, measured test concentrations used in the study, or, if contact or oral study with bees, the nominal and measured doses applied. As appropriate tabulate nominal vs. measured concentrations in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if any and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). Note: Specific tables may be required. For micro-organisms average achieved dose in colony forming units (cfu) must be reported.	Text (2,000 char.)
Reference substance (positive control)	Indicate if a positive control was tested, i.e. a reference substance with known toxicity. If yes, include the concentrations and the date of last reference test (if not conducted in parallel with the current substance test) in the supplementary remarks field. The selection of the positive control should also be justified (e.g. positive control indicated by the test guideline). Indicate the identity of the toxic reference substance(s) in the field below. You can provide results on the positive control in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".	List (picklist with remarks) sup.

Identity of the reference substance (positive control)	Indicate the identity of the toxic reference considered in the study.	Link to entity (multiple)
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block ".	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable. The following units should only be used in the case of microbial active substances: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ cells ▪ CFU (colony-forming unit) ▪ ITU (International Toxic Unit) ▪ IU (International Unit) ▪ OB (occlusion bodies) ▪ spores 	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Numeric range (decimal)
Nominal measured /	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average	List (picklist)

	= TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.		
Conc. based on	<p>Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification.</p> <p>Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.</p>	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Slope of the curve	Indicate the slope of the concentration-response curve. This is relevant information for the further risk assessment of bees.	Text (2,000 char.)	
Life stage	Specify the life stage of the test organism related to the reported result.	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Basis for effect	<p>Select effect parameter such as mortality, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.</p> <p>Any other types of effects can be described using the option "other:", or described in the field "Details on results".</p> <p>For example, behavioural observations such as moribund bees, bees with cramps, etc can be considered symptoms of overall toxicity, and are not normally considered for the basis of effects.</p> <p>Brood development refers mainly to effects observed in brood termination rate, which is the main objective of brood developmental studies. Further information that can also be of help for the evaluation include e.g. brood index, brood compensation rate. These should be reported using graphs under the section "Overall remarks, attachments".</p> <p>Colony conditions may give an indication of the reliability of the results. Information such as number of bees, presence of queen, the amount of brood, food provisions, etc. can give information to evaluate the colony strength and this can be conducted in line with the Liebefeld assessment and to be reported under "Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables".</p> <p>Noting that reproduction is the functional capacity, the common measurable endpoints such as fecundity and fertility can be directly reported by selecting the entry in the picklist. However, other endpoints such as sperm performance, queen oviposition, hibernation success, number of sexuals, colony foundation success etc, can also be reported.</p>	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with

		The basis for effects called 'homing success' covers both multiple physiological and cognitive functions that are involved in homing ability under field conditions (e.g. navigation, memory, flight muscle contraction and energetic metabolism). The measurable parameter would be homing rate %.	
Remarks on result	on	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; ▪ giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or ▪ entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' <p>Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.</p>	List (picklist with 2,000 char.) sup. with -
Detailed results		See instructions reported in the "Dose response – common block".	Header 2
Details results	on	<p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Depending on the type of study, you can delete/add elements as appropriate.</p> <p>Include the following information, for bees as non-target organisms:</p> <p>Lower tier - LD50 and NOED values and potentially differentiate between the types of test (i.e. acute oral, acute contact, chronic and life stage (adult / larvae), the species)).</p> <p>Higher tier – indicate the major effects, e.g. mortality, brood development etc. Where relevant, the residue measurements/pollen characterisation should be specified to guarantee the proper exposure.</p> <p>In the mortality assessment the insects should be classed as being live, affected, moribunds, dead and/or not seen. If applicable, it should also be described how mortality was defined, with respect to e.g. number of animals escaped and number of animals that have died.</p> <p>Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p>	Text template

	Note: Specific tables may be required. Consult the programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD HPVC, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) thereof.	
Results with reference substance (positive control)	If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information, for example whether the results are in line with those indicated in the test guideline. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship. Include the results of the goodness-of-fit. Further information on the results of statistical analyses can be provided in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".	Text (2,000 char.)
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

8.4 Effect on terrestrial arthropods other than bees – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details, e.g.:

- Group: Specify species tested;
- Test type (laboratory/others);
- Dose;
- Exposure route/time-scale (hours, days, weeks);
- Toxicity (endpoint or other description of effects).

A summary on potential infectivity and pathogenicity of the microorganism to non-target arthropods other than bees must be provided, based on the information already provided under

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

Sections 1, 2, 3 and 7 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439 and on other information which may be retrieved from any other reliable source.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

Links to supporting material:

EU Guidance Document on Terrestrial Ecotoxicology (SANCO/10329/2002 rev 2) https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-10/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_ecotox_terrestrial.pdf

Candolfi et al (2001). Guidance Document on Regulatory Testing and Risk Assessment Procedures for Plant Protection Products With Non-Target Arthropods: From the Escort 2 Workshop (European Standard Characteristics of Non-Target Arthropod Regulatory Testing). SETAC press, pp 46. ISBN 1-880611-52-x.

Candolfi et al, 2001. Guidance document on regulatory testing and risk assessment procedures for plant protection products with non-target arthropods. Report of the SETAC/ESCORT 2 Workshop, Wageningen, the Netherlands, and SETAC-Europe, Brussels, Belgium.

8.4 Effect on terrestrial arthropods other than bees – Endpoint study record

Relevant pathogenicity/infectivity studies must be performed, unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

If studies are required, they shall be performed on two arthropod species other than bees playing a role in biological control and comprising different taxonomic groups (orders), where possible, for which agreed testing protocols are available, and the applicant shall provide a justification for number and taxonomy of the tested species. Moreover, these tests may require conditions affecting growth or viability of the micro-organism.

Where adverse effects are observed in such studies, further relevant studies (e.g. extended laboratory tests or field studies under representative conditions in accordance with the proposed conditions of use) shall be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToTerrestrialArthropodsOtherThanBees		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Material and methods – common block"</p> <p>Applicable test guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ OECD Guideline 228 (Determination of Developmental Toxicity of a Test Chemical to Dipteran Dung Flies (<i>Scathophaga stercoraria</i> L. (Scathophagidae), <i>Musca autumnalis</i> De Geer (Muscidae))) ▪ EPA OPPTS 885.4340 (Microbial Pesticide, Nontarget Insect Testing, Tier I) ▪ Extended laboratory test for evaluating the effects of plant protection products on the parasitic wasp, <i>Aphidius rhopalosiphi</i> by Mead-Briggs et al. (2010) ▪ IOBC: Guidelines to evaluate side-effects of plant protection products to non-target 	Header 1

	<p>arthropods; ISBN 92-9067-129-7; pages: 1-12 - [rove beetle, <i>Aleochara bilineata</i>]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ IOBC: Guidelines to evaluate side-effects of plant protection products to non-target arthropods; ISBN 92-9067-129-7; pages: 27-44 - [green lacewing, <i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>] ▪ IOBC: Guidelines to evaluate side-effects of plant protection products to non-target arthropods; ISBN 92-9067-129-7; pages: 45-56 - [ladybird beetle, <i>Coccinella septempunctata</i>] ▪ IOBC: Guidelines to evaluate side-effects of plant protection products to non-target arthropods; ISBN 92-9067-129-7; pages: 57-70 - [predatory bug, <i>Orius laevigatus</i>] ▪ IOBC: Guidelines to evaluate side-effects of plant protection products to non-target arthropods; ISBN 92-9067-129-7; pages: 71-86 - [spider, <i>Pardosa</i>] ▪ IOBC: Guidelines to evaluate side-effects of plant protection products to non-target arthropods; ISBN 92-9067-129-7; pages: 87-106 - [carabid beetle, <i>Poecilus cupreus</i>] ▪ IOBC: Guidelines to evaluate side-effects of plant protection products to non-target arthropods; ISBN 92-9067-129-7; pages: 107-120 - [<i>Trichogramma cacoeciae</i>] ▪ IOBC: Guidelines to evaluate side-effects of plant protection products to non-target arthropods; ISBN 92-9067-129-7; pages: 121-144 - [predatory mite, <i>Typhlodromus pyri</i>] ▪ Laboratory test for evaluating the effects of plant protection products on the parasitic wasp, <i>Aphidius rhopalosiphi</i> by Mead-Briggs et al. (2000) 	
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis		Header 2
Analytical monitoring	<p>Indicate whether test substance was monitored in the test solutions or suspensions.</p> <p>For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details on sampling and analytical methods in the corresponding freetext fields.</p>	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Details on sampling	<p>If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter details on sampling. Use freetext template as appropriate and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p> <p>Note: Indicate which concentrations were measured if not all. As applicable, provide information for soil, stock and/or spray solution.</p>	Text template

Details on analytical methods	If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter any details on the analytical methods used. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Test substrate		Header 2
Application method	Select the method of application as appropriate. If not available from the picklist, select 'other:' and specify.	List (picklist)
Application rate	In case the application is done under field/semi-field conditions, indicate the application rate.	Numeric range (decimal)
Vehicle	Indicate whether vehicle was used to emulsify or mix the experimental test material to enhance its solubility. If yes, specify in field 'Details on preparation and application of test substrate'.	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Details on preparation and application of test substrate	Depending on the type of study, select appropriate freetext template (e.g. Honeybees: contact study) and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	List (picklist)
Animal group	Indicate the animal group, for example by choosing Coleoptera (ground-dwelling rove beetle) for a test with <i>Aleochara bilineata</i> . Helpful for searching purposes.	List (picklist)
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design		Header 2
Study type	Indicate the study type, i.e. laboratory study, semi-field study (mimicking a near-natural environment with ambient climatic conditions) or field study (using natural populations).	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	List (picklist)
Total exposure duration	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to the total exposure duration.	Text (255 char.)
Post exposure observation period	Indicate the post-observation period (with unit) if appropriate.	Text (2,000 char.)
Test conditions		Header 2

Test temperature	<p>Indicate test temperature values measured in the treatment and control vessels during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As appropriate state the location and type of measurement (e.g. continuous monitoring). As applicable indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different temperatures were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies. Example: 20+/-1°C (adults), 25+/-1.5°C (larval exposure), 18+/-1°C (pupal development), 25+/-1°C (fecundity).</p> <p>Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.</p>	Text (2,000 char.)
Humidity	<p>Indicate the relative humidity of the experimental room during the test measured in the treatment and control vessels. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As applicable indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different humidities were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies.</p> <p>Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.</p>	Text (2,000 char.)
Photoperiod and lighting	<p>Indicate the photoperiod and lighting intensity and sources in the experimental room during the test measured in the treatment and control vessels. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As applicable, indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different lighting conditions were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies.</p> <p>Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.</p>	Text (2,000 char.)
Number of replicates	Indicate the number of organisms per treatment container/unit, the number of replicates per treatment group and the number of replicates per control group.	Text (2,000 char.)
Details on test conditions	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Nominal and measured concentrations	<p>List nominal and, if available, measured test concentrations used in the study, or, if contact or oral study with bees, the nominal and measured doses applied. As appropriate tabulate nominal vs. measured concentrations in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if any and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>Note: Specific tables may be required.</p> <p>For micro-organisms average achieved dose in colony forming units (cfu) must be reported.</p>	Text (2,000 char.)

Reference substance (positive control)	<p>Indicate if a positive control was tested, i.e. a reference substance with known toxicity. If yes, include the concentrations and the date of last reference test (if not conducted in parallel with the current substance test) in the supplementary remarks field.</p> <p>The selection of the positive control should also be justified (e.g. positive control indicated by the test guideline).</p> <p>Indicate the identity of the toxic reference substance(s) in the field below.</p> <p>You can provide results on the positive control in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".</p>	List (picklist with remarks) sup. with remarks)
Identity of the reference substance (positive control)	Indicate the identity of the toxic reference considered in the study.	Link to entity (multiple)
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	List (picklist with remarks) sup. with remarks)
Effect conc.	<p>Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.</p> <p>The following units should only be used in the case of microbial active substances:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - cells - CFU (colony-forming unit) - ITU (International Toxic Unit) 	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IU (International Unit) - OB (occlusion bodies) - spores 	
95% CI	<p>For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant.</p> <p>Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.</p>	Numeric range (decimal)
Nominal measured /	<p>Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.</p>	List (picklist)
Conc. based on	<p>Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification.</p> <p>Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.</p>	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Life stage	<p>Specify the life stage of the test organism related to the reported result.</p>	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Basis for effect	<p>Select effect parameter such as mortality, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.</p> <p>Any other types of effects can be described using the option "other:", or described in the field "Details on results".</p>	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Remarks on result	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; ▪ giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or ▪ entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' <p>Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value</p>	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)

	with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC ₅₀ >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.	
Detailed results	See instructions reported in the "Dose response – common block".	Header 2
Details on results	<p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Depending on the type of study, select freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p> <p>Include the following information:</p> <p>Lower tier: EC₅₀, LR₅₀, ER₅₀ values (separate section or separate summary), type of exposure, species (For this type of studies optional reporting of NOEC).</p> <p>In the mortality assessment the insects should be classed as being live, affected, moribunds, dead and/or not seen. If applicable, it should also be described how mortality was defined, with respect to e.g. number of animals escaped and number of animals that have died.</p> <p>Higher tier: EC₅₀, LR₅₀, ER₅₀, NOAER, NOER values (separate section or separate summary), type of exposure, species. (For this type of studies optional reporting of NOEC).</p> <p>Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>For microorganisms indicate that information on toxicity, infectiveness and pathogenicity to arthropods other than bees must be reported. The text from the US EPA guideline could also be included afterwards. The guideline should be cited (885.4340 - Nontarget Insect Testing, Tier I (February 1996)).</p> <p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Depending on the type of study, select appropriate freetext template (i.e. soil or above-ground arthropods or honeybees) and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p> <p>For protozoan diseases, e.g.the most appropriate end-point for protozoan diseases for determining pathogenic effects is the presence of the vegetative stages (shizonts or merozoites) in the tissues of nontarget insects.</p> <p>Mortality time, expressed as LT50 (time course of population mortality), could be considered a reliable parameter for bioassaying fungi of insects in the laboratory</p> <p>Relevant information to record for higher tier: Study site/location, irrigation or other application techniques, sampling method, crop rotation in field study, as well as</p>	Text template

	the field history concerning agricultural management (including PPPs) should be reported.	
Results with reference substance (positive control)	If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information, for example whether the results are in line with those indicated in the test guideline. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship. Include the results of the goodness-of-fit. Further information on the results of statistical analyses can be provided in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".	Text (2,000 char.)
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

8.5 Effects on non-target meso- and macro-organisms in soil

8.5.1 EFFECTS ON SOIL ARTHROPODS – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose:

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details.

A summary on potential infectivity and pathogenicity of the microorganism to non-target soil meso- and macro-organisms must be provided, based on the information already provided under Sections 1, 2, 3 and 7 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439 and on other information which may be retrieved from any other reliable source.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

8.5.1 EFFECTS ON SOIL ARTHROPODS – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

This document is to be used to report effects on soil organisms (other than earthworms), except in situations where soil organisms are not exposed.

Relevant pathogenicity/infectivity studies must be performed unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

If studies are required, they shall be performed on two non-target meso- and macro-organisms species chosen based on the biological properties of the microorganism under evaluation, where possible, for which agreed testing protocols are available.

Where adverse effects are observed in such studies, further relevant studies (e.g. under representative conditions in accordance with the proposed conditions of use) must be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToSoilArthropods		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guideline: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ OECD Test Guideline No. 226: Predatory mite (<i>Hypoaspis (Geolaelaps) aculeifer</i>) reproduction test in soil. https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264264557-en ▪ OECD Test Guideline No. 232: Collembolan Reproduction Test in Soil. https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264264601-en ▪ ISO 11267 (Inhibition of Reproduction of Collembola by Soil Pollutants). 	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis		Header 2
Analytical monitoring	Indicate whether test substance was monitored in the test solutions or suspensions. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details on sampling and analytical methods in the corresponding freetext fields.	List (picklist with remarks) sup. with remarks)
Details on sampling	If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter details on sampling. Use freetext template as appropriate and delete/add elements as appropriate. Note: Indicate which concentrations were measured if not all. As applicable, provide information for soil, stock and/or spray solution.	Text template

Details on analytical methods	If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter any details on the analytical methods used. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Test substrate		Header 2
Application method	Select the method of application as appropriate. If not available from the picklist, select 'other:' and specify.	List (picklist)
Vehicle	Indicate whether vehicle was used to emulsify or mix the experimental test material to enhance its solubility. If yes, specify in field 'Details on preparation and application of test substrate'.	List (picklist) sup. with remarks
Details on preparation and application of test substrate	Depending on the type of study, select appropriate freetext template (e.g. Honeybees: contact study) and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. Consult the programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD HPVC, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) thereof.	Text template
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	List (picklist)
Animal group	Indicate the animal group, for example by choosing 'Collembola (soil-dwelling springtail)' for a test with <i>Folsomia candida</i> .	List (picklist)
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design		Header 2
Study type	Indicate the study type, i.e. laboratory study, semi-field study (mimicking a near-natural environment with ambient climatic conditions) or field study (using natural populations).	List (picklist) sup. with remarks
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	List (picklist)
Total exposure duration	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to the total exposure duration.	Text (255 char.)
Post exposure observation period	Indicate the post-observation period (with unit) if appropriate.	Text (2,000 char.)
Extraction method	Indicate the extraction method used for the determination of surviving test organisms. Also indicate the calculation method used.	Text (2,000 char.)

Test conditions		Header 2
Test temperature	<p>Indicate test temperature values measured in the treatment and control vessels during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As appropriate state the location and type of measurement (e.g. continuous monitoring). As applicable indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different temperatures were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies. Example: 20+/-1°C (adults), 25+/-1.5°C (larval exposure), 18+/-1°C (pupal development), 25+/-1°C (fecundity).</p> <p>Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.</p>	Text (2,000 char.)
Humidity	<p>Indicate the relative humidity of the experimental room during the test measured in the treatment and control vessels. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As applicable indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different humidities were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies.</p> <p>Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.</p>	Text (2,000 char.)
Photoperiod and lighting	<p>Indicate the photoperiod and lighting intensity and sources in the experimental room during the test measured in the treatment and control vessels. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As applicable, indicate the life-stage in parentheses if different lighting conditions were used e.g. in case of predator and parasite studies.</p> <p>Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.</p>	Text (2,000 char.)
Details on test conditions	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Nominal and measured concentrations	<p>List nominal and, if available, measured test concentrations used in the study, or, if contact or oral study with bees, the nominal and measured doses applied. As appropriate tabulate nominal vs. measured concentrations in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if any and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>Note: Specific tables may be required.</p> <p>For microorganisms average achieved dose in colony forming units (cfu) or the relevant unit must be reported.</p>	Text (2,000 char.)

Reference substance (positive control)	<p>Indicate if a positive control was tested, i.e. a reference substance with known toxicity. If yes, include the concentrations and the date of last reference test (if not conducted in parallel with the current substance test) in the supplementary remarks field.</p> <p>The selection of the positive control should also be justified (e.g. positive control indicated by the test guideline).</p> <p>Indicate the identity of the toxic reference substance(s) in the field below.</p> <p>You can provide results on the positive control in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".</p>	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Identity of the reference substance (positive control)	Indicate the identity of the toxic reference considered in the study.	Link to entity (multiple)	
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2	
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block ".	Header 2	
Results and discussion		Header 1	
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.		
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box	
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Numeric (decimal including unit)	
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	List (picklist remarks)	sup. with
Effect conc.	<p>Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.</p> <p>The following units should only be used in the case of microbial active substances:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - cells - CFU (colony-forming unit) 	Numeric (decimal picklist)	range with

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ITU (International Toxic Unit) - IU (International Unit) - OB (occlusion bodies) - spores 	
95% CI	<p>For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant.</p> <p>Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.</p>	Numeric range (decimal)
Nominal measured /	<p>Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.</p>	List (picklist)
Conc. based on	<p>Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification.</p> <p>Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.</p>	List (picklist) sup. with remarks)
Life stage	<p>Specify the life stage of the test organism related to the reported result.</p>	List (picklist) sup. with remarks)
Basis for effect	<p>Select effect parameter such as behaviour, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.</p> <p>Any other types of effects can be described using the option "other:", or described in the field "Details on results".</p>	List (picklist) sup. with remarks)
Remarks on result	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' <p>Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not</p>	List (picklist) sup. with remarks - 2,000 char.)

		determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.	
Detailed results		See instructions reported in the " Dose response – common block ".	Header 2
Details results	on	<p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Depending on the type of study, you can delete/add elements as appropriate.</p> <p>For species level testing (laboratory studies), include the following information: EC₁₀, EC₂₀ and NOEC.</p> <p>For higher tier testing (field studies), key effect end-points include: changes in community and population structure of both micro and macro-organisms; species diversity; number and biomass of key species/groups.</p> <p>Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>For microorganisms indicate that information on toxicity, infectiveness and pathogenicity to arthropods other than bees must be reported. The text from the US EPA guideline could also be included afterwards. The guideline should be cited (885.4340 - Nontarget Insect Testing, Tier I (February 1996).</p> <p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Depending on the type of study, select appropriate freetext template (i.e. soil or above-ground arthropods or honeybees) and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p> <p>Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>Ability to record multiple endpoint values (we can have different species, populations, communities etc.)</p> <p>For microorganisms - The most appropriate endpoint for protozoan diseases for determining pathogenic effects is the presence of the vegetative stages (shizonts or meronts) in the tissues of nontarget insects; Mortality time, expressed as LT50 (time course of population mortality), is considered the most reliable parameter for bioassaying fungi of insects in the laboratory.</p> <p>Relevant information to record for higher tier. Study site/location, irrigation or other application techniques, sampling method, crop rotation in field study, as well as the field history concerning</p>	Text template

	agricultural management (including PPPs) should be reported.	
Results with reference substance (positive control)	<p>If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information, for example whether the results are in line with those indicated in the test guideline.</p> <p>Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p>	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	<p>Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship. Include the results of the goodness-of-fit.</p> <p>Further information on the results of statistical analyses can be provided in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".</p>	Text (2,000 char.)
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

8.5.2 EFFECTS ON SOIL MACROORGANISMS EXCEPT ARTHROPODS – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details.

- Group: Specify species;
- Route/time-scale
- Toxicity, infectivity and pathogenicity (endpoint, value or other description of effects);
- Test type (laboratory/others);
- Dose (e.g., kg /ha).

A summary on potential infectivity and pathogenicity of the microorganism to non-target soil meso- and macro- organisms must be provided, based on the information already provided

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

under Sections 1, 2, 3 and 7 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439 and on other information which may be retrieved from any other reliable source.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

Links to supporting material:

EU Guidance Document on Terrestrial Ecotoxicology (SANCO/10329/2002 rev 2) https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-10/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_ecotox_terrestrial.pdf

8.5.2 EFFECTS ON SOIL MACROORGANISMS EXCEPT ARTHROPODS – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to be used to report information on the effects on growth, reproduction and behaviour of the earthworm.

Relevant pathogenicity/infectivity studies must be performed unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

If studies are required, they shall be performed on two non-target meso- and macro-organisms species chosen based on the biological properties of the micro-organism under evaluation, where possible, for which agreed testing protocols are available.

Where adverse effects are observed in such studies, further relevant studies (e.g. under representative conditions in accordance with the proposed conditions of use) shall be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToSoilMacroorganismsExceptArthropods		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guideline: OECD Test Guideline 222: Earthworm Reproduction Test (<i>Eisenia fetida</i> / <i>Eisenia andrei</i>) ISO 11268-3:2014: Soil quality - Effects of pollutants on earthworms - Part 3: Guidance on the determination of effects in field situations ISO 23611-1:2018: Soil quality - Sampling of soil invertebrates - Part 1: Hand-sorting and extraction of earthworms	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis		Header 2
Analytical monitoring	Indicate whether test substance was monitored in the test solutions or suspensions. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details on	List (picklist with remarks) sup. with

	sampling and analytical methods in the corresponding freetext fields.	
Details on sampling	<p>If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter details on sampling. Use freetext template as appropriate and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p> <p>Note: Indicate which concentrations were measured if not all. As applicable, provide information for soil, stock and/or spray solution.</p>	Text template
Details on analytical methods	If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter any details on the analytical methods used. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Test substrate		Header 2
Vehicle	Indicate whether vehicle was used to emulsify or mix the experimental test material to enhance its solubility. If yes, specify in field 'Details on preparation and application of test substrate'.	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Details on preparation and application of test substrate	Depending on the type of study, select appropriate freetext template (e.g. Honeybees: contact study) and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Test organisms		Header 2
Test organisms (species)	Select the species from the picklist. If not available, select 'other' and enter the species name of the test organism.	List (picklist)
Animal group	Indicate the animal group.	List (picklist)
Details on test organisms	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use free-text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Study design	Follow instructions reported in " Study design – common block (OHT: Terrestrial toxicity) "	Header 2
Test conditions		Header 2
Test temperature	Indicate test temperature values measured in the treatment and control vessels during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As appropriate state the location and type of measurement (e.g. continuous monitoring). Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text area
pH	Indicate the pH of the soil and water at the start and end of the test. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text area
Moisture	Indicate the water content of the soil at the start and end of the test. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see	Text area

	table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	
Details on test conditions	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Nominal and measured concentrations	<p>List nominal and, if available, measured test concentrations used in the study, or, if contact or oral study with bees, the nominal and measured doses applied. As appropriate tabulate nominal vs. measured concentrations in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if any and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>Note: Specific tables may be required.</p> <p>For microorganisms: average achieved dose in colony forming units (cfu) or the relevant unit must be reported.</p>	Text (2,000 char.)
Reference substance (positive control)	<p>Indicate if a positive control was tested, i.e. a reference substance with known toxicity. If yes, include the concentrations and the date of last reference test (if not conducted in parallel with the current substance test) in the supplementary remarks field.</p> <p>The selection of the positive control should also be justified (e.g. positive control indicated by the test guideline).</p> <p>Indicate the identity of the toxic reference substance(s) in the field below.</p> <p>You can provide results on the positive control in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".</p>	List (picklist with remarks) sup.
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)

Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal measured /	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	Closed list
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Basis for effect	Select effect parameter such as inhibition of respiratory rate or growth inhibition, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; ▪ giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or ▪ entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' <p>Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.</p>	Open list with remarks (2000)

Detailed results	See instructions reported in the " Dose response – common block ".	Header 2
Details on results	<p>For microorganisms: Information on toxicity, pathogenicity and infectiveness to earthworms should be reported.</p> <p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined table(s) if any or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p>	Text template
Results with reference substance (positive control)	<p>If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information, for example whether the results are in line with those indicated in the test guideline.</p> <p>Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p>	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	<p>Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship. Include the results of the goodness-of-fit.</p> <p>Further information on the results of statistical analyses can be provided in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".</p>	Multi-line text
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS 1/RM/44), 13.3.2 Earthworms

8.6 Effects on non-target terrestrial plants – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the information from the most relevant study(ies) on seedling emergence and/or vegetative vigor from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details, including:

- Study type;
- Species tested;
- Time scale (exposure duration);
- Derived endpoint and concentration.

A summary on potential infectivity and pathogenicity of the microorganism to non-target terrestrial plants must be provided, based on the information already provided under Sections 1, 2, 3 and 7 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439 and on other information which may be retrieved from any other reliable source.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

8.6 Effects on non-target terrestrial plants – Endpoint study record

Purpose

Relevant studies on pathogenic/infective effects on non-target terrestrial plants must be performed if the microorganism is known to have an herbicidal mode of action or to be closely related to a plant pathogen, unless the applicant demonstrates no exposure or pathogenicity/infectivity is well characterized by the weight of evidence analysis.

Where adverse effects are observed in such studies, further relevant studies (e.g. under representative conditions in accordance with the proposed conditions of use) shall be performed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToTerrestrialPlants		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OECD Test Guideline 208: Terrestrial Plant Test: Seedling Emergence and Seedling Growth Test - OECD Test Guideline 227: Terrestrial Plant Test: Vegetative Vigour Test - OPPTS 885.4300 - Nontarget Plant Studies, Tier I 	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Sampling and analysis		Header 2

Analytical monitoring	Indicate whether test substance was monitored in the test solutions or suspensions. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details on sampling and analytical methods in the corresponding freetext fields.	List (picklist remarks) sup. with
Details on sampling	If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter details on sampling. Use freetext template as appropriate and delete/add elements as appropriate. Note: Indicate which concentrations were measured if not all. As applicable, provide information for soil, stock and/or spray solution.	Text template
Details on analytical methods	If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, enter any details on the analytical methods used. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Test substrate		Header 2
Vehicle	Indicate whether vehicle was used to emulsify or mix the experimental test material to enhance its solubility. If yes, specify in field 'Details on preparation and application of test substrate'.	List (picklist remarks) sup. with
Details on preparation and application of test substrate	Depending on the type of study, select appropriate freetext template (e.g. Honeybees: contact study) and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study record or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Test organisms	Indicate the species and corresponding plant group. As appropriate you can prepare a study record for each species used in a given study or cover all species tested in one record. In the latter case, copy this field block and enter the information required for each species.	Header 2
Species	Select from drop-down list.	Open list
Plant group	Select from drop-down list.	Open list
Details on test organisms	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, also include relevant details on the test organism in the respective subfield. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Study design	Follow instructions reported in " Study design – common block (OHT: Terrestrial toxicity) "	Header 2
Test conditions		Header 2
Test temperature	Indicate test temperature values measured in the treatment and control vessels during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As appropriate state the location and type of measurement (e.g. continuous monitoring). Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if	Text area

	the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	
pH	Indicate the pH of the soil and water at the start and end of the test. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text area
Moisture	Indicate the water content of the soil at the start and end of the test. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text area
Details on test conditions	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
Nominal and measured concentrations	List nominal and, if available, measured test concentrations used in the study, or, if contact or oral study with bees, the nominal and measured doses applied. As appropriate tabulate nominal vs. measured concentrations in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if any and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). Note: Specific tables may be required. For microorganisms : average achieved dose in colony forming units (cfu) or the relevant unit must be reported.	Text (2,000 char.)
Reference substance (positive control)	Indicate if a positive control was tested, i.e. a reference substance with known toxicity. If yes, include the concentrations and the date of last reference test (if not conducted in parallel with the current substance test) in the supplementary remarks field. The selection of the positive control should also be justified (e.g. positive control indicated by the test guideline). Indicate the identity of the toxic reference substance(s) in the field below. You can provide results on the positive control in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".	List (picklist with remarks) sup. with
Model software and	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1

Effect concentrations	Report the relevant effect levels (e.g. EC50, LC50 and/or other). Repeat this block of fields for entering more than one effect level if necessary.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Species	Select from drop-down list.	Open list
Duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Dose descriptor	Indicate the derived dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects.	Open list with remarks
Effect conc.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
95% CI	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if relevant. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range
Nominal measured /	Indicate whether the effect concentration is based on nominal, measured (initial / geometric mean / arithmetic mean), measured (time weighted average = TWA), measured (not specified), acid equivalent or estimated. Select 'not specified' if not known.	Closed list
Conc. based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Basis for effect	Select effect parameter such as inhibition of respiratory rate or growth inhibition, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not 	Open list with remarks (2000)

	<p>determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' <p>Note: Where a test was done, but no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used it is recommended to report the upper or lower value with relevant qualifier, e.g. EC50 >10 mg/L (if this was the highest concentration tested). An additional explanation should be given in this field, e.g. 'not determinable because of methodological limitations' plus free text, e.g. 'highest concentration tested'.</p>	
Detailed results	See instructions reported in the "Dose response – common block" .	Header 2
Details results on	<p>Observations and reporting 885.4300 - Nontarget Plant Studies, Tier I (February 1996):</p> <p>Any abnormal adverse or beneficial effects in treatment and/or control groups, including dates and times the effects were observed.</p> <p>Briefly summarise relevant observations and any dose response relationship. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.</p> <p>Include table(s) with raw data in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if any available, and tailor it/them to your needs or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). As appropriate also attach a figure with growth curves in field 'Attached background material'.</p>	Text template
Results with reference substance (positive control)	<p>If reference substance(s) was/were tested, indicate whether the results with it/them are valid and provide relevant effect levels and other relevant information.</p> <p>Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p>	Text template
Reported statistics and error estimates	<p>Indicate the parameters analysed, the statistical method used and the statistical test performed. If probit analysis was used, indicate the intercept and probit slope. As appropriate state any relevant error estimates associated with the determination of concentration-response relationship.</p>	Multi-line text
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in "Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block"	Header 2

Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material

EU Guidance Document on Terrestrial Ecotoxicology (SANCO/10329/2002 rev 2) https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-10/pesticides_ppp_app-proc_guide_ecotox_terrestrial.pdf

EFSA PPR Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues), 2014. Scientific Opinion addressing the state of the science on risk assessment of plant protection products for non-target terrestrial plants. EFSA Journal 2014;12(7):3800, 163 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3800

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016) Guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS 1/RM/44), 12.2 Terrestrial plants

8.7 Additional studies on the microorganism – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the information from the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details.

For the structure see '[New Harmonised format for Ecotoxicological Endpoint Summaries](#)'

8.7 Additional studies on the microorganism – Endpoint study record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report additional studies, that might include further data on potential pathogenicity/infectivity of the microorganism on non-target species different from those species assessed to fulfil the requirements set out in points 8.1 to 8.6 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1439.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AdditionalEcotoxicologicalInformation		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ".	Header 2

	Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

8.8 Information and ecotoxicity of metabolites

Purpose

This document is to be used to conclude on the toxicity of metabolites based on literature search, with the aim of identifying metabolites of concern for non-target organisms and determining whether certain metabolites can be excluded as being of concern.

All the metabolites of potential concern should be listed, providing further information to demonstrate whether they are of concern or not.

Identified metabolites of concern to be reported in *Flexible_Summary.Metabolites & Other Substance for Assessment* dataset (see instructions above).

FLEXIBLE.SUMMARY_InformationEcotoxicityMetabolites		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality

Description of key information	<p>This document is for Metabolites of Concern for Non-Target Organisms</p> <p>See SANCO/2020/12258 Guidance on the risk assessment of metabolites produced by micro-organisms used as plant protection active substances.</p> <p>Stage 1 and Stage 2 the collection of basic information from literature should be reported in the Biological Properties document.</p> <p>This document should be used to report the results of targeted literature searches for all metabolites of potential concern in order to identify 'Metabolites of Concern'.</p> <p>If the identity is known, complete list of metabolites of potential concern should be listed in the 'Information on Metabolites' document and for the metabolites of concern the experimental data should be provided in the linked datasets.</p> <p>Provide additional information from the metabolite specific literature searches which cannot be reported in the repeatable block below.</p>	Header 1
		Text (rich-text area)
Metabolites		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Link to metabolite		Link to entity (single)
Link to Literature Search		Link to endpoint (single)
Hazardous effect observed in ecotoxicology studies	<p>If the picklist value 'no' is selected provide the justification in the remarks field. No further information is required in this table.</p> <p>If the picklist value 'yes' is selected complete all the information required in the table.</p>	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Non-target organisms	Where effects on non- target organisms are observed indicate the species group.	List multi. (multi-select list)
Conditions	Describe the conditions under which the microorganism produces the metabolite.	Text (2,000 char.)
LOQ of method	Any available information about the LOQ of the method used to determine/quantify the metabolite.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Expected quantities	Any available information about the expected quantities.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Regulation mechanism	Any available information on the mechanism by which the microorganism regulates the production of the metabolite shall be provided.	Text (2,000 char.)

Mode of action	Any available information on the influence of the produced metabolites on the microorganism's mode of action against the target organism(s) must be provided.	Text (2,000 char.)
Sufficient body of knowledge	Is there enough published literature to assume that a literature search would provide sufficient information on metabolite production? Make reference to the literature search included in the 'Link to Literature Search' in the table when justifying the selection of 'yes' or 'no' in the remarks field.	List sup. (picklist with remarks - 2,000 char.)
Nature of observed ecotoxic effect	Indicate any observed toxic effect(s) of the metabolite. Multiple choices are possible.	List multi (multi-select list)
Relevant antimicrobial activity	The checkbox should be ticked if the metabolite shows any relevant antimicrobial activity	Check box
Remarks	Provide any other information to support the classification of this metabolite as 'of concern'.	Text (2,000 char.)
Metabolites		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Step 5: Is the genus of the strain under evaluation well studied?		Header 2
	Literature data. Is the microorganism well studied? (see step 5.1 of SANCO/2020/12258) Provide a further evaluation of the body of knowledge that includes the history of safe use, the ecology of a microorganism in the agro-food chain or in other sectors, the scientific literature, clinical observations and reports (e.g. like infections in immunocompromised people where the microorganism has been isolated), industrial and/or medicinal applications, and other factors as considered appropriate. Is there sufficient information to conclude on the metabolites of concern? As a matter of principle, it is highly recommended to the applicant to conduct the search beyond the normally requested period of 10 years before the application, in order to gather all the possible relevant scientific literature to support the risk assessment.	Text (rich-text area)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information - common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

Guidance on the risk assessment of metabolites produced by micro-organisms used as plant protection active substances. SANCO/2020/12258 Rev. 1
https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/ffdf09b5-77a5-45b5-95f9-b16272f7535a_en

9. Change Log

9. Change log – Flexible record

Purpose

To facilitate the automated generation of the “List of references” report (field ‘Previously used’).

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.ChangeLog		
Name	Instructions	Type
General information		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: “User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests” available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Summary	Provide any additional explanation needed to facilitate the compilation of the final list of the tests and studies relied upon and whether the study was already submitted in the framework of national authorisations.	Rich text area
Change log		Header 1
Change entries	Create an entry in the table for each test or study	
Link to document	Select each of the IUCLID documents included in the dataset	Endpoint reference field
Status	For each of the documents indicate if the document is ‘new’, ‘previously used’ ‘obsolete’ or ‘updated’	Closed list
Remark	Indicate for which data point the study was previously used	Multi-line text
Change entries		

10. Summary and evaluation

10.1 Assessment from other authorities

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide information on previous assessments of the active substance, as a pesticide or under other regulatory processes, both within Europe and outside of Europe.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.AssessmentOtherAuthorities		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Assessments in Europe	In this section, provide information on previous or ongoing evaluations in Europe.	Header 1
Biocide	Indicate if this active substance has been or is being assessed under the Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR, Regulation (EU) 528/2012) Select the status of the application and provide details on the nature of the application	Open list with remarks (2000)
Veterinary medicine	Indicate if this active substance has been or is being assessed under the veterinary medicinal products Regulation (EU) 2019/6. Select the status of the application and provide details on the nature of the application	Open list with remarks (2000)
Other product safety assessments	In this section provide information on previous or ongoing evaluations in Europe under regulations other than Biocides or Veterinary Medicines	
Evaluation	If this active substance has been or is being assessed under any other product or food safety regulations indicate the context of the evaluation.	Open list
Status	Select the status of the application and provide details on the nature of the application	Open list with remarks (2000)
Existing residue definitions		Header 2
Monitoring purposes (plant)	Check the current existing RD in the EU MRL data base. The field refers to the enforcement residue definition of plant commodity/ies for which the MRL application is submitted. An EU Pesticides data base could be consulted If different enforcement residue definitions are set in different commodities under consideration, this shall be indicated.	Multi-line text
Risk assessment (plant)	The field refers to the risk assessment residue definitions for plant commodity/ies for which the MRL application is submitted.	Multi-line text

	<p>If different risk assessment residue definitions are set in different plant commodities under consideration, this shall be indicated.</p> <p>If for processed commodities residue definitions differ from residue definitions in raw agricultural commodity (RAC), this shall be indicated.</p> <p>If for rotational crops the residue definition differs from the residue definition in primary crops, this shall be indicated.</p> <p>Available in EFSA ccl and Registration reports</p>	
Monitoring purposes (animal)	<p>The field refers to the enforcement residue definitions for animal commodity/ies for which the MRL application is submitted. An EU Pesticides data base could be consulted.</p> <p>If different enforcement residue definitions are set in different commodities under consideration, this shall be indicated.</p> <p>Please check the current existing RD in the EU MRL data base.</p>	Multi-line text
Risk assessment (animal)	<p>The field refers to the risk assessment residue definitions for animal commodity/ies for which the MRL application is submitted.</p> <p>If different risk assessment residue definitions are set in different commodities under consideration, this shall be indicated.</p> <p>Available in EFSA ccl and Registration reports</p>	Multi-line text
Remarks	Any comment on the existing RD for risk assessment (e.g. provisional, clarify the source, data gaps, ...)	Multi-line text
EFSA paramCode		
RD paramCode	<p>Enter one or more EFSA param codes to identify the substance/s which comprise the residue definition for monitoring purpose (as used for reporting pesticide residue monitoring data)</p> <p>EFSA paramCodes can be downloaded or accessed by the EFSA catalogue browser application</p>	Text
EFSA paramCode		
Existing MRL		Header 2
EU MRL	List the existing EU MRLs for this active substance	
Commodity	<p>Select the commodity</p> <p>The picklist comprises commodities as listed in Part A of Annex I to Reg. 396/2005 and in addition feed commodities.</p>	Multi select closed list with remarks
MRL value	Enter the MRL value in mg/kg	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Residue definition monitoring	Enter the enforcement residue definition in the commodity/ies for the MRL	Multi-line text
Remarks	Any comment on the existing MRL (provisional, confirmatory data required.)	Multi-line text

Assessments outside Europe	In this section provide information on previous or ongoing evaluations outside of Europe	Header 1
Biocide	Indicate if this active substance has been or is being assessed for use as a biocide outside of Europe. Select the status of the application and provide details on the nature of the application	Open list with remarks (2000)
Veterinary medicine	Indicate if this active substance has been or is being assessed for use as a veterinary medicine outside of Europe Select the status of the application and provide details on the nature of the application	Open list with remarks (2000)
Other product safety assessments	In this section provide information on previous or ongoing evaluations outside Europe under regulations other than Biocides or Veterinary Medicines	
Evaluation	If this active substance has been or is being assessed under any other product or food safety regulations indicate the context of the evaluation.	Open list
Status	Indicate if this active substance has been or is being assessed under any other product or food safety regulations. If yes provide details on the nature and status of the application	Open list with remarks (2000)
Existing residue definitions	Enter the enforcement residue definitions for the MRL in the exporting country if they differ from those listed above	Header 2
Monitoring purposes (plant)	The field refers to the enforcement residue definition in the exporting country for plant commodity /-ies for which the MRL application is submitted. If different enforcement residue definitions are set in different commodities under consideration, this shall be indicated.	Multi-line text
Risk assessment (plant)	The field refers to the risk assessment residue definition in in the exporting country in the plant commodity for which the MRL application is submitted. If different risk assessment residue definitions are set in different commodities under consideration, this shall be indicated. If the MRL application is submitted to account for residues in rotational crops and the residue definition in rotational crops differs from the residue definition in primary crops, this shall be indicated.	Multi-line text
Monitoring purposes (animal)	The field refers to the enforcement residue definition in the exporting country for the animal commodity/ies for which the MRL application is submitted. If different enforcement residue definitions are set in different commodities under consideration, this shall be indicated.	Multi-line text
Risk assessment (animal)	The field refers to the risk assessment residue definition in the exporting country for the animal commodity for which the MRL application is submitted.	Multi-line text

	If different risk assessment residue definitions are set in different commodities under consideration, this shall be indicated.	
Remarks	Any comment on the existing RD for risk assessment (e.g., provisional, clarify the source, data gaps, ...)	Multi-line text
Existing MRL in the exporting country		Header 2
Exporting country MRL		
Country	Select the exporting country from the list	Multi select open list
Commodity	The commodity plant parts which were analyzed for and for which results should be reported in this table. The picklist comprised commodities as listed in Part A of Annex I to Reg. 396/2005 and in addition feed commodities. ONLY in case the tested commodity is not present in the picklist choose "other" and enter manually.	Multi select open list with remarks
MRL value	If MRL setting processes are established in exporting countries. If MRL setting processes are not established in exporting countries, specify if Codex residue limit (CXL) is applicable. If there are no CXL and no MRL in the exporting country, report 'not relevant' and specify the reason in remark box.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Residue definition monitoring	Enter the enforcement residue definition of plant commodity/ies for the MRL	Multi-line text
Remarks	Any additional remark on the MRL in the exporting country. If MRL setting processes are not established in exporting countries, specify if Codex residue limit (CXL) is applicable. If no CXL and no MRL in the exporting country, report 'not relevant' and specify the reason in remark box.	Multi-line text
Additional information	This section is only relevant for MRL applications	Header 1
Evidence of registration in the exporting country	Please confirm with this checkbox that the evidence of the registration in the exporting country and, if available, the registered use pattern in the exporting country were attached.	Check box
Evidence of registration in the exporting country (remark)	Clarification should be given in remark field if no evidence can be provided.	Multi-line text
Evidence of registration in the exporting country attached	Upload attachments with evidence of registration in the exporting country (these attachments will be published and should not contain confidential information)	Attachments list

Type	Specify the type of attachment inserted, for example the 'full study report'.	Picklist
Attached (confidential) document	An electronic copy of the full study report or other documents can be attached as Word, pdf or other file types.	Single Attachment File
Attached (sanitised) documents for publication	An electronic copy of a public (non-confidential) version of the full study report or other relevant documents can be attached. This attachment should be sanitised if needed.	Single Attachment File
Remarks	As appropriate, include remarks, e.g. a short description of the content of the attached document if the file name is not self-explanatory.	Text
Registered use pattern in the exporting country		Header 2
Type	Specify the type of attachment inserted, for example the 'full study report'.	Picklist
Attached (confidential) document	An electronic copy of the full study report or other documents can be attached as Word, pdf or other file types.	Single Attachment File
Attached (sanitised) documents for publication	An electronic copy of a public (non-confidential) version of the full study report or other relevant documents can be attached. This attachment should be sanitised if needed.	Single Attachment File
Remarks	As appropriate, include remarks, e.g. a short description of the content of the attached document if the file name is not self-explanatory.	Text
Legislation in the exporting country concerning the MRL	Please confirm with this checkbox that the Legislation in the exporting country concerning the MRL attached.	Check box
Legislation in the exporting country concerning the MRL (remark)	Clarification should be given if no MRLs are established in the originating country.	Multi-line text
Legislation in the exporting country concerning the MRL attached	Upload copies of the Legislation in the exporting country concerning the MRL	Attachments list
Type	Specify the type of attachment inserted, for example the 'full study report'.	Picklist
Attached (confidential) document	An electronic copy of the full study report or other documents can be attached as Word, pdf or other file types.	Single Attachment File
Attached (sanitised) documents for publication	An electronic copy of a public (non-confidential) version of the full study report or other relevant documents can be attached. This attachment should be sanitised if needed.	Single Attachment File
Remarks	As appropriate, include remarks, e.g. a short description of the content of the attached document if the file name is not self-explanatory.	Text

Links to supporting material:

EU Pesticides Database <https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/public/?event=homepage&language=EN>

European Food Safety Authority (2020). Harmonized terminology for scientific research [Data set]. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3243215>

EFSA Catalogue Browser User Guide 10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1726

<https://github.com/openefsa/catalogue-browser/releases>

10.2 Other reports

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the overall conclusions for the substance or mixture, and/or to provide a place to upload files or reports which could not be attached in other sections but are used to support the evaluation.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation_EU_PPP		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Complementary information	Select the type of bibliography or supporting documentation. This field is relevant for basic substance applications.	Picklist with remarks
Reports and administrative information	Upload here all additional reports needed for the assessment of the dossier and specify the type of report in the first column (e.g. draft evaluation report, list of studies, LOEP, etc.). Repeat the block for each document.	Header 1
Type of report	Indicate the type of document that has been uploaded e.g. 'Document C Existing or proposed labels'	Multi-line text
Attached document	The original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions. If a file is uploaded under this field, (a) confidentiality request(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.	Single file attachment
Attached (sanitised) document for publication	Any document uploaded here must be uploaded in their public (non-confidential) version. The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised. Save for the	Single file attachment

	<p>elements blackened, if applicable, content and layout-wise the public version must be fully identical with the confidential version. Upon conclusion of the confidentiality assessment, if applicable, a revised public version removing the redactions relating to confidentiality requests that were rejected in part or in full must be uploaded here.</p>	
Letter(s) of access	<p>Link here the relevant letter(s) of access. For each document, add new row by clicking on '+ New item'. Attach the confidential document and the sanitised document for publication. If the letter of access covers selected studies, you can establish link to each study directly from the table. If a record for a study has not been created yet, you can create it from the table. To do it, click on the 'Related studies', and then select 'Create'. In each endpoint study record, you need to fill in following fields: 'Reference' and 'Data access'.</p>	Header 1
Type of document	<p>Indicate the type of document that has been uploaded</p>	Multi-select list with remarks
Attached document	<p>The original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions. If a file is uploaded under this field, (a) confidentiality request(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.</p>	Single file attachment
Attached (sanitised) document for publication	<p>Any document uploaded here must be uploaded in their public (non-confidential) version. The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised. Save for the elements blackened, if applicable, content and layout-wise the public version must be fully identical with the confidential version. Upon conclusion of the confidentiality assessment, if applicable, a revised public version removing the redactions relating to confidentiality requests that were rejected in part or in full must be uploaded here.</p>	Single file attachment
Related studies	<p>If the letter of access covers selected studies, you can establish link to each study.</p>	Reference
Remarks		Multi-line text
Other references (including SDS)	<p>Link to other reports not referenced in the endpoint study records needed to support the assessment. The bibliographic information should be completed and the PDF uploaded in the literature reference entity</p> <p>This would include:</p>	Header 1

	'Safety datasheets' 'Scientific opinions of national/international regulatory bodies'	
References		Literature reference list
Additional information		Header 1
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block " Overall summary of the main conclusions for the substance or mixture can be entered here.	Rich text area

Additional considerations

The applicant must ensure that terms and conditions asserted by any copyright holder of publications or information submitted to EFSA are fully satisfied. The applicant should consult with copyright licensing authorities (i.e. at national level) for guidance on purchasing copyright licenses to reproduce any publications provided to EFSA. The applicant remains solely responsible and liable for obtaining all necessary authorisations and rights to use, reproduce and share the publications provided to EFSA

11. Documents applicable to the former data requirement

This section is not intended to be used by the applicants. It was kept to maintain documents submitted in DOSSIERS prepared using previous version of IUCLID and now obsolete.

PRODUCT DATASET

This section includes instructions on how to compile the IUCLID documents in the product dataset in line with the relevant changes released with IUCLID 6.9.

Instructions are focused on documents included in the product dataset only. For documents included also in the active substance dataset consult the dedicated section in the 'active substance dataset' of the manual.

1. Identity of the applicant, identity of the plant protection product and manufacturing information

1.1 Applicant, trade name or proposed trade name

Purpose

This document must be completed to report information on the Legal Entity owner and contact person for the plant protection product. The trade name or proposed trade name and producer's development code number of the plant protection product can also be provided.

Mixture		
Name	Instructions	Type
Mixture/ Product name	This must be completed; this information is also included in the dossier header as 'Dossier subject'	Multi-line text
Public name	Public name of the mixture	Multi-line text
Legal entity flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Legal entity owner	This must be completed; this information is also included in the dossier header as 'Submitting Legal Entity'. When submitting a dossier through the Submission Portal the same legal entity should be used, third party consultants may do this as foreign entities. For task forces, the lead applicant can act as the legal entity. Links the dossier to the Legal entity of the dossier owner.	Entity reference field
Third party flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Third party	Option to link to the legal entity of a third party	Entity reference field
Other identifiers		Header 1
	All former and current trade names and proposed trade names and development code numbers of the plant	

	protection product/preparation shall be provided. Flags can be used to indicate if the trade name is confidential	
Confidential	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Name type	Select name type	Open list
Name	Provide name	Multi-line text
Country	Provide the country where the identifier is relevant.	Multi select open list
Remarks	Include remarks if relevant	Text area
Contact persons	Link to the relevant Contact entity . The primary contact point for the dossier should be provided, name, position, telephone and e-mail address. This information is not published by default.	
Person flags	This flag is not needed since the details on the Contact persons are not published by default.	Confidentiality
Person	See Legal Entity (including contact person)	Entity reference field
Role in the supply chain		Header 1
	Check 'Manufacturer' to indicate the applicant is the Producer of the plant protection product	
Role flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality

Links to supporting materials:

[Legal entity](#)

1.2 Producer of the preparation and the microorganism(s)

See instructions in [Section 1.2](#) of the active substance dataset.

1.2.1 LOCATION OF MANUFACTURING PLANTS

See instructions in [Section 1.2.1](#) of the active substance dataset

1.3 Producer's development code number of the preparation if appropriate

Purpose

Development code numbers of the preparation referred to in the dossier as well as the current names and numbers must be provided.

Full detail of any differences must be provided.

Note: For pesticides this document is **optional** as the development code and any other relevant codes should be included in the **REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE entity** under **"Synonyms"** with an explanation in the "remark" field.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Identifiers		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Regulatory programme identifiers		Header 1
Regulatory programme identifiers		
Flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Regulatory programme	Select one identifier type from the drop-down list. If none of the pre-defined items applies, select 'other:'. A text field is then activated next to the list field in which you can enter any free text.	Open list
ID	Not relevant for EU-PPP Insert the identification number distributed by different regulatory programmes (e.g. the REACH registration number).	Text
Remarks	If necessary, provide any additional comments here.	Text area
Regulatory programme identifiers		
Other IT system identifiers		Header 1
Other IT system identifiers		
Flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
IT system	Specify the IT System identifier (e.g. IUCLID 4)	Text
ID	Insert the corresponding identification number.	Text
Remarks	If necessary, provide any additional comments here.	Text area
Other IT system identifiers		

1.4 Detailed quantitative and qualitative information on the composition of the preparation

Purpose

The full composition of the plant protection product as laid down in the applicable data requirements must be provided in this document, including information on co-formulants and relevant impurities.

Any Safety Data Sheets (SDS) related to co-formulants should be provided and included in the [FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.SummaryEvaluation_EU_PPP_Document](#) (Section 12).

This document is used to link the active substance dataset (and if relevant the other substance dataset) to the Mixture/product.

Note: for **microorganisms**, the **nominal content of viable material is required**. For reporting the typical concentration it is recommended to select the most appropriate units of measurement depending on the type of micro-organism (e.g. **CFU/kg**).

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.MixtureComposition		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
General information		Header 1
Mixture/product name	Report name of the main formulation/mixture. In case of additional mixtures, more than one document can be completed in Section 1.4.5 Other Representative products. The reference substance with the function 'active substance' must be the same for all mixture composition documents included in the dossier	Text
Trade names		
Country	Provide the country in which the trade name is relevant.	Multi select open list
Trade name	Report trade name of formulation/mixture	Multi-line text
Brief description	Additional information on the formulation/mixture can be added here	Text
Formulation type	Select the formulation type in accordance with the international coding system for pesticides from the scroll down list	Picklist
Components		Header 1
Component flag	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Name	Link to a 'reference substance' or 'substance'.	Entity reference field

	<p>Select 'substance' for the Active substance/micro-organism and Relevant impurities, Active substance (other, not to be assessed), Safeners and Synergists or any other component which has linked studies or summaries This creates a dataset for each component of this type.</p> <p>Link to 'reference substance' for other components e.g. co-formulants, by-products, culture medium where no information other than the amount in the formulation is required.</p> <p>If a component of the mixture is confidential it is important that the confidentiality flag of the reference substance entity is also set to CBI to ensure substance identifiers are not shown in the mixture composition document.</p>	
Function	<p>Indicate the function of the component in the formulation.</p> <p>For all mixture formulations in the dossier only one component with the function 'active substance' can be reported. This must be linked to a substance dataset. If an additional active substance is included in the formulation but is not the substance under assessment the function should be 'active substance (other, not to be assessed)'.</p> <p>For impurities select "Other" from the picklist and specify "Impurity" in the 'Remark' field.</p> <p>Important: Active substance, Active substance (other, not to be assessed), Safener and Synergist datasets are always published and should not be claimed confidential.</p>	Open list
Typical concentration	<p>Complete the Typical concentration reporting % (w/w) – never to be used for micro-organisms.</p> <p>For microorganisms, the nominal content of viable material is required. For reporting the typical concentration it is recommended to select the most appropriate units of measurement depending on the type of microorganism (e.g. CFU/kg). If the relevant unit is not included in the picklist, select 'other' and specify.</p> <p>For relevant impurities the range including the maximum content is required.</p> <p>For microorganisms the range - maximum and minimum viable material is required</p>	Half-bounded with open list (Decimal)
Concentration range	<p>Scientific notation can be used, e.g. $1e-3 = 0.001$ or $1e6 = 1000000$</p>	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks	<p>Additional information on the quantity of each component in the formulation/preparation which cannot be provided in the other fields, e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - content of the technical active substance - any of the contents (pure, technical) in an additional unit – e.g. g/L if w/w was reported in the field 'typical concentration' 	Text area

Substance of concern	The additional check boxes in this table are not relevant for European Plant Protection Products	Check box
Generic component identifier (GCI)	Not relevant for EU PPP	Check box
Interchangeable component group (ICG)	Not relevant for EU PPP	Check box
Standard formula (SF) component	Not relevant for EU PPP	Check box
Substance generated in situ		Check box
Unacceptable co-formulant	The check box should be checked if the co-formulant is included in a list of unacceptable co-formulants e.g Annex III to Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 (Regulation (EU) 2021/383) listing co-formulants which are not accepted for inclusion in plant protection products.	Check box

Links to supporting material:

[Catalogue of pesticide formulation types and international coding system](#)

Type at least 3 characters X

Expand all Collapse all

- 🔍 EU PPP Microorganisms - active substance application (product)
- 🔍 EFSA tender: GREENB (MPCP)
- 1 Identity of the applicant, identity of the plant protection product and manufacturing information 12
 - 1.1 Applicant, trade name or proposed trade name 1
 - 1.2 Producer of the preparation and the microorganism(s) 3
 - 1.3 Producer's development code number of the preparation if appropriate 1
 - 1.4 Detailed quantitative and qualitative information on the composition of the preparation 4
 - 🔍 2023_Detailed quantitative and qualitative information on the composition of the preparation
 - 1.4.1 Information on metabolites 1
 - 1.4.2 Other representative products 1
 - 1.4.3 Impurities 1
 - 1.4.4 Microorganisms defining consortium
 - 1.5 (Cf. 1.4) Physical state and nature of the preparation 1
 - 1.6 Method of production of the preparation and quality control 1
 - 1.7 Packaging and compatibility of the preparation with proposed packaging materials 2

2023_Detailed quantitative and qualitative information on the composition of the preparation

UUID: 010c595f-2450-4f9e-9d9b-2d51153bb551

Administrative data
General information
Components

Formulation type
WP Wettable powder

Components

+ New item
 📄 Import file

#	Component flag	Name	Function	Typical concentration	Concentration range	Remarks	Substance of concern
1	🔍 🔍	🔍 EFSA tender: Microorganism active substance MAS123 Beauveria bassiana sp Beauveria bassiana	active substance	>= 4600000000 CFU/g	>= 3600000000 - < 9600000000 CFU/g	Minimum 3.6 x 10 ⁹ CFU/g of dry matter	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	🔍 🔍	🔍 EFSA Tender: SecMetB (Metabolite of concern) EFSA Tender: SecMetB SecMetB	other: Secondary metabolite	0.85 g/kg	0.82 - 0.88 g/kg	Secondary metabolite part of the active substance	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	🔍 🔍 🔍 🔍	Inert component Dummy name	filler	<= 90	>= 89.8 - < 90.2		<input type="checkbox"/>

1.4.1 INFORMATION ON METABOLITES

Purpose

This document should be used to compile the list required for Stage 2: Collecting a basic set of information on metabolites, resulting in a list of metabolites of potential concern. See dedicated instructions in the introduction to this manual.

Any information on potentially harmful effects of metabolites on human and animal health, the environment or on groundwater shall be included in the dossier.

Chemical name in accordance with IUPAC and CA nomenclature, CAS-number, EC number, molecular and structural formula, molar mass, where available, should be reported.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.Metabolites		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Metabolites information		Header 1
Metabolites information overview	Include a summary of the metabolites included in the dossier.	Rich text area
Parent of metabolites	Not applicable to microorganisms	Entity reference field
List of metabolites		Header 1
Metabolites		Block of fields (repeatable)
	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/user-guide-submission-confidentiality-requests.pdf	Confidentiality
Link to metabolite dataset	<p>A metabolite dataset is required where further studies have been performed using a metabolite as the test material.</p> <p>The link must be made using a substance to create a dataset. In the dataset linked to the substance endpoint study records and endpoint summaries can be completed in the relevant sections e.g. Toxicological and metabolism studies, Fate and behavior in the environment, Ecotoxicological studies. The Table of Contents for a metabolite is the 'Other substance' dataset.</p> <p>Where a metabolite is detected and reported in an endpoint study record and the test material is the active substance only a link to a reference substance is required.</p> <p>In both cases the IUPAC and CA nomenclature, CAS-number EC number, molecular and structural formula, molar mass should be reported in the reference substance document. SMILES and InChi are recommended.</p>	Entity reference field
Remarks	Further information on the inclusion of the metabolite in document can be included e.g. 'metabolite produced by the strain but below LOQ'	Multi-line text
Toxicological assessment	<p>Indicate the toxicological assessment of the metabolite resulting as the outcome of the stage 3 (or the stages before) of the SANCO/2020/12258 Guidance.</p> <p>Indicate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 'MoC', in case of metabolites identified as being of concern. • 'MoPC', in case of metabolites identified as being of potential concern. • 'MoNC', in case of metabolites identified as being of no concern 	List (picklist)
The metabolite is claimed active metabolite	Check this box if the metabolite is claimed active metabolite	Checkbox

Metabolite WGS-evidence	Check this box if there is any WGS-evidence demonstrating the production of the metabolite	Checkbox
Remarks		Multi-line text
Metabolites		
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

Guidance on the risk assessment of metabolites produced by microorganisms used as plant protection active substances in accordance with article 77 of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009. SANCO/2020/12258 Rev 1. https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/ffdf09b5-77a5-45b5-95f9-b16272f7535a_en

Information on secondary metabolites
 UID: 75c3a9a9-e5e7-46b6-b9ca-e4ab68e11b9c

Metabolites information | List of metabolites

Metabolites information

[Metabolites information overview](#)

According to SANCO/2020/12258, a specific assessment needs to be completed to evaluate whether the secondary metabolites produced by Microorganism active substance MASI23 are relevant for risk assessment. The following secondary metabolites (potentially produced by MASI23) were identified: SecMetA, SecMetB and SecMetC. A specific literature search on SecMetA, SecMetB and SecMetC was conducted, focusing on hazardous or antimicrobial effects. Please find the information on the literature searches conducted under (MA 3.5 Literature data). For the information retrieved from the Literature searches, refer to the datasets for each secondary metabolite (linked here).

From the WGS presented under 1-3, only SecMetA and SecMetB can be produced by MASI23. The strain does not have the genomic capacity to produce SecMetC. The overview of the metabolite assessment is as follows:

- SecMetA can genomically be produced by the strain, however it cannot be detected in the active substance (see Sbatch analysis report). Therefore, there are no relevant exposure groups and it is not considered a secondary metabolite of concern.
- SecMetB can genomically be produced by the strain, and can be quantified in the active substance and product (see Sbatch analysis report and Document J). Please refer to the relevant document under the MA dossier Point 2.8 for an evaluation of the toxicological data. No toxicological reference value could be derived from the data available in the literature. There are indications of hazardous properties of SecMetB, therefore the TTC approach was used. An initial risk assessment was performed for non-dietary and dietary exposure based in the TTC value for genotoxic substances. The risk assessment was not safe. Therefore as refinement, a QSAR study on genotoxicity was conducted, where SecMetB was found not genotoxic. The risk assessment for non-dietary and dietary exposure was conducted with the TTC Dramer class III value, which shows acceptable risk. Therefore, SecMetB is considered a metabolite of concern with acceptable risk.
- SecMetC cannot be genomically be produced by the strain. Therefore it is not considered a secondary metabolite of concern.

[Parent of metabolites](#)

List of metabolites

Metabolites	Link to metabolite dataset	Remarks	Toxicological assessment	The metabolite is claimed active metabolite	Metabolite WGS-evidence	Actions
1	Microorganism active substance MASI23 Not applicable	Remarks were given for Microorganism active substance MASI21 instead.	metabolite of no concern (NoC)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	EFSA tender: SecMetA Secmet A		metabolite of no concern (NoC)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	EFSA Tender: SecMetB (Metabolite of concern) EFSA Tender: SecMetB SecMetB	SecMetB is present in the MPCP. Please refer to MA Section 6/ MP Section 7 for the risk assessment.	metabolite of potential concern (MoPC)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
4	SecMetC	SecMetC is known to be produced by this species. However, whole genome analysis shows that the strain MASI23 cannot produce this secondary metabolite.	metabolite of concern (MoC)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

1.4.2 OTHER REPRESENTATIVE PRODUCTS

Purpose

Where multiple representative product formulations are included in a dossier this document should be used to link the relevant product datasets

FIXED_RECORD.OtherRepresentativeProducts		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Other representative product(s)	<p>Link to the relevant datasets for other representative products.</p> <p>All mixture datasets linked in this document should contain a single component with the function 'active substance' in their mixture composition. This should correspond to a substance dataset and should be the same in all linked mixture datasets and in the main product dataset.</p>	Entity reference list

1.4.3 IMPURITIES

Purpose

Relevant information on all impurities of the active substance must be included in this document including:

- A link to the impurity data:
 - If no studies for the impurity are to be reported, a Reference substance entity must be created including all required chemical identifiers (e.g. name, CAS number, molecular and structural formula, SMILES, etc)
 - If studies for the impurity are to be reported, a substance dataset must be created, including i) the Reference substance entity with all required chemical identifiers (e.g. name, CAS number, molecular and structural formula, SMILES, etc), and ii) all relevant studies performed with the impurity
- The type of the impurity, i.e. significant, relevant, non-significant or theoretical
- A high-level toxicological and ecotoxicological assessment and conclusion for the impurity (introduced in IUCLID 6.9)
- Details on the origin of the impurity, including the link to the Manufacturing plant and an image of the chemical reaction, if available. The link to the Manufacturing plant is key to connecting the impurity to the corresponding manufacturing process and batch analysis information. If the impurity has different origins at different manufacturing processes, more than one entry should be created in the repeatable block.

Relevant, significant, and non-significant impurities (if applicable) reported within this document should correspond to the impurities listed in [section 1.4 Specification of the microbial pest control agent as manufactured](#).

Relevant impurities should also be part of the product composition in [Section 1.4](#).

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.Impurities		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Impurities information		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Impurities information overview	Report overview of impurities	Text (rich-text area)
Active substance	Link the active substance where the impurities are present.	Link to entity (single)
List of Impurities		Header 1
Impurities		Block of fields (repeatable)
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see:	Confidentiality

	"User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page"	
Link to impurity dataset	If studies are performed on the impurity, link the corresponding substance dataset. If no studies are performed, link the reference substance.	Link to entity (single)
Code/Name of the impurity	Indicate the code or name of the impurity used to identify the impurity in the different studies provided in the dossier.	Text
Type	Indicate the type of impurity.	List (picklist)
Toxicological / Ecotoxicological assessment	Provide a high-level toxicological and ecotoxicological assessment and conclusion for the impurity. Additional information (e.g., studies performed, more detailed assessments) should be provided within the impurity dataset.	Text
Remarks	Provide any additional details about the impurity, if needed.	Text
Information on the formation of the impurity	Create a separate entry for each different origin, manufacturing plant or formation reaction of the impurity.	Block of fields (repeatable)
Origin of the impurity	Indicate the origin of the impurity.	Open list with remarks
Manufacturing plant/site	Link the manufacturing plant/site where the technical material containing the impurity was produced. The manufacturing plant/site linked should be the same indicated in the Method of manufacture and Analytical Profile of Batches documents of the active substance dataset, if applicable.	Link to document (single)
Reaction scheme	Upload the (chemical) reaction scheme describing the formation of the impurity.	Image upload
Remarks	Provide any additional details about the formation of the impurity, if needed.	Text

1.4.4 MICROORGANISMS DEFINING CONSORTIUM

Purpose

This document is to be used when the dossier concerns active substances consisting of a qualitatively defined combination of strains (a microbial consortium).

The document should be used to report all relevant information about the consortium and to provide a link to the dataset of active substance (i.e. the consortium) and to the datasets of its constituents (i.e. consorts), providing relevant information for each component.

Information needed to be reported at consort level should be included in the dataset of that component.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.MicroConsortium		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1

	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see:</p> <p>"User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Consortium information		Header 1
General description of the consortium	Provide a general description of the microbial consortium.	Text (rich-text area)
Source type	Indicate whether the consortium is of natural origin or derives from the manufacturing process	List (picklist)
Active substance (consortium)	Link the active substance (consortium) in which the microorganisms are present	Link to entity (single)
List of microorganisms defining consortium		Header 1
Microorganisms (consorts)		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
		Confidentiality
Microorganism (consort)	<p>Select the microorganism defining the consortium.</p> <p>Link the corresponding substance dataset to report data on each microbials otherwise link the reference substance. This is done by creating a link with the desired dataset created previously in your database. Click the Link button.</p> <p>If the dataset is not present in your database, you need to create it before you will be able to link it.</p>	Link to entity (single)
Typical concentration	Give the typical concentration of the component in the consortium. Depending on the legislation you are following, you might need to specify the upper and lower limits for each of the main components.	Numeric range (half bounded)
Concentration range	Give the percentage of the component(s) with the upper and lower limit if it is required by the legislation.	Numeric range (decimal with picklist)
Remarks	<p>If necessary, provide any additional comments.</p> <p>For example, the function or mode of action of the consort within the consortium can be indicated.</p>	Text (32,768 char.)
Microorganism (consort)		Block of fields (repeatable) End

Consortium composition

Administrative data | Consortium information | List of microorganisms defining consortium

Consortium information

General description of the consortium
 Consortium XY is intended for use as a plant protection product to enhance disease suppression and promote plant growth through synergistic interactions among its constituent microorganisms. Each strain contributes complementary modes of action:

- microorganism A: Produces lipopeptides for antifungal activity.
- microorganism B: Acts as a mycoparasite and induces plant defense mechanisms

Qualitative Definition:
 The consortium is defined by the presence of the above strains in specified proportions, ensuring functional stability and efficacy. No additional microbial species are permitted.

Source type
 manufactured

Active substance (consortium)
 Consortium (Micro A + B)

List of microorganisms defining consortium

Microorganisms (consorts)	Microorganism (consort)	Typical concentration	Concentration range	Remarks	Actions
1	Microorganism A	300000000 CFU/g	> 100000000 - <= 500000000 CFU/g	Function: Produces lipopeptides for antifungal activity	
2	Microorganism B	100000000 CFU/g	>= 500000000 - <= 2000000000 CFU/g	Function: Mycoparasite, induces plant defense mechanisms	

Save

1.5 (Cf. 1.4) Physical state and nature of the preparation

1.6 Method of production of the preparation and quality control

See instructions in **Section 1.5.1** of the active substance dataset.

1.7 Packaging and compatibility of the preparation with proposed packaging materials

Purpose

(i) Packaging to be used must be fully described and specified in terms of the materials used, manner of construction (e.g. extruded, welded, etc.), size and capacity, size of opening, type of closure and seals. It must be designed in accordance with the criteria and guidelines specified in the FAO 'Guidelines for the Packaging of Pesticides'. (ii) The suitability of the packaging, including closures, in terms of its strength, leakproofness and resistance to normal transport and handling, must be determined and reported in accordance with ADR methods 3552, 3553, 3560, 3554, 3555, 3556, 3558, or appropriate ADR Methods for intermediate bulk containers, and, where for the preparation child-resistant closures are required, in accordance with ISO standard 8317. (iii) The resistance of the packaging material to its contents must be reported in accordance with GIFAP Monograph No 17.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Packaging		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page"	Confidentiality
Packaging		Header 1
If relevant, specify to which product(s) it applies:	The field is used to identify the product(s) being a member (members) of a product family (in case the concept applies), to which the packaging description in this very endpoint applies. After clicking the golden chain the list of product composition from section	Endpoint reference list

	<p>product composition. The applicant should select the relevant product composition(s).</p> <p>It is possible to include different sizes of packaging in one record, as long as the packaging shape is similar and the material is identical.</p> <p>One product (member of the product family) can use several types of packaging, therefore the same product composition can be linked to several packaging documents.</p> <p>If the product is not a member of a product family, this field remains empty.</p>	
Type of packaging in contact with the product (container type)	<p>This field is used to indicate the material of container that is in contact with a product.</p> <p>Please note that the secondary packaging should be indicated, if relevant, in the field Description of secondary packaging (not in contact with the product), and not here.</p>	Open list
Size of packaging in contact with the product (container size)		
Size of packaging in contact with the product (container size)	<p>This field is used to indicate the size of the container that is in contact with a product. The minimum and maximum size must be indicated.</p> <p>Please note that the secondary packaging should be indicated, if relevant, in the field Description of secondary packaging (not in contact with the product).</p>	Range with open list (Decimal)
Size of packaging in contact with the product (container size)		
Material of packaging in contact with the product (container material)	<p>This field is used to indicate the material of the container that is in contact with a product. Additional text fields are available, when option plastic composite, metal, or other is selected.</p> <p>Please note that the secondary packaging should be indicated, if relevant, in the field Description of secondary packaging (not in contact with the product).</p>	Open list
Compatibility of the product with the packaging materials proposed to be in contact with the product	<p>This field is used to give any information that is needed to prove that the packaging material is compatible with the product.</p>	Text area
Further description of the packaging	<p>If needed, give any further explanations concerning the packaging being in contact with product.</p>	Text area

in contact with the product		
Safety features of the packaging	Any information that is related to safety of packaging should be described here, i.e. existence of a child-resistant fastening, labelling in such way that hazard can be identified by people with special needs, etc.).	Text area
Description of the secondary packaging (not in contact with the product)	This field is used to describe the secondary packaging, i.e. boxes, tape, and pallet stretch film that was used to get a product to a retail or distribution centre.	Text area
Packaging related attachments		
Type of attachment	This field is used to indicate the type of document which is attached. The option 'other' is available, with specification in the additional text field. This is the correct place to attach a picture of label of packaging.	Open list
Attached (confidential) document	The original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions. If a file is uploaded under this field (a) confidentiality claim(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.	Single file attachment
Attached (sanitised) documents for publication	<p>Provide any additional documents relevant for the submission, not already provided under the literature reference entity.</p> <p>For test guidelines that provide a reporting template (data analysis file), that file must be completed and can be uploaded here if not yet done in the results section.</p> <p>See IUCLID templates for PPP Risk Assessment Templates on EFSA Knowledge Junction (zenodo).</p> <p>Any additional background documents uploaded here must be uploaded in their public (non-confidential) version. The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised. Save for the elements blackened, if applicable, content and layout-wise the public version must be fully identical with the confidential version. Upon conclusion of the confidentiality assessment, if applicable, a revised public version removing the redactions relating to confidentiality requests that were rejected in part or in full must be uploaded here.</p>	Single file attachment

	Any document uploaded here must be uploaded in their public (non-confidential) version. The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised.	
Remarks	If needed, give any further explanations concerning attachment(s).	Text
Packaging related attachments		
Additional information on packaging	Please provide any additional information about the packaging.	Rich text area

2. Physical, chemical and technical properties of the plant protection product – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to report a short summary of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated.

Provide only the most relevant details for:

- Appearance
- Flammability (state purity)
- Explosive properties (state purity)
- Oxidizing properties (state purity)

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.PhysicalChemicalProperties		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
Legal entity flags	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	Provide a brief description of the phys-chem properties	Rich text area
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

2.1 Appearance (colour and odour) – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information about the colour and the physical state of the plant protection product.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.GeneralInformation		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
	Provide a description of the colour and of the physical state of the plant protection. Provide a description of both the colour, if any, and the physical state of both the active substance as manufactured and purified active substance. Report the purity and/or the specification of the test material and the guideline and method used	Rich text area
Key value for assessment		Header 1
Physical state at 20°C and 1013 hPa	Indicate state at room temperature and atmospheric pressure	Closed list
Form		Open list
Colour	Indicate colour	Multi select closed list
Colour intensity		Closed list
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

2.1 Appearance (colour and odour) – Endpoint study record

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide a description of the colour and of the physical state of the plant protection product.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.GeneralInformation		
Name	Instructions	Data Type

Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Physical state at 20°C and 1013 hPa	Indicate the physical state of the substance at 20°C and 1013 hPa, i.e. gaseous, liquid or solid. In the case of an aerosol (which means aerosol dispenser or aerosol generator), this field can be left empty. However, the type of aerosol dispenser should be reported in the field "Form". Note: The fields on Test Material Information (TMI) should be completed as far as possible even if the information provided is not derived from a study, but taken from non-experimental information. Create separate records if different physical states need to be reported.	Closed list with remarks
Form / colour / odour	This repeatable block is for recording the physical form of the substance odour and colour. Odour is not a data requirement under regulation (EC) No 1107/2009, provision of this information is optional. If the substance can have more than one of these properties, copy this block of fields or create additional records as appropriate.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Form	Select the physical form of the substance from the picklist, e.g. solid: particulate/powder, solid: nanomaterial, solid: compact, liquid: viscous, etc. If necessary, add further free text description in the adjacent text field, e.g. for further characterising a viscous liquid or an aerosol. The form selected should match with the physical state entered in field 'Physical state at 20°C and 1013 hPa'. The picklist provided is not exhaustive. It includes both comprehensive terms (e.g. 'solid: particulate/powder' or 'solid: nanomaterial') and more specific terms which should be used if possible (e.g. 'solid: flakes' or 'solid:	Open list with remarks

	<p>nanomaterial, low aspect ratio'). If substances or mixtures contained in aerosol dispensers are addressed within a specific regulatory framework (e.g. related to classification and labelling), indicate the type of aerosol dispenser.</p> <p>Refer to the guidance documents of the relevant regulatory framework as to the use of this or other template(s) for specifying the physical state, form and other properties of the submission substance during reasonably expected use.</p> <p>Please note: The field 'Test material form' provided in section 'Materials and methods' may be exceptionally obsolete for this template because details on the physical state and form are normally derived from non-experimental information, i.e. handbooks, SDS etc., or based on a visual inspection of the substance.</p>	
Colour	Describe the colour of the substance at 20°C and 1013 hPa. If other environmental conditions apply, specify them.	Multi-line text
Odour	Select the odour of the substance from picklist, e.g. biting, pungent, etc.	Open list
Form / colour / odour		
Substance type	Select as appropriate or use 'other:' to describe substance type if not available from picklist.	Open list
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

2.2 Explosive and oxidising properties

2.2.1 EXPLOSIVE PROPERTIES – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated.

Provide only the most relevant details e.g explosive properties (state purity).

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.Explosiveness		
Name	Instructions	Type

Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study records		Header 1
	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
		Rich text area
Key value for assessment		Header 1
Explosiveness	Select 'explosive', 'non explosive' or 'no information available'	Closed list
Justification for classification or non-classification		Header 1
	The available information should be compared against the classification criteria and the reasons for fulfilling or not fulfilling the classification criteria should be presented.	Rich Text
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information - common block "	Header 1

2.2.1 EXPLOSIVE PROPERTIES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to be used to report explosivity properties of the plant protection product, unless it can be justified that it is technically or scientifically not necessary to perform such studies.

A theoretical estimation based on structure shall be accepted if it meets the criteria set out in Appendix 6 of the United Nations' Recommendations on the Transport of Dangerous Goods Manual of Tests and Criteria.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Explosiveness		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data - common block "	Header 1

Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guideline: Method A.14 Explosive properties (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008) is relevant for this endpoint	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods and incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Small-scale preliminary tests	If a small-scale preliminary test was conducted (e.g. according to EU Method A.14), report the parameter and results. In field 'Remarks on result' you can indicate any qualitative results or if it was not determinable or measured. Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Parameter	Select the parameter measured to which the result value relates.	Open list with remarks
Value	Enter a numeric value to specify the result of the test.	Decimal
Number of fragments	For thermal sensitivity tests with fragmentation of the test tube, indicate the number of fragments.	Decimal
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Small-scale preliminary tests		
Results of test series for explosives	If a substance has explosive properties or is intended to function as explosive, the quantitative and/or qualitative outcome of the relevant tests should be recorded in this repeatable block of fields, as derived according to the test series indicated in the respective field.	

	In field 'Remarks on result' you can give a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived. Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Test series	Select the UN test series to which the result value relates. If the test data were derived by a competent authority, select the corresponding phrase.	Open list with remarks
Method	Select UN test method to which the result relates.	Open list
Parameter	Select the parameter measured to which the result value relates.	Open list with remarks
Value	Enter a numeric value to specify the result of the test.	Decimal
Result	Report the outcome of the test.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Results of test series for explosives		
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

United Nations New York and Geneva (2009) Publication ISBN 978-92-1-139135-0.
<https://unece.org/DAM/trans/danger/publi/manual/Rev5/English/ST-SG-AC10-11-Rev5-EN.pdf>

2.2.2 OXIDISING PROPERTIES – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.OxidisingProperties		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study records		Header 1
	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
		Reach text area
Key value for assessment		Header 1
Oxidising properties		Closed list
Justification for classification or non-classification		Header 1
	The available information should be compared against the classification criteria and the reasons for fulfilling or not fulfilling the classification criteria should be presented.	Rich Text
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

2.2.2 OXIDISING PROPERTIES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to be used to report the oxidising properties of plant protection product, unless it can be justified that it is technically or scientifically not necessary to perform such studies.

A theoretical estimation based on structure shall be accepted if it meets the criteria set out in Appendix 6 of the United Nations' Recommendations on the Transport of Dangerous Goods Manual of Tests and Criteria

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.OxidisingProperties		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Material and methods – common block"</p> <p>Applicable test guidelines:</p> <p>Solids: Method A.17 Oxidising properties (solids) (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008);</p> <p>Liquids: Method A.21 Oxidising properties (liquids) (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008); Test O.1: Test for oxidizing solids (UN RTDG Manual of Tests and Criteria ST/SG/AC.10/11/;</p> <p>Test O.2: Test for oxidizing liquids (UN RTDG Manual of Tests and Criteria ST/SG/AC.10/11/;</p> <p>Test O.3: Gravimetric test for oxidising solids (UN) (UN RTDG Manual of Tests and Criteria ST/SG/AC.10/11/Rev. 6;</p> <p>are relevant for this endpoint</p>	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Study design		Header 2
Contact with	Indicate the chemical with which the test substance was brought in contact. Use separate records for each oxidising or reducing agent tested.	Open list
Duration of test (contact time)	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with closed list (Decimal)
Details on methods	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary, particularly if no guideline was used. For instance, provide the temperature at which the test was started and indicate whether the test was conducted at temperatures expected during the normal use of the substance.	Text area
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1

Test results (Oxidising gases)	Indicate the type of the parameter measured, i.e. coefficient of oxygen equivalency (Ci), and the numeric results. As appropriate, enter remarks in the respective subfield and/or field 'Remarks on result'. Copy this block of fields for more than one parameter as appropriate.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Parameter	Select the parameter, e.g. coefficient of oxygen equivalency (Ci). Additional free text explanation can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list
Result	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Test results (Oxidising gases)		
Test results (Oxidising liquids)	Depending on the method used, indicate the type of sample tested, e.g. 1:1 sample-to-cellulose ratio, and the parameter measured in the respective subfield, e.g. 'mean pressure rise time'. Provide the mean value measured or a range if reported so, and the unit of measurement. As appropriate, enter remarks in the respective subfield and/or field 'Remarks on result'. Copy this block of fields for more than one parameter as appropriate, i.e. to record the maximum burning rate of both the test mixture and the reference mixture.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Sample tested	Select the type of sample tested from drop-down list, e.g. 1:1 sample-to-cellulose ratio. Additional free text explanation can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Parameter	Select the parameter, e.g. maximum burning rate. Additional free text explanation can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list
Result	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'.	Range with open list (Decimal)

	Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Test results (Oxidising liquids)		
Test results (Oxidising solids)	Depending on the method used, indicate the type of sample tested, e.g. 1:1 sample-to-cellulose ratio, and the parameter measured in the respective subfield, e.g. 'mean pressure rise time'. Provide the mean value measured or a range if reported so, and the unit of measurement. As appropriate, enter remarks in the respective subfield and/or field 'Remarks on result'. Copy this block of fields for more than one parameter as appropriate, i.e. to record the maximum burning rate of both the test mixture and the reference mixture.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Sample tested	Select the type of sample tested from drop-down list, e.g. 1:1 sample-to-cellulose ratio. Additional free text explanation can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Parameter	Select the parameter, e.g. maximum burning rate. Additional free text explanation can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list
Result	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)

Test results (Oxidising solids)		
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

2.3 Flash point and other indications of flammability or spontaneous ignition

2.3.1 FLASH POINT – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details, e.g. temperature.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.Flashpoint		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study records		Header 1
	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
		Reach text area
Key value for assessment		Header 1

Flash point	Enter the temperature for flashpoint. Provide a unique numeric value to be used in the assessment. A justification for why this specific value was selected should be provided in the field "Additional information". You may provide a numeric range in the field "Description of key information".	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
at the pressure of	Provide pressure value and unit measure. Usually, the flash point is provided at 101,325 Pa (1 atm).	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

2.3.2 FLASH POINT – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to be used to report the flash point of liquids which contain flammable solvents or the flammability of solid plant protection products and gases. A theoretical estimation based on structure shall be accepted if it meets the criteria set out in Appendix 6 of the United Nations Recommendations on the Transport of Dangerous Goods Manual of Tests and Criteria.

Flash point must be determined, unless it can be justified that it is technically or scientifically not necessary to perform such studies.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.FlashPoint		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: Method A.9 Flash-point (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008) Test methods according to table 2.6.3 of Annex I, Part 2 of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (liquids)	Header 1
Flash point apparatus	Indicate the apparatus used for determining the flash point.	Open list with remarks
Dynamic viscosity of test material	For viscous liquids, report the dynamic viscosity of the test material at 20°C (mPa s) and verify that the method chosen is valid according to the criteria given in the relevant test guideline.	Multi-line text
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2

Results and discussion		Header 1
Flash point	Enter mean flash point or range if reported so, normally determined at 1013 hPa. If necessary, copy this block of fields for each pressure condition at which the flash point was determined.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Flash point	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with closed list (Decimal)
Atm. press.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Flash point		
Sustaining combustibility	If a sustaining combustibility test was conducted, specify the test procedure used and report the test result. If necessary, copy this block of fields for test run.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Test procedure	Specify the test procedure used.	Open list with remarks
Result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results - indicating why no result could be determined, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Sustaining combustibility		

Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

United Nations New York and Geneva (2009) Publication ISBN 978-92-1-139135-0.
<https://unece.org/DAM/trans/danger/publi/manual/Rev5/English/ST-SG-AC10-11-Rev5-EN.pdf>

2.3.2 FLAMMABILITY – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.Flammability		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study records		Header 1
	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
		Reach text area
Key value for assessment		Header 1
Flammability	Indicate 'flammable', 'pyrophoric', 'substances and mixtures which in contact with water emit flammable gases', 'not classified'	Closed list

Justification for classification or non-classification		Header 1
	The available information should be compared against the classification criteria and the reasons for fulfilling or not fulfilling the classification criteria should be presented.	Rich Text
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

2.3.2 FLAMMABILITY – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to report information on flammability of the plant protection product, unless it can be justified that it is technically or scientifically not necessary to perform such studies.

The flammability of solid plant protection products and gases must be determined and reported. A theoretical estimation based on structure shall be accepted if it meets the criteria set out in Appendix 6 of the United Nations' Recommendations on the Transport of Dangerous Goods Manual of Tests and Criteria.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Flammability		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: Methods A.10 Flammability (solids), A.11 Flammability (gases), A.12 Flammability (contact with water) (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008) Test N.1: test method for readily combustible solids (UN RTDG Manual of Tests and Criteria ST/SG/AC.10/11/	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Flammable gases (Lower and upper explosion limit)	Depending on the information requirement addressed in field 'Endpoint' the respective block of fields should be used for recording study results. Please note that flammable liquids are not covered by this section, but should be recorded in section 'Flash point'.	

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

	<p>If a gas was tested for flammability, report the lower and upper explosion limit, sometimes also referred to as lower and upper flammability limit. If a calculation method was used fill in the results as far as possible.</p> <p>In field 'Remarks on result' you can indicate if no flammability occurred (no flammable range with air at 20°C and a standard pressure of 101.3 kPa) or if it was not determinable or measured.</p> <p>Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values.</p>	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Parameter	Select the parameter from drop-down list, i.e. lower explosion limit or upper explosion limit.	Open list with remarks
Value	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks on result	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; <p>or</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Flammable gases (Lower and upper explosion limit)		
Aerosols	<p>Depending on the information requirement addressed in field 'Endpoint' the respective block of fields should be used for recording study results. Please note that flammable liquids are not covered by this section, but should be recorded in section 'Flash point'.</p> <p>If an aerosol (which means an aerosol dispenser) was tested for flammability, indicate the type of aerosol tested, the respective test parameter and the result.</p> <p>In field 'Remarks on result' you can indicate for instance if no ignition occurred or if it was not determinable or measured.</p> <p>Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values.</p>	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Type of aerosol tested	Indicate the type of aerosol dispenser tested, i.e. 'aerosol dispenser: foam aerosol' or 'aerosol dispenser: spray aerosol'. Select 'aerosol dispenser:	Open list with remarks

	not specified' if the type is not specified. Specific test parameters apply depending on the aerosol type.	
Content of flammable components (%)	Specify the content of flammable components in %. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Test parameter	Select the parameter from drop-down list.	Open list with remarks
Value	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Aerosols		
Flammable solids	Depending on the information requirement addressed in field 'Endpoint' the respective block of fields should be used for recording study results. Please note that flammable liquids are not covered by this section, but should be recorded in section 'Flash point'. If a solid was tested for flammability, report the test procedure used and the measured burning time. In field 'Remarks on result' you can indicate if no flammability occurred or if it was not determinable or measured. Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Test procedure	Select the parameter from drop-down list, i.e. burning rate test: preliminary screening test, burning rate test over 100 mm length, burning rate test with wetted zone, burning time over 250 mm for metal powders or metal alloys.	Open list with remarks
Burning time	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with closed list (Decimal)
Moisture (wt %)	Enter a numeric value to specify the moisture as wt %.	Decimal
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived;	Open list with remarks (2000)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	
Flammable solids		
Pyrophoric solids	<p>Depending on the information requirement addressed in field 'Endpoint' the respective block of fields should be used for recording study results. Please note that flammable liquids are not covered by this section, but should be recorded in section 'Flash point'.</p> <p>If a pyrophoric solid was tested for flammability, report the test procedure used and the measured result, i.e. ignition time on contact with air.</p> <p>In field 'Remarks on result' you can indicate if no ignition occurred or if it was not determinable or measured.</p> <p>Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values.</p>	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Test procedure	Select the parameter from drop-down list, i.e. ignition time on contact with air.	Open list with remarks
Result	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Temp.	Enter a numeric value to specify the air temperature.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Relative air humidity (%)	Enter a numeric value to specify the relative air humidity in %.	Decimal
Remarks on result	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Pyrophoric solids		
Pyrophoric liquids	<p>Depending on the information requirement addressed in field 'Endpoint' the respective block of fields should be used for recording study results. Please note that flammable liquids are not covered by this section, but should be recorded in section 'Flash point'.</p> <p>If a pyrophoric liquid was tested for flammability, report the test procedure used and the measured result, i.e. ignition time on contact with air.</p>	

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	In field 'Remarks on result' you can indicate if no ignition occurred or if it was not determinable or measured. Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Test procedure	Select the parameter from drop-down list, i.e. ignition time on contact with air or effect on filter paper.	Open list with remarks
Result	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Temp.	Enter a numeric value to specify the air temperature.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Relative air humidity (%)	Enter a numeric value to specify the relative air humidity in %.	Decimal
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Pyrophoric liquids		
Self-heating substances / mixtures	Depending on the information requirement addressed in field 'Endpoint' the respective block of fields should be used for recording study results. Please note that flammable liquids are not covered by this section, but should be recorded in section 'Flash point'. If a self-heating substance / mixture was tested for oxidative self-heating, report the test procedure used and the result. Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values for each test procedure used.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Test procedure	Select the parameter from drop-down list, i.e. 25 mm sample cube at 140°C, 100 mm sample cube at 140°C, 100 mm sample cube at 120°C or 100 mm sample cube at 100°C.	Open list with remarks
Max. temp. reached	Enter a numeric value to specify the maximum temperature reached.	Decimal
Induction time (h)	Enter a numeric value to specify the induction time.	Decimal

Result	Report the outcome of test using the test criteria and method of assessing results of the relevant (e.g. UN) test method.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Self-heating substances / mixtures		
Substances / mixtures which in contact with water emit flammable gases	Depending on the information requirement addressed in field 'Endpoint' the respective block of fields should be used for recording study results. Please note that flammable liquids are not covered by this section, but should be recorded in section 'Flash point'. If a substance / mixture was tested for release of flammable gas, report the test procedure, i.e. step according to the test guideline (i.e. UN Test N.5) and the maximum release rate. In field 'Remarks on result' you can indicate if no ignition occurred or if it was not determinable or measured. Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values. In field 'Remarks on result' you can indicate if no ignition occurred or if it was not determinable or measured. Copy this block of fields for specifying the relevant values.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Test procedure	Select the step(s) of the test procedure from the multiple drop-down list.	Multi select open list with remarks
Max. rate of gas release	Enter a numeric value to specify the maximum rate of gas release.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Identity of evolved gas	If gas evolved specify the identity or, if not known, select 'unknown'.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)

Substances / mixtures which in contact with water emit flammable gases		
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

United Nations New York and Geneva (2009) Publication ISBN 978-92-1-139135-0.
<https://unece.org/DAM/trans/danger/publi/manual/Rev5/English/ST-SG-AC10-11-Rev5-EN.pdf>

2.3.3 SPONTANEOUS IGNITION – ENDPOINT SUMMARY**Purpose**

This document is to be used to summarise the most of the relevant study(-ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Provide only the most relevant details e.g. state purity.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.AutoFlammability		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study records		Header 1
	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
		Reach text area

Key value for assessment		Header 1
Autoflammability / Self-ignition temperature	Provide a unique numeric value to be used in the assessment. A justification for why this specific value was selected should be provided in the field "Additional information". You may provide a numeric range in the field "Description of key information".	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
at the pressure of	Provide pressure value and unit measure. Usually the autoflammability/self-ignition temperature is provided at 101 325 Pa (1 atm).	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
No self-ignition	Check this box if the substance does not self-ignite / is not autoflammable, and therefore an autoflammability / self-ignition temperature value cannot be reported.	Checkbox
Justification for classification or non-classification		Header 1
	The available information should be compared against the classification criteria and the reasons for fulfilling or not fulfilling the classification criteria should be presented.	Rich Text
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

2.3.3 SPONTANEOUS IGNITION – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to be used to report the self-heating of the plant protection product, unless it can be justified that it is technically or scientifically not necessary to perform such studies.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AutoFlammability		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: Methods A.15 Auto-ignition temperature (liquids and gases), A16 Relative self-ignition temperature for solids, (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008) Test N.4: test method for self-heating substances (UN RTDG Manual of Tests and Criteria ST/SG/AC.10/11/	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2

Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Auto-ignition temperature (liquids / gases)	Enter the auto-ignition temperature for liquids or gases, i.e. the lowest temperature at which the test substance will ignite in contact with air under the conditions defined in the test method. Also indicate the atmospheric pressure at which it was determined in the respective subfield. If necessary, copy this block of fields for each condition.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Auto-ignition temperature	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with closed list (Decimal)
Atm. Press.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with 343emark (2000)
Auto-ignition temperature (liquids / gases)		
Relative self-ignition temperature (solids)	Enter the relative self-ignition temperature for solids, i.e. the minimum ambient temperature at which a certain volume of a substance will ignite under defined conditions. If necessary, copy this block of fields for each condition.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Relative self-ignition temperature	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with closed list (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; 	Open list with 343emark (2000)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	
Relative self-ignition temperature (solids)		
Self-ignition temperature of dust accumulation	Enter the self-ignition temperature for a dust, i.e. the lowest temperature, at which under specified test conditions a dust accumulation under the influence of high temperature in the surroundings will just be ignited by self-heating. The self-ignition temperature of a dust accumulation depends on the volume and the shape of the dust sample. Therefore the field 'Volume / surface ratio (m)' should be completed as well. If necessary, copy this block of fields for each condition.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Self-ignition temperature	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with closed list (Decimal)
Volume / surface ratio (m)	Enter a numeric value to specify the volume / surface ratio (unit: m).	Decimal
Remarks on result	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with 344emark (2000)
Self-ignition temperature of dust accumulation		
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1

Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1
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Links to supporting material:

United Nations New York and Geneva (2009) Publication ISBN 978-92-1-139135-0.
<https://unece.org/DAM/trans/danger/publi/manual/Rev5/English/ST-SG-AC10-11-Rev5-EN.pdf>

2.4 Acidity, alkalinity and if necessary pH value – Endpoint summary**Purpose**

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated.

Provide only the most relevant details e.g. state purity, pH.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.pH		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page"	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	Conclude on the pH of the product/preparation.	Text
Key value for assessment		Header 1
pH is not relevant	Check the box if pH is not relevant and complete the justification below	Check box
Justification		Closed list
pH value	Provide pH value a range can be reported	Range (Decimal)
Solution concentration (%)		Decimal
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block ". Provide additional information related to the endpoint. If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.	Header 1

2.4 Acidity, alkalinity and if necessary pH value – Endpoint study record**Purpose**

This document is to report information on acidity, alkalinity and pH of the plant protection product, unless it can be justified that it is technically or scientifically not necessary to perform such studies.

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In the case of aqueous plant protection products, the pH value of the neat plant protection product shall be determined and reported.

In the case of solid and non-aqueous liquid plant protection products which are to be applied as aqueous dilutions the pH of a 1 % dilution of the plant protection product shall be determined and reported.

In the case of plant protection products which are acidic (pH < 4) or alkaline (pH > 10) the acidity or alkalinity shall be determined and reported.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.pH		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Reagents		Header 2
Reagent	Select as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.	Open list
Titration of acidity and alkalinity		Header 2
Details on titrant used	Use free text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant. Note that any information that can be claimed confidential should be included in the subsequent field 'Confidential details on test material'. Explanations: - Volume of titrant used is usually expressed in mL	Text template
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
pH value	Enter mean pH value or range if reported so and indicate the temperature and concentration at which the pH was determined. If necessary, copy this block of fields for different conditions	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
pH value	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)

Temp.	Enter a numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Concentration	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
pH value		
Acidity or alkalinity	Enter the information on acidity or alkalinity. If necessary, copy this block of fields for different conditions.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Acidity or alkalinity	Enter a numeric value or a range of numeric values according to following conventions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) In the first numeric field, enter a single value (Qualifier subfield left blank) or a value if preceded by '>', '>=' or 'ca.' (e.g. '2', 'ca. 2', '>2'). (ii) In the second numeric field, enter a single value if preceded by '<' or '<='. (iii) Use both numeric fields and, as required, the lower and upper qualifier field to enter a range of numeric values (e.g. '2 - 8' or '>2 <8'). Please note: These are examples only. <p>Allowed values are defined for each numeric field.</p>	Closed list
Value	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Acidity or alkalinity		

Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

2.5 Viscosity and surface tension

2.5.1 VISCOSITY – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated. Conclude on the viscosity of the product/preparation.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.Viscosity		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint
Description of key information		Header 1
	If all key information is provided in the linked study records, this field can be left empty. In case there is no linked study record, or in case you want to point to specific information in the linked study record, provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here. The summary could include, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the test type 	Text (rich-text area)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) ▪ the test organism ▪ the exposure duration ▪ other contextual information on the origin of the key value 	
Key value for assessment		Header 1
Viscosity		Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
at the temperature of		Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Additional information	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Additional information – common block"</p> <p>Provide additional information related to the endpoint. If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.</p>	Header 1

2.5.1 VISCOSITY – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to report information on the viscosity of the plant protection product, unless it can be justified that it is technically or scientifically not necessary to perform such studies.

For liquid formulations the viscosity shall be determined at two shear rates and at 20°C and 40°C and reported together with the test conditions.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Viscosity		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Standard covering the apparatus used	<p>Indicate the standard which covers apparatus used in the method (ISO, DIN, DIN ISO, ASTM, CIPAC, national standard or other).</p> <p>A list of such possible standards is provided in the OECD Guideline 114, section 'Description of the Method – Apparatus'.</p>	Text area
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2

Viscosity	<p>If applicable, enter mean viscosity value or range if reported so and indicate the temperature at measurement in the respective subfield. If necessary, copy this block of fields for each temperature.</p> <p>Note specific to viscosity of liquids: For non-Newtonian fluids the results obtained are preferred in table or graph form, in the order of increasing shear rates. Include table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'.</p> <p>Upload image file in field 'Illustration (picture/graph)'.</p>	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Temp.	Select the appropriate value of temperature. If not available from the picklist, select 'other' and specify.	Open list
Shear rate	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal) with unit
Parameter	Indicate the parameter measured.	Open list
Value	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Remarks on result	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Viscosity		
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

2.5.2 SURFACE TENSION – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated.

Provide only the most relevant details e.g. Surface tension

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.SurfaceTension		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study records		Header 1
	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
		Reach text area
Key value for assessment		Header 1
Surface tension	Provide a unique numeric value to be used in the assessment. A justification for why this specific value was selected should be provided in the field "Additional information". You may provide a numeric range in the field "Description of key information".	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
at the temperature of		Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
at the concentration of		Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Critical micelle concentration (CMC)		Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

2.5.2 SURFACE TENSION – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to be used to report the surface tension of the PPP, unless it can be justified that it is technically or scientifically not necessary to perform such studies. For liquid plant protection products containing ≥ 10 % hydrocarbons and for which the kinematic viscosity is less than 7×10^{-6} m²/sec at 40 °C the surface tension of the neat formulation shall be determined at 25 °C and reported.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SurfaceTension		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guidelines: Method A.5 Surface tension (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008) OECD Test Guideline 115: Surface tension of aqueous solutions	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Study design		Header 2
Details on methods	Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary. Use freetext template as appropriate.	Text template
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Surface tension	Enter mean surface tension or range if reported so and indicate the temperature and test substance concentration in the respective subfields. If necessary, copy this block of fields.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Surface tension	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Temp.	Enter numeric value and unit.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Conc.	Enter numeric value and unit.	Unit measure with Open List (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived;	Open list with remarks (2000)

	- giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	
Surface tension		
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

2.6 Storage stability and shelf life

2.6.1 (CF. 1.7 AND 3) USE CONCENTRATION

2.6.2 EFFECTS OF TEMPERATURE AND PACKAGING – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the optimal temperature and packaging required to ensure the storage stability of the plant protection product in line with the recommended maximum shelf life. If the shelf life is less than two years, the shelf life in months must also be reported.

Information of the effects of light, temperature, and humidity should be summarised, as well as the effect of low temperatures on physical stability for liquid preparations.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.StabilityThermal		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1

Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint
Description of key information		Header 1
	<p>If all key information is provided in the linked study records, this field can be left empty. In case there is no linked study record, or in case you want to point to specific information in the linked study record, provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here.</p> <p>The summary could include, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ the test type ▪ the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) ▪ the test organism ▪ the exposure duration ▪ other contextual information on the origin of the key value 	Text (rich-text area)
Justification for classification or non-classification		Header 1
	The available information should be compared against the classification criteria and the reasons for fulfilling or not fulfilling the classification criteria should be presented.	Text area
Additional information	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Additional information – common block"</p> <p>Provide additional information related to the endpoint. If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.</p>	Header 1

2.6.2 EFFECTS OF TEMPERATURE AND PACKAGING – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to be used to report information under the specified storage conditions on:

- The physical stability of the preparation during and after storage at the recommended temperature and, for liquid preparations, at low temperatures, evaluated using tests in the original packaging.
- The content of the active substance (microorganism), which must comply with the minimum and maximum certified content declared by the applicant before and after storage at the recommended temperature and, if applicable, at low temperatures.
- The growth of any relevant contaminating micro-organisms before and after storage at the recommended temperature, described using appropriate microbiological units (e.g., number of active units per volume or weight, CFU, international units per volume or weight, or other relevant measures).
- The presence of metabolites of concern identified in accordance with point 2.8 of Part B of the Annex to Regulation (EU) No 283/2013, before and after storage.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.StabilityThermal

Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Study design		Header 2
Details on methods	<p>Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary, particularly if no guideline was used.</p> <p>For example, the packaging materials used in the storage stability testing.</p>	Text area
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
For thermal stability study		Header 2
Test substance thermally stable	<p>Indicate whether the test substance was stable under the test conditions or not. Describe any details on results in field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'.</p> <p>The melting point should be recorded in the corresponding data entry screen.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Operating temperature	<p>Provide the operating temperature or range at which the thermal stability was determined. For comparison reason, the data should be recorded in degree C. If reported in other units, it is recommended to convert to °C. By copying this block of fields both the original and converted value(s) can be entered.</p> <p>If analytical method is used to determine the concentration, provide method details including method validation data in fields 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables' and attach all relevant chromatograms in field 'Attached background materials'.</p>	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Operating temp.	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range with closed list (Decimal)

Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Operating temperature		
Sublimation	Indicate whether sublimation occurred.	Closed list with remarks
Transformation products	Indicate whether transformation products occurred. If yes, provide the identified transformation products in following block of fields. Any further details can be entered in field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'.	Closed list with remarks
Identity of transformation products	Indicate the identity of the transformation products using an appropriate identifier, e.g. CAS number, CAS name, IUPAC name. Copy this block of fields for each relevant substance. Any further details on transformation products can be provided in field 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables'.	
No.	For easier distinction select a consecutive number for each transformation product from drop-down list if more than one transformation product is entered. If the same substance is identified by more than one identifier (e.g. by CAS name and Common name), make sure that the same number is allocated to these entries.	Closed list
Reference substance	Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name. If not available in the inventory, create a new one.	Entity reference field
Parent compound(s)	If the compound is a transformation product, link to the identity of the substance that is characterised as the parent of this transformation product. Link to multiple parent substances if applicable. Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name. If not available in the inventory, create a new one.	Link to entity (multiple)
Maximum occurrence (%)	Indicate the maximum occurrence of the transformation product.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Identity of transformation products		
For study on stability to sunlight		Header 2
Test substance stable to sunlight	Indicate whether the test substance was stable under the test conditions or not. Describe any details on results in field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'.	Closed list with remarks

For study on stability to metals		Header 2
Test substance stable to metals / metal ions	Indicate whether the test substance was sensitive to contact with metals or metal ions under the test conditions or not. Describe any details on results in field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'.	Closed list with remarks
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

2.6.3 OTHER FACTORS AFFECTING STABILITY – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the effect of exposure to air, light, and similar factors on the plant protection product's stability.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.StorageStability		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint
Description of key information		Header 1
	If all key information is provided in the linked study records, this field can be left empty. In case there is no	Text (rich-text area)

	<p>linked study record, or in case you want to point to specific information in the linked study record, provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here.</p> <p>The summary could include, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ the test type ▪ the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) ▪ the test organism ▪ the exposure duration ▪ other contextual information on the origin of the key value 	
Additional information	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Additional information – common block"</p> <p>Provide additional information related to the endpoint. If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.</p>	Header 1

2.6.3 OTHER FACTORS AFFECTING STABILITY – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose

This document is to be used to report the effect of exposure to air, light, and similar factors on the plant protection product’s stability. It should also include the optimal moisture conditions required to ensure storage stability. For dry preparations, describe the effects of contaminating water on the viability of the micro-organism. This information may be provided either by direct measurement of moisture content before and after storage or by describing packaging integrity and microorganism viability before and after storage.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.StorageStability		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Material and methods – common block"</p> <p>Applicable test guidelines: CIPAC Methods MT 39, MT 48, MT 51 or MT 54 as appropriate</p>	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Study design		Header 2
Type of container material	<p>Indicate the overall results with regard to storage stability or reactivity towards container material.</p> <p>Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. Any additional information can be provided in the supplementary remarks text.</p>	Open list with remarks
Details on study design	<p>Using the freetext template (delete/add elements as appropriate) describe the test procedure and conditions. If the test product is to be supplied in different packaging, test results for each type should be provided (possibly in separate records if appropriate).</p> <p>Explanations:</p>	Text template

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ PACKAGING: Describe the type of container (e.g. can, spray, bottle, sachet, etc.) used in the study, the pack size and approximate empty weight or volume. ▪ TEST CONDITIONS: Report the study duration, the time at sampling, temperature and humidity recorded at regular intervals (e.g. average monthly values or monthly maximum/minimum values). Add any other relevant parameters as appropriate. ▪ ANALYTICAL METHODS: If the active ingredient was analysed in storage stability studies, describe the method used and/or refer to the record in the submission where the validated analytical method of the active ingredient is described. Also note any relevant handling of test samples prior to sampling (e.g. shaking). ▪ OTHER: Include any other relevant information. 	
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block".</p>	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Results	<p>Briefly summarise relevant observations test results. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate depending on the type of study. Where appropriate include table(s) in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>As appropriate also attach any figures in field 'Attached background material'.</p>	Text template
Transformation products	<p>Transformation products BLOCK (OHT)</p> <p>Indicate whether transformation products occurred. If yes, provide the identified transformation products in following block of fields. Any further details can be entered in field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Identity of transformation products	<p>Indicate the identity of the transformation products using an appropriate identifier, e.g. CAS number, CAS name, IUPAC name. Copy this block of fields for each relevant substance.</p> <p>Any further details on transformation products can be provided in field 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables'.</p>	
No.	<p>For easier distinction select a consecutive number for each transformation product from drop-down list if more than one transformation product is entered. If the same substance is identified by more than one identifier (e.g.</p>	Closed list

	by CAS name and Common name), make sure that the same number is allocated to these entries.	
Reference substance	Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name. If not available in the inventory, create a new one.	Entity reference field
Parent compound(s)	If the compound is a transformation product, link to the identity of the substance that is characterised as the parent of this transformation product. Link to multiple parent substances if applicable. Click the Link button to navigate to the Substances Inventory and select the relevant substance name. If not available in the inventory, create a new one.	Link to entity (multiple)
Maximum occurrence (%)	Indicate the maximum occurrence of the transformation product.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Identity of transformation products		
Storage stability / reactivity towards container material	Indicate the overall results with regard to storage stability or reactivity towards container material. If not listed select 'other:' and specify. Any additional information can be provided in the supplementary remarks text. Multiple selection is possible.	Multi select open list with remarks
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

OECD Guidance Document on storage stability of microbial pest control products
[http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono\(2016\)54&doclanguage=en](http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono(2016)54&doclanguage=en)

Technical Monograph n°17 Guidelines for Specifying the Shelf Life of Plant Protection Products
<https://croplife.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/Technical-Monograph-17-2nd-edition-June-2009.pdf>

2.7 Technical characteristics of the plant protection product

Purpose

This document is to be used to report the technical characteristics of the plant protection product at appropriate concentrations, including the wettability of solid plant protection products which are diluted for use; the persistence of foaming of plant protection products to be diluted with water; the suspensibility of water dispersible plant protection product; the spontaneity of dispersion of water dispersible plant protection products; the dispersion stability of plant protection products such as aqueous suspo-emulsions (SE); oil-based suspension concentrates (OD) or emulsifiable granules (EG); dry sieve test and wet sieve, where applicable; particle size distribution (dustable and wettable powders, granules), content of dust/fines (granules), attrition and friability (granules), when applicable; emulsifiability, re-emulsifiability and emulsion stability, when applicable; flowability, pourability (rinsability) and dustability, when applicable.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.TechnicalCharacteristics		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Administrative data – common block"</p> <p>This document can be used to report the following endpoints (complete a separate document for each endpoint):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wettability - Persistent foaming - Suspensibility, spontaneity of dispersion and dispersion stability - Dry sieve test and wet sieve test - Particle size distribution, dust content, attrition and friability - Emulsifiability, re-emulsifiability, emulsion stability - Flowability, pourability (rinsability), dustability. <p>Where necessary data waiving can be used for an endpoint.</p>	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Study type	This field is used to specify which technical characteristic is going to be described in the study.	Open list
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussions		Header 1

Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

2.7.1 (CF. 2.7) WETTABILITY

2.7.2 (CF. 2.7) PERSISTENT FOAMING

2.7.3 (CF. 2.7) SUSPENSIBILITY, SPONTANEITY OF DISPERSION AND DISPERSION STABILITY

2.7.4 (CF. 2.7) DRY SIEVE TEST AND WET SIEVE TEST

2.7.5 (CF. 2.7) PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION (DUSTABLE AND WETTABLE POWDERS, GRANULES), CONTENT OF DUST/FINES (GRANULES), ATTRITION AND FRIABILITY (GRANULES)

2.7.6 (CF. 2.7) EMULSIFIABILITY, RE-EMULSIFIABILITY AND EMULSION STABILITY

2.7.7 (CF. 2.7) FLOWABILITY, POURABILITY (RINSABILITY) AND DUSTABILITY

2.8 Physical, chemical compatibility with other products including plant protection products with which its use is to be authorized

Purpose

This document is to be used to report the physical and chemical compatibility of the plant protection product with other plant protection products or adjuvants indicated for use in the same recommended tank mixes, as stated on the label. Compatibility must be determined and documented unless, after examining the individual properties of the plant protection product, it is established that no reaction can occur. In such cases, provide a clear justification for not performing practical compatibility tests.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.PhysicalChemicalCompatibility		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Administrative data – common block"</p> <p>Separate documents can be created for each endpoint (Chemical, Physical)</p> <p>Use the remarks to indicate the endpoint covered by the document</p>	Header 1

Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Type of compatibility of the biocidal product with other products including biocidal products with which its use is to be authorised		Header 2
	This field is used to specify which type of compatibility is going to be described in the study. Physical compatibility or chemical compatibility is the available option. For microorganisms biological compatibility can also be indicated.	Closed list
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussions		Header 1
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

[2.8.1 \(CF. 2.8\) PHYSICAL COMPATIBILITY](#)[2.8.2 \(CF. 2.8\) CHEMICAL COMPATIBILITY](#)

2.9 Adherence and distribution to seeds, and additional physico-chemical information - Endpoint summary

Purpose

This documents is to be used to summarise information of the most relevant study(ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated.

Provide a summary only of the most relevant details for other physico-chemical properties which cannot be reported in other summaries. This would include e.g. adherence and distribution to seeds; physical and chemical compatibility with other products including plant protection products with which its use is to be authorised; supplementary studies necessary for the classification of the plant protection product by hazard shall be carried out in accordance with Regulation (EC) 1272/2008; determination of the dissolution rate of the water-soluble bag; effectiveness of cleaning procedures etc.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.AdditionalPhysicoChemical		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study records		Header 1
	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Description of key information		Header 1
		Reach text area
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information - common block "	Header 1

2.9 Adherence and distribution to seeds, and additional physico-chemical information – Endpoint study record

Purpose

This document can be used to report studies on any physical, chemical and technical properties of the plant protection product not covered by the other documents in this section. **In the case of plant protection products for seed treatment, distribution and adhesion of the plant protection should be reported.**

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AdditionalPhysicoChemical		
Name	Instructions	Data type

Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Note: See Guidance on physical, chemical and technical properties - SANCO/10473/2003 – rev.5 - October 2021	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Results	Report the results of the test(s) performed. Include an interpretation of the results in field 'Conclusions'.	Text area
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

3. Data on application

3.1 Data on application (GAP)

Purpose

The Good Agricultural Practice (GAP) describes the intended or registered safe use of plant protection products, according to Article 3(2)(a) of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005. The different fields required to define the use of the plant protection product unambiguously are listed in Table 4.

The IUCLID GAP form implements the following data requirements:

- Details of intended use
- Application rate
- Method of application
- Number and timing of applications and duration of protection
- Necessary waiting periods or other precautions to avoid phytotoxic effects on succeeding crops

If you click on the red plus sign next to the header 'x Good agricultural practices (GAP)' you can create a new GAP. A name will be assigned automatically to the GAP, containing as default name 'Good agricultural practices (GAP)' followed by a dot and three numbers.

Please note that separate GAP documents need to be created, if the GAPs differ in one or more of the parameters. For some fields multiple options from a picklist can be selected. Please read carefully below the instructions to see whether in a given case a separate GAP document needs to be created or whether it is appropriate to describe the different use options in one form.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.GAP	
Name	Instructions
Administrative data	
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .
Product	This field is mandatory. Click on the red plus sign to select the appropriate mixture composition document If not available in the inventory, create first a new one. In general, the GAP has to be completed for the target a.s., i.e. the a.s. for which the approval/renewal of the approval is requested or for which the MRL application is submitted. If the product contains a second (non-target) a.s., it is not required to provide a separate GAP form for the second a.s.
Description of key information	The free text field can be used to give a short explanation/description of the GAP. This information is not mandatory. For GAPs that involve different application methods at different growth stages (e.g. drench application at sowing followed by foliar application at a later growth stage), the GAP should be split in separate GAPs (in the example the first GAP being the drench application, the second the foliar use). In this field, the GAPs belonging to a sequential application should be labelled (e.g. GAP 1 of 2, GAP 2 of 2).
Purpose of the GAP	

Active substance / microorganism / basic substance applications	<p>Select the term that describes the purpose of the GAP. Not relevant for EU PPP MRL applications.</p> <p>For existing uses (D2 document), indicate "authorised use" in this field; otherwise the document will be interpreted as for an intended use (D1).</p>
MRL applications	<p>Select the term that describes the purpose of the GAP. Only relevant for EU PPP MRL applications.</p>
Crop information	
Crop/treated object	<p>Information on the crop/treated object is mandatory. A picklist is implemented to describe the crop or object to be treated with the product. The picklist is based on EPPO codes which have been enhanced with additional information to make them more user friendly/self-explanatory. The extended EPPO codes cover the following types of information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the first 5 digits are the EPPO code (see EPPO Plant Protection Thesaurus at http://eppt.eppo.org) (e.g. PIBSX), - followed by the scientific name of the crop (PIBSX <i>Pisum sativum</i>); - in brackets, the crop name in English is reported (PIBSX <i>Pisum sativum</i> (English pea); - for the most important crops, the corresponding food code of the MRL food classification is reported after a dash (code of Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005). For some crops, more than one food code is applicable (e.g. PIBSX <i>Pisum sativum</i> (English pea) - 0260030, 0260040, 0300030). <p>In the current version of IUCLID, the link with the food codes of the MRL legislation has been established only for codes listed in Part A of Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005; food codes listed in Part B of Annex I to, the connection to the crop code has not yet been implemented (the link will be included in the next release of IUCLID).</p> <p>Please note that not for all codes all four name elements are available.</p> <p>To find the codes for the crop/object, the user can either use the hierarchy search tool which requests to choose between crops or treated products. Alternatively, a text string (e.g. the EPPO code, the scientific name) can be directly entered in the search window, resulting in a subset of matching options.</p> <p>In the hierarchy tool, the user should first select between the two highest hierarchy levels 'crops' or 'treated product'. Treated products is relevant only for post-harvest uses and for uses on non-crop objects (e.g. treatment of railways).</p> <p>As a next step, a text string (EPPO code, scientific name, name of the crop in English or the food code of the MRL legislation) can be inserted. EPPO codes matching with the search term are displayed in yellow, and the user should select the relevant one.</p> <p>For post-harvest treatment of food products, two EPPO codes are available (HARFO and HARPO) which were combined with all food codes (Part A) of Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If the treatment with the product is intended on the fresh harvested product (e.g. oranges), the code combining HARFO and the respective food code should be selected (e.g. 3HARFO – Oranges – 011020). - For GAPs describing a use on a processed harvested product (e.g. raisins), the code HARPO in combination with the food code should be used (e.g. 3HARPO – Table grapes – 0151010).

	<p>In general, codes for crop groups should not be selected. Instead the EPPO codes for the individual crops should be chosen. A multiple selection of crop codes is allowed, only if all parameters of the GAP are identical for all crops selected. If the GAPs differ for the individual crops in one or several fields, a separate GAP form needs to be completed. To facilitate the work to complete separate GAP forms, an existing GAP can be copied and modified for the respective parameters.</p> <p>Further remarks on the crop/treated product can be reported in a free text field, which is created when the user clicks on the symbol .</p> <p>Remarks are necessary to specify whether food or feed has been in contact with the plant protection product indirectly if one of the following codes for treated product has been selected:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="454 611 1396 846"> <tr> <td>3IRRWO</td> <td>irrigation water (treatment of)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>BULBO</td> <td>bulbs, tubers, corms (treatment of)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>PLABO</td> <td>plant base (treatment of)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SEEDO</td> <td>seeds (treatment of)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>WOUNO</td> <td>wounds (treatment of)</td> </tr> </table>	3IRRWO	irrigation water (treatment of)	BULBO	bulbs, tubers, corms (treatment of)	PLABO	plant base (treatment of)	SEEDO	seeds (treatment of)	WOUNO	wounds (treatment of)
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BULBO	bulbs, tubers, corms (treatment of)										
PLABO	plant base (treatment of)										
SEEDO	seeds (treatment of)										
WOUNO	wounds (treatment of)										
Genetical modification of crop	<p>If relevant, describe variety of genetically modified crops on which the use of the product is intended to be used or authorised.</p>										
Crop destination(s)	<p>The field is not mandatory.</p> <p>Please select the relevant EPPO code for crop destination. Multiple selection is allowed (e.g. grown for animal consumption (3ANICD) and grown for human consumption (3HCOND)).</p> <p>In remarks field more details on the crop destination can be described. See also EPPO code list https://gd.eppo.int/PPPUse/3CRODK</p>										
Authorisation zone	<p>Please select the relevant Authorisation zone from the picklist.</p> <p>The assignment of countries to the different zones for the authorisation of products can be found in Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009.</p> <p>Please note that multiple selection of codes is not allowed.</p> <p>Information on the authorisation zone is not mandatory if at least one country has been selected in the field 'Country or territory'.</p> <p>If no information is provided in 'Country or territory' and in 'Authorisation zone', it is assumed that the GAP is relevant for all EU zones.</p>										
MRL zone	<p>Select the MRL zone in which the GAP is intended. The assignment of the individual European countries to the zones can be found in the guidance document SANTE/2019/12752 (https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/plant/docs/pesticides_mrl_guidelines_app-d.pdf) (or a subsequent revision of this document).</p>										
Country or territory	<p>Select the country or the territory related to the GAP. The selection of more than one country is possible if the same GAP applies.</p>										
Crop location (F/G/I)	<p>This data element is mandatory for GAPs that refer to crops (children codes listed under crops and children codes of '3HARVO harvested crops (treatment of)'). For other GAPs the field should remain empty.</p> <p>The available picklist contains EPPO codes with detailed descriptions of the cases.</p> <p>I: Code to be used for crops grown or stored in closed walk-in buildings. This code includes for example mushroom houses and structures for witloof chicory or rhubarb forcing.</p>										

	<p>G: A walk-in, static, closed place of crops production with a usually translucent outer shell, which allows controlled exchange of material and energy with the surroundings and prevents release of products into the environment.</p> <p>F: Fields and other structures which do not prevent release of products into the environment.</p> <p>For crops grown outdoor (F), more details can be reported using the more specific subcodes. The detailed description of the subcodes is provided in the picklist.</p>
Remark	This field should be used only to report any information not already covered by other fields.
Pest/disease to be treated	
Target organisms	Select 'New item' and compile the block consisting of 'Scientific name', 'Common name', 'Development stage of target pest' and 'Development stage of target plant'. See detailed descriptions below.
Scientific name	<p>Select the appropriate code and scientific name from picklist. The picklist is based on the EPPO list (https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/).</p> <p>At least one target organism needs to be defined in a GAP. It is possible to select more than one target organism, if the GAP parameters are identical for the different target organisms.</p> <p>If the target organism is not listed, select 'other' and specify.</p> <p>If a scientific name is not relevant or not known, select 'no data'.</p> <p>Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for target organism if required according to a programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses, e.g. 'I.1.1.1 (EU BPD)'.</p> <p>Please make sure that the scientific name entered in this field matches with the organism described in the field 'Common name'.</p>
Common name	Please add the common name of the target organism in this field that matches with the Scientific name.
Development stage of target pest	<p>For insecticide and fungicide uses, indicate the developmental stage of the target organism/pest (e.g. development stage of the insect or of the disease for diseases caused by fungi).</p> <p>If no appropriate description is available in the list, select 'other:' and specify the development stage in the remarks.</p> <p>If the development stage is not known or not further specified, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If the development stage is not relevant/applicable, leave field empty. Multiple selection of terms is allowed.</p>
Development stage of target plant	<p>For herbicide uses, indicate the developmental stage of the target plant. In the picklist BBCH codes have been implemented. Although these codes have been developed for describing the development stages of crops, they can be used in analogy for the target plants.</p> <p>Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance an alternative description of the developmental stage which is not available in the picklist.</p>
Major/minor use	<p>Select the applicable code from the picklist. Minor use according to Art. 51 of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 should be flagged as 'minor use'.</p> <p>Other EU uses are to be considered as major use (combination of crop/target organism).</p>

	<p>Please note that GAPs need to be split in separate documents/GAP forms, if the different crops selected in the field 'crops/treated object' would require different the flags (e.g. not all crops are major crops).</p> <p>The field is not relevant for uses in third countries (e.g. import tolerances).</p>																														
Application details																															
Application target	<p>The target to be treated can be selected from a picklist. The following terms are implemented:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Picklist value</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Foliage/Plant</td> <td>Application to a plant or the leaves of a plant.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Seed / Seed Pieces</td> <td>Application to a small object produced by a plant from which a new plant can grow.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Propagation Stock</td> <td>Application to a specimens of a plant, used for breeding by natural processes from the parent stock.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Root/Bulb</td> <td>Applications (such as dip applications) to a rootball (the compact mass of roots), or bulb (a part of plants that functions as a food storage during dormancy).</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Bark</td> <td>Application to or into the tough, protective outer sheath of the trunk, branches, and twigs of a tree or woody shrub.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Stump / cut stem</td> <td>Application to the recently cut of a tree or woody shrub (excludes cut flowers).</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Containerized plant</td> <td>Application to a plant and soil grown in a movable container.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agricultural Commodity</td> <td>Post-harvest application to an agricultural product that can be bought and sold (e.g., treatment to grain, fibre, cut flowers, packaged animal feed, etc).</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Soil (surface)</td> <td>Application to the ground in which plants can grow.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Soil (subsurface)</td> <td>Application below the ground, or immediately incorporated.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Water</td> <td>Application to water in systems, pools, pipes, tanks or other containers, or bodies of water, such as lakes, ponds, bays, estuaries, oceans, reservoirs.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Air</td> <td>Application directed to a space, rather than a specific target. Examples of these types of applications include foggers, mosquitocides, ozone generators, knock-down insecticides, etc. This does not include aerial broadcast applications over a crop because the target is the crop, not the air over the crop.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Surface</td> <td>Application to the interior and/or exterior boundaries of an inanimate object. Examples of these types of applications include boat hulls, countertops, hives, nests, etc.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Non-porous Surface</td> <td>Surfaces where liquids will not absorb such as ceramic, porcelain, glass, metal, plastic/vinyl, rubber, stainless steel.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Picklist value	Description	Foliage/Plant	Application to a plant or the leaves of a plant.	Seed / Seed Pieces	Application to a small object produced by a plant from which a new plant can grow.	Propagation Stock	Application to a specimens of a plant, used for breeding by natural processes from the parent stock.	Root/Bulb	Applications (such as dip applications) to a rootball (the compact mass of roots), or bulb (a part of plants that functions as a food storage during dormancy).	Bark	Application to or into the tough, protective outer sheath of the trunk, branches, and twigs of a tree or woody shrub.	Stump / cut stem	Application to the recently cut of a tree or woody shrub (excludes cut flowers).	Containerized plant	Application to a plant and soil grown in a movable container.	Agricultural Commodity	Post-harvest application to an agricultural product that can be bought and sold (e.g., treatment to grain, fibre, cut flowers, packaged animal feed, etc).	Soil (surface)	Application to the ground in which plants can grow.	Soil (subsurface)	Application below the ground, or immediately incorporated.	Water	Application to water in systems, pools, pipes, tanks or other containers, or bodies of water, such as lakes, ponds, bays, estuaries, oceans, reservoirs.	Air	Application directed to a space, rather than a specific target. Examples of these types of applications include foggers, mosquitocides, ozone generators, knock-down insecticides, etc. This does not include aerial broadcast applications over a crop because the target is the crop, not the air over the crop.	Surface	Application to the interior and/or exterior boundaries of an inanimate object. Examples of these types of applications include boat hulls, countertops, hives, nests, etc.	Non-porous Surface	Surfaces where liquids will not absorb such as ceramic, porcelain, glass, metal, plastic/vinyl, rubber, stainless steel.
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	<p>Porous Surface</p>	<p>Surfaces where a liquid is likely to absorb such as fabric, drywall, composition board surfaces, paint films and surfaces, plaster surfaces, and wood.</p>
	<p>other</p>	
<p>Please select the most appropriate treatment target.</p>		
<p>Method of application</p>	<p>Information on the application method is <u>mandatory</u>.</p> <p>Select the treatment/application method relevant for the GAP. The picklist is based on the EPPO list (https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/).</p> <p>If no EPPO code is available to describe the method of application, select 'other:' from the picklist and describe the method of application in the remarks. Examples for methods of application with no EPPO codes are listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bait treatment - basal bark treatment - dabbing/rubbing - [local treatment] - incorporation into compost - material incorporation or impregnation - [no class] - paint - [local treatment] - paste guns for volatile substances - pressure treatment - prune/wound treatment - [local treatment] - soil bed solarization <p>The remarks field can be also used to provide further details on the EPPO code selected to describe the method of application.</p> <p>Examples for further specification of some EPPO codes are listed below:</p> <p>Circulating water application (3CWATM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - hydroponic/aquaponic water treatment <p>Fogging (3FOGGM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mechanical fogging - thermal fogging <p>Fumigating (3FUMIM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fumigation: enclosed spaces - fumigation: vacuum chamber - gassing <p>Injecting (3INJEM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stem injection <p>Placing (3PLACM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - doseable matrix dispensors for volatile substances - retrievable active dispensors for volatile substances - retrievable passive dispensors for volatile substances - non retrievable active dispensors for volatile substances 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - non retrievable passive dispensors for volatile substances <p>Spraying (3SPRYM):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - air assisted broadcast spraying - high volume spraying - low volume spraying - ultra low volume spraying - application in overhead irrigation water - banded spraying - spot treatment (spraying) <p>Spreading (3SPRDM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - granules application in row - granules application overall <p>If different application methods are foreseen on a crop (e.g. seed treatment followed by foliar broadcast), two uses should be described as separate GAPs, including in the remarks that the two GAPs are combined.</p>
Application equipment	<p>Select the types of application equipment used. This information is used in the operator and worker exposure scenarios</p>
Growth stage and season	<p>Click on 'New item' and compile the block of fields that comprises the following fields:</p> <p>Growth stage of crop (first application), Growth stage of crop (last application), Treatment season.</p> <p>If the GAP foresees treatments at different treatment windows (e.g. first treatment window before flowering, second treatment window after flowering), the block can be repeated.</p> <p>Information on the growth stage is mandatory if the GAP refers to a crop; if the GAP refers to treatment of non-crop objects (children of 3NOCFO), it is not required;</p> <p>if the GAP refers to treatment of harvested crops (children codes of 3HARVO), BBCH 99 should be entered;</p> <p>if the GAP refers to children codes of 3CRPAO (treatment of crop parts), it is not required.</p> <p>If number of applications is greater than 1, the information on the growth stage needs to be reported for the first and the last application. Treatment season is not mandatory.</p>
Growth stage of crop (first application)	<p>This field is intended to describe the growth stage of the crop at the first treatment with the product. The picklist offers the BBCH codes which describe the phenomenologically similar growth stages of all mono- and dicotyledonous plant species (source: BBCH Monograph edited by Uwe Meier, Julius Kühn-Institut, 2018, https://www.julius-kuehn.de/media/Veroeffentlichungen/bbch%20epaper%20en/page.pdf).</p> <p>Select the growth stage of the crop at first application. If a treatment is foreseen at one specified growth stage, select the BBCH code only in this field (Growth stage of crop (first application)).</p> <p>For a range, also select the relevant BBCH code in the field 'Growth stage of crop (last application)'.</p> <p>If necessary, more details on the treatment timing shall be reported in remarks (e.g. a description of the timing/growth stage at the application to specify more detailed the timing of the application (e.g. pre-plant, before transplant, etc.)).</p>

	<p>The letters in bracket after the description of the crop development show to which plant group the respective definition refers. (D = Dicotyledons, M = Monocotyledons, G = Gramineae, P = Perennial plants, V = Development from vegetative parts or propagated organs).</p> <p>Please note that BBCH codes 71 to 79 is not used, if the main fruit growth happens in principal growth stage 8.</p>
Growth stage of crop (last application)	Please select from the picklist the growth stage of crop at last application. See above (Growth stage of crop (first application)) for further details.
Treatment season	For autumn/winter sown crops, report whether the treatment is foreseen in autumn/winter or in spring/summer. Multiple selection is allowed. If necessary, any other restrictions for the treatment season can be reported in the remarks field, selecting the option 'other:'
Number of applications (range)	Information on the number of applications is mandatory. Report the number of applications (e.g. 1 – 3) per crop cycle. If only one treatment is foreseen, report '1' in the lower numeric field.
Re-treatment interval (in days)	Enter the interval between treatments (re-treatment interval); if relevant, a range for minimum interval and maximum interval between treatments, expressed in days, can be reported.
Application rate per treatment (product) – range	<p>Mandatory information. For reporting the application rate, follow the recommendations on dose expression for products (EPPO General Standard PPI/239(3)).</p> <p>Enter the numeric value in the first numeric field corresponding the lower application rate (for the formulation) per treatment.</p> <p>Use the second numeric field to report the upper application rate per treatment. Select the most appropriate unit to express the application rate.</p> <p>For applications on crops, the application rate should preferably be expressed as application rate per hectare.</p> <p>See also below application rate per treatment for target a.s. (range).</p>
Remarks on application rate	<p>Any further explanations related to the application rate can be provided in this field.</p> <p>For 3-dimensional crops, the application rate expressed on leaf wall area can be reported in addition to the application rate reported per hectare.</p>
Water amount per treatment / spray volume	For products applied after dilution with water, the minimum and maximum amount of water used in spray application (spray volume) should be reported.
Concentration of target a.s. in dilution	For products applied after dilution with water, report the concentration of the active substance in the diluted solution.
Concentration of formulation in dilution	For products applied after dilution with water, report the concentration of the formulation in the solution.
Safener/synergist/ adjuvant added	<p>Is a safener/synergist/adjuvant intended to be added to the tank mix?</p> <p>If yes, the information on the type and the amount of safener/synergist/adjuvant is mandatory. Please indicate whether the addition of the safener/synergist/adjuvant is mandatory or whether it is only recommended.</p> <p>Indicate the safener/synergist/additive type, the name and the amount added to the tank mix (volume (%)).</p> <p>See also EPPO standard PP1/291(1).</p>
Application rate per	It is mandatory to report the application rate for the target a.s.

treatment for target (range) a.s.	<p>The field is intended to specify the application rate for the target active substance (i.e. the a.s. defined in the active substance dataset (EU PPP Active substance information) of the IUCLID dossier).</p> <p>For reporting the application rate, follow the recommendations on dose expression for products (EPPO General Standard PPI/239(3)).</p> <p>Enter the numeric value in the first numeric field corresponding the lower application rate per treatment.</p> <p>Use the second numeric field to report the upper application rate per treatment.</p> <p>If the formulation contains a variant of the active substance (e.g. an ester), the application rate should be expressed for the a.s. (not for the variant!).</p> <p>Example for a variant: the formulation contains quizalofop-P-terfuryl which is a variant of the a.s. quizalofop-P. In the field defining the application rate for the target a.s. the application rate should be expressed as quizalofop-P. The factor to recalculate the application rate of quizalofop-P-terfuryl (molecular weight 428.9) to quizalofop-P (molecular weight 344.7) is derived as the ratio of the molecular weight ($344.7/428.9=0.804$).</p>
Maximum annual application rate (a.s.)	<p>If restrictions need to be defined for the annual application rate (in case of crops which have more than one harvest per season), please report the maximum annual application rate for the active substance. The application rate should be reported for the a.s. (not the variant).</p>
Non-target a.s.	
Non-target a.s.	Select non-target active substance
Application rate per treatment for other (range) a.s.	<p>This field is intended to specify the application rate for other active substance.</p> <p>For reporting the application rate, follow the recommendations on dose expression for products (EPPO General Standard PPI/239(3)).</p>
Maximum annual application rate for other a.s.	<p>If restrictions need to be defined for the annual application rate (in case of crops which have more than one harvest per season), please report the maximum annual application rate for other active substance. The application rate should be reported for the a.s. (not the variant).</p>
Concentration of other a.s. in dilution	<p>For products applied after dilution with water, report the concentration of other active substance/s in the diluted solution.</p>
Treatment window (for dispensers)	<p>For dispensers or similar application forms, the duration of treatment window needs to be reported.</p> <p>For fumigation the duration of treatment should be reported for each temperature range e.g. 14 days (10 °C - 15 °C).</p>
Seeding rate	<p>Field relevant for seed treatments only.</p> <p>Enter the seeding rate: For crops where the seeds are usually sold by number of units (e.g. sugar beet, maize, sunflower), the seeding rate should be expressed as unit/ha (unit is usually 100.000 individual kernel). For seeds sold by weight (e.g. cereals the seeding rate is normally expressed in kg or g seeds /ha or m²).</p> <p>If 'other:' is selected as unit, describe the seeding rate unit in the additional field.</p>
Planting density	<p>The field is not mandatory.</p> <p>Describe the planting density (number of plants per ha or m²).</p>

Pre-harvest interval not applicable	The checkbox should be ticked if the PHI is 'Not Applicable' e.g. cases where the pesticide is applied to empty storage rooms, or for treatment of fields after harvest. In case 'not applicable' is selected, further clarifications should be provided in the 'Remark' field.
Minimum pre-harvest interval (in days)	Specify the minimum pre-harvest interval (PHI) in days (i.e. the minimum time between the last treatment of a crop and the harvest). This field should also be used to describe the time between post-harvest treatment of a food/feed item and the placement on the market. Enter a single numeric value.
Re-entry period livestock	The field is not mandatory. This field should be used to describe the minimum re-entry period (hours/days) for livestock, i.e. the time that needs to elapse before animals may enter treated pastures.
Withholding period animal feed	The field is not mandatory. This field is intended to define the minimum time (in days) between harvest of a feed crop and the use of the feed.
Re-entry period	The field is not mandatory. Describe the minimum re-entry period (in days or hours) for workers in the field/room treated with pesticide, in order to safeguard human health. If no re-entry period is defined/required, select 'not applicable'.
Waiting period handling treated product	The field is not mandatory. This field is intended to describe the minimum waiting periods (hours/days) that need to be respected between treatment and handling of treated products (e.g. handling of products after fumigation).
Ventilation practices	The field is mandatory for indoor fumigation. When relevant, please describe the ventilation practices to be carried out after indoor treatments, to safeguard human health e.g. for fumigant "Until the air concentration reaches xx ppm or mg/kg"
Plant-back interval	The field is not mandatory. If relevant, please describe the plant-back interval (expressed as days) that has to be respected (e.g. in case of crop failure) before the planting of succeeding crops is allowed.
Restrictions	The field is not mandatory. If relevant, please report any relevant restrictions that would have an impact on the risk assessment e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - geographical restrictions, - restriction related to use of other a.s., - maximum number of applications per season for a.s. belonging to the same group (e.g. dithiocarbamates, triazoles), - restrictions for rotational crops, - PPE, - buffer zones, - temperature range at application, - soil incorporation depth and time, - restricted soil type, - restriction to crops grown in artificial substrate, - restriction to be used only in crops grown in hydroponic systems, - restriction to crops grown in pots/no connection to natural soil, - restrictions to be used in crops up to a certain crop height, - minimum percent soil organic matter, - restrictions to protect pollinators, - restriction regarding application equipment.

Type of user	The field is not mandatory. Please select one or several terms from the picklist (professional/non-professional/other:). If other is selected, please provide more details in the remark field.
Additional information	Any relevant information on the GAP that cannot be reported in any of the data fields above should be entered in this field.

3.2 Mode of action, function, target organisms, and plants or plant products to be protected and possible risk mitigation measures – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide summary information on the effectiveness against target organisms.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.EffectivenessAgainstTargetOrganisms		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	Provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here.	Text (rich-text area)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block " Provide additional information related to the endpoint. If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.	Header 1

3.2 Mode of action, function, target organisms, and plants or plant products to be protected and possible risk mitigation measures – Endpoint study record

Purpose:

This document is to be used to report information covering the following endpoints:

- Function
- Effects on harmful organisms / Information on target organisms
- Mode of action
- possible risk mitigation measures

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.EffectivenessAgainstTargetOrganisms		
Name	Instructions	Type

Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
General information		Header 1
Background information	<p>Use this field to include any background information, if required, or any relevant introductory remark. Leave field empty if not applicable. Do not include information for which specific fields are provided.</p> <p>PURPOSE OF THIS TEMPLATE:</p> <p>This template can be used for recording general information on the effectiveness of an active substance, a plant protection product or a biocidal product, together with its active substances (as required by the relevant legislation).</p> <p>For products, efficacy studies should be reported using the corresponding template 'Efficacy data'. For active substances, the effectiveness achieved or claimed should be briefly described in this template. If required or sensible such description can be supported by including summary table(s) which give an overview of relevant efficacy studies performed with a product or products.</p> <p>As appropriate, the general information can be provided in one record or in several individual records. For instance, one record may be sensible if several target organisms, but same function and product type are addressed. Separate records may be sensible for addressing different types of target organisms and functions.</p> <p>Note that this template focuses primarily on biocides. If used for other than this purpose additional pieces of information may have to be added in several fields. Consult the programme-specific guidance on the details to be included.</p>	Multi-line text
Pest / target organisms to be controlled		Header 2
Target organisms	Specify the target organism(s) to be controlled. Repeat this block of fields as necessary. Due to the great number of possible target organisms this picklist is not exhaustive. If the species name is not listed, choose an appropriate superior term (e.g. 'Acaridae:') and specify by entering free text in the related field. If organism is not listed at all, choose 'other:' and enter the name or several names in a row in the related text field.	
Scientific name	<p>Select appropriate scientific name from picklist. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. See also instructions on this block of fields.</p> <p>Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for target organism if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses. If scientific name is not available in the</p>	Open list with remarks

	picklist, select "other" and refer to EPPO lists available at https://gd.eppo.int/	
Common name	Select appropriate common name from picklist. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. See also instructions on this block of fields. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field. EPPO codes for common name relevant to plant protection products can be retrieved at https://gd.eppo.int/ .	Open list with remarks
Developmental stage of target pest	Indicate the developmental stage of the target organism. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. If not applicable, leave field empty. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for the developmental stage if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses.	Open list with remarks
Developmental stage of target plant	Indicate the developmental stage of the target organism. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. If not applicable, leave field empty.	Multi select open list with remarks
Target organisms		
Products, organisms or objects to be protected / under study		Header 2
Organisms (to be protected) or treated materials	Describe and specify the organism(s) or materials(s) / object(s) to be protected, e.g. human, pets, farm animals, fur- and wool-bearing animals, plants, plant products, seeds, storage goods, drinking water, hard surface material, porous surface.	Multi-line text
Information on intended use and application		Header 2
Function addressed	Indicate the function of the substance. Multiple selection is possible for indicating additional functions provided they relate to the same product type indicated in the next field. However, it may be sensible or required according to legislation-specific guidance to use separate records for each function. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for the function if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses.	Multi select open list with remarks
Product type	Indicate the product type in which the active substance is intended to be included or which is envisaged for the product. In case of multiple product types use separate records for each of them. Note that only product types related to EU BPD are listed. For other legislations, choose 'other:' and specify in the related text field.	Open list

Field of use envisaged / User	If the use conditions are fully described in a GAP document in the dossier, it is sufficient to make reference to the GAP document which describes the use. IUCLID document name and UUID. If this is provided additional information on the use of the product already described in the GAP document does not need to be provided	Text area
Information on application of product		Header 2
Method of application	For the product, indicate the method of application. Multiple selection is possible for indicating more than one method. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for the method of application if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses, e.g. 'VII.1 (EU BPD)'. Reference to use description document is sufficient. Alternatively, see Field of use envisaged / User	Multi select open list with remarks (2000)
Details on application	See Field of use envisaged / User	Text template
General information on effectiveness		Header 2
Effects on target organisms	The effects on the target organisms required for the claimed efficacy should be described and specified if possible for each use and method of application if these have different effects, including any effect-concentration dependencies or the possible existence of a threshold concentration of the active substance. Refer to the instructions given in the relevant guidance documents (e.g. EU BPD TNsG, SANCO and EPPO standards). In case of a submission of an active substance the effectiveness achieved or claimed should be briefly described. If required or sensible such description can be supported by including summary table(s) which give an overview of relevant efficacy studies performed with a product or products. Upload predefined table(s) in the rich text field 'Overall remarks'. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). To show possible differences, the use, i.e. product type and method of application of the product(s) envisaged should also be given. For products, efficacy studies should be reported using the corresponding template 'Efficacy data'.	Text area
Mode of action	Indicate the principles of the mode of action for the function indicated in above field, e.g. 'acute toxin: contact poison'. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for the mode of action if required so according to programme-specific guidance. If so, indicate the type of coding system in parentheses, e.g. 'III.1.2 (EU BPD)'. For plant protection products mode of action, FRAC, HRAC and IRAC codes can be reported.	Open list with remarks

Details on mode of action	For the function indicated in above field, indicate the principles of the mode of action; e.g. 'contact poison' or 'stomach poison'. Briefly describe the biochemical and physiological mechanisms, e.g. 'cholinesterase inhibition' and the biochemical pathway and specify any time delay between application and effect. Use the freetext template as appropriate (delete/add elements). For further instructions refer to the relevant guidance documents	Text template
(Possible) Occurrence of resistance	Indicate whether resistance can possibly develop including cross-resistance. As appropriate include an appraisal of the information gained from the efficacy studies.	Text area
Management strategies to avoid resistance	Describe any appropriate management strategies towards the minimization of the development of resistance.	Text area
Any other known limitations and management strategies	As applicable describe any other known limitations and relevant management strategies towards them.	Text area
Results and discussion		Header 1
Details on results		Text area
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

3.3 (Cf. 3.2) Function, target organisms, and plants or plants products to be protected and possible risk mitigation measures

3.4 (Cf. 3.1) Application rate

3.5 (Cf. 3.1) Content of microorganism in material used (e.g. in the diluted spray, baits or treated seeds)

3.6 (Cf. 3.1) Method of application

3.7 (Cf. 3.1) Number and timing of applications on the same crop, duration of protection and waiting period(s)

3.8 (Cf. 3.1) Proposed instructions for use

3.9 (Cf. 3.1) Safety intervals and other precautions to protect human health, animal health and the environment

4. Further information on the plant protection product

4.1 Procedures for cleaning and decontaminating of application equipment)

See instructions in **Section [1.5.2](#)** of the active substance dataset

4.2 (Cf. 4.1) Recommended methods and precautions concerning: handling, storage, transport, fire or use

4.3 (Cf. 4.1) Measures in case of accident

4.4 (Cf. 4.1) Procedures for destruction or decontamination of the plant protection product and its packaging

5. Analytical methods

5. Analytical methods – Endpoint summary

See instructions in [Section 4](#) of the active substance dataset

5. Analytical methods - Endpoint summary record

See instructions in [Section 4](#) of the active substance dataset

5.1 (Cf. 5) Methods for the analysis of the preparation

5.2 (Cf. 5) Methods to determine and quantify residues

6. Efficacy data

6. Efficacy data – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to summarise the conclusions on the evaluation of the nature and extent of benefits that accrue following use of the plant protection product, in comparison to an untreated control and where they exist in comparison to suitable reference products and damage thresholds, and to define its conditions of use.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.Efficacy		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page"</p>	Confidentiality
Description of key information		Header 1
	<p>Enter a short description of key findings of the submitted studies including</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - target organisms - overview of use descriptions - overview of crops and locations where testing was performed - minimum effective dose - possible indications of development of resistance, unintended side effects or other limitations observed <p>Do the number of trials to be conducted and reported reflect factors such as the extent to which the properties of the active substances it contains are known and on the range of conditions that arise, including variability in plant health conditions, climatic differences, the range of agricultural practices, the uniformity of the crops, the mode of application the type of harmful organism and the type of plant protection product?</p> <p>Statement on whether representative uses GAPs are supported.</p>	Text (rich-text area)
Additional information	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Additional information – common block"</p> <p>A summary table of the performance of [a.s.] against named targets representative of proposed uses at the proposed dose (and including data from reduced doses) and a summary table of crop safety of [a.s.] on named crops representative of proposed uses at the proposed dose and twice the proposed dose can be included here. Where appropriate a separate table should be included</p>	Header 1

	<p>showing the results of any yielded crop safety trials should also be added.</p> <p>If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.</p>	
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Links to supporting material:

Guidance Document on data requirements on efficacy for the dossier to be submitted for the approval of new active substances contained in plant protection products SANCO/10054/2013-rev.3 11 July 2013

6. Efficacy Data – Endpoint Study Record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report information to evaluate the nature and extent of benefits that accrue following use of the plant protection product, in comparison to an untreated control and where they exist in comparison to suitable reference products and damage thresholds, and to define its conditions of use.

Sufficient data must be submitted to document:

- That the design, analysis, conduct, and reporting of trials comply with relevant standards, and any deviations are justified while meeting minimum requirements.
- A detailed and critical assessment of all data collected.
- The number of trials conducted, based on factors such as properties of the active substance (microorganism), variability of conditions, agricultural practices, crop uniformity, application mode, target organism, climatic region, and product type.
- Data that is representative of regions and conditions of practical use, including justification for any read-across applied.
- Additional data generated where read-across cannot address seasonal differences, ensuring efficacy is confirmed for each crop/target organism combination across agronomic and climatic regions.
- Trials on efficacy or phytotoxicity, where relevant, reported for at least two growing seasons.
- Any observed effects, positive or negative, on non-target organisms during tests performed under these requirements.

Description of **Compatibility in plant protection programmes**, as requested in point 6.7 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1440.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.EfficacyData		
Field name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Basic information		Header 1
Background information		Text
Objective / label claim(s) addressed		Text
Source of information / type of study(ies)		List (picklist with remarks) sup. with

Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Compliance with quality standards	<p>Indicate whether the efficacy data were generated according to GEP (Good Experimental Practice) or by an officially recognised organisation. If this is not the case, enter 'no', 'no data' or 'not required' as applicable. Refer to programme-specific guidance as to the required adherence to official recognition, GEP or other quality assurance standards.</p> <p>In the supplementary remarks field, you can add explanations as appropriate, e.g. provide a certificate number. If required, attach any (signed and dated) certificate or quality assurance statement in field 'Attached background material'.</p>	
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	List (picklist with remarks) sup.
Formulation type	<p>Indicate the type of formulation used in the study. If not listed, select 'other' and specify.</p> <p>Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for the formulation type, if required, according to programme-specific guidance.</p>	
Analytical monitoring	Indicate whether the active substance was monitored during the test.	
Details on sampling and analytical methods	If the amount of test material exposed to the organisms was monitored, provide details on sampling and analytical methods used.	List (picklist)
Pest / target organisms to be controlled		
Test / target organisms	<p>Specify the test / target organism(s) used in the study. Repeat this block of fields for specifying all organisms covered by this record. Due to the great number of possible test organisms this picklist is not exhaustive.</p> <p>If the species name is not listed, choose an appropriate superior term (e.g. 'Acaridae:') and specify by entering free text in the related field. If organism is not listed at all, choose 'other:' and enter the name or several names in a row in the related text field.</p> <p>If this template is used to summarise several efficacy studies (e.g. by attaching summary tables as described in the instructions for field 'Background information'), this block of fields can be left empty.</p> <p>However, if the number of different species is reasonable, you should also specify them here in addition to the summary tables. This will allow searching.</p>	
Scientific name	<p>Select appropriate scientific name from picklist. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. The EPPO database can be consulted to retrieve the scientific names of target organisms. If not given/known, select 'no data'. See also instructions on this block of fields.</p> <p>Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field, for instance any code for target organism</p>	Check box

	if required so according to programme-specific guidance.	
Common name	Select appropriate common name from picklist. If not listed, select 'other' and specify; if necessary, consult the EPPPO database. If not given/known, select 'no data'. See also instructions on this block of fields. Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field.	
Developmental stage of target pest	Indicate the developmental stage of the target organism. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. If not applicable, leave field empty.	
Developmental stage of target plant	Indicate the developmental stage of the target organism. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. If not given/known, select 'no data'. If not applicable, leave field empty. For herbicide uses, indicate the developmental stage of the target plant. In the picklist BBCH codes have been implemented. Although these codes have been developed for describing the development stages of crops, they used in analogy for the target plants.	Check box
Details on test / target organisms	Freetext template: Option 1 For single species test - Strain: - Source: - Wild type: [yes/no] - Any selection pressure (sensitivity, resistance): - Pre-conditioning / rearing conditions: - Weight at study initiation: - Age (of the stadium) at study initiation: [mixed age population /] - Numbers used in the test: - Sex of those used in the test (where appropriate): - Other (specify): Option 2 For test with microbial population / inoculum - Nature: - Origin: - Collection / storage of samples: - Preparation of inoculum for exposure: - Pretreatment: - Initial biomass / density / numbers in test system: - Other (specify):	
Products (materials), organisms or objects to be protected / under study		
Organisms (to be protected) or treated materials	If applicable, describe and specify the organism(s) or materials(s) / object(s) to be protected as addressed by these efficacy data.	Check box

Study design		
Total exposure duration (contact time)	If applicable, enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Display: Basic
Remarks	Enter any remarks related to the total exposure duration.	Date
Mode of efficacy assessment	<p>Freetext template:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Effects investigated: - Method for recording / scoring effects: - Intervals of examination: - Post monitoring of test organisms <p>Describe the parameter(s) measured for assessing efficacy and the intervals of measurements, together with the scoring or assessment system used. Where appropriate, describe the duration of post monitoring of test organisms.</p> <p>Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary.</p>	
Method of application	<p>Indicate the method of application. If not listed, select 'other' and specify.</p> <p>Any remarks can be entered in the supplementary remarks field.</p>	
Details on study design	<p>Option 1 Optional items for laboratory studies</p> <p>FURTHER DETAILS ON APPLICATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Application/dosage and dilution rates (incl. dose justification): - Adjuvans/vehicle/carrier: - Presence of interfering substances: - Other (specify) <p>MONITORING OF TEST SUBSTANCE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring of active substance concentration: - Method of analysis: <p>TEST CHAMBER / DEVICE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type and design of test chamber / device: - Other (specify) <p>SURFACE TYPES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type: [porous, non-porous] <p>TEST CONDITIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature: - Rel. humidity: - Aeration: - Light cycles during test: - pH: - Water hardness: - Soil type: - Nutrient supply conditions: 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Any additions or alterations to the test environment during the study: - Other (specify) <p>INITIAL DENSITY/NUMBERS OF TARGET ORGANISMS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial density / numbers in test system: - Frequency or level of infestation / infection: <p>REPLICATES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of replicates: <p>CONTROLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Untreated controls: - Positive controls (reference substance): <p>OTHER (specify):</p> <p>Option 2 Optional items for field and use tests</p> <p>APPLICATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type/method of application: - Code of application type (if any): - Application rates: More than one application rate can be needed. Number and timing of applications have to be stated. The water volume/ha should also be stated. - Application/dosage and dilution rates (incl. dose justification): - Adjuvans/vehicle/carrier: - Other (specify) <p>EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN</p> <p>GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For efficacy evaluation the EPPO climatic zones should be mentioned <p>TEST CONDITIONS / METEOROLOGICAL INFORMATION</p> <p>INITIAL DENSITY/NUMBERS OF TARGET ORGANISMS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial density / numbers in test system: - Frequency or level of infestation / infection: <p>REPLICATES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of replicates: <p>CONTROLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Untreated controls: - Positive controls (reference substance): <p>OTHER (specify):</p>	
<p>Model and software</p>	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	<p>Header 2</p>

<p>Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables</p>	<p>In this field, you can enter any information on materials and methods, for which no distinct field is available, or transfer free text from other databases.</p> <p>You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format. You can also upload any htm or html document.</p> <p>Note: One rich text editor field each is provided for the MATERIALS AND METHODS and RESULTS section. In addition, the fields 'Overall remarks' and 'Executive summary' allow rich text entry.</p>	
<p>Results and discussion</p>		<p>Display: Basic</p>
<p>Efficacy / performance assessment</p>	<p>If possible, indicate the percentage of efficacy in terms of control, reduction, damage of target organisms or reduction of disease caused by pest organisms. Copy this field block for entering more than one efficacy level (e.g. based on other exposure duration, dose or endpoint) if necessary.</p> <p>Note: It may be appropriate to record, in this block of fields, only the mean level of effect or control. If the effect level relates to several test runs (i.e. test conditions), give ranges.</p>	<p>Text (255 char.)</p>
<p>Efficacy parameter</p>	<p>Indicate the efficacy / performance parameter (e.g. % kill/cidal activity) to which the index entered in the next field refers to.</p>	
<p>Efficacy (in %)</p>	<p>Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.</p>	<p>Display: Basic</p>
<p>Time to produce effect</p>	<p>Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.</p>	<p>List (picklist)</p>
<p>Treatment</p>	<p>If efficacy results are recorded for different treatment conditions (by repeating this block of fields), briefly indicate the type of treatment/application the results refer to. Specify dose, application rate, duration, etc.</p>	
<p>Interfering substances</p>	<p>Indicate if interfering substances were present. If 'yes' is selected, briefly specify in the supplementary remarks field.</p>	<p>Display: Basic</p>
<p>Remarks on result</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - not determinable - not determinable because of methodological limitations - not measured/tested - other: <p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not 	<p>List sup. (picklist with remarks - 32,000 char.)</p>

	determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	
Minimum effective dose	If determined, provide the minimum effective dose, i.e. the dose or concentration considered the minimum necessary to achieve sufficient efficacy against the target organism(s) studied under the treatment conditions indicated. Copy this field block for recording values based on different treatment conditions if necessary	
Minimum effective dose	Enter minimum effective dose.	Display: Basic
Time to produce effect	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	List (picklist)
Treatment	If efficacy results are recorded for different treatment conditions (by repeating this block of fields), briefly indicate the type of treatment/application the results refer to. Specify dose, application rate, duration, etc.	
Interfering substances	Indicate if interfering substances were present. If 'yes' is selected, briefly specify in the supplementary remarks field.	Display: Basic
Remarks on result	- not determinable - not determinable because of methodological limitations - not measured/tested - other: This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any remarks by selecting 'other:'.	List multi. (multi-select list with remarks - 32,000 char.)
Details on results	RESULTS - Effects observed: - Dose/concentration dependence of effects: - Begin and duration of effectiveness: - Observed effects in post-monitoring phase: - Reinvasion/reinfestation: - Existence of threshold concentration: - Other: REPORTED STATISTICS: REFERENCE SUBSTANCE - Results with reference substance: - Results with reference substance valid Summarise any relevant results. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report, upload predefined table(s) in the rich text field 'Any	

	<p>other information on results incl. tables' or attach graphs in field 'Attached background material'.</p> <p>Note: Observed limitations on efficacy in terms of resistance, undesirable or unintended side effects, or other limitations should be described in the corresponding fields below.</p>	
Observed limitations on efficacy		Display: Basic
Indication of resistance	<p>Indicate whether any development of resistance was observed or not. In below field 'Details on development of resistance', give details or provide any further explanation, e.g. stating that effects were observed, but considered negligible.</p> <p>Select 'not examined' or 'no data' as applicable.</p>	Text template
Details on development of resistance	<p>Provide details on the development of resistance as observed in the efficacy study(ies), including any evidence of cross-resistance.</p>	
Undesirable or unintended side effects	<p>Indicate whether any undesirable or unintended side effects were observed or not. In below field 'Details on undesirable or unintended side effects', give details or provide any further explanation, e.g. stating that effects were observed, but considered negligible.</p> <p>Select 'not examined' or 'no data' as applicable.</p>	Display: Basic
Details on undesirable or unintended side effects	<p>Provide details on undesirable or unintended side effects as observed in the efficacy study(ies).</p> <p>Where appropriate or required by the relevant legislation, insert subheadings, e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Adverse effects on plants - Adverse effects on health of host animals - Adverse effects on site of application (e.g. discoloration, corrosion, etc.) - Adverse effects on beneficial and other non-target organisms - Adverse effects on objects to be protected: 	Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Other limitations observed	<p>Where there is evidence of other possible limitations as derived from the study results, describe the relevant factors that can possibly reduce the efficacy, e.g. certain climatic or edaphic conditions.</p>	Attachment (single)
Compatibility in plant protection programmes	<p>Where the proposed PPP label claim include other plant protection products in tank mix, spray sequences or other relevant types of applications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Indicate potential effects on the activity of the product after mixing, spraying in sequence ▪ Possible loss of efficacy due to interaction in tank mix, spray sequences ▪ Intervals between applications to avoid negative effects ▪ Potential adverse effects on natural enemies, non-target arthropods, conservation biological control. 	Text
Relevance of study results	<p>For laboratory studies, provide arguments for performing such studies instead of a field test. If a study was conducted in a reduced scale, the dimension should</p>	Display: Basic

	<p>be given as compared to the actual scale of the product (e.g. 'Test was reduced to a scale of 1:100').</p> <p>If the study or studies summarised in this record were conducted with another formulation type or application method, provide a justification for this read-across through either the provision of a reasoned case based on data or through bridging arguments.</p> <p>Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p>	
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	List (picklist with remarks) sup.
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Display: Basic

6.1 (CF. 6) PRELIMINARY TESTS6.2 (CF. 6) MINIMUM EFFECTIVE DOSE6.3 (CF. 6) TESTING EFFECTIVENESS6.4 (CF. 6) INFORMATION ON POSSIBLE DEVELOPMENT OF RESISTANCE IN TARGET ORGANISMS6.5 (CF. 6) ADVERSE EFFECTS ON TREATED CROPS6.6 (CF. 6) OBSERVATIONS ON UNDESIRABLE OR UNINTENDED SIDE-EFFECTS ON SUCCEEDING CROPS AND OTHER PLANTS6.7 (CF. 6) COMPATIBILITY IN PLANT PROTECTION PROGRAMMES

7. Effects on human health

7. Effects on human health – Endpoint summary

Purpose

If, based on results of the studies required in point 7.3 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1440, one or more substances of concern is present in the plant protection product (e.g. metabolites of concern and/or co-formulants) for which the risk is for human and animal health is considered not acceptable based on those studies already performed, relevant additional information on toxicity may be necessary for the plant protection product. The need to perform supplementary studies on the plant protection product shall be based on expert judgement case-by-case, in the light of the particular parameters to be investigated and the objectives to be achieved, for example, if concern on the toxicity of the plant protection products has arisen from studies described in points 7.3.1 to 7.3.6 or a conclusion on toxicity could not be reached.

See instructions in **Section 5.6** of the active substance dataset

7.1 Medical data – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 5.1** of the active substance dataset

7.1.1 DIRECT OBSERVATIONS

See instructions in **5.1.4** of the active substance dataset

7.1.2 EPIDEMIOLOGICAL STUDIES

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide data of relevant epidemiological studies, if available.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.EpidemiologicalData		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Study type	Select appropriate study type.	Open list with remarks
Endpoint addressed	If the study recorded gives useful information on one or several of the classic endpoints, select the endpoint(s) addressed from the picklist. Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. NOTE: The list of endpoints provided is a generic list. Some endpoints may not be applicable for the type of study summarised in this record.	Multi select open list
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Method		Header 2
Type of population	Indicate whether subjects of the general population and/or from an occupational environment were	Multi select open list

	investigated. If two independent studies are reported by the same report, use two separate records.	
Ethical approval	Where ethical approval is required, indicate whether and what kind of consent was received from the persons studied. Include details in the supplementary remarks field. If 'not applicable' or 'no' is selected, give reasoning as appropriate.	Open list with remarks
Details on study design	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Explanations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HYPOTHESIS TESTED: If study type is cohort or case control study, state the hypothesis(es) tested in this study. - STUDY PERIOD: Give dates during which the data were collected (from ... to ...) - SETTING: Indicate the setting where this study took place, e.g., occupational, residential, hospital-based, clinical practice, environmental (e.g., fenceline of waste sites, air monitoring); its geographic location(s); and any other pertinent information. - STUDY POPULATION: Include details on the study population using the predefined items and inserting additional ones if required. Alternatively include or a attach a table and refer to respective Table no. - COMPARISON POPULATION: Indicate one of the predefined types; delete those being not applicable. Provide details, e.g., note the parameters that were 'matched' (i.e., smoking, age, sex, etc.). - HEALTH EFFECTS STUDIED: Describe as appropriate. Note whether the diagnosis of the effects was made blind to exposure status. Alternatively include or a attach a table and refer to respective Table no. 	Text template
Exposure assessment	Indicate whether the exposure was measured or estimated. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details in the following freetext field.	Closed list with remarks
Details on exposure	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Explanations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TYPE OF EXPOSURE: Characterise type of exposure including information on manufacturing / processing / use as applicable. If available, describe special exposure situations / workplaces. - TYPE OF EXPOSURE MEASUREMENT: Indicate relevant predefined type(s); delete those being not applicable. - EXPOSURE LEVELS: Give exposure level(s) reported (with units) or insert/attach table, for several exposure conditions and levels. 	Text template

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EXPOSURE PERIOD: Describe when subjects were exposed and duration of exposure, i.e., hours, hours per day, days, days per week, weeks, months, years, person years, other. - POSTEXPOSURE PERIOD: State period of time elapsed between last exposure/first examination or time study was conducted. - DESCRIPTION / DELINEATION OF EXPOSURE GROUPS / CATEGORIES: If several exposure groups (e.g. different concentrations or durations) are analysed, identify the exposure groups or categories, number of subjects within each group, sex, other categorical descriptions, etc. 	
Statistical methods	Describe all statistical methods used and the data to which they were applied (include sample size and power calculations, if available).	Multi-line text
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Results	Provide exposure data as available. Give numbers of cases for each effect/disease/parameter under consideration, include measures of disease frequency (SMRs, ORs, PMRs, RR, prevalence, incidence, adjusted and/or crude rates), correlations, distributions etc., statistical data (significance, confidence intervals). If appropriate present the data in tabular form. Upload predefined table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1').	Text template
Confounding factors	Indicate any (possible) confounding factor(s), e.g. multi chemical exposure or smoking, and discuss their influence on the observed causal association.	Text area
Strengths and weaknesses	Explain findings and discuss any other factors, i.e. bias, validity issues, reliability issues (including the adequacy of the exposure estimation or measurements), representativeness concerns, unique nature of study, influence of past exposures, latency, turnover rates in occupation studies.	Text area
Effect levels	Follow instructions reported in 'Effect Levels – common block'	Header 2
Target system/organ toxicity	Record the target system(s) where toxicity was observed that is considered of biological relevance and the specific target organ(s). Copy this block of fields for referring to different target systems, lowest effective dose(s) / concentration(s)	Header 3

	and/or treatment relationship, dose response relationship and relevance for humans.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose. Consult any programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) on how to use this field.	Check box
Critical effects observed	Flag to indicate if critical effects were observed in the study within specific organs or systems.	Closed list
Lowest effective dose / conc.	Enter a numeric value and select the unit in the next field for indicating the lowest dose / concentration with significant and/or severe toxic effects on the target organ(s) affected.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
System	Select any specific system where toxicity was observed that is considered of biological relevance.	Open list
Organ	Select from the multiple drop-down list the target organ(s) where toxicity was observed. This field provides context-related picklist values depending on the selection made in the preceding field 'System'.	Multi select open list
Treatment related	Flag to indicate if the effects in systems and/or organs are treatment related.	Closed list
Dose response relationship	Flag to indicate if the effects observed and reported in systems and/or organs are in a dose-response manner.	Closed list
Target system / organ toxicity		
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 4
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

7.2 Assessment of potential toxicity of the plant protection product

Purpose

This document is to be used to conclude on the absence of toxicity of the plant protection product to humans, including links to relevant toxicological studies and literature search and using weight of evidence (WoE) approach as described in [EFSA Scientific Committee, 2017](#).

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.AssessmentOfPotentialToxicity		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Assessment of potential toxicity	Scientific Opinion on the guidance on the use of the weight of evidence approach in scientific assessments. EFSA Scientific Committee, Hardy, A, Benford, D, Halldorsson, T, Jeger, MJ, Knutsen, HK, More, S, Naegeli, H, Noteborn, H, Ockleford, C, Ricci, A, Rychen, G, Schlatter, JR, Silano, V, Solecki, R, Turck, D, Benfenati, E, Chaudhry, QM, Craig, P, Frampton, G, Greiner, M, Hart, A, Hogstrand, C, Lambre, C, Luttik, R, Makowski, D, Siani, A, Wahlstroem, H, Aguilera, J, Dorne, J-L, Fernandez Dumont, A, Hempen, M, Valtueña Martínez, S, Martino, L, Smeraldi, C, Terron, A, Georgiadis, N and Younes, M, 2017 EFSA Journal 2017;15(8):4971, 69 pp. First published: 03 August 2017 https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4971	Header 1
	Conclude on potential toxicity of the plant protection product based on the lines of evidence presented below.	Text (rich-text area)
Assembling evidence	Link to any literature searches for evidence on toxicity.	Link to endpoint (multiple)
Weighing evidence		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Description of key conclusion for the study	Include consideration of the relevance and reliability of the study.	Text
Identified uncertainties		Text
Link to relevant study record	Link to the endpoint study describing the supporting evidence.	Link to endpoint (single)
Weighing evidence		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Integrating evidence		Header 2
Sufficient information to classify the product	Based on the evidence presented above conclude on whether or not sufficient information is available to classify the plant protection product in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 with regard to toxicity to humans and whether or not acute toxicity studies on animals are needed.	List sup. (picklist with remarks)
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block "	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

EFSA Scientific Committee, Hardy, A, Benford, D, Halldorsson, T, Jeger, MJ, Knutsen, HK, More, S, Naegeli, H, Noteborn, H, Ockleford, C, Ricci, A, Rychen, G, Schlatter, JR, Silano, V, Solecki, R, Turck, D, Benfenati, E, Chaudhry, QM, Craig, P, Frampton, G, Greiner, M, Hart, A, Hogstrand, C, Lambre, C, Luttik, R, Makowski, D, Siani, A, Wahlstroem, H, Aguilera, J, Dorne, J-L, Fernandez Dumont, A, Hempen, M, Valtueña Martínez, S, Martino, L, Smeraldi, C, Terron, A, Georgiadis, N and Younes, M, 2017. Scientific Opinion on the guidance on the use of the weight of evidence approach in scientific assessments. EFSA Journal 2017;15(8):4971, 69 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4971>

7.3 Acute toxicity

7.3 ACUTE TOXICITY – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

See instructions in **Section 5.3.1** of the active substance dataset

7.3.1 ACUTE ORAL TOXICITY – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose:

This document is to be used to provide information on the acute oral toxicity of the plant protection product, unless information can be provided to allow an assessment to be conducted on the possible acute oral toxicity of the plant protection product as set out in point 7.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1440.

See instructions in **Section 5.3.1.1** of the active substance dataset

7.3.2 ACUTE DERMAL TOXICITY – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose:

This document is to be used to provide information on the acute dermal toxicity of the plant protection product, unless information can be provided to allow an assessment to be conducted on the possible dermal toxicity of the plant protection product as set out in point 7.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1440.

Findings of severe skin irritation (Grade 4 erythema or oedema) in the dermal study shall be used instead of performing a specific irritation study.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AcuteToxicityDermal		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guideline: Method B.3 Acute toxicity (dermal) (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008). OECD Test Guideline 402: Acute Dermal Toxicity	Header 1
Test type	If possible, indicate whether the fixed dose procedure or standard acute method was used. The latter method should not be used any more. However, it may apply to existing studies. If neither of these test types applies, either leave field empty or use 'other:'.	Open list

	Note: This field may be redundant with the information given in field 'Guideline', but is considered useful for searching reasons.	
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	Closed list
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Test animals	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Test animals – common block"</p> <p>Species:</p> <p>NOTE: Human data should be reported in an appropriate subsection of section 'Exposure related observations', particularly subsection 'Direct observations: clinical cases, poisoning incidents and other'.</p> <p>It can be useful to document, in the section on acute toxicity, that human data are provided by creating a record and referring to the human data in field 'Cross-reference'. This could be relevant if lack of animal experiments is defended by the availability of data on experience with human exposure.</p> <p>Sex: Testing in one sex (usually females) is generally considered sufficient. Provide rationale for use of males (if applicable), in field 'Details on test animals and environment conditions'.</p>	Header 2
Administration / exposure		Header 2
Type of coverage	Select type of coverage used. For robust study summaries specify the area of application in field 'Details on dermal exposure'.	Open list
Vehicle	<p>Select 'unchanged (no vehicle)' if none was used or select vehicle used if any. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field.</p> <p>Note that some of the vehicles provided in this list are used for specific routes of administration only.</p>	Open list with remarks
Details on dermal exposure	Indicate details of exposure. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report.	Text template
Duration of exposure	Indicate total duration of exposure in hours, e.g. '4 hrs'.	Multi-line text
Doses	<p>Include the doses including unit administered to the test animals, e.g. 50, 200, 1000 and 2000 mg/kg bw', or mention the doses after '- other:'. As appropriate include notes in parentheses, e.g. '(male)'.</p> <p>For a robust study summary also indicate the analytical concentrations of the test substance in the vehicle in the results table (see field 'Mortality').</p>	Text template
No. of animals per sex per dose	<p>Enter value or specify according to dose if different number of animals per dose, e.g. '10 (controls), 5 (in dose groups)'.</p> <p>For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, also include a detailed table on the animal assignment in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined</p>	Multi-line text

	table(s) if any or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). Note: Specific tables may be required.	
Control animals	Indicate whether and what type of concurrent control groups were used or select 'not required' if applicable.	Open list with remarks
Details on study design	Include any further details on the study design, i.e. observation period, frequency of observations/weighing, necropsy of survivors and other examinations performed. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. If TG 402 (9 October 2017) was used, see flowchart for the testing procedure in its Annex 2.	Text template
Statistics	Indicate the method of calculating the LD50 or other, if applicable.	Multi-line text
High dose level used	Where a test method offers flexibility in the study design, for example in relation to the choice of dose levels, the chosen study design shall ensure that the data generated are adequate for hazard identification and risk assessment. To this end, testing shall be performed at appropriately high dose levels. If dose (concentration) selection is limited by the physicochemical properties or biological effects of the test substance, justification shall be provided.	
Justification for deviation from the high dose level	Provide a justification for deviating from the high dose level.	Text template
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block ".	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Preliminary study	Summarise evidence of toxicity and mortality of any preliminary sighting study.	Multi-line text
Effect levels		
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Sex	Select from drop-down list.	Closed list
Dose descriptor	Select the relevant dose descriptor from drop-down list, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects. If a fixed dose procedure was used, select 'discriminating dose', i.e. the dose causing evident toxicity but not mortality. With the up-and-down procedure an 'approximate LD50' may be derived. Where no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used, the upper or lower dose level for the relevant dose descriptor can be reported as appropriate with relevant	Open list with remarks

	qualifier, e.g. LD50 >10 mg/kg bw or LD50 <10 mg/kg bw. An additional explanation may be given in field 'Remarks on result', e.g. 'not determinable due to absence of adverse toxic effects'.	
Effect level	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable. For GHS classification, see 'Interpretation of results' under section 'Applicant's summary conclusion' below.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
95% CL	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide the 95% confidence limits if available. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results where required and in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:' 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Effect levels		
Mortality	Include raw data on mortality and evident toxicity for each sex and approximate time of deaths. As appropriate include a detailed table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined table(s) if any or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). If the fixed dose method was used, tabulate the evidence of toxicity and mortality (number of animals) for each sex and dose group. 'Evidence of toxicity' describes clear signs of toxicity following administration of test substance, which should be such that an increase in the exposure concentration can be expected to result in the development of severe toxic signs and probable mortality. Note: Specific tables may be required.	Multi-line text
Clinical signs	Briefly describe significant effects found, including the numbers of animals showing signs, time of onset, duration of the major clinical signs and time when most animals	Multi-line text

	recovered. Distinguish between effects at the site of application (local) and systemic effects. Do not dwell on effects that are most likely due to agonal death. Focus on any important findings, i.e. compound-related or suspected related effects. In case particular effects are considered control-related e.g. because of abnormal control values, this should be specifically addressed. Note if there was a reference point (e.g. NOAELs) for clinical findings.	
Body weight	Briefly describe whether animals gained or lost weight.	Multi-line text
Gross pathology	Briefly describe whether there were any treatment related effects. Do not stress effects due to agonal death.	Multi-line text
Other findings	Report results related to pathogenicity, infectiveness or clearance in studies with micro-organisms	Text template
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables)	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

7.3.3 ACUTE INHALATION TOXICITY – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

Purpose:

This document is to be used to provide information on the acute inhalation toxicity of the plant protection product, unless information can be provided to allow an assessment to be conducted on the possible inhalation toxicity of the plant protection product as set out in point 7.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1440, if the product:

- is used with fogging equipment,
- is used as a smoke generating formulation,
- is used as a vapour releasing preparation,
- is to be applied from aircraft in cases where inhalation exposure is relevant (broadcast air-assisted sprayer),
- is an aerosol,
- is a powder containing a significant proportion of particles of diameter < 50 micrometre (> 1 % on a weight basis),
- is to be applied in a manner which generates a significant proportion of particles or droplets of diameter < 50 micrometre (> 1 % on a weight basis), or
- contains a volatile component at greater than 10 %.

See instructions in **Section 5.3.1.2** of the active substance dataset

7.3.4 Irritation – Endpoint summary

Purpose:

This document is to be used to summarise information indicating whether Skin irritation and/or Eye irritation is observed.

The document should contain the information needed to be reported according to the list of end points for skin and eye irritation (SANCO/12592/2012-rev. 2, 22 March 2019).

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.IrritationCorrosion		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality
Description of key information	Provide a brief description of irritation studies and effects	
Key value for assessment		Header 1
Skin irritation / corrosion		Header 2
Link to relevant study records	Follow instructions reported in "Endpoint summary block for relevant study record" The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the robust study summary is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score, duration of the study, whether or not the study is GLP).	Header 3
Endpoint conclusion		Header 3
Endpoint conclusion	"Adverse effect observed (irritating)" should be chosen if the substance meets the classification criteria for skin irritation (Category 2). "Adverse effect observed (corrosive)" should be chosen if the substance meets the classification criteria for skin corrosion (Categories 1A, 1B or 1C). "No adverse effect observed (not irritating)" should be chosen if the substance does not meet the criteria for classification. If "No study available" is chosen, a justification needs to be provided.	Closed list
Eye irritation		Header 2
Link to relevant study records	Follow instructions reported in "Endpoint summary block for relevant study record". The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the robust study summary is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score, duration of the study, whether or not the study is GLP).	Header 3
Endpoint conclusion		Header 3

Endpoint conclusion	<p>“Adverse effect observed (irritating)” should be chosen if the substance meets the classification criteria for eye irritation (Category 2).</p> <p>“Adverse effect observed (irreversible damage)” should be chosen if the substance meets the classification criteria for irreversible effects on the eye (Category 1).</p> <p>“No adverse effect observed (not irritating)” should be chosen if the substance does not meet the criteria for classification.</p> <p>If “No study available” is chosen, a justification needs to be provided.</p>	Closed list
Respiratory irritation		Header 2
Endpoint conclusion		Header 3
Endpoint conclusion	<p>“Adverse effect observed (irritating)” should be chosen if the substance is found to cause respiratory irritation.</p> <p>“Adverse effect observed (irreversible damage)” should be chosen if the substance does not cause respiratory irritation.</p> <p>“No study available” should be chosen if there is no data to conclude on respiratory irritation.</p>	Closed list
Justification for classification or non-classification		Header 1
	The available information should be compared against the classification criteria and the reasons for fulfilling or not fulfilling the classification criteria should be presented.	Rich text area
Additional information	<p>Follow instructions reported in “Additional information – common block”</p> <p>Provide additional information related to the endpoint, for example: skin/eye irritant or non-irritant</p>	Header 1

7.3.4.1 Skin irritation – Endpoint study record

Purpose:

This document is to be used to report information on skin irritation of the plant protection product, unless information can be provided to allow an assessment to be conducted on the skin irritation potential of the plant protection product from the available information regarding its components, including the active substance, co-formulants, safeners, synergists, and relevant impurities as set out in point 7.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1440.

The test must provide the potential of skin irritancy of the plant protection product including the potential reversibility of the effects observed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SkinIrritationCorrosion		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in “ Administrative data – common block ”	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in “ Data source – common block ”	Header 1

Materials and methods	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Material and methods – common block"</p> <p>Applicable test guideline: Method B.4 Acute toxicity: dermal irritation/corrosion (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OECD Test Guideline 430 / Method B.40 <i>In vitro</i> skin corrosion: transcutaneous electrical resistance test (TER) (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008). - OECD Test Guideline 431 / Method B.40 bis <i>In vitro</i> skin corrosion: human skin model test (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008). - OECD Test Guideline 404: Acute Dermal Irritation/Corrosion - OECD Test Guideline 431: <i>In vitro</i> Skin Corrosion: Human Skin Model Test - OECD Test Guideline 430: <i>In vitro</i> Skin Corrosion: Transcutaneous Electrical Resistance Test - OECD Test Guideline 435: <i>In vitro</i> Membrane Barrier Test Method for Skin Corrosion - OECD Test Guideline 439: <i>In vitro</i> Skin Irritation: Reconstructed Human Epidermis Test Method - OECD TG 439 / Method B.46 <i>In vitro</i> skin irritation: reconstructed human epidermis model test (Annex III of Regulation (EC) No 761/2009 (7)) 	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
In vitro test system		Header 2
Test system	<p>Select as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other:' and specify. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field.</p> <p>Use of other than the test systems recommended by the test guidelines is to be considered as deviation from guideline and should be noted and justified in the field "Test guideline - Deviations".</p>	Open list with remarks
Source species	Select as appropriate. Indicate the species used as source of the <i>in vitro</i> test system. If not available from picklist, select 'other:' and specify.	Open list
Cell type	For <i>in vitro</i> tests, e.g. according to OECD Guidelines 431 and 439, indicate the cell type used to construct the <i>in vitro</i> test system. If not available from picklist, select 'other:' and specify.	Open list
Cell source	For <i>in vitro</i> tests, e.g. according to OECD Guidelines 431 and 439, indicate the source of the cells used to construct the <i>in vitro</i> test system. If not available from picklist, select 'other:' and specify.	Open list
Source strain	<p>For <i>in vitro</i> tests, e.g. according to OECD Guideline 430, indicate the strain used as source of the test system. If not available from picklist, select 'other:' and specify.</p> <p>Use of other than the strain recommended by the test</p>	Open list

	guideline is to be considered as deviation from guideline and should be noted and justified in the respective fields.	
Details on animal used as source of test system	<p>For <i>in vitro</i> tests, e.g. according to OECD Guideline 430, give details on the animal used as source of the skin discs. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p> <p>Explanations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diet: Describe type of diet (e.g. conventional laboratory diet / caloric restriction) and whether it was provided ad libitum. - Water: Describe type (e.g. drinking water) and whether it was provided ad libitum. 	Text template
Justification for test system used	Provide a justification for the test system used	Multi-line text
Vehicle	Select 'unchanged (no vehicle)' if none was used or select vehicle used if any. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field	Open list with remarks
Details on test system	<p>For <i>in vitro</i> tests, e.g. according to OECD Guidelines 430, 431, 435 or 439, indicate details on the test system used including test conditions. Select freetext template for the respective type of study (i.e. Transcutaneous electrical resistance test (TER) (e.g OECD TG 430) or Artificial membrane barrier test method (e.g OECD TG 435) or Human skin model test (e.g OECD TG 431) or Reconstructed human epidermis test method) (e.g OECD TG 439)) and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p> <p>Explanations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SKIN DISC PREPARATION (if Transcutaneous electrical resistance test): Summarise the procedure used to prepare the skin discs and, for each animal skin used as source for skin discs, indicate the electrical resistances obtained with two of the isolated skin discs before testing (should be ≥ 10 kΩ) - RECONSTRUCTED HUMAN EPIDERMIS (RHE) TISSUE: For human skin model tests, e.g. according to OECD Guidelines 431 and 439, indicate the Reconstructed human Epidermis (RhE) tissue model used, batch number(s) used, the production date, the shipping date, the delivery date, and the date of initiation of testing. - TEMPERATURE USED FOR TEST SYSTEM: Indicate the temperature used during treatment / exposure (e.g. room temperature, 25°C, 37°C, etc). If more than one temperature was used, indicate the different sequential temperatures used and the exact exposure time at each temperature. 	Text template

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REMOVAL OF TEST MATERIAL AND CONTROLS: Indicate the volume (if applicable) and number of washing steps used to remove the test item from the test system after treatment / exposure. Indicate if any observable damage was induced by the washing procedure. Indicate any modification to the validated SOP introduced in the washing procedure. - FUNCTIONAL MODEL CONDITIONS WITH REFERENCE TO HISTORICAL DATA (if human skin model test): Provide details on viability (negative control OD values of each tissue batch in comparison to historical acceptability ranges); barrier function (for each tissue batch, indicate the IC50 obtained with 18 h treatment with SDS or the ET50 obtained with treatment with 1% Triton X-100 in comparison to historical acceptability ranges); morphology (number and type of viable epithelial cell layers (basal layer, stratum spinosum, stratum granulosum) and the approximate number of layers of the stratum corneum, as assessed by histological examination); contamination (indicate if the tissue batches used were free of contamination by bacteria, viruses, mycoplasma or fungi, reproducibility (indicate the reproducibility of the negative and positive controls over time) - PREDICTION MODEL / DECISION CRITERIA: Describe and justify the prediction model / decision criteria used to derive the corrosion/irritation classification 	
Control samples	Indicate whether and what type of concurrent control groups were used or select 'not required' if applicable. In the supplementary remarks field, specify the name of the control substance and other identifiers (e.g. CAS number, the physical state, lot/batch No. including expiration date, purity and any other relevant information. Multiple selection is possible if more than one type of control was used, e.g. a concurrent positive control, a concurrent negative control, non-specific colour controls and non-specific MTT reduction controls.	Multi select open list with remarks
Amount/concentration applied	Give the amount(s) of substance / controls applied (volume or weight with unit) and the concentration of the substance, controls and vehicle (if used) in the test solution. Specify if different doses were applied. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Duration of treatment exposure	Indicate length of time test material was in contact with test system, e.g. '3 min. ' or '4 hours'. Also indicate if different exposure time periods were applied in different tests of this study.	Multi-line text
Duration of post-treatment incubation (if applicable)	Indicate length of post-treatment incubation period as applicable.	Multi-line text
Number of replicates	Indicate the number of replicate tissues/skin discs used in each treatment / exposure and control groups.	Multi-line text

Test animals	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Test animals – common block"</p> <p>Species: For <i>in vitro</i> tests, indicate the species used as source of the test system. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.</p> <p>Use of other than the species recommended by the test guideline is to be considered as deviation from guideline and should be noted and justified in the respective fields</p> <p>NOTE: Human data should be reported in an appropriate subsection of section 'Exposure related observations', particularly subsection 'Direct observations: clinical cases, poisoning incidents and other'.</p> <p>It can be useful to document, in section 'Skin irritation / corrosion', that human data are provided by creating a record and referring to the human data in field 'Cross-reference'. This could be relevant if lack of animal experiments is defended by the availability of data on experience with human exposure.</p>	Header 2
Test system		Header 2
Type of coverage	Select as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.	Open list
Preparation of test site	Select as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.	Open list with remarks
Vehicle	Select 'unchanged (no vehicle)' if none was used or select vehicle used if any. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Controls	<p>Indicate whether and what type of concurrent control groups were used or select 'not required' if applicable. In the supplementary remarks field, specify the name of the control substance and other identifiers (e.g. CAS number, the physical state, lot/batch No. including expiration date, purity and any other relevant information).</p> <p>Multiple selection is possible if more than one type of control was used, e.g. a concurrent positive control and a concurrent negative control.</p>	Multi select open list with remarks
Amount / concentration applied	Give the amount(s) of substance applied (volume or weight with unit) and the concentration of the substance and vehicle (if used) in the test solution. Specify if different doses were applied. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template
Duration of treatment / exposure	Indicate length of time test material was in contact with test animal, including unit, e.g. '4 hours'. Also indicate if different exposure time periods were applied in different tests of this study.	Multi-line text
Observation period	Indicate length of observation period.	Multi-line text
Number of animals	Indicate number of animals used.	Multi-line text
Details on study design	For <i>in vivo</i> tests, e.g. according to OECD Guideline 404, give details on study design. Describe the method of calculation of maximum average score given in the results table used (if applicable).	Text template

	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	
High dose level used	Where a test method offers flexibility in the study design, for example in relation to the choice of dose levels, the chosen study design shall ensure that the data generated are adequate for hazard identification and risk assessment. To this end, testing shall be performed at appropriately high dose levels. If dose (concentration) selection is limited by the physicochemical properties or biological effects of the test substance, justification shall be provided. Select as appropriate.	
Justification for deviation from the high dose level	Provide a justification for deviating from the high dose level.	Text template
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block ".	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
<i>In vitro</i>		Header 2
Results	Indicate the overall irritation / corrosion results for the test substance in terms of tissue viability, transcutaneous electrical resistance, penetration time or other. Copy this block of fields as appropriate. In case of a robust study summary or as requested by the regulatory programme, also provide the raw data of the results (including means and standard deviations) for the test material and all controls used in the field "Irritant/corrosive response data" and/or upload a table in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables". (Q)SAR results can be reported under the appropriate heading, i.e. ' <i>In vitro</i> ' or ' <i>In vivo</i> ', depending on the applicability domain of the model behind and based on what kind of data the model was mainly validated. At least the field 'Remarks on result' should be completed by entering the adequate qualitative description of the prediction. Note that a separate field "Interpretation of results" is provided in the section "APPLICANT'S SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION" for indicating a classification based on the study results.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	

	Consult any programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) on how to use this field.	
Irritation corrosion parameter	/ Select type of parameter from picklist, if applicable. Further details can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. "based on optical density measurement".	Open list with remarks
Run experiment	/ Indicate the run / experiment the measurement relates to, if more than one run / experiment was performed and the length of time the test material was in contact with the test system, if different exposure time periods were applied in different test runs of this study. Examples: Run 1 (duration of exposure: 2 hours); Run 1, replicate 1 (duration of exposure: 2 hours), Mean of three runs with two replicates each.	Text
Value	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Vehicle controls validity	Indicate whether test(s) with vehicle control(s) (i.e. without test substance, with/without solvent) is/are valid. Relevant remarks can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Negative controls validity	Indicate whether test with negative control(s) is valid, i.e. substance(s) with known lack of irritation/corrosion in the test conducted. Relevant remarks can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Positive controls validity	Indicate whether test with positive control(s) is valid, i.e. substance(s) with known irritation/corrosion in the test conducted. Relevant remarks can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Results		
Other effects / acceptance of results	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Provide the following information as appropriate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OTHER EFFECTS: Describe any other observed effects (e.g. visible damage on test system, no visible damage on test system, direct-MTT reduction, colour interference with MTT, etc). Discuss the applicability of the test method to test colorants and/or direct MTT-reducers in reference to the %NSC and/or %NSMTT values reported in the block of fields above. - DEMONSTRATION OF TECHNICAL PROFICIENCY: If required according to the test guideline, indicate if and when technical proficiency has been demonstrated using the proficiency chemicals listed in the guideline used. Upload table(s) with data for each individual proficiency 	Text template

	<p>chemical in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'.</p> <p>- ACCEPTANCE OF RESULTS: Demonstrate that the assay acceptance criteria (for negative control, positive control, and variability between replicate measurements) were met in reference to historical ranges. Indicate the range of historical values if different from the ones indicated in the relevant test guideline.</p> <p>Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p>	
In vivo		Header 2
Results	<p>For <i>in vivo</i> test results, provide individual time point scores per animal and mean scores. If reported or required by the relevant legislation, indicate overall irritation / corrosion results in terms of an Overall irritation score, Primary dermal irritation index or other (specify). Copy this block of fields as appropriate. (Q)SAR results can be reported under the appropriate heading, i.e. '<i>In vitro</i>' or '<i>In vivo</i>', depending on the applicability domain of the model behind and based on what kind of data the model was mainly validated. At least the field 'Remarks on result' should be completed by entering the adequate qualitative description of the prediction.</p> <p>In case of a robust study summary or as requested by the regulatory programme, also provide the raw data of the results (including means and standard deviations) for the test material and all controls used in the field "Irritant/corrosive response data" and/or upload a table in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables". Note that a separate field "Interpretation of results" is provided in the section "APPLICANT'S SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION" for indicating a classification based on the study results.</p>	
Key result	<p>Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.</p> <p>Consult any programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) on how to use this field.</p>	
Irritation parameter	Select type of parameter from picklist. Further details can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Basis	Indicate if the score is the mean of all scoring results for the parameter selected on the preceding subfield or based on individual animals, e.g. animal #1. Option 'animal:' allows to enter text/numbers in the related supplementary remarks field, e.g. 'animal: #1, 2 and 3').	Open list with remarks
Time point	Indicate the time point(s) the score relates to by selecting the appropriate value from the picklist, e.g. '24' or '24/48/72 h' (if the same score applies), and in the following field, the unit.	Open list

Score	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Max. score	Provide the numeric value of the total possible score depending on the scale used.	Decimal
Reversibility	Indicate whether the irritation was reversible or not. As appropriate use supplementary remarks field linked to the picklist item selected for indicating average time for (non-)reversibility.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other:' An explanation should be provided when there was a need to humanely sacrifice animals in pain or showing signs of severe and enduring distress. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Results		
Irritant / corrosive response data	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, tabulate the raw data for each individual animal at each observation time up to removal of each animal from the test (unless these data are given in above block of fields 'Irritation / corrosion results'). Upload predefined table(s) if any in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables' or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1'). In field "Details on study design (<i>in vivo</i>)", describe the method of calculation used. Note: Specific tables may be required.	Text area
Other effects	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. For <i>in vivo</i> tests, e.g. according to OECD Guideline 404, describe any other adverse local (e.g. defatting of skin) and systemic effects in addition to dermal irritation or corrosion.	Text template
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2

results incl. tables		
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

7.3.4.2 Eye Irritation – Endpoint study record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report information on eye irritation of the plant protection product, unless:

- information can be provided to allow an assessment to be conducted on the eye irritating potential of the plant protection product as set out in point 7.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1440, or
- the microorganism is an already known eye irritant or it is likely, as indicated in the test guideline, that severe effects on the eyes may be produced.

The test must provide the potential for eye irritation of the plant protection product, including the potential reversibility of the effects observed.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.EyeIrritation		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Material and methods – common block"</p> <p>Applicable test guideline:</p> <p>Method B.5 Acute toxicity: eye irritation/corrosion OECD 405</p> <p>OECD Test Guideline 437: Bovine Corneal Opacity and Permeability Test Method for Identifying i) Chemicals Inducing Serious Eye Damage and ii) Chemicals Not Requiring Classification for Eye Irritation or Serious Eye Damage</p> <p>OECD Test Guideline 438: Isolated Chicken Eye Test Method for Identifying i) Chemicals Inducing Serious Eye Damage and ii) Chemicals Not Requiring Classification for Eye Irritation or Serious Eye Damage</p> <p>Method B.47 Bovine corneal opacity and permeability test method for identifying ocular corrosives and severe irritants</p> <p>Method B.48 Isolated chicken eye test method for identifying ocular corrosives and severe irritants</p>	Header 1
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2

Test material physicochemical properties	Use this field for highlighting the physicochemical properties of the test material that are relevant for evaluating this study summary, if not already provided elsewhere in the dataset. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text Template
Test animals / tissue source		Header 2
Species	Select as appropriate. For <i>in vitro</i> / <i>ex vivo</i> tests, indicate the species used as source of the test system. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify. Use of other than the species recommended by the test guideline is to be considered as deviation from guideline and should be noted and justified in the respective fields. NOTE: Human data should be reported in an appropriate subsection of section 'Exposure related observations', particularly subsection 'Direct observations: clinical cases, poisoning incidents and other'. It can be useful to document, in section 'Irritation / corrosion', that human data are provided by creating a record and referring to the human data in block 'Cross-reference'. This could be relevant if lack of animal experiments is defended by the availability of data on experience with human exposure.	Open list
Strain	Select strain as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.	Open list with remarks
Details on test animals or tissues and environmental conditions	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. Explanations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diet: Describe type of diet (e.g. conventional laboratory diet / caloric restriction) and whether it was provided ad libitum. - Water: Describe type (e.g. drinking water) and whether it was provided ad libitum. - Food quality and water quality: provide analytical information on the nutrient and dietary contaminant levels. Similarly provide analytical information on the drinking water used in the study. - IN-LIFE DATES: If required, specify the in-life dates (i.e. the phase of a study following treatment in which the test system is alive/growing). 	Text template
Test system		Header 2
Vehicle	Select 'unchanged (no vehicle)' if none was used or select vehicle used if any. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Controls	Indicate whether and what type of concurrent control groups were used or select 'not required' if applicable. In the supplementary remarks field, specify the name of the control substance and other identifiers (e.g. CAS	Multi select open list with remarks

	<p>number, the physical state, lot/batch No. including expirations date, purity and any other relevant information.</p> <p>Multiple selection is possible if more than one type of control was used, e.g. a concurrent positive control and a concurrent negative control.</p>	
Amount / concentration applied	<p>Give the amount(s) of substance / controls applied (volume or weight with unit) and the concentration of the substance, controls and vehicle (if used) in the test solution. Specify if different doses were applied. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate.</p>	Text template
Duration of treatment / exposure	<p>Indicate length of time test material was in contact with animal/cell/tissue including unit, e.g. '4 hours'. Also indicate if different exposure time periods were applied in different tests of this study.</p>	Multi-line text
Observation period (in vivo)	<p>Indicate length of observation period.</p>	Multi-line text
Duration of post-treatment incubation (in vitro)	<p>Indicate length of post-treatment incubation period as appropriate.</p>	Multi-line text
Number of animals or in vitro replicates	<p>Indicate number of animals used (if <i>in vivo</i>) or, in the case of <i>in vitro</i> tests, the number of replicate tissues used in each treatment / exposure and control group.</p>	Multi-line text
Details on study design	<p>Select freetext template for the respective type of study (i.e. <i>In vivo</i> test method, <i>In vitro</i> test method (BCOP) or <i>In vitro</i> test method (ICE) and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p>	Text template
High dose level used	<p>Where a test method offers flexibility in the study design, for example in relation to the choice of dose levels, the chosen study design shall ensure that the data generated are adequate for hazard identification and risk assessment. To this end, testing shall be performed at appropriately high dose levels. If dose (concentration) selection is limited by the physicochemical properties or biological effects of the test substance, justification shall be provided.</p>	
Justification for deviation from the high dose level	<p>Provide a justification for deviating from the high dose level.</p>	Text template
Model and software	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Model and software – common block".</p> <p>Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.</p>	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block".</p>	Header 2

Results and discussion		Header 1
<i>In vitro</i>		Header 2
Results	<p>Indicate the overall irritation / corrosion results for the test substance in terms of the relevant endpoints examined (e.g. cornea opacity score) and the overall irritation / corrosion results (specify as appropriate). Copy this block of fields for reporting several scores, e.g. means of individual replicates.</p> <p>In case of a robust study summary or as requested by the regulatory programme, also provide the raw data of the results (including means and standard deviations) for the test material and all controls used in the field "Irritant/corrosive response data" and/or upload a table in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".</p> <p>(Q)SAR results can be reported under the appropriate heading, i.e. '<i>In vitro</i>' or '<i>in vivo</i>', depending on the applicability domain of the model behind and based on what kind of data the model was mainly validated. At least the field 'Remarks on result' should be completed by entering the adequate qualitative description of the prediction.</p> <p>Note that a separate field "Interpretation of results" is provided in the section "APPLICANT'S SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION" for indicating a classification based on the study results.</p>	
Key result	<p>Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.</p> <p>Consult any programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) on how to use this field.</p>	
Irritation parameter	Select type of parameter from picklist, if applicable. Further details can be given in the supplementary remarks field. For instance, in the case of morphological effects, specify if and to what severity pitting of corneal epithelial cells, loosening of epithelium, roughening of the corneal surface and sticking of the test substance to the cornea occurred.	Open list with remarks
Run experiment /	Indicate the run / experiment the measurement relates to, if more than one run / experiment was performed and the length of time the test material was in contact with the test system, if different exposure time periods were applied in different test runs of this study. Examples: Run 1 (duration of exposure: 10 min.); Run 1, replicate 1 (duration of exposure: 10 min.), Mean of three runs with two replicates each.	Text
Value	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Vehicle controls validity	Indicate whether test(s) with vehicle control(s) (i.e. vehicle only without test substance) is/are valid. Relevant remarks can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks

Negative controls validity	Indicate whether test with negative control(s) demonstrated lack of irritation/corrosion of the known non-irritant/non-corrosive substance, and/or that the negative control falls within the acceptance criteria range as described in the TG. Relevant remarks can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Positive controls validity	Indicate whether test with positive control(s) demonstrated irritation/corrosive effects of the known irritant/corrosive substance and/or that positive control results fall within the acceptance criteria as described in the TG. Relevant remarks can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other:'.	Open list with remarks (2000)
Results		
Other effects / acceptance of results	Select freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Provide the following information as appropriate: - OTHER EFFECTS: Describe any other observed effects (e.g. visible damage on test system) - DEMONSTRATION OF TECHNICAL PROFICIENCY: If required according to the test guideline, indicate if and when technical proficiency has been demonstrated using the proficiency chemicals listed in the guideline used. Upload table(s) with data for each individual proficiency chemical in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. - ACCEPTANCE OF RESULTS: Demonstrate that the assay acceptance criteria (for negative and positive control) were met in reference to historical ranges. Indicate the range of historical values if different from the ones indicated in the relevant test guideline. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.	Text template
In vivo		
Results	Indicate the scores of the relevant endpoints examined (e.g. cornea opacity score) and the overall irritation / corrosion results (specify as appropriate). In subfield "Basis of irritation parameter" indicate if the score is an average value (i.e. mean), or for a give animal, or other. Copy this block of fields for reporting several scores, e.g. means or for individual animals. In case of a robust study summary or as requested by the regulatory programme, also provide the raw data of the results (including means and standard deviations) for the test material and all controls used in the field "Irritant/corrosive response data" and/or upload a table in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables".	Header 2

	<p>(Q)SAR results can be reported under the appropriate heading, i.e. '<i>In vitro</i>' or '<i>in vivo</i>', depending on the applicability domain of the model behind and based on what kind of data the model was mainly validated. At least the field 'Remarks on result' should be completed by entering the adequate qualitative description of the prediction.</p> <p>Note that a separate field "Interpretation of results" is provided in the section "APPLICANT'S SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION" for indicating a classification based on the study results.</p>	
Key result	<p>Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.</p> <p>Consult any programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) on how to use this field.</p>	
Irritation parameter	Select type of parameter from picklist. Further details can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Basis	Indicate if the score is the mean of all scoring results for the parameter selected on the preceding subfield or based on individual animals, e.g. animal #1. Option 'animal:' allows to enter text/numbers in the related supplementary remarks field, e.g. 'animal: #1, 2 and 3').	Open list with remarks
Time point	Indicate the time point(s) the score relates to by selecting the appropriate value from the picklist, e.g. '24' or '24/48/72 h' (if the same score applies), and in the following field, the unit.	Open list
Score	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)
Max. score	Provide the numeric value of the total possible score depending on the scale used.	Decimal
Reversibility	Indicate whether the irritation was reversible or not. As appropriate use supplementary remarks field linked to the picklist item selected for indicating average time for (non-)reversibility.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	<p>This field can be used for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:'. 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Results		
Irritant / corrosive response data	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, tabulate the raw data for each individual animal at each observation time (unless these data are given in above block of fields 'Irritation / corrosion results').	Text area

	<p>Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text (e.g. '... see Table 1').</p> <p>Describe the method of calculation of maximum average score given in the results table.</p> <p>Note: Specific tables may be required.</p>	
Other effects	Select freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Describe any other relevant results including lesions and clinical observations, ophthalmoscopic and histopathological findings, effects of rinsing or washing if applicable.	Text template
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

7.3.5 (Cf. 7.3.4.2) Eye irritation

7.3.6 Skin sensitisation – Endpoint Summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide summary information of the most relevant study(-ies) from which the key value for assessment is extrapolated.

ENDPOINT_SUMMARY.Sensitisation		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Description of key information	Provide a brief description of the study and the potential of the micro-organism to provoke sensitisation reactions.	
Key value for assessment		Header 1

Skin sensitisation		Header 2
Link to relevant study records	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Endpoint summary block for relevant study record".</p> <p>The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the robust study summary is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score, duration of the study, whether or not the study is GLP).</p>	Header 3
Endpoint conclusion		Header 3
Endpoint conclusion	<p>"Adverse effect observed (sensitising)" should be chosen if the micro-organism shows effects of skin sensitisation.</p> <p>"No adverse effect observed (not sensitising)" should be chosen if the substance does not show effects of skin sensitisation.</p> <p>If "No study available" is chosen, a justification needs to be provided.</p>	Closed list
Additional information	<p>Provide additional information related to the endpoint, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - relevance of the results for the risk assessment - the rationale for the choice of the key study(ies) and the choice for the key value that characterises the endpoint - the rationale for any user-derived values for the sake of transparency - the possible reasons for differentiating results when several studies were identified to be relevant for the assessment. <p>If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.</p>	Rich text area
Respiratory sensitisation		Header 2
Link to relevant study records	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Endpoint summary block for relevant study record".</p> <p>The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the robust study summary is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score, duration of the study, whether or not the study is GLP).</p>	Header 3
Endpoint conclusion		Header 3
Endpoint conclusion	<p>"Adverse effect observed (sensitising)" should be chosen if the micro-organism shows effects of respiratory sensitisation.</p> <p>"No adverse effect observed (not sensitising)" should be chosen if the substance does not show effects of respiratory sensitisation.</p> <p>If "No study available" is chosen, a justification needs to be provided.</p>	Closed list
Justification for classification		Header 1

or non-classification		
	The available information should be compared against the classification criteria and the reasons for fulfilling or not fulfilling the classification criteria should be presented.	Rich text area
Additional information	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information – common block " Provide additional information related to the endpoint, for example: sensitising (state source of evidence, e.g. type of study, clinical data, etc)	Rich text area

7.3.6 Skin sensitisation – Endpoint Study record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report information on skin sensitisation when available, unless information can be provided to allow an assessment to be conducted on the skin sensitisation properties of the plant protection product from the available information regarding its chemical components (i.e. co-formulants, metabolites of concern and relevant impurities) as set out in point 7.2 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1440.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SkinSensitisation		
Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1
Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block " Applicable test guideline: OECD 406 Method B.42 Skin sensitisation: Local lymph node assay (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008). Method B.6 Skin sensitisation (Annex to Regulation (EC) No 440/2008). OECD 429 OECD 442A + 442B.	Header 1
Type of study	Select type of study as appropriate. If another than the LLNA test system was used, a justification may be required in the following field.	Open list
Justification for non-LLNA method	Provide a justification for the use of another than the LLNA test system (if <i>in vivo</i>), if the relevant legislation so requires. For instance it could be argued that the LLNA method was not available yet by the time the study was conducted or that the LLNA test is not suitable for that substance or that an appropriate guinea pig maximisation test is available which would not justify conducting an additional LLNA due to animal welfare. Refer to the relevant legislation-specific guidance document.	Multi-line text
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2

In vitro test system		Header 2
Details of test system	If standard cell lines not used, please select 'other:' and specify in the freetext field exact details of the cell line used.	Open list
Details on the study design	<p>PREPARATION OF TEST SOLUTIONS: describe how test solutions were prepared to obtain suitable concentration including specific substance details on the materials used (EC/CAS, purity, treatment of the material) etc. If stable dispersion is not obtained and the test solution is still used, add an explanation why this is not considered to affect the validity of the study.</p> <p>DOSE RANGE FINDING ASSAY: describe the highest concentration used for the dose range finding assay and how appropriate doses were selected taking solubility and cytotoxicity into account. Specify which solvents were used and finally selected and how cytotoxicity assessment was performed.</p> <p>APPLICATION OF THE TEST CHEMICAL AND CONTROL SUBSTANCES: describe the application of test chemical and control substance exposure conditions in detail.</p> <p>SEEDING AND INCUBATION: describe the seeding and incubation conditions and whether precipitation was noted.</p> <p>MEASUREMENT OF CELL SURFACE EXPRESSION/LUCIFERASE ACTIVITY: describe the steps taken to ensure the suitability of the cell surface marker expression/luciferase activity measurements for the test chemical, including solvents used.</p> <p>LUCIFERASE ACTIVITY MEASUREMENTS: describe the steps taken to ensure the suitability of the luciferase activity measurements for the test chemical, including solvents used.</p> <p>DATA EVALUATION: report the cytotoxicity measurements taken and the prediction model to be used.</p>	Text template
Vehicle / solvent control	Select the vehicle/solvent as appropriate. If not available from the picklist, select 'other:' and provide detailed justification for not using a standard vehicle/solvent.	Open list
Negative control	Select the negative control as appropriate. If no negative control required (Keratinosens), select 'not applicable'. If not available from the picklist, select 'other:' and provide detailed justification for not using a standard vehicle/solvent.	Open list
Positive control	Select the positive control as appropriate. If not available from the picklist, select 'other:' and provide detailed justification for not using a standard positive control.	Open list
In chemico test system		Header 2
Details of test system	<p>Indicate the purity of the peptides used in the 'remarks' field.</p> <p>If standard peptides are not used, please select 'other:' and specify in the freetext field the exact details of the peptide used and supporting information on the scientific validity of their use.</p>	Multi select open list with remarks

Details on the study design	<p>PREPARATION OF TEST SOLUTIONS: describe how test solutions were prepared to obtain suitable concentration including specific substance details on the materials used (EC/CAS, purity, treatment of the material) etc.</p> <p>INCUBATION: describe the incubation conditions and whether precipitation was noted.</p> <p>PREPARATION OF THE HPLC: describe the steps taken to ensure the suitability of the HPLC for the test chemical, including solvents used.</p> <p>DATA EVALUATION: report the UV wavelength used for peptide/derivative detection.</p>	Text template
Vehicle solvent /	Select the vehicle/solvent as appropriate. If not available from the picklist, select 'other:' and provide detailed justification for not using a standard vehicle/solvent.	Open list
Positive control	Select the positive control as appropriate. If not available from the picklist, select 'other:' and provide detailed justification for not using a standard positive control.	Open list
In silico test system		Header 2
Details of test system	Select the test system as appropriate. If not available from the picklist, select 'other:' and provide detailed justification for not using a standard test system.	Multi select open list with remarks
Details on the study design	<p>TEST PROTOCOL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Derek Nexus: Skin sensitisation predictions according to OECD TG 497 (Annex 2): - OECD (Q)SAR Toolbox: Skin sensitisation predictions according to OECD TG 497 (Annex 2): - other: 	Text template
In vivo test system		Header 2
Test animals		Header 3
Species	<p>Select as appropriate. For <i>in vitro</i> tests, indicate the species used as source of the test system. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify. NOTE: Human data should be reported in an appropriate subsection of section 'Exposure related observations', particularly subsection 'Sensitisation data'.</p> <p>It can be useful to document, in section 'Skin sensitisation', that human data are provided by creating a record and referring to the human data in field 'Cross-reference'. This could be relevant if lack of animal experiments is defended by the availability of data on experience with human exposure.</p>	Open list
Strain	Select strain as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify. In the supplementary remarks field, also specify the substrain if not specified by picklist item. Provide rationale for choice of strain and substrain if deviating from the ones recommended by the test guideline used.	Open list with remarks
Sex	Select as appropriate. If females were used, indicate in field "Details on test animals and environmental conditions" whether nulliparous and non-pregnant.	Closed list
Details on test animals and	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for	Text template

environmental conditions	evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. Explanations: - Diet: Describe type of diet (e.g. conventional laboratory diet / caloric restriction) and whether it was provided ad libitum. - Water: Describe type (e.g. drinking water) and whether it was provided ad libitum. - IN-LIFE DATES: If required, specify the in-life dates (i.e. the phase of a study following treatment in which the test system is alive/growing).	
Study design: <i>in vivo</i> (non-LLNA)		Header 3
Induction	Record the vehicle, test substance concentrations used for induction exposure(s), the total amount of substance applied and the day(s) and duration of the induction. Copy this block of fields as appropriate.	
Route	Indicate the route of induction exposure.	Open list
Vehicle	Select 'unchanged (no vehicle)' if none was used or select vehicle used if any. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field. If the vehicle used is not from the list provided in the test guideline, a rationale should be provided.	Open list with remarks
Concentration / amount	Provide the test substance concentrations used for induction exposures and the total amount of substance applied (i.e. undiluted, %, % active substance, FCA, mg, g). Provide justification for dose selection (including results from pre-screen test, if conducted).	Multi-line text
Day(s)/duration	Indicate the day number(s) on which the induction took place and as appropriate the duration (e.g. day 5-7 and day 6-8).	Text
Adequacy of induction	Indicate if the test concentration used for the induction exposure was well-tolerated systemically and the highest to cause mild-to-moderate skin irritation, or if the highest technically applicable concentration used. If the substance is a non-irritant, indicate in field 'Details on study design' the appropriate pre-treatment applied for causing local irritation.	Open list
Induction		
Challenge	Record the vehicle, test substance concentrations used for challenge exposure(s), the total amount of substance applied and the day(s) and duration of challenge. Copy this block of fields as appropriate. Consecutive numbers can be entered in the subfield "No." for indicating multiple challenges.	
No.	For indicating multiple challenges or rechallenge select a consecutive number from drop-down list.	Closed list
Route	Indicate the route of challenge exposure.	Open list
Vehicle	Select 'unchanged (no vehicle)' if none was used or select vehicle used if any. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field. If the vehicle used is not from the list provided in the test guideline, a rationale should be provided.	Open list with remarks

Concentration / amount	Provide the test substance concentrations used for challenge exposures and the total amount of substance applied (i.e. undiluted, %, % active substance, FCA, mg, g). Provide justification for dose selection (including results from pre-screen test, if conducted).	Multi-line text
Day(s)/duration	Indicate the day number(s) on which the induction took place and as appropriate the duration (e.g. day 5-7 and day 6-8).	Text
Adequacy of challenge	Indicate if the test concentration used for the challenge exposure was the highest non-irritation dose.	Open list
Challenge		
No. of animals per dose	Provide number of animals per dose or range if different numbers were used, e.g. '10 (controls), 10-20 (in test groups)'.	Multi-line text
Details on study design	<p>For <i>in vivo</i> non-LLNA sensitisation tests, describe any range finding tests (pilot study) and for the main study the induction and challenge procedures including the type of information given in the freetext template. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p> <p>Example for Freund's Complete Adjuvant (FCA) test (partly adopted from OECD 406):</p> <p>A. INDUCTION EXPOSURE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of exposures: 5 - Exposure period: - - Test groups: TS in FCA - Control group: FCA only - Site: R flank - Frequency of applications: every 2nd day - Duration: 0-8 d - Concentrations: same throughout <p>B. CHALLENGE EXPOSURE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of exposures: 2 - Day(s) of challenge: 22 & 35 - Exposure period: - - Test groups: TS - Control group: TS - Site: L flank - Concentrations: 4 different - Evaluation (hr after challenge): 24, 48, 72 	Text template
Challenge controls	Discuss the use of a challenge (i.e. naive) control group: number and sex of animals, dose for challenge application.	Multi-line text
Positive control substance(s)	Indicate if positive control substance(s) was/were used. If yes, describe the positive control(s) in supplementary field as appropriate. If no, describe any periodic or historic positive control(s).	Closed list with remarks
Study design: in vivo (LLNA)		Header 3
Vehicle	Select 'unchanged (no vehicle)' if none was used or select vehicle used if any. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field. If the vehicle used is	Open list with remarks

	not from the list provided in the test guideline, a rationale must be provided.	
Concentration	Describe dose selection, i.e. at least 3 consecutive concentrations (100%, 50%, 25% 10%, 5%, 2.5%, 1%, 0.5% etc.) of the test substance. Adequate scientific rationale should accompany the selection of the concentration series used.	Multi-line text
No. of animals per dose	Provide number of animals per dose or range if different numbers were used.	Multi-line text
Details on study design	<p>For LLNA, LLNA:DA or LLNA:BrdU-ELISA, describe details on materials and methods as indicated in the freetext template. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Details on radio isotope: to be included in field 'Details on test material' - RANGE FINDING TESTS: Briefly describe compound solubility, irritation and lymph node proliferation response if significant. - PRE-SCREEN TESTS: Briefly describe compound solubility, irritation, systemic toxicity (changes in: nervous system function, behaviour, respiratory patterns, food and water consumption), ear thickness measurements, erythema scores (0-3 on any day of measurement). <p>MAIN STUDY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ANIMAL ASSIGNMENT AND TREATMENT: Indicate name of test method used. Comment on criteria used to consider a positive response - TREATMENT PREPARATION AND ADMINISTRATION: Describe dose preparation and administration. (e.g. for LLNA:BrdU-ELISA 25 µl of compound x was applied to the entire dorsal surface of each ear of each mouse. The application was repeated on days 2 and 3). On day 5 an injection of 0.5 ml (5mg/mouse) of BrdU (10 mg/ml) solution was made inter-peritoneally for each experimental mouse. Twenty-four hours later, the draining auricular lymph node of each ear was excised into PBS (indicate individual animal approach or pooled animal approach). A single cell suspension of lymph node cells was prepared from each mouse (describe method of cell suspension). 	Text template
Positive control substance(s)	<p>Indicate the positive control substance(s) used and give additional remarks in supplementary field as appropriate, e.g. the concentration used.</p> <p>Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify.</p>	Multi select open list with remarks
Statistics	Provide the statistical procedures employed (e.g., linear regression analysis or William's test to assess dose-response trends; Dunnett's test to make pairwise comparisons).	Multi-line text
High dose level used	Where a test method offers flexibility in the study design, for example in relation to the choice of dose levels, the	

	chosen study design shall ensure that the data generated are adequate for hazard identification and risk assessment. To this end, testing shall be performed at appropriately high dose levels. If dose (concentration) selection is limited by the physicochemical properties or biological effects of the test substance, justification shall be provided.	
Justification for deviation from the high dose level	Provide a justification for deviating from the high dose level.	Text template
Model and software	Follow instructions reported in " Model and software – common block ". Note: This block of fields is displayed only when "Type of information" is set to (Q)SAR.	Header 2
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block ".	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Positive control results	Discuss the positive control results and demonstrate that the laboratory has the capability to identify positive dermal sensitizers.	Multi-line text
In vitro / in chemico		Header 2
Results	Indicate the test results. Copy this block of fields as appropriate. In case of a robust study summary or as requested by the regulatory programme, also provide the raw data of the results (including means and standard deviations) for the test material and all controls used in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables". (Q)SAR results can be reported under the appropriate heading, i.e. ' <i>In vitro / in chemico</i> ', ' <i>In vivo</i> (non-LLNA)' or ' <i>In vivo</i> (LLNA)', depending on the applicability domain of the model behind and based on what kind of data the model was mainly validated. At least the field 'Remarks on result' should be completed by entering the adequate qualitative description of the prediction. Note that a separate field "Interpretation of results" is provided in the section "APPLICANT'S SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION" for indicating a classification based on the study results.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Group		Open list
Run / experiment	Indicate the run / experiment the measurement relates to.	Open list
Parameter	Select type of parameter from picklist, if applicable. Further details can be given in the supplementary	Open list with remarks

	remarks field. Please include EC150 and EC200 values, if those can be calculated.	
Value	Indicate also the unit of measurement e.g. μM , mM, $\mu\text{g/ml}$, mg/ml etc.	Unit measure with Closed List
At concentration		Unit measure with Open List
Cell viability		Text area
Vehicle controls validity	Indicate whether test(s) with vehicle control(s) (i.e. without test substance, with/without solvent) is/are valid. Relevant remarks can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Negative controls validity	Indicate whether test with negative control(s) is valid, i.e. substance(s) with known lack of irritation/corrosion in the test conducted. Relevant remarks can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Positive controls validity	Indicate whether test with positive control(s) is valid, i.e. substance(s) with known irritation/corrosion in the test conducted. Relevant remarks can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other:' 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Results		
Outcome of the prediction model	For DPRA, the mean peptide % depletion values have been specified for each reactivity group in the test guideline for each prediction model.	Open list
Other effects / acceptance of results	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Provide the following information as appropriate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OTHER EFFECTS: Describe any other observed effects (e.g. visible damage on test system) - DEMONSTRATION OF TECHNICAL PROFICIENCY: If required according to the test guideline, indicate if and when technical proficiency has been demonstrated using the proficiency chemicals listed in the guideline used. Upload table(s) with data for each individual proficiency chemical in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. - ACCEPTANCE OF RESULTS: Demonstrate that the assay acceptance criteria (for negative control, positive control, and variability between replicate measurements) were met in reference to historical ranges. Indicate the range of historical values if different from the ones indicated in the relevant test guideline. <p>Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme.</p>	Text template

In silico		Block
Results		Repeatable table
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Checkbox
Group		Picklist
Parameter		Picklist
Value	For the in silico prediction, a positive outcome is assigned a score of 1 and a negative outcome is assigned a score of 0.	Picklist
Remarks on results	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other:' 	Picklist
Outcome of the prediction model		Picklist
In vivo (non-LLNA)		Header 2
Results	Record the results of <i>in vivo</i> non-LLNA tests at the different readings for each test or control group used. Copy this block of fields as appropriate. Present the scores from the challenge responses in a table. (Q)SAR results can be reported under the appropriate heading, i.e. ' <i>In vitro / in chemico</i> ', ' <i>In vivo (non-LLNA)</i> ' or ' <i>In vivo (LLNA)</i> ', depending on the applicability domain of the model behind and based on what kind of data the model was mainly validated. At least the field 'Remarks on result' should be completed by entering the adequate qualitative description of the prediction.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Reading	Select from drop-down list.	Open list
Hours after challenge	Enter numeric value.	Decimal
Group	Select from drop-down list.	Open list
Dose level	If more than one concentration was tested at challenge, specify the concentration(s) the reading refers to, e.g. '0.15 g of a 10% aqueous solution'. Several dose levels can be given if the results reported in this block of fields is the same for all challenge groups, e.g. '0.15 or 0.3 g of a 10% aqueous solution'.	Text
No. with reactions +	Enter numeric value.	Integer

Total no. in group	Enter numeric value.	Integer
Clinical observations	Briefly describe relevant clinical observations.	Text
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other:' 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Results		
In vivo (LLNA)		Header 2
Results	Indicate the cell proliferation results for the test substance, i.e. either ATP (measured adenosine triphosphate content of lymphocytes) or BrdU (measured 5-bromo-2-deoxyuridine content in DNA of lymphocytes) or DPM (incorporated radioactivity as disintegrations per minute) or other. Copy this block of fields as appropriate. (Q)SAR results can be reported under the appropriate heading, i.e. ' <i>In vitro / in chemico</i> ', ' <i>In vivo</i> (non-LLNA)' or ' <i>In vivo</i> (LLNA)', depending on the applicability domain of the model behind and based on what kind of data the model was mainly validated. At least the field 'Remarks on result' should be completed by entering the adequate qualitative description of the prediction. In case of a robust study summary or as requested by the regulatory programme, also provide the raw data of the results (including means and standard deviations) for the test material and all controls used in the field "Cellular proliferation data / Observations" and/or upload a table in the field "Any other information on results incl. tables". Note that a separate field "Interpretation of results" is provided in the section "APPLICANT'S SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION" for indicating a classification based on the study results.	
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Parameter	Select type of parameter from picklist, if applicable, i.e. either SI (stimulation index) or EC3 (estimated concentration of a test substance needed to produce a stimulation index of three) or ECt (estimated concentration of a test substance needed to produce a stimulation index that is indicative of a positive response) or other (specify). Further details can be given in the supplementary remarks field.	Open list with remarks
Value	Provide the numeric value or a range of values if reported so. Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable.	Range (Decimal)

Variability	Indicate the standard deviation or other appropriate measure of variability that takes into account the inter-animal variability in both the test substance and control groups when using the individual animal approach.	Text
Test group / Remarks	Indicate the concentration of the test material, the run / experiment number the calculated value relates to and any other relevant information. Examples: Exp. 1 (0%); Exp. 1 (0.5%); Exp. 1 (1%), etc. or Mean of three runs (0%), etc.	Text
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable' and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information by selecting 'other:' 	Open list with remarks (2000)
Results		
Cellular proliferation data / Observations	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, tabulate the raw data (unless these data are given in above block of fields 'Stimulation index / EC value') and indicate any relevant observations. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Alternatively or in addition refer to appropriate table(s), which were uploaded in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Use predefined table if any or adapt table(s) from study report. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them (e.g. '... see Table 1'). Provide the results of cellular proliferation measurements (DPM values for conventional LLNA or ATP content values for LLNA: DA or BrdU content values for LLNA: BrdU-ELISA). Comment on dose-response trends and comparisons with the vehicle control group. Give statistical comparisons of group mean measurements compared to control. Indicate whether results are from the individual animals or pooled. Indicate whether the overall result is positive or negative. Note: Specific tables may be required.	Text template
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions	Follow instructions reported in " Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block "	Header 2
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1

Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1
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7.4 (Cf. 1.4 and 1.4.1) Additional toxicity information

7.5 Data on exposure – Endpoint summary

Purpose

This document is to be used to report an overview of the non-dietary exposure estimates for operator, worker, bystander, and resident as a percentage of the AOEL and AAOEL, if appropriate, according to the representative uses evaluated. The document is reflecting the list of end points for non dietary exposure (SANCO/12592/2012-rev. 2, 22 March 2019).

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.NonDietaryExpo		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to critical and non-critical GAP descriptions.	Link to endpoint
Description of key information		Header 1
	Enter a short description of the most relevant summary data. EFSA Guidance on Non-Dietary exposure, 2014, DOI:10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3874 or 2022, doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7032 (when applicable) can be consulted when preparing this summary.	Rich text area
Description of use		Header 1
Uses		Block of fields (repeatable)
Use description	Include a brief description of the use. For example: "Use: potatoes, tractor mounted equipment, application rate 2.5 kg a.s./ha"	Rich text area
Exposure scenarios		Header 2
Operator exposure		Header 3

	Describe the model, and the resulting exposure estimates (% of AOEL / %AAOEL, with appropriate personal protective equipment if necessary)	Rich text area
Worker exposure		Header 3
	Describe the model, and the resulting exposure estimates (% AOEL / %AAOEL, with appropriate personal protective equipment if necessary)	Rich text area
Bystander / resident exposure		Header 3
	Describe the model, and the resulting exposure estimates (% of AOEL / %AAOEL, with appropriate personal protective equipment if necessary)	Rich text area
Uses		
Additional information	<p>Follow instructions reported in "Additional information – common block"</p> <p>Provide additional information related to the endpoint. If there is no additional information to be reported this field may be left empty.</p>	Header 1

Links to support materials

SANCO/12592/2012-rev. 2, 22 March 2019. [Templates To Be Used For Assessment Reports and Proposals for Classification- Word Version](#)- March 2019

EFSA Guidance on the assessment of exposure of operators, workers, residents and bystanders in risk assessment for plant protection products, 2014. Available online: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/3874>

EFSA Guidance on the assessment of exposure of operators, workers, residents and bystanders in risk assessment for plant protection products, 2022. Available online: <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7032>

Richardson, Jane, Grosskopf, Claudia, Hamey, Paul Y, Machera, Kyriaki, Martin, Sabine, Jacobi, Lena Elisabeth, & Tiramani, Manuela. (2016, October 17). Exposure of operators, workers, residents and bystanders in risk assessment for plant protection products calculator (Version 30MAR2015). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161298>

7.5 Data on exposure – Endpoint study record

Purpose

This document is to be used to provide sufficient information and data to assess the extent of human exposure to the plant protection product under the proposed conditions of use, where effects on human health cannot be excluded based on data from Section 5 of Part B of the Annex to Regulation (EU) No 283/2013 and this Section.

This document can also be used to report Dislodgeable Foliar Residues studies cited in operator exposure assessments.

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ExposureRelatedObservationsOther		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data	Follow instructions reported in " Administrative data – common block "	Header 1
Data source	Follow instructions reported in " Data source – common block "	Header 1

Materials and methods	Follow instructions reported in " Material and methods – common block "	Header 1
Type of study / information	Briefly indicate the type of information (which does not fit into any of the specific chapter.)	Multi-line text
Endpoint addressed	If the study recorded gives useful information on one or several of the classic endpoints, select the endpoint(s) addressed from the picklist. Multiple selection is possible. If not listed, select 'other' and specify. NOTE: The list of endpoints provided is a generic list. Some endpoints may not be applicable for the type of study summarised in this record.	Multi select open list
Test material	Follow instructions reported in " Test material – common block "	Header 2
Method		Header 2
Ethical approval	Where ethical approval is required, indicate whether and what kind of consent was received from the persons studied. Include details in the supplementary remarks field. If 'not applicable' or 'no' is selected, give reasoning as appropriate.	Open list with remarks
Details on study design	Describe the study design including any relevant information from a study report, publication or other source. Include or attach tables or excerpts from study report as appropriate.	Text area
Exposure assessment	Indicate whether the exposure was measured or estimated. For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide further details in the following freetext field.	Closed list with remarks
Details on exposure	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. As an option you may include an excerpt from the study report. Explanations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ TYPE OF EXPOSURE: Characterise type of exposure including information on manufacturing / processing / use as applicable. If available, describe special exposure situations / workplaces. ▪ TYPE OF EXPOSURE MEASUREMENT: Indicate relevant predefined type(s); delete those being not applicable. ▪ EXPOSURE LEVELS: Give exposure level(s) reported (with units) or insert/attach table, for several exposure conditions and levels. ▪ EXPOSURE PERIOD: Describe when subjects were exposed and duration of exposure, i.e., hours, hours per day, days, days per week, weeks, months, years, person years, other. ▪ POSTEXPOSURE PERIOD: State period of time elapsed between last exposure/first examination or time study was conducted. ▪ DESCRIPTION / DELINEATION OF EXPOSURE GROUPS / CATEGORIES: If several exposure groups (e.g. different concentrations or durations) are analysed, 	Text template

	identify the exposure groups or categories, number of subjects within each group, sex, other categorical descriptions, etc.	
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Results and discussion		Header 1
Results	Provide exposure data as available and describe any relevant outcome of the study. If appropriate present the data in tabular form and/or attach excerpt(s) from the study report.	Text area
Any other information on results incl. tables	Follow instructions reported in " Any other information on results incl. tables – common block "	Header 2
Overall remarks, attachments	Follow instructions reported in " Overall remarks, attachments – common block "	Header 1
Applicant's summary and conclusion	Follow instructions reported in " Applicant's summary and conclusion – common block "	Header 1

7.6 (Cf. 1.4, other substance dataset) Available toxicological data relating to non-active substances

7.7 Supplementary studies on the plant protection product – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 5.6** of the active substance dataset

7.8 Classification and labelling of the product – Flexible record

Purpose

This document is to be used to report proposals for the classification and labelling of the plant protection product in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 shall be submitted and justified, including:

- pictograms,
- signal words,
- hazard statements, and
- precautionary statements.

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.Ghs		
Name	Instructions	Data type
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page .	Confidentiality

General Information		Header 1
Name	When a Substance or a Mixture has more than one classification and labelling record it is recommended to specify a name for each individual record so that they can be easily identified (e.g. 'classification with more/equal 0.1% of substance C' and 'classification with less than 0.1% of substance C').	Text
Not classified	Select this checkbox if your Substance or Mixture is not classified.	Check box
Implementation	The GHS implementation can be different depending on certain regions (e.g. EU, Japan, Australia). Specify the Implementation by selecting from the drop-down list. If none of the pre-defined items applies, select 'other:'. A text field is then activated next to the list field in which you can enter any freetext. If you wish to record a GHS for another region, add a new block.	Open list
Type of classification	Indicate whether the classification is harmonised or if a self-classification is provided.	Closed list
Remarks	If necessary provide any additional comments here.	Rich text area
Related composition		Header 2
Related composition	This section relates to section 1.2 (Composition – Composition ID). It allows links to be created from a classification to one or more compositions of a substance. Related composition is a repeatable block section. Click the green Plus button to add a new repeatable block. The data entry screen appears and an empty block is now ready to be filled in. Add a new block for each link.	Endpoint reference list
Classification		Header 1
Physical Hazards		Header 2
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Explosives		Row label
Flammable gases and chemically unstable gases		Row label
Aerosols		Row label
Chemicals under pressure		Row label
Oxidising gases		Row label

Gases under pressure		Row label
Flammable liquids		Row label
Flammable solids		Row label
Self-reactive substances and mixtures		Row label
Pyrophoric liquids		Row label
Pyrophoric solids		Row label
Self-heating substances and mixtures		Row label
Substances and mixtures which in contact with water emit flammable gases		Row label
Oxidising liquids		Row label
Oxidising solids		Row label
Organic peroxides		Row label
Corrosive to metals		Row label
Desensitized explosives		Row label
Health hazards		Header 2
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Acute toxicity - oral		Row label
Acute toxicity - dermal		Row label
Acute toxicity - inhalation		Row label
Skin corrosion / irritation		Row label
Serious eye damage / eye irritation		Row label

Respiratory sensitisation		Row label
Skin sensitisation		Row label
Aspiration hazard		Row label
Reproductive toxicity		Header 3
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Reproductive toxicity		Row label
Specific effect		Text
Route of exposure		Multi select closed list with remarks
Effects on or via lactation		Row label
Germ cell mutagenicity		Header 3
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Germ cell mutagenicity		Row label
Route of exposure		Multi select closed list with remarks
Carcinogenicity		Header 3
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Carcinogenicity		Row label
Route of exposure		Multi select closed list with remarks

Specific target organ toxicity - single (STOT-SE)		Header 3
Specific target organ toxicity - single (STOT-SE)		Header
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
System	Select any specific system where toxicity was observed that is considered of biological relevance.	Open list
Affected organs	Select from the multiple drop-down list the target organ(s) where toxicity was observed. This field provides context-related picklist values depending on the selection made in the preceding field 'System'.	Multi select open list
Route of exposure		Multi select closed list with remarks
Specific target organ toxicity - repeated (STOT-RE)		Header 3
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
System	Select any specific system where toxicity was observed that is considered of biological relevance.	Open list
Affected organs	Select from the multiple drop-down list the target organ(s) where toxicity was observed. This field provides context-related picklist values depending on the selection made in the preceding field 'System'.	Multi select open list
Route of exposure		Multi select closed list with remarks
Endocrine disruption for human health (EU CLP)		Header 2
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label

Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Specific concentration limits		Header 2
Concentration range (%)		Range (Decimal)
Hazard categories		Multi select closed list
Acute Toxicity Estimates (ATE)		Header 2
Oral		Numeric (decimal including unit)
Dermal		Numeric (decimal including unit)
Inhalation		Numeric (decimal including unit)
Environmental hazards		Header 2
Aquatic environment		Header 3
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Hazardous to the aquatic environment (acute / short-term)		Row label
Hazardous to the aquatic environment (long-term)		Row label
M factor		Header 4
M-Factor acute		Integer
M-Factor chronic		Integer
Ozone layer		Header 3

Hazardous to the ozone layer		Row label
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Endocrine disruption for the environment (EU CLP)		Header 3
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Persistent, Bioaccumulative and Toxic or Very Persistent, Very Bioaccumulative properties (EU CLP)		Header 3
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label
Persistent, Mobile and Toxic or Very Persistent, Very Mobile properties (EU CLP)		Header 3
Hazard category	Enter hazard category, if any.	Column label
Hazard statement	Enter hazard statement, if any.	Column label
Reason for no classification	Enter reason for no classification, if any.	Column label
Reason for classification	Enter reason for classification, if any.	Column label

Additional hazard classes		Header 2
Additional hazard classes		Text area
Additional hazard statements		Text area
Labelling		Header 1
Signal word		Closed list
Hazard pictogram		Header 2
Code		Closed list
Hazard statements		Header 2
Hazard statement		Closed list
Additional text		Text
Precautionary statements		Header 2
Precautionary statement		Closed list
Additional text		Multi-line text
Additional labelling requirements		Header 2
Additional non-GHS hazard statements		
Additional non-GHS hazard statement		Closed list
Additional text		Text
Additional labelling		
Additional labelling		Text
Notes (EU CLP)		Header 1
		Closed list

8. Residues in or on treated products, food and feed

8 (Cf. active substance, section 6) Residues in or on treated products, food and feed

9. Fate and behaviour in the environment

9. Fate and behaviour in the environment – Endpoint summary

See instructions in [Section 7](#) of the active substance dataset

9.1 Predicted concentrations in the environment

See instructions in [Section 7.1.1](#) of the active substance dataset

10. Effects on non-target organisms

The same information submitted on the microorganism (and/or on a plant protection product containing that active substance with respect to a representative use) as detailed in points 8.2.4, 8.7 and 8.8 of Part B of the Annex to Regulation (EU) No 283/2013 shall be provided for the plant protection product subject of the application, unless the applicant can:

- justify the applicability and relevance of the outcome of the assessment made on the same data submitted for the micro-organism approval (and/or on a plant protection product containing that active substance with respect to a representative use),
- predict the effects of the plant protection product on the basis of the data available for the co-formulants (e.g. qualitative and quantitative composition), as well as for the micro-organism and possible metabolites of concern (based on data submitted in accordance with in Section 8 of Part B of the Annex to Regulation (EU) No 283/2013 for the approval of the micro-organism(s) in the plant protection product), or
- justify that aquatic macrophytes will not be exposed to the components of the plant protection product (based on data submitted in accordance with Section 9).

If generation of data is required based on the provisions laid down under this point, relevant studies shall be performed.

10. Effects on non-target organisms – Flexible record

Purpose

This document should be used to provide an overall assessment of the ecotoxicological effects of the active substance/plant protection product on the different groups of non-target organisms (NTOs) based on the available studies.

For each group of NTOs (birds and other terrestrial vertebrates, aquatic organisms, bees and other non-target arthropods, soil macro, terrestrial non-target higher plants), the outcome of the risk assessment according to the agreed guidelines should be summarised.

FLEXIBLE_SUMMARY.EcotoxRiskAssessmentPesticides		
Name	Instructions	Data type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Ecotoxicological risk assessment of pesticides	This document can be used to provide an overall assessment of the toxicological effects on non-target organisms based on the studies provided in this section.	Header 1
Risk assessment to birds		Header 2
	Provide a summary of the risk assessment to birds. A table with the toxicity: exposure ratios following the EFSA birds and mammals guidance (EFSA, 2009) can be included.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to wild mammals		Header 2

	Provide a summary of the risk assessment to wild mammals. A table with the toxicity: exposure ratios following the EFSA birds and mammals guidance (EFSA, 2009) can be included.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to other terrestrial vertebrates		Header 2
	Provide a summary of the risk assessment to other non-target vertebrates other than birds and mammals.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to aquatic organisms		Header 2
	Provide a summary of the risk assessment to aquatic organisms. A table with the regulatory acceptable concentrations for the relevant groups of aquatic organisms following the EFSA aquatic guidance document (EFSA, 2013) can be included.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to bees		Header 2
	Provide a summary of the risk assessment to bees. A table with the hazard quotients and exposure: toxicity ratios for the relevant routes of exposure can be included.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to non-target arthropods other than bees		Header 2
	Provide a summary of the risk assessment to non-target arthropods other than bees. A table with the hazard quotients for the species tested and for the in-field and off-field scenarios following ESCORT 2 can be included.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to non-target soil meso- and macrofauna		Header 2
	Provide a summary of the risk assessment to soil organisms. A table with the toxicity: exposure ratios for the relevant groups of soil organisms (earthworms, collembolans, predatory mites) following the guidance document on terrestrial ecotoxicology SANCO/10329/2002 can be included.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to soil nitrogen transformation		Header 2
	Provide a summary of the risk assessment to soil nitrogen transformation.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to terrestrial non-target higher plants		Header 2

	Provide a summary of the probabilistic/deterministic risk assessment to terrestrial non-target higher plants. A table with the toxicity: exposure ratios following the guidance document on terrestrial ecotoxicology SANCO/10329/2002 can be included.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to biological methods for sewage treatment		Header 2
	Provide a summary of the risk assessment to micro-organism involved in biological sewage treatment.	Rich text area
Risk assessment to other terrestrial organisms (flora and fauna)		Header 2
		Rich text area
Additional information for the ecotoxicological risk assessment of pesticides	A document as attachment pdf/doc can be provided where the risk assessment for the different taxa is conducted according to the agreed guidelines and for addressing the EU pesticides data requirements. The original version of the document should be provided if it differs from the publication version.	Header 1

Links to supporting material:

EU Working document to the Environmental Safety Evaluation of Microbial Biocontrol Agents (SANCO/12117/201)

US EPA 885.4000 (1996) Background for non-target organism testing of microbial pest control agents

Environment and Climate Change Canada (2016), guidance document for testing the pathogenicity and toxicity of new microbial substances to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (EPS1/RM/44)

10.1 Effects on terrestrial vertebrates

10.1.1 EFFECTS ON TERRESTRIAL VERTEBRATES BIRDS – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

See instructions in **Section 8.1.1** of the active substance dataset

10.1.1 EFFECTS ON TERRESTRIAL VERTEBRATES BIRDS – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

See instructions in **Section 8.1.1** of the active substance dataset

10.1.2 EFFECTS ON TERRESTRIAL VERTEBRATES OTHER THAN BIRDS AND MAMMALS – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

See instructions in **Section 8.1.2** of the active substance dataset

10.1.2 EFFECTS ON TERRESTRIAL VERTEBRATES OTHER THAN BIRDS AND MAMMALS – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

See instructions in **Section 8.1.2** of the active substance dataset

10.2 Effects on aquatic organisms

10.2 Effects on aquatic organisms – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.2** of the active substance dataset

10.2.1 EFFECTS ON FISH

10.2.1.1 Chronic effects on fish – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.2.1.1** of the active substance dataset

10.2.1.1 Chronic effects on fish – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 8.2.1.1** of the active substance dataset

10.2.1.2 Acute effects on fish – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.2.1.2** of the active substance dataset

10.2.1.2 Acute effects on fish – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 8.2.1.2** of the active substance dataset

10.2.2 EFFECTS ON AQUATIC INVERTEBRATES

10.2.2.1 Chronic effects on aquatic invertebrates – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.2.2.1** of the active substance dataset

10.2.2.1 Chronic effects on aquatic invertebrates – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 8.2.2.1** of the active substance dataset

10.2.2.2 Acute effects on aquatic invertebrates – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.2.2.2** of the active substance dataset

10.2.2.2 Acute effects on aquatic invertebrates – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 8.2.2.2** of the active substance dataset

10.2.2.3 Aquatic sediment toxicity – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.2.2.3** of the active substance dataset

10.2.2.3 Aquatic sediment toxicity – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 8.2.2.3** of the active substance dataset

10.2.3 EFFECTS ON ALGAE – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

See instructions in **Section 8.2.3** of the active substance dataset

10.2.3 EFFECTS ON ALGAE – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

See instructions in **Section 8.2.3** of the active substance dataset

10.2.4 EFFECTS ON AQUATIC MACROPHYTES – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

See instructions in **Section 8.2.4** of the active substance dataset

10.2.4 EFFECTS ON AQUATIC MACROPHYTES – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

See instructions in **Section 8.2.4** of the active substance dataset

10.3 Effects on bees – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.3** of the active substance dataset

10.3 Effects on bees – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 8.3** of the active substance dataset

10.4 Effect on terrestrial arthropods other than bees – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.4** of the active substance dataset

10.4 Effect on terrestrial arthropods other than bees – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 8.4** of the active substance dataset

10.5 Effects on non-target soil meso- and macro-organisms in soil

10.5.1 EFFECTS ON SOIL ARTHROPODS – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

See instructions in **Section 8.5.1** of the active substance dataset

10.4.1 EFFECTS ON SOIL ARTHROPODS – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

See instructions in **Section 8.5.1** of the active substance dataset

10.5.2 EFFECTS ON SOIL MACROORGANISMS EXCEPT ARTHROPODS – ENDPOINT SUMMARY

See instructions in **Section 8.5.2** of the active substance dataset

10.5.2 EFFECTS ON SOIL MACROORGANISMS EXCEPT ARTHROPODS – ENDPOINT STUDY RECORD

See instructions in **Section 8.5.2** of the active substance dataset

10.6 Effects on non-target terrestrial plants – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.6** of the active substance dataset

10.6 Effects on non-target terrestrial plants – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 8.6** of the active substance dataset

10.7 Additional studies – Endpoint summary

See instructions in **Section 8.7** of the active substance dataset

10.7 Additional studies – Endpoint study record

See instructions in **Section 8.7** of the active substance dataset

11. Change log and additional information

11.1 Change log

See instructions in **Section 9** of the active substance dataset

11.2 Additional Transparency Regulation information

Purpose

This document is to be used to report additional information related to Transparency Regulation

FIXED_RECORD.AddTranspRegInfo		
Name	Instructions	Data type
EFSA identifiers		Header 1
EFSA system IT and regulatory identifiers	Provide here identifiers required for integration with EFSA IT systems	Block of fields (repeatable) Start
Identifier	Select the type of identifier you wish to provide using the picklist. If none of pre-defined items apply, select 'other:'. A text field is then activated next to the list field in which you can specify the type of identifier you wish to provide.	List (picklist with remarks) sup.
Identity	Enter here the identity (name, number, code) corresponding to the identifier type selected.	Text (2,000 char.)
Remarks		Text (32,768 char.)
EFSA system IT and regulatory identifiers		Block of fields (repeatable) End
Confidentiality assessment		Header 1
Contact for confidentiality assessment	Report the contact person or persons who will receive communications and decisions on the EFSA confidentiality assessment from the EFSA confidentiality team	Link to entity (multiple)
Studies requiring confidential NoS justification	This section provides the possibility to provide justifications with confidential information. A JUSTIFICATION FOR PUBLICATION MUST ALWAYS BE PROVIDED IN THE DOSSIER HEADER OR LITERATURE REFERENCE ENTITY	Header 2
Confidential NoS justification		Block of fields (repeatable) Start
	Set the confidentiality flag and regulatory purpose.	Confidentiality
NoS ID	List the Notification of Studies identifier where more information is provided in a confidential justification	Text (255 char.)

Link to study	If no notification of studies identifier exists link to the study via the literature reference entity	Link to entity (single)
Confidential justification	Confidential Justification for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) the absence of notification of a study ii) the delayed notification of a study iii) the withdrawal of a notification iv) the non-inclusion in the dossier of a notified study 	Text (2,000 char.)
Confidential NoS justification		Block of fields (repeatable) End

12. Summary and evaluation

12. Summary and evaluation – Flexible summary

See instructions in **Section 10.2** of the active substance dataset.

Additional considerations

The applicant must ensure that terms and conditions asserted by any copyright holder of publications or information submitted to EFSA are fully satisfied. The applicant should consult with copyright licensing authorities (i.e. at national level) for guidance on purchasing copyright licenses to reproduce any publications provided to EFSA. The applicant remains solely responsible and liable for obtaining all necessary authorisations and rights to use, reproduce and share the publications provided to EFSA

13. Literature Data

13. Literature Data – Flexible record

See instructions in **Section 3.5** of the active substance dataset.

14. Documents applicable to the former data requirements

This section is not intended to be used by the applicants. It was kept to maintain documents submitted in DOSSIERS prepared using previous version of IUCLID and now obsolete.

REFERENCED ENTITIES AND COMMON BLOCKS

This section includes instructions on how to compile the reference entities and the common blocks.

Reference substance

Purpose

A 'Reference substance' entity enables you to store identification information on a given substance or a given constituent of a substance, such as chemical names (EC name, CAS name, IUPAC name, synonyms, etc.), identity codes (EC number, CAS number), molecular and structural information.

Chemicals (e.g. metabolites of potential concern): Identity of the active substance – ISO common name and synonyms, Chemical name in accordance with IUPAC and CA nomenclature, CAS Reg number EC number, molecular and structural formula, molar mass.

Microorganisms: Identity of the microorganism – Name, taxonomy, species description and strain characterisation.

The Reference substance inventory gives the possibility to use the same information for the same chemical/microorganism identity avoiding duplicate data entry and to ensure that the data is centrally managed and updated. Each reference substance can be linked to an unlimited number of substance or mixture datasets. Reference substance/s can be exported and shared from the Reference substance entity manager.

REFERENCE_SUBSTANCE		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page . Important: Setting this flag ensures that substance identity is not published in any IUCLID document where a link to the reference substance is used. This should be used for confidential substances included mixture or substance composition documents.	Confidentiality
Reference substance name	Indicate name of substance, microorganism, metabolite, residue, impurity or other substance included in the dossier.	Multi-line text
IUPAC name	IUPAC name (Note that, if a name following the IUPAC nomenclature cannot be derived, you should still provide a name defining the chemical nature of the substance). For microorganisms the scientific name (genus, species and strain) should be reported in this field.	Multi-line text
Description	Specify any additional information relevant for the description of the reference substance in this field For microorganisms the taxonomic information family, genus, species, strain, serotype, pathovar or any other denomination relevant to the micro-organism should be reported. In addition it should be indicated whether the micro-organism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ is indigenous or non-indigenous at the species level to the intended area of application ▪ is a wild type 	Text template

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ is a spontaneous or induced mutant ▪ has been modified using techniques described in Part 2 of Annex IA and in Annex IB to Directive 2001/18/EC (*) of the European Parliament and of the Council 	
Inventory		Header 1
Inventory number	This field can be used to select existing substances with pre-assigned EC numbers.	Entity reference list
No inventory information available - Justification	Not relevant for EU PPP	Open list with remarks
CAS number	Indicate CAS Registry Number	Text
CAS name	Indicate CAS name	Multi-line text
CIPAC number	Indicate CIPAC number	
Synonyms		Header 1
Synonyms	<p>Provide in this table synonym identifiers of the reference substance, as appropriate.</p> <p>For microorganisms alternative names should be added in the table and the accession number/s from internationally recognised culture collections.</p> <p>EFSA paramCode should be added in the table.</p>	
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Identifier	Select the type of identifier you wish to provide using the picklist. If none of pre-defined items apply, select 'other:'. A text field is then activated next to the list field in which you can specify the type of identifier you wish to provide.	Open list
Identity	Enter here the identity (name, number, code) corresponding to the identifier type selected.	Text area
Remarks	Provide additional information if relevant	Text
Molecular and structural information		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page.</p>	Confidentiality
Molecular formula	Molecular formula (if a molecular formula cannot be derived from the reference substance, a justification should be indicated in the Remarks field at the bottom of the section)	Multi-line text
Molecular weight	Molecular weight should be reported as a single numeric value	Range (Decimal)

SMILES notation	The SMILES notation should be in the canonical form https://cactus.nci.nih.gov or generated by ChemSketch or ChemDraw	Multi-line text
InChI	The IUPAC international chemical identifier https://cactus.nci.nih.gov or generated by ChemSketch or ChemDraw	Multi-line text
InChIKey	The condensed, 27 character InChIKey is a hashed version of the full InChI (using the SHA-256 algorithm)	Multi-line text
Structural formula	The structural formula for the active substance https://chem.nlm.nih.gov/chemidplus/structure3D/viewer/ ChemSketch, ChemDraw	Image
Remarks	Provide additional information if relevant. Such information may for example include an explanation to why molecular and structural information could not be provided due to the nature of the substance.	Text area
Chemical structure files	Upload chemical structures files (both machine readable and an image file) For machine readable files the format should be .sk2 or .cdx or .mol For image files the format should be jpg or png	
Structure file	Select file to be attached	Single file attachment
Remarks on structure file	Provide additional information if relevant.	Text
Related substances	Not relevant for EU PPP	Header 1
Identifier	Not relevant for EU PPP	Open list
Identity	Not relevant for EU PPP	Text area
Remarks	Not relevant for EU PPP	Text
Relation	Not relevant for EU PPP	Open list
Group category information /	Insert information about chemical groups and categories the substance belongs to.	Multi-line text

Links to supporting material:CIPAC number: <https://cipac.org/index.php/code-numbers/navigate-code-numbers><https://www.cas.org/support/documentation/chemical-substances>European Food Safety Authority, 2023. Harmonized terminology for scientific research. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.779880><https://iupac.org/who-we-are/divisions/division-details/inchi/><https://www.iso.org/committee/50160/x/catalogue/>http://www.alanwood.net/pesticides/index_cn_frame.html<https://cactus.nci.nih.gov/chemical/structure/><https://iuclid6.echa.europa.eu/inventories-iuclid>

Legal entity

Purpose

Submissions require a Legal entity which must be defined including contact details prior to submission. A Legal Entity (LE) may represent anything between a complex business structure and a simple organised business, for example, a corporation, a company, or a single person. LEs are identified by their name, universally unique identifier (UUID), address, country, and general contact information. You can create a LEO via ECHA accounts.

A legal entity should identify in an unambiguous manner a company or organisation with a role in the submission of dossiers. The submissions attributed to a specific company/applicant should all have the same legal entity. The same applies to third party consultants, they should also maintain a unique legal entity that can be included in the 'Third Party' field.

Information provided in the Legal entity should be similar to that provided in a publicly accessible company register. It should contain the address and contact details, including fax and phone number as well as e-mail address, of the legal person.

Note: information provided in the Legal Entity is published. Hence, no personal information relating to natural persons should be provided under these fields.

Note that information regarding the Contact person is to be managed in the Contact entity manager. The information provided in the Contact entity is by default not published.

If you are installing a local version of IUCLID, a LEO will have been created during the installation of the client version of IUCLID. You can then export it from IUCLID and import it to you ECHA account. If you have an ECHA account and define a LEO there, you can export the LEO and import it to your own local IUCLID installation.

You can add more legal entities within the IUCLID application via the inventory.

LEGAL_ENTITY		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
General information		Tab
Legal name	Indicate name of the legal entity i.e. Company name	Text
Legal entity type	Select one legal entity type from the dropdown menu. If other, please include an explanation in the free text field below.	List (picklist)
Remarks	Add any additional information on the legal entity, if relevant	Text
Other names		Block of fields (repeatable)
Name	Other names can be specified and if needed these names can be marked as confidential	
Address		Header 1
	See Confidentiality Requests	Confidentiality
Address 1	Street address of the legal entity	Text
Address 2	Secondary address, if relevant	Text
Postal Code	Postal code of the legal entity	Text
Town	Town of the legal entity	Text
Region/State	Region/State of the legal entity	Text
Country	Select the country in which the legal entity is located from the dropdown menu. If other, enter the appropriate country information in the free text field below.	List (picklist)

Phone	Phone number of the legal entity (this field must not contain personal data, therefore e.g. the number of a switchboard should be provided)	Text
Fax	Fax number of the legal entity (this field must not contain personal data)	Text
Email	Email address of the legal entity (this field must not contain personal data, therefore e.g. the email address of a functional mailbox should be provided)	Text
Website	Legal entity website	Text
Legal entity identifiers	Optional: Other identifiers can be reported. Legal entity identifiers, Regulatory programme identifiers, and Other IT system identifiers. Each type contains a menu from which relevant sub-types of identifier can be selected. For example, Legal entity has an option for DUNS (Data Universal Numbering System for identification of a Legal Entity. Click on New Item and set values. See Confidentiality Requests.	Tab
Contact information	See instructions reported below under "Contact entity" common block	Tab

Links to supporting material:

<https://echa.europa.eu/support-echa-accounts-and-eu-login>

https://iuclid6.echa.europa.eu/documents/21812392/22308501/iuclid_functionalities_html_en.pdf/9d01cb53-902d-dbb6-fb00-fa141688c395

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/21721613/echa_accounts_en.pdf

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4JGsQUbGYqw>

Contact entity

Note: contact entities must never be claimed confidential (using the confidentiality flags in the documents where they are referenced) because they are not published by default.

CONTACT_ENTITY		
Name	Instructions	Data Type
General information		Header 1
Contact type	Select one contact type from the dropdown menu. If other, enter the appropriate contact type in the free text field below.	Open list
Last name	Last name of the contact person. Note that this field is mandatory	Text
First name	First name of the contact person.	Text
Organisation	Name of the Organisation. Note that this field is mandatory	Text
Department	e.g. scientific department.	Text
Title	Title of the contact person (e.g. Mr.).	Text
Phone	Phone number of the contact person.	Text
Mobile	Mobile phone number of the contact person.	Text
Fax	Fax number of the contact person.	Text

Email	Email address of the contact person.	Text
Address 1	Street address of the contact person.	Text
Address 2	Secondary address, if relevant	Text
Postal code	Postal code of the street address of the contact person.	Text
Town	Town of the contact person.	Text
Region / state	Region/State of the contact person.	Text
Country	Select the country in which the contact person is located from the dropdown menu. If other, enter the appropriate country information in the free text field below.	Open list
Remarks	Any additional information, if relevant.	Text area

Literature reference

Purpose

The literature Reference entity should be used for storage of bibliographic metadata with attached documents including full study reports and published scientific papers and for linking studies to the Notification of Studies Database.

It is important to create a Literature reference for all studies used as evidence in the dossier. This would also include all relevant studies selected for full-text assessment identified from a literature search (when required). The literature Reference entity should always be linked in the "data source" section of Endpoint Study Records.

Additional considerations

The applicant must ensure that terms and conditions asserted by any rightsholder of studies, information or data submitted to EFSA are fully satisfied. The applicant may consult with copyright licensing authorities (i.e. at national level) for guidance on purchasing the appropriate licenses to provide studies, information or data to EFSA, taking into account the proactive disclosure requirements as detailed in the relevant section of this manual. For publications already available to the public upon payment of fees (e.g. studies published in scientific journals) for which the applicant does not have or cannot obtain IPRs for the purposes of the proactive public disclosure requirements, the applicant must provide (a) a copy of the relevant publications along with the relevant bibliographic references/ citations for scientific assessment purposes only, in the confidential version of its application and (b) these relevant bibliographic references/citations where these publications are available to the public in the non-confidential version of its application for public dissemination on the OpenEFSA portal.

LITERATURE		
Name	Instructions	Data type
General information		Header 1
Reference Type	<p>Select 'study report' for a full study report used as a data source for an endpoint study record.</p> <p>Select 'publication' for relevant studies identified from a literature search to address data requirements.</p> <p>Select 'other company data' to characterise any unpublished information from a company other than a study report.</p> <p>For any other select 'other:' and specify.</p> <p>Only in case of a publication already available to the public (studies published in scientific journals or similar publications) but subject to access restrictions (e.g. upon payment of a fee) for which the applicant does not have or cannot obtain IPRs for the purposes of the proactive</p>	Open list

	public disclosure requirements, select 'publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)'.	
Title	Report title of the study report, publication or other report type	Text
Author	Report author names for the study. These will be redacted from the published dossier for unpublished toxicology studies.	Multi-line text
Year	The year the report must be reported (this is used for sorting and filtering)	Integer
Bibliographic source	For published studies information on the journal and edition should be completed. This should include the DOI (Digital Object Identifier)	Text
Testing facility	For study reports information on the testing facility should be completed. This information will not be published for studies involving tests on vertebrate animals.	Text
Report date	Specify the full date of the study report, e.g. '2005-05-12' for 12 May 2005. Note that the 'Year' subfield should always be completed for sorting and searching purposes. By default, the date of the final report is expected here. In case of a draft report, this field should be left empty, and the expected date of the final report as well as a justification on why a draft report was provided should be given in the 'Remarks' field below.	Date
Report number	Specify the report number allocated by the testing laboratory. This information will not be published for studies involving tests on vertebrate animals.	Text
Study sponsor	Information on the source of funding of the study can be provided.	Text
Study number	Report the company identifier, if it differs from the laboratory report number	Text
Other study identifier(s)	Applies to study reports. When other study identifiers are available e.g. NOS number or MAP number, click on 'New item' and compile relevant fields accordingly.	
Study ID type	For all studies carried out or commissioned after March 2021 for which the study notification requirement applies: - Select 'Notification of studies (NoS) ID and report the NoS ID in the 'Study ID' field below. For studies carried out or commissioned before March 2021: - Select 'Notification of studies (NoS) ID and provide a justification for not providing a NoS ID in the 'Remarks' field e.g. "Study was commissioned before 27 March 2021". For rat/plant/livestock metabolism studies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ if a MSS/DER composer file is already available in the existing collections of maps (and therefore is not attached to the dossier), select 'other' and specify "Unique Individual MetaPath File Number (MAP-number/card number)" in the free text field. Optionally, if a Master Record Identification (MRID) is 	Open list

	<p>available for the existing MSS/DER composer file, create an additional item and select "Master Record Identification (MRID)".</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If a MSS/DER composer file is not available in the collection of maps and is submitted within the dossier, leave this field empty. 	
Study ID	Report the relevant identification number (e.g. the NoS ID generated from the NoS database).	Text
Remarks	<p>If the study was not notified provide a justification to explain why the study is included in the dossier to meet the data requirements but was not included in the Notification of Studies database. Example 'Study commissioned before 27 March 2021'.</p> <p>Provide any remarks on the literature reference. In case of a draft study report, please indicate the expected date of the final report as well as a justification on why a draft report was provided.</p>	Text area
Attachments		Header 1
Attachment type	<p>Select 'full study report' to identify the original study report. Only one set of attachments (original and sanitised) can be set to 'full study report'.</p> <p>Use 'other' to indicate the type of content of the other sets of attachments e.g. addendum.</p> <p>For rat/plant/livestock metabolism studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ if a MSS/DER composer file is newly created for this dossier (because it was not available in the existing collections of maps), select "other" and specify "MSS composer file" or "DER composer file". ▪ if a MSS/DER composer file is already available in the existing collections of maps, only the reference to the Individual MetaPath File Number (MAP-number) is required (cf. above instructions in "Other study identifier(s)"). 	Open list
Attached confidential document	<p>If the applicant has selected the option "publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)" from the drop-down list pertaining to the field "GeneralInfo.ReferenceType", a full copy of the relevant publication in PDF format needs to be provided under the field "Attached confidential document".</p> <p>For the purposes of proactive publication, it is sufficient to provide the following bibliographic metadata in the literature reference entry enabling the retrieval of the published literature online: title, author, year and bibliographic source. No public version of the published literature must be provided.</p> <p>If the applicant has not selected the option "publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)" from the drop-down list pertaining to the field "GeneralInfo.ReferenceType", the original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions. If a file is uploaded under this field,</p>	Single file attachment

	<p>(a) confidentiality claim(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential via the related endpoint record and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.</p> <p>For rat/plant/livestock metabolism studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ if a MSS/DER composer file is newly created for the dossier (because it was not available in the existing collections of maps) the newly created MSS/DER composer file should be attached here. ▪ if a MSS/DER composer file is already available in the existing collections of maps it is not required to be attached here. 	
<p>Attached (sanitised) document for publication</p>	<p>The applicant has selected the option "publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)" from the drop-down list pertaining to the field "GeneralInfo.ReferenceType":</p> <p>Only a citation including the abstract of the relevant publication should be uploaded in this field. The uploaded attachment will be included in the published dossier.</p> <p>The applicant has not selected the option "publication (copyright not owned for reproduction)" from the drop-down list pertaining to the field "GeneralInfo.ReferenceType":</p> <p>any document uploaded here must be uploaded in their public (non-confidential) version. The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised. Save for the elements blackened, if applicable, content and layout-wise the public version must be fully identical with the confidential version. Upon conclusion of the confidentiality assessment, if applicable, a revised public version removing the redactions relating to confidentiality requests that were rejected in part or in full must be uploaded here.</p> <p>Other supporting documentation e.g. addendum can be uploaded.</p> <p>For rat/plant/livestock metabolism studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ if a MSS/DER composer file is newly created for the dossier (because it was not available in the existing collections of maps) and confidentiality requests are made on the MSS.xml /DER.xml file (regarding confidential business information (CBI) or personal data (PD)), a sanitised pdf version of the word report generated from the MSS/DER render function, where the items for which a confidentiality request has been submitted are blackened, must be attached here (in case no 	<p>Single file attachment</p>

	<p>confidentiality requests are submitted with regard to the MSS.xml /DER.xml file a pdf version without blackening for proactive publication must be attached here).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ if a MSS/DER composer file is already available in the existing collections of maps it is not required to be attached it here. 	
Remarks	<p>Additional remarks on the uploaded literature reference content can be added here.</p> <p>Note: if an applicant provides a sanitised/public attachment which contains personal data (and this is not an issue because the document is already publicly available), this should be mentioned in the Remarks field to avoid misunderstanding.</p>	Text

Links to supporting material:

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/stakeholders/transparency-regulation-implementation>

Practical arrangement for Notification of studies

UUID: b7a08e40-7dbd-4591-9d54-fec23c7bda03

General information

Reference Type
study report

Title*
An avian oral pathogenicity and toxicity study in the bobwhite

Author
An author

Year
1993

Bibliographic source
None

Testing facility
Laboratory A, Country B

Report date
1993-06-23

Report number
None

Study sponsor
Study sponsor

Study number
xxxxx123456

Other study identifier(s) [+ New item](#) [📄 Import file](#) [▼](#)

#	Study ID type	Study ID	Remarks
1	Notification of Studies (NoS) ID	EFSA_2021_793478584756987	NOS_ID

Attachments [+ New item](#) [📄 Import file](#) [▼](#)

#	Attachment type	Attached confidential document	Attached (sanitised) documen...
1	other: Raw data	None	BirdMeasuredEndpoints.csv
2	full study report	Full original study report.pdf	Sanitised Study Report.pdf

Remarks
None

Test material

Purpose

The Test material describes the identity of the material(s) used in a study. Each Test material entry consists of a Composition used to report the different constituents of the test material, plus additional details such as the test material form and purity. Note that the composition/purity refers to the concentration of the active substance in the plant protection product and not to the purity of the test material itself.

Test material must clearly identify the batches used as test material in the different studies included in the dossier and should be as detailed as possible. Providing accurate data for the Test material will give the evaluator an overview of which batches were used in the studies submitted in the dossier.

When carrying out toxicological, ecotoxicological, environmental and residue testing and assessment, the test material used should essentially be the same. In the case of studies in which dosing extends over a period of time (e.g. repeated dose studies), dosing shall be done using a single batch of active substance if the stability permits this. When tests are conducted using the purified active substance, the purity must be ≥ 980 g/kg of stated specification otherwise a justification must be provided if the degree of purity achieved is lower.

The test material of studies reported within the active substance dataset should have the reference substance of the active substance as a main constituent. Exceptions can be made e.g. in case of isomeric composition of the active substance.

For the **product**: A detailed description of the composition used shall be provided.

Microorganisms: Where studies are conducted using microorganisms produced in the laboratory or in a pilot plant production system, the studies must be repeated using microorganisms as manufactured, unless it can be demonstrated that the test material used is essentially the same for the purposes of the testing and assessment

TEST_MATERIAL		
Name	Instructions	Type
Name	Indicate number of the batch	Multi-line text
Composition		Header 1
Composition	Use this repeatable block of fields for providing details on all relevant constituents, impurities and additives of the test material, including their concentration if known. If the test material refers to a mixture/product composition, there is no need to enter values for the fields Type, Reference substance, Concentration and Remarks, because in this context those values are relevant only for a substance.	Block of fields (repeatable list)
Component flag		Confidentiality
Type	Indicate for each component if it is a constituent, impurity or additive. In the case of co-formulants, safeners and synergists, from IUCLID 6.9 the specific function must be selected in the picklist.	Closed list
Reference substance	Link to the reference substance for the component.	Entity reference field
Concentration	Indicate concentration of the component. For the chemical active substance and impurities this should be in g/kg. For microorganisms, select the most appropriate unit.	Range with open list (Decimal)
Remarks	Specific remarks related to the concentration of the component can be reported in this field.	Multi-line text
Composition / purity: other information	'analytical grade' or 'technical grade' can be used to provide a qualitative indication of the purity for active substances where quantification is not technically possible.	Open list with remarks
Other characteristics		Header 2
Test material form	Select the form of the test material.	Open list with remarks (2000)

Details on test material	Provide the expiry date. Differences between non-radio labelled and radio labelled can be indicated in this field.	Text template
Confidential details on test material	The percent difference in concentration from the reference specification can be indicated for the active substance and impurities.	Text template

Links to supporting material:

Guidance Document on the assessment of the equivalence of technical materials of substances regulated under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009. SANCO/10597/2003 -rev 10.1 https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-10/pesticides_guidance_equivalence-chemicals_en.pdf

Template 1.1– Template for presentation the assessment for the equivalence of batches (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4557366>)

Endpoint Summaries – Common blocks

Administrative data – common block

Name	Instructions	Data Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s). For further information see: "User Guide: submission of confidentiality requests" available under the IUCLID software section of the Toolkit page "	Confidentiality
Link to relevant study record(s)		Header 1
Link to relevant study record(s)	Provide here the link(s) to the study record(s) supporting the choice of the key value for assessment. The study(ies) giving rise to the highest concern should be chosen. The following factors, among others, should be taken into account when the study record is selected: quality of the study (e.g. Klimisch score), type of study (e.g. duration, experimental design, observed effects), whether or not the study is GLP. Please provide your rationale for the selection of the relevant study record in the field "Additional information".	Cross-reference: ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AnalyticalMethods
Description of key information		Header 1
	If all key information is provided in the linked study records, this field can be left empty. In case there is no linked study record, or in case you want to point to specific information in the linked study record, provide a summary of the key information related to the studies here. The summary could include, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the test type - the test guideline used (and any deviations from it) - the test organism - the exposure duration - other contextual information on the origin of the key value 	Rich text area

The screenshot shows the IUCLID 6.9 interface for a study titled "Solubility in water.001". The "Administrative data" section is highlighted with a red box and includes the following fields:

- Link to relevant study record(s):** Study name / type: WaterSolubility
- Description of key information:** None
- Key value for chemical safety assessment:** Water solubility: None; at the temperature of: None
- Additional information:** None

The "Set Flags" dialog box is open, showing the following options:

- Confidentiality:** Please select
- Justification:** Insert existing templates
- Use restricted to selected regulatory programmes:** 0/32768

A blue arrow points from the "Administrative data" section to the "Set Flags" dialog box.

Additional information – common block

Name	Instructions	Type
Additional information		Header 1
	<p>Provide information related to the assessment of the endpoint, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> any endpoint specific information relevant for the interpretation of the results the rationale for the choice of the key study(ies) and the choice for the key value that characterises the endpoint information on the potential data gaps and the quality of the whole database for this endpoint relevance of the results for the risk assessment (e.g. in case no effects have been observed at the limit dose) the rationale for any user-derived values for the key result for assessment (for example, if a corrected value or a geometric mean is reported) any additional information such as epidemiological data or higher tier testing 	Rich text area

	(e.g. mesocosm studies or field studies) when relevant If there is no additional information to be reported, this field may be left empty.	
Attached background material		
Attached confidential document	Provide any additional documents relevant for the assessment of the endpoint, for example, a scientific publication. Provide the original version of any document that contains confidential material.	Single file attachment
Attached (sanitised) documents for publication	If required, public (non-confidential) versions of other relevant documents can be attached. These attachments should be sanitised, if needed.	Single File Attachment
Remarks	As appropriate, include remarks, e.g. a short description of the content of the attached document, if the file name is not self-explanatory.	Text
Attached background material		

Additional information

None

[Attached background material](#)

[+ New item](#) [📄 Import file](#) [▼](#)

#	Attached confidential docu...	Attached (sanitised) docum...	Remarks
1	None	Animal model 2017 (2).xls	OECD Animal burden calculator

Endpoint study records – Common blocks

Administrative data – common block

Name	Instructions	Type
Administrative data		Header 1
	<p>Use this field to set flags for confidentiality and regulatory purpose(s).</p> <p>For further information see “Confidentiality of dossiers submitted via IUCLID - practical instructions for applicant”.</p>	Confidentiality
Endpoint	<p>From the picklist select the relevant endpoint addressed by this study summary. An endpoint must always be selected when entering data into an Endpoint Study Record.</p> <p>In some cases, there is only one endpoint title, which may be entered automatically depending on the software application.</p> <p>If multiple study types are covered by the same data entry form, the specific study type should be selected. If none matches, select the more generic endpoint description '<Generic endpoint>, other' (e.g. Skin irritation / corrosion, other) and give an explanation in the adjacent text field. The generic endpoint title reflects the title of the corresponding OECD Harmonised Template (OHT).</p> <p>Please note: For (Q)SAR studies, if an 'in silico' option does not exist, the generic endpoint title should be selected, normally with no need to fill in the adjacent text field, as '(Q)SAR' needs to be indicated in field 'Type of information' and the model should be described in field 'Justification of non-standard information' or 'Attached justification'. A specific endpoint title may be used, if addressed by the (Q)SAR information, i.e. the model behind has been validated by experimental data addressing this endpoint.</p> <p>Note: For the purpose of OHTs, an 'endpoint' is defined in the rather broad sense as an observable or measurable inherent property of a chemical substance which may be specified by the relevant regulatory framework as 'information requirement' (e.g. Boiling point, Sub-chronic toxicity: oral, Fish early-life stage toxicity). In a narrower sense, the term '(eco)toxicity endpoint' refers to an outcome or effect observed in a study.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Type of information	<p>Indicate 'experimental study' or 'read-across from similar mixture/product' or 'read-across from supporting substance (structural analogue or surrogate)' or 'read-across based on grouping of substances (category approach)' unless the information is retrieved from a literature search in this case indicate 'other': 'Study from literature search'.</p>	Open list with remarks
Adequacy of study	<p>Indicate the purpose of the record selecting the adequacy in terms of usefulness for fulfilling the information requirements for the hazard/risk assessment.</p>	Closed list

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A key study is a study that has been identified as most suitable to describe an endpoint from the perspective of quality, completeness and representativeness of data. • A supporting study provides some additional information to support the conclusions from the key study/ies or the weight of evidence approach. • A weight of evidence is selected to indicate that an endpoint study record contributes to a weight of evidence approach. • Disregarded due to major methodological deficiencies is a study that is available to the applicant but is not taken into account because of lack of reliability or because the study is obsolete. • Other information is other available information which does not directly contribute to the conclusions for the setting the endpoint. <p>For each data requirement at least one 'key study' or two records identified as 'weight of evidence' is expected unless data waiving has been indicated.</p> <p>Where 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' is selected, the Validation assistant checks for document completeness.</p>	
Robust study summary	Not relevant for EU-PPP	Check box
Used for classification	Not relevant for EU-PPP	Check box
Used for SDS	Not relevant for EU-PPP	Check box
Study period: start date	<p>If applicable indicate the period during which the study was conducted, i.e. start date.</p> <p>If more than one start date is available in the study report, please indicate the one relevant for NoS obligations.</p> <p>For (Q)SAR predictions, add date of QPRF.</p> <p>Note: independent of the study period, the in-life period (i.e. the phase of a study following treatment in which the test system is alive/growing) may have to be specified for some toxicology endpoints.</p> <p>Note: for 'Notified' studies this should be after the date of notification.</p>	Text
End date	Indicate the end date of the study	Text
Remark	Add remarks if relevant	Text
Reliability	<p>The term reliability defines the inherent quality of a test report or publication.</p> <p>In field Reliability, enter a reliability score as judged at your discretion, i.e. 1 (reliable without restriction), 2 (reliable with restrictions), 3 (not reliable) or 4 (not assignable).</p> <p>The "other:" option may be selected if this scoring system is not used.</p> <p>Studies indicated as key study must have a reliability score of 1 or 2.</p> <p>The validation check will verify consistency between 'Adequacy of study' field and 'Reliability' field (EU_PPP_007, EU_PPP_003).</p>	Open list

	<p>Further explanations on the reliability assessment can be provided in the 'Rationale for reliability incl. deficiencies' field.</p> <p>In terms of 'Acceptability / Reliability'</p> <p>Key studies and weight of evidence studies are considered to have 'Acceptability / Reliability' = Yes.</p> <p>A supporting study is considered to be 'Supportive only'</p> <p>The others are considered to have 'Acceptability / Reliability' = No.</p>	
Rationale for reliability incl. deficiencies	<p>Describe the rationale for the reliability score chosen considering the possible impact of deficiencies and/or implications on test results.</p> <p>The deviations from the guideline should be described in 'Test guideline' section but the impact of these deviations should be considered in the rationale for reliability.</p> <p>When assessing an older study against the current guideline, the current guideline can be specified in this field.</p> <p>Standard justifications from picklist may be sufficient in some cases. Otherwise select 'Other' and provide for additional explanation in the 'Remarks' field.</p> <p>For (Q)SAR results (i.e. 'Type of information' is '(Q)SAR'), reliability scores are associated to the uncertainty of the result as described in the OECD (Q)SAR Assessment Framework.</p>	Open list with remarks (32000)
Data waiving	<p>If no 'key study' or 'weight of evidence' study is provided for a data requirement, then data waiving must always be completed. The validation check will flag when this field must be completed (EU_PPP_013).</p> <p>Select the reason for data waiving or other and provide a justification in 'Justification for data waiving' field.</p>	Closed list
Justification for data waiving	<p>In addition to the more generic justification selected in the preceding field 'Data waiving', it is possible to provide here a more detailed justification.</p> <p>To this end one of the specific standard phrase(s) can be selected if it/they give an appropriate rationale of the description given in the preceding field 'Data waiving'.</p> <p>If you select the option 'Other' you need to indicate the type of data waiving you are submitting</p> <p>Validation check will flag uncomplete compiling (EU_PPP_002).</p>	Multi select open list with remarks (32000)
Justification for type of information	<p>This field can be used for entering free text. As appropriate, one of the freetext templates can be selected (e.g. Justification for read-across (analogue)) to use pre-defined headers and bulleted elements. Delete/add elements as appropriate.</p> <p>Consult any programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) on what should be taken into account when providing justifications or whether specific reporting formats should be used.</p>	Text template

	<p>Explanations:</p> <p>Option 1: Type 'Waiving of standard information':</p> <p>This field should be used for entering any further lines of argumentation, if necessary, in addition to those provided in the field 'Justification for data waiving'.</p> <p>Option 2: Type 'Experimental study planned / Testing proposal':</p> <p>Further details can be entered here on the study design / methodology proposed in addition to details given in the distinct fields on test guideline, test material, species, route of administration and other relevant fields.</p> <p>Option 3: Type '(Q)SAR prediction':</p> <p>This freetext template can be used and modified as appropriate for providing a justification for the fitness-for-purpose of (Q)SAR results according to the assessment elements of the OECD (Q)SAR Assessment Framework.</p> <p>Option 4: Type 'Read-across (analogue)' and Option 5: Type 'Read-across (category)'</p> <p>This freetext template can be used and modified as appropriate for providing a justification for read-across, particularly if it is endpoint-specific.</p> <p>Please note: Any information that can be re-used for several study summaries can be entered once and then assigned to the relevant studies using either the 'Attached justification' or 'Cross-reference' feature.</p>	
Attached justification		Header 2
Attached justification	<p>A document can be uploaded to support data waiving, but it is recommended to complete in full the data waiving fields.</p> <p>Upload file by clicking the upload icon.</p>	Single file attachment
Reason purpose /	<p>Indicate the reason for / purpose of the attached document. Select the relevant item from the picklist or, if none applies, select 'justification, other:' and specify.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Cross-reference	<p>In case the study has been reported for another data requirement use cross reference to link to the study to this section.</p> <p>The creation of duplicate versions of endpoint studies should be avoided.</p> <p>Cross reference should be used to link to an 'Analytical Methods' document when a specific method is used in a study. This allows an overview of methods used in different studies e.g. toxicology and ecotoxicology.</p>	

Reason purpose cross-reference / for	Select the appropriate reason of the cross-reference, i.e. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ adverse outcome pathway (AOP) (in case the information is related to a key event that is part of an AOP). Consult the AOP wiki at: https://aopwiki.org) and provide the reference in the remarks field ▪ assessment report (for referring to a record that contains an assessment report as attachment) ▪ data waiving: supporting information (for referring to a record containing relevant endpoint information that is used to justify a data waiver) ▪ defined approach for combining with results from another methods (in vitro, in chimico, in silico) ▪ exposure-related information (for referring to a record containing exposure-related information that is used for instance to justify a data waiver) ▪ method used in study ▪ read-across source (for linking to another study summary used for read-across. This can be useful in cases where results are derived from one or several read-across sources and recorded in a separate (target) study summary.) ▪ read-across supporting information (for linking to another record which contains read-across justification that applies also for the current study summary) ▪ (Q)SAR model reporting (QMRF) (for referring to a record containing the relevant model description. Note: The (Q)SAR prediction should be reported specifically for each endpoint in the field 'Justification for type of information'.) ▪ reference to other assay used for intermediate effect derivation (for optional indication in a study summarising 'intermediate effects' if reference is made to the outcome of another assay) ▪ reference to same study (e.g. if different species were tested and the results recorded in different records), ▪ reference to other study (e.g. if another study is considered relevant in the interpretation of the test results), ▪ other: (to be specified). 	Open list with remarks
Related information	As appropriate, select the record containing the related information, thus creating a link.	Endpoint reference field
Remarks	If relevant, add remarks	Text area

Links to support material:

Appendix to: EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2011. Submission of scientific peer-reviewed open literature for the approval of pesticide active substances under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009. EFSA Journal 2011;9(2):2092. 49 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.2092

<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/action/downloadSupplement?doi=10.2903%2Fj.efsa.2011.2092&file=efs22092-sup-0001-Appendix.pdf>

Administrative data None EU: PPP

Endpoint
stability of residues in stored commodities

Type of information
experimental study

Adequacy of study
key study

Robust study summary

Used for classification

Used for SDS

Study period
6. April 1993 - 27. April 1995

Reliability
1 (reliable without restriction)

Rationale for reliability incl. deficiencies
guideline study

Data waiving
None

Justification for data waiving
None

Justification for type of information
None

Reason / purpose for cross-reference
reference to other study
Validation data for the analytical method(s) used in the present study

Related information
 AnalyticalMethods (Endpoint Study Record) | 4.1.1 NEW_Adolph S. (2013)

Remarks
None

Data waiving
other justification

Justification for data waiving
 other: Study not needed due to the use described in the GAP document

Data source – common block

Name	Instructions	Data Type
Data source		Header 1
Reference	<p>Link to Literature reference.</p> <p>Indicate the bibliographic reference of the study report or publication the study summary is based on. Provide general information such as the Title, Author, Year, Bibliographic source, Testing Facility, Report Number, Study number, Report date etc. as requested in the core template for literature search (https://www.oecd.org/ehs/templates/Generic%20elements%20for%20all%20OHTs.zip).</p> <p>Always enter the primary reference in the first block of fields or sort it to the first position, if there is more than one reference to be cited. Copy this block of fields for specifying any other references related to this record (e.g. report of a preliminary study or other documentation). If results of a study report have been published, indicate the full citation of the publication(s) in addition to the reference of the original study.</p>	Literature reference list
Data access	<p>Select appropriate indication for data access. Enter 'Not applicable' if the summary consists of information that is commonly accessible such as guidance on safe use.</p> <p>Select 'data submitter has permission to refer' if the information requirement can be covered based on a permission to refer to old data as issued by the relevant regulatory agency. In addition, provide, in the adjacent free-text field, the statement according to instructions you received from the relevant regulatory authority together with the permission to refer.</p>	Open list with remarks
Data protection claimed	<p>Indicate as appropriate.</p> <p>Note: 'yes' should be selected only if 'Data submitter is data owner' or 'Data submitter has Letter of Access'. Options 'yes, but willing to share' or 'yes, but not willing to share' may be relevant for specific regulatory programmes where the submitter is requested to indicate whether he is willing to share studies conducted (e.g. with vertebrates).</p> <p>In the supplementary remarks field, include an explanation as appropriate, i.e. justification for denial of sharing the corresponding study or refer to a document attached that provides justification (e.g. 'for justification see attached document X').</p> <p>Note that this field is always published so do not put any confidential data in it.</p>	Closed list with remarks

Additional considerations:

The applicant must ensure that terms and conditions asserted by any rightsholder of studies, information or data submitted to EFSA are fully satisfied. The applicant may consult with

copyright licensing authorities (i.e. at national level) for guidance on purchasing the appropriate licenses to provide studies, information or data to EFSA, taking into account the proactive disclosure requirements as detailed above. For publications already available to the public upon payment of fees (e.g. studies published in scientific journals) for which the applicant does not have or cannot obtain IPRs for the purposes of the proactive public disclosure requirements, the applicant must provide (a) a copy of the relevant publications along with the relevant bibliographic references/ citations for scientific assessment purposes only, in the confidential version of its application and (b) these relevant bibliographic references/citations where these publications are available to the public in the non-confidential version of its application for public dissemination on the OpenEFSA portal.

Data source

Reference

 study report | Flammability of solids | An Author | 2000

Data access

data no longer protected

Data protection claimed

yes

Material and methods – common block

Name	Instructions	Data Type
Test guideline	<p>Indicate according to which test guideline the study was conducted. If no test guideline was explicitly followed, but the methodology used is equivalent or similar to a specific guideline, you can indicate so in the 'Qualifier' subfield preceding the field 'Guideline'.</p> <p>Copy this block of fields for specifying more than one guideline (e.g. US EPA in addition to OECD guideline).</p>	Header
Qualifier	<p>Select appropriate qualifier, i.e.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 'according to guideline' (if a given test guideline was followed); - 'equivalent or similar to guideline' (if no test guideline was explicitly followed, but the methodology is equivalent or similar to a specific guideline); - 'no guideline followed' (if none of above qualifiers apply. If so, fill in field 'Principles of method if other than guideline'); - 'no guideline available' (if so, fill in field 'Principles of method if other than guideline') ; - 'no guideline required' (if so, fill in field 'Principles of method if other than guideline'). 	Closed list
Guideline	<p>Select the applicable test guideline, e.g. 'OECD Guideline xxx'. If the test guideline used is not listed, choose 'other:' and specify the test guideline in the related text field. Information on the version and date of the guideline used and/or any other specifics can be entered in the next field 'Version / remarks'.</p> <p>If no test guideline can be specified, this should be indicated in the preceding field 'Qualifier'. The method</p>	Open list

	<p>used should then be shortly described in the field 'Principles of method if other than guideline', while details can be given in other distinct fields.</p> <p>Please note: Test guidelines used for the validation of (Q)SAR models should be reported in the description of the relevant model in field 'Justification for type of information' or 'Attached justification'.</p>	
Version remarks	<p>/</p> <p>In this text field, you can enter any remarks as applicable, particularly:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To include any other title of the test guideline draft used, a subtitle, another version or update number and the year of update (For instance, different titles and/or numbers may exist for a given EU test guideline); - To indicate if the study was performed prior to the adoption of the test guideline specified; - To indicate if the methodology used was based on an extension of the test guideline specified; - To indicate what protocol was followed for methods that allow the optional determination of more than one parameter if this cannot be indicated in a distinct field of the Materials and methods section. 	Multi-line text
Deviations	<p>In case a test guideline or other standardised method was used, indicate if there are any deviations. Briefly state relevant deviations in the supplementary remarks field (e.g. 'other test system used', 'different exposure duration'); details should be described in the respective fields of the section MATERIALS AND METHODS.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Principles of method if other than guideline	<p>If no guideline was followed, include a description of the principles of the test protocol or estimated method used in the study. As appropriate use the available pre-defined freetext template. Delete / add elements and edit text set in square brackets [...] as appropriate.</p> <p>For a non-guideline experimental study a high-level freetext template can be used for summarising the principle of test, test conditions and parameters analysed / observed.</p> <p>Details should be entered in appropriate distinct fields of section MATERIALS AND METHODS if available. Also provide a justification for using this method if appropriate.</p>	Text template
GLP compliance	<p>Indicate whether the study was conducted following Good Laboratory Practice or not. In case 'yes' is selected, a Quality Assurance (QA) statement must be provided with the report. You can give an explanation in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for explaining why GLP was not complied with or for specifying which (national) GLP was followed.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Other quality assurance	<p>Indicate any non-GLP quality assurance system adhered to, if any.</p>	Open list with remarks
Type of method	<p>Indicate which type of method was used according to the options provided in the test guideline or, if no guideline was applied, according to the methodology used.</p>	Closed list with remarks

Links to supporting material:

Good Experimental Practice (GEP):
https://www.eppo.int/ACTIVITIES/plant_protection_products/gep

Materials and methods

Test guideline + New item Import file

#	Qualifier	Guideline	Version / remarks	Deviations
1	according to guideline	OECD Guideline 407 (Repeated Dose 28-Day Oral Toxicity Study in Rodents)	1981	None

Principles of method if other than guideline
None

GLP compliance
yes
This study was carried according to GLP principles but not subjected to periodic quality assurance evaluation.

Test material – common block

Name	Instructions	Data type
Test material		Header
Test material information	<p>Each study submitted for the active substance and the formulation must include a reference to a duly completed TEST MATERIAL INFORMATION record, including the identity and content of all test material components. These can be constituents (e.g. the active substance, a metabolite), impurities, additives, or co-formulants (for the formulation).</p> <p>Select the appropriate Test material information record. If not available in the repository, create a new one. You may also copy (clone) an existing TMI record, edit it and store it as new TMI.</p> <p>To change the link to an existing TMI, click the Delete button, then the Link button and proceed as described above.</p> <p>Depending on the purpose of the reporting or data submission, the information that must be provided may change. As a minimum, the chemical name, identifier and/or CAS number and molecular weight must be provided.</p> <p>For (Q)SAR results the TMI record is intended as the input for the (Q)SAR model (chemical identifiers and/or parameters).</p>	Reference
Additional test material information	Select additional Test material entities if relevant. For example, in long term studies where more than one batch of test material has been applied or there may be differences between the labelled and unlabelled test materials.	Reference
Specific details on test		Text template

<p>material used for the study</p>	<p>"Use this field for reporting specific details on the test material as used for the study if they differ from the starting material specified under 'Test material information'. This can include information on the pre-defined items, but not all or additional ones may be relevant.</p> <p>Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. Consult the programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) thereof.</p> <p>If applicable, relevant available information on the following items should be given:</p> <p>SOURCE OF TEST MATERIAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Source and lot/batch No. of test material - Expiration date of the lot/batch - Purity test date: provide if available <p>RADIOLABELLING INFORMATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Radiochemical purity - Specific activity - Locations of the label - Expiration date of radiochemical substance <p>STABILITY AND STORAGE CONDITIONS OF TEST MATERIAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storage condition of test material - Stability under test conditions - Solubility and stability of the test substance in the solvent/vehicle - Reactivity of the test substance with the solvent/vehicle or the cell culture medium <p>TREATMENT OF TEST MATERIAL PRIOR TO TESTING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Treatment of test material prior to testing (e.g. warming, grinding) - Preliminary purification step - Final dilution of a soluble solid, stock liquid, or gel (e.g., neat liquid, stock diluted liquid, or dissolved solid) to final concentration and the solvent(s) used - Final preparation of a solid (e.g. stock crystals ground to fine powder using a mortar and pestle) <p>FORM AS APPLIED IN THE TEST (if different from that of starting material)</p> <p>Specify the relevant form characteristics if different from those in the starting material, such as state of aggregation, shape of particles or particle size distribution.</p> <p>FORMULATED PRODUCT (for biocides/pesticides)</p>
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	<p>Description of the formulation, e.g. formulated product for foliar application; formulated product soil application; solution in organic solvent for soil application: formulated product seed treatment; solution in organic solvent seed treatment.</p> <p>OTHER SPECIFICS</p> <p>Provide any other relevant information needed for characterising the tested material.</p> <p>Note: for (Q)SARs results, indicate the exact input structure and input parameters."</p>	
<p>Specific details on test material used for the study (confidential)</p>	<p>Use this field for reporting specific details on the test material as used for the study if they differ from the starting material specified under 'Test material information'. This can include information on the pre-defined items, but not all or additional ones may be relevant.</p> <p>Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. Consult the programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) thereof.</p> <p>If applicable, relevant available information on the following items should be given:</p> <p>SOURCE OF TEST MATERIAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Source and lot/batch No. of test material - Expiration date of the lot/batch - Purity test date: provide if available <p>RADIOLABELLING INFORMATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Radiochemical purity - Specific activity - Locations of the label - Expiration date of radiochemical substance <p>STABILITY AND STORAGE CONDITIONS OF TEST MATERIAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storage condition of test material - Stability under test conditions - Solubility and stability of the test substance in the solvent/vehicle - Reactivity of the test substance with the solvent/vehicle or the cell culture medium <p>TREATMENT OF TEST MATERIAL PRIOR TO TESTING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Treatment of test material prior to testing (e.g. warming, grinding) - Preliminary purification step 	<p>Text template</p>

	<p>- Final dilution of a soluble solid, stock liquid, or gel (e.g., neat liquid, stock diluted liquid, or dissolved solid) to final concentration and the solvent(s) used</p> <p>- Final preparation of a solid (e.g. stock crystals ground to fine powder using a mortar and pestle)</p> <p>FORM AS APPLIED IN THE TEST (if different from that of starting material)</p> <p>Specify the relevant form characteristics if different from those in the starting material, such as state of aggregation, shape of particles or particle size distribution.</p> <p>FORMULATED PRODUCT (for biocides/pesticides)</p> <p>Description of the formulation, e.g. formulated product for foliar application; formulated product soil application; solution in organic solvent for soil application: formulated product seed treatment; solution in organic solvent seed treatment.</p> <p>OTHER SPECIFICS</p> <p>Provide any other relevant information needed for characterising the tested material.</p> <p>Note: for (Q)SARs results, indicate the exact input structure and input parameters.</p>	
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Test animals – common block

Name	Instructions	Data type
Test animals		Header
Species	Select species as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.	Picklist
Strain	Select strain as appropriate. If not available from picklist, select 'other' and specify.	Picklist
Details on species / strain selection	For robust study summaries or as requested by the regulatory programme, provide details explaining the choice of species and strain.	Text area
Sex	Select as appropriate. If females were used, indicate in field "Details on test animals and environmental conditions" whether nulliparous and non-pregnant.	Picklist
Details on test animals or test system and environmental conditions	Use free text template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study summary or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. Consult the programme-specific guidance (e.g. OECD Programme, EU pesticides, Pesticides NAFTA or EU REACH) thereof. Explanations: - Individual weight of animals at the start of the test: including body weight range, mean and standard deviation for each dosing group.	Text template

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diet: Describe type of diet (e.g. conventional laboratory diet / caloric restriction) and whether it was provided ad libitum. - Water: Describe type (e.g. drinking water) and whether it was provided ad libitum. - Food quality and water quality: provide analytical information on the nutrient and dietary contaminant levels. Similarly provide analytical information on the drinking water used in the study. - IN-LIFE DATES: If required, specify the in-life dates (i.e. the phase of a study following treatment in which the test system is alive/growing). 	
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Test animals

Species

rat

Strain

other: Tif RAIf

Sex

male/female

Details on test animals or test system and environmental conditions

Weight at study initiation: 166-227 g

Source: xxx

Initial age: 7-8 weeks

Husbandry: Caging in Macrolon cages type 4 (5 animals per cage) with standardized soft wood bedding. The animal room was air conditioned:

Temperature: 22+/-3°C

Relative humidity: 55+/-15%

12 hours light/day, approximately 15 air changes/h

Acclimatization period: at least 5 days

Sampling and analysis / Test solutions – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity)

Name	Instructions	Data type
Sampling and analysis		Header 2
Analytical monitoring	Indicate whether test substance was monitored in the test solutions or suspensions. The remarks field can be used to reference the analytical methods endpoint study record for the method used	Closed list with remarks
Details sampling on	If the concentration of test material was monitored, enter details on sampling. Use freetext template as appropriate and delete/add elements as appropriate.	Text template

Details analytical methods	on If the concentration of test material was monitored, enter any details on the analytical methods used. Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Copy any subheading(s) for the different matrices as appropriate.	Text template
Test solutions		Header 2
Vehicle	Indicate whether vehicle was used to emulsify or mix the experimental test material to enhance its solubility. If yes, specify in field 'Details on test solution'.	Closed list with remarks
Details on test solutions	Use freetext template and delete/add elements as appropriate. Enter any details that could be relevant for evaluating this study record or that are requested by the respective regulatory programme. If a solvent control is included, detail whether a dilution water (procedural) control was also included or omitted.	Text template

Sampling and analysis

Analytical monitoring

yes

Details on sampling

- Concentrations: all concentrations
- Sampling method: at days 0, 7, 14 and 21, from appr. centre of test vessels
- Sample storage conditions before analysis: kept at -18 °C to -22 °C until analysis

Details on analytical methods

IDENTIFICATION AND QUANTIFICATION OF TEST SUBSTANCE/PRODUCT

- Separation method (e.g. HPLC, GC): HPLC
- Conditions (column, mobile phase, etc.): NUCleosil C18 5 µm (250 x 4.6 mm i.d.) mobile phase: acetonitrile
- Detection method (e.g. ECD, UV, MS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS): UV

Test solutions

Vehicle

yes

Details on test solutions

PREPARATION AND APPLICATION OF TEST SOLUTION (especially for difficult test substances)

- Method: a stock solution was prepared by mixing 2.54 g test substance with 1750 mg TWEEN 20. The mixture was made up to 2000 mL with test water.
- Chemical name of vehicle (organic solvent, emulsifier or dispersant): TWEEN 20

Study design – common block (OHT: Terrestrial toxicity)

Name	Instructions	Data type
Study design		Header 2
Study type	Indicate the study type, i.e. laboratory study, extended laboratory study (e.g. with a more natural substrate), aged-residue study, semi-field study (mimicking a near-natural environment with ambient climatic conditions) or field study (using natural populations).	Open list with remarks
Substrate type	Select type of substrate.	Open list with remarks
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	Closed list
Total exposure duration	Enter numeric value.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)

Remarks	Enter any remarks related to the total exposure duration.	Text area
Post exposure observation period	Indicate the post-observation period (with unit) if appropriate, e.g. in the case of a reproduction test.	Text area

Study design – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity)

Name	Instructions	Data type
Study design		Header 2
Test type	Select appropriate test type.	List with remarks
Water media type	Indicate whether organisms were tested in fresh-/salt- or brackish/estuarine or other water.	List with remarks
Limit test	Indicate if the experiment was a limit test.	Closed list
Total exposure duration	Enter numeric value & unit.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
Remarks on exposure duration	Enter any remarks related to the total exposure duration.	Text area
Post exposure observation period	Indicate the post-observation period if appropriate.	Text area

Study design

Test type

flow-through

Water media type

freshwater

Limit test

no

Total exposure duration

21 d

Remarks on exposure duration

None

Post exposure observation period

None

Model and software – common block

Name	Instructions	Data type
Model and software		Header 2
Model name and version	Provide the name and version of the model used (e.g., ECOSAR v.1.0).	Text
Software name and version	Provide the name and version of the software used (e.g., OECD (Q)SAR Toolbox v.4.6).	Text

Remarks	Specify the exact model settings used to generate the (Q)SAR results. Indicate information on accessibility of the models (e.g., how can the model be accessed, is the model freely or commercially available).	Text
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Test conditions – common block (OHT: Aquatic toxicity)

Name	Instructions	Data type
Test conditions		
Hardness	Indicate water hardness as mg/L calcium carbonate equivalent values measured in the treatment and control solutions during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text
Test temperature	Indicate test temperature values measured in the treatment and control solutions during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. As appropriate state the location (e.g. water bath, test chambers) and type of measurement (e.g. continuous monitoring). Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text
pH	Indicate pH values measured in the treatment and control solutions during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. Indicate how mean pH is to be obtained. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text
Dissolved oxygen	Indicate dissolved oxygen values measured in the treatment and control solutions during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text
TOC	Indicate the TOC (total organic carbon) values measured during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the field 'Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables'.	Text
Salinity	Indicate salinity (if relevant) values measured in the treatment and control solutions during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit. Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	Text
Conductivity	Indicate conductivity values measured in the treatment and control solutions during test. Include range, mean, standard deviation and unit.	Text

	Alternatively refer to table (e.g. 'see table no. 2') if the test conditions are presented in tabular form in the rich text editor field.	
Nominal and measured concentrations	<p>List nominal and, if available, measured test concentrations used in the study. As appropriate tabulate nominal vs. measured mean concentrations in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Upload predefined or other appropriate table(s) if available, and tailor it/them to your needs. Use table numbers in the sequence in which you refer to them in the Remarks text.</p> <p>Use alternative predefined tables if data for both the technical end product and the active ingredient are to be recorded.</p>	Text
Reference substance (positive control)	<p>Indicate whether a positive control was tested, i.e. a reference substance with known bioaccumulation potential.</p> <p>If yes, include the identity of the substance(s) and the concentrations in the supplementary remarks field.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Details on test conditions	<p>Freertext template:</p> <p>Option 1</p> <p>TEST SYSTEM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test vessel: - Type (delete if not applicable): open / closed - Material, size, headspace, fill volume: - Aeration: - Type of flow-through (e.g. peristaltic or proportional diluter): - Renewal rate of test solution (frequency/flow rate): - No. of organisms per vessel: - No. of vessels per concentration (replicates): - No. of vessels per control (replicates): - No. of vessels per vehicle control (replicates): - Biomass loading rate: <p>TEST MEDIUM / WATER PARAMETERS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Source/preparation of dilution water: - Total organic carbon: - Particulate matter: - Metals: - Pesticides: - Chlorine: - Alkalinity: - Ca/mg ratio: - Culture medium different from test medium: - Intervals of water quality measurement: <p>OTHER TEST CONDITIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adjustment of pH: - Photoperiod: - Light intensity: 	Text template

	<p>EFFECT PARAMETERS MEASURED (with observation intervals if applicable) :</p> <p>TEST CONCENTRATIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spacing factor for test concentrations: - Justification for using less concentrations than requested by guideline: - Range finding study - Test concentrations: - Results used to determine the conditions for the definitive study: <p>Option 2 <i>In vitro</i> fish cell line acute toxicity test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Source of RTgill-W1 cells used: - Passage number and level of confluence of cells used for testing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cell counting method used for seeding prior to testing and measures taken to ensure homogeneous cell number distribution: - Fluorescent plate reader used (e.g. model), incl. instrument settings: - Method of preparation of stock solutions and dosing mixtures: - Analytical method used for quantification of exposure concentrations (e.g. accuracy, limit of detection, quantification and working range): - Justification in case nominal concentrations are used for EC50 calculation: - Procedure used to demonstrate proficiency of the laboratory in performing the test method or to demonstrate reproducible performance of the test method over time: - Test chemical concentrations, application procedure and exposure time used (if different than the one recommended): - Description of any modifications of the test procedure: 	
<p>Reference substance (positive control)</p>	<p>Picklist values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - yes - no - not specified - not required <p>Indicate if a positive control was tested, i.e. a reference substance with known toxicity.</p> <p>If yes, include the identity of the substance(s) (e.g. 3,5-dichlorophenol, copper(II) sulfate pentahydrate, 3,4-dichloroaniline, other) and the concentrations in the supplementary remarks field.</p>	<p>List (picklist remarks) sup. with</p>
<p>High dose level used</p>	<p>Picklist values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - yes - no 	

	Where a test method offers flexibility in the study design, for example in relation to the choice of dose levels, the chosen study design shall ensure that the data generated are adequate for hazard identification and risk assessment. To this end, testing shall be performed at appropriately high dose levels. If dose (concentration) selection is limited by the physicochemical properties or biological effects of the test substance, justification shall be provided.	
Justification for deviation from the high dose level	Freetext template: Justification for deviation from the high dose level	Text template

Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables – common block

Name	Instructions	Data Type
Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables		Header
	<p>In this field, you can enter any information on materials and methods, for which no distinct field is available, or transfer free text from other databases.</p> <p>You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format. You can also upload any htm or html document.</p> <p>Note: One rich text editor field each is provided for the MATERIALS AND METHODS and RESULTS section. In addition, the fields 'Overall remarks' and 'Executive summary' allow rich text entry.</p>	Rich text field

Any other information on materials and methods incl. tables

Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions – common block

Name	Instructions	Type
Additional information about applicability domain and reliability of (Q)SAR predictions		Header 2
Fit with the applicability domain	Indicate if the structure fits with the applicability domain of the model as defined by the model developers.	Picklist with remarks
Justification for the fit with the applicability domain	Justify the assessment of the fit of the structure with the applicability domain. Indicate if there is any additional known limitation of the applied model, not included in the applicability domain definition, that may influence the reliability of the prediction.	Text
Fit with the space defined by the training set of the model	Indicate if the structure fits with the physicochemical, structural and response spaces defined by the training set of the model.	Picklist with remarks
Mechanistic and metabolic considerations	Indicate mechanistic and metabolic considerations relevant for the predictions, if applicable.	Text

Results of examinations – common block

Name	Instructions	Type
Clinical signs	Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not. Select 'not examined' or 'not specified' as applicable.	Closed list
Description (incidence and severity)	Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible. Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s). NOTE: Depending on the regulatory programme some form of a table(s) (predefined table) may be mandatory.	Text area
Dermal irritation (if dermal study)	Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.	Closed list

	<p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	
<p>Description (incidence and severity) (field available only for dermal study)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p> <p>NOTE: Depending on the regulatory programme some form of a table(s) (predefined table) may be mandatory.</p>	Text area
<p>Mortality</p>	<p>Indicate whether mortality was observed and whether it was treatment-related or not.</p>	Closed list
<p>Description (incidence)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence of mortality by sex and dose group.</p> <p>An explanation should be provided when there was a need to humanely sacrifice animals in pain or showing signs of severe and enduring distress.</p>	Text area
<p>Body weight and weight changes</p>	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>The effects should be also considered in relation to organ weight.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study,select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	Closed list

<p>Description (incidence and severity)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Describe the maximum body weight change compared to the control.</p> <p>Preferably include a graph to illustrate body weight development in the attachment fields "Attached (confidential) document" or "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication".</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Food consumption and compound intake (if feeding study)</p>	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	<p>Closed list</p>
<p>Description (incidence and severity)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p> <p>For a feeding study, preferably include a graph to illustrate food consumption in the attachment fields "Attached (confidential) document" or "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication".</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Food efficiency</p>	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not. Select 'not examined' or 'not specified' as applicable.</p>	<p>Closed list</p>

<p>Description (incidence and severity)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Water consumption and compound intake (if drinking water study)</p>	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	<p>Closed list</p>
<p>Description (incidence and severity)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Ophthalmological findings</p>	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	<p>Closed list</p>

<p>Description (incidence and severity)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Haematological findings</p>	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	<p>Closed list</p>
<p>Description (incidence and severity)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Clinical biochemistry findings</p>	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	<p>Closed list</p>

<p>Description (incidence and severity)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Endocrine findings</p>	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, then select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p> <p>For more detailed information on the expected contents, please refer to the selected test guideline or the OECD Revised Guidance Document 150 on Standardised Test Guidelines for Evaluating Chemicals for Endocrine Disruption (2018).</p>	<p>Closed list</p>
<p>Description (incidence and severity)</p>	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	<p>Text area</p>
<p>Urinalysis findings</p>	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was</p>	<p>Closed list</p>

	decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'. 	
Description (incidence and severity)	Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible. Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s). 	Text area
Behaviour (functional findings)	Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not. If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'. Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'. If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, then select 'not specified'. If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'. 	Closed list
Description (incidence and severity)	Where relevant describe functional investigations in relation to motor activity, sensory function, grip strength or bizarre behaviour (e.g. walking backwards). Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible. Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s). 	Text area
Immunological findings	Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not. If no effects were noted select 'no effects observed'. Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'. 	Closed list

	<p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	
Description (incidence and severity)	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	Text area
Organ weight findings including organ / body weight ratios	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	Closed list
Description (incidence and severity)	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	Text area
Gross pathological findings	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p>	Closed list

	<p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	
Description (incidence and severity)	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	Text area
Neuropathological findings	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	Closed list
Description (incidence and severity)	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	Text area
Histopathological findings: non-neoplastic	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p>	Closed list

	<p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	
Description (incidence and severity)	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	Text area
Histopathological findings: neoplastic	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not.</p> <p>If no effects were noted, select 'no effects observed'.</p> <p>Do not leave the field empty, i.e. if this particular parameter was not evaluated, please select 'not examined'.</p> <p>If this parameter was evaluated but no results were reported in the results section of the study, select 'not specified'.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'.</p>	Closed list
Description (incidence and severity)	<p>Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible.</p> <p>Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).</p>	Text area
Other effects	<p>Indicate whether any effects were observed and whether they were treatment-related or not. Select 'not examined' or 'not specified' as applicable.</p> <p>If 'effects observed, treatment related' or 'effects observed, non-treatment-related' are selected, please provide a justification as to why this was</p>	Closed list

	decided in the field 'Description (incidence and severity)'. Description (incidence and severity)	
Description (incidence and severity)	Describe the incidence and severity of effects by sex and dose group. At a minimum provide a qualitative description where dose effect related observations were seen, whether the effects observed are adverse or non-adverse and if the data allows, whether the effects are reversible or irreversible. Particularly with comprehensive data, include a table in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'. Narrative accompanying such tabular data should mainly address the toxicological significance of the results and not repeat the details presented in the table(s).	Text area
Details on results	Provide any other relevant details if not entered in the specific "Description" fields for the examined parameters.	Text area

Results and discussion

Results of examinations

Clinical signs

effects observed, treatment-related

Description (incidence and severity)

Beginning with day 5 of treatment all male animals of group 4 (200 mg/kg) showed symptoms like apathia, ruffled fur, hunched posture, altered locomotion, ptosis, muscular weakness and in some cases salivation, ventral body position and bluish discoloration of the tail. No clinical symptoms were noted in all other treated male groups. Only one female (group 4, 200 mg/kg) showed similar symptoms like apathia, ruffled fur and hunched body position prior to death. Female number 60 (group 2, 5 mg/kg) died following misapplication by gavage.

Mortality

mortality observed, treatment-related

Description (incidence)

All treated males of group 4 (200 mg/kg bw.) died between day 7 and 10 of the treatment, while only one treatment-related death occurred in female group 4 (200 mg/kg). Female number 60 (group 2, 5 mg/kg bw.) died from causes unrelated to the treatment (misapplication) and female number 47 (control) died following blood withdrawal at scheduled sacrifice. No other deaths were registered during the course of the study.

Body weight and weight changes

effects observed, treatment-related

Description (incidence and severity)

The mean body weight of treated male group 4 (200 mg/kg) was depressed at week 1 prior to death of the animals. Further, the mean body weight of treated male group 3 (40 mg/kg) was slightly and that of female group 4 (200 mg/kg) was significantly depressed. The mean body weight of all other treated male and female groups was comparable to that of the respective controls (see Table 1)

Food consumption and compound intake (if feeding study)

effects observed, treatment-related

Description (incidence and severity)

The mean food consumption of male group 4 (200 mg/kg) was markedly reduced during the first week. Further, the mean food consumption in male group 3 (40 mg/kg) and in female group 4 (200 mg/kg) was depressed. The mean feed consumption in all other treated male and female groups was similar to that of the respective control groups during the whole experiment. No statistical analysis was performed.

Effect levels – common block

Name	Instructions	Type
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Dose descriptor	Select the relevant dose descriptor, i.e. the exposure level that corresponds to a quantified level of effects, e.g. NOAEL or LOAEL. If a benchmark dose / concentration was calculated, select appropriate BMD indicator (e.g. 'BMD05' or 'BMD:') and specify in the related text field). If the critical effects at a specific dose or concentration level are reported only, select 'dose. level:' or 'conc. level:' and specify. Where no value could be achieved based on the method and boundaries used, the upper or lower dose level for the relevant dose descriptor can be reported as appropriate with relevant qualifier, e.g. NOAEL >200 mg/kg bw/day or NOAEL <200 mg/kg bw/day. An additional explanation may be given in field 'Remarks on result', e.g. 'not determinable due to absence of adverse toxic effects'.	Closed list with remarks
Effect level	Enter a single numeric value in the first numeric field if you select no qualifier or '>', '>=' or 'ca.'. Use the second numeric field if the qualifier is '<' or '<='. For a range use both numeric fields together with the appropriate qualifier(s) if applicable. The following units should only be used in the case of microbial active substances: - cells - CFU (colony-forming unit) - ITU (International Toxic Unit) - IU (International Unit) - OB (occlusion bodies) - spores	Range with closed list (Decimal)
Based on	Indicate whether the concentration is based on the test material (test mat.), active ingredient (act. ingr.) or element. As appropriate the measured / addressed fraction can be specified for either of these entities by selecting the relevant item, e.g. 'element (dissolved fraction)' or 'test mat. (total fraction)'. Further information can be given in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for specifying the type of fraction if it is not clear per se from the test material specification. Select 'not specified' if the effect concentration type is not known.	Open list with remarks
Sex	Select from drop-down list.	Closed list
Basis for effect level	Indicate the parameter(s) used to establish the given effect level. Multi-selection of different pre-defined values is possible. If none is available, you can select 'other:'. Any explanations can always be entered in the related supplementary text field.	Multi select closed list with remarks (32000)
Remarks on result	This field can be used for: - giving a qualitative description of results in addition to or if no numeric value(s) were derived; - giving a pre-defined reason why no numeric value is provided, e.g. by selecting 'not determinable'	Open list with remarks (2000)

	and entering free text explanation in the supplementary remarks field; or - entering any additional information on the effect level by selecting 'other:'	
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Target system/organ toxicity – common block

Record the target system(s) where toxicity was observed that is considered of biological relevance and the specific target organ(s).

Copy this block of fields for referring to different target systems, lowest effective dose(s) / concentration(s) and/or treatment relationship, dose response relationship and relevance for humans.

Name	Instructions	Type
Key result	Set this flag for identifying the key information which is of potential relevance for hazard/risk assessment or classification purpose.	Check box
Critical effects observed	Flag to indicate if critical effects were observed in the study within specific organs or systems.	Closed list
Lowest effective dose / conc.	Enter a numeric value and select the unit in the next field for indicating the lowest dose / concentration with significant and/or severe toxic effects on the target organ(s) affected.	Unit measure with Closed List (Decimal)
System	Select any specific system where toxicity was observed that is considered of biological relevance.	Open list
Organ	Select from the multiple drop-down list the target organ(s) where toxicity was observed. This field provides context-related picklist values depending on the selection made in the preceding field 'System'.	Multi select open list
Treatment related	Flag to indicate if the effects in systems and/or organs are treatment related.	Closed list
Dose response relationship	Flag to indicate if the effects observed and reported in systems and/or organs are in a dose-response manner.	Closed list
Relevant for humans	Flag to indicate if the effects observed and reported in systems and/or organs on the basis of animal experiments are also relevant for humans. Choose "no" from the picklist if the effects in target system/organ are species specific and not relevant for humans.	Closed list

Target system / organ toxicity

[+ New item](#) [Import file](#) v

#	Key result	Critical effects observ...	Lowest effective dose...	System	Organ	Treatment related	Dose response relatio...	Relevant for humans
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	yes	None	hepatobiliary	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> liver	yes	yes	not specified

Dose response – common block

Name	Instructions	Type
Detailed results		Header 2
Dose response	If requested by the relevant regulatory programme, report here detailed information related to the outcome of the study at the different tested exposure levels (and, if applicable, at different time points). This	Block of fields

	type of information should otherwise be provided as tables in the rich text field 'Any other information on results incl. tables'.	
Replicate ID	Provide an identification for the specific replicate used in the experiment.	Text
Treatment group	Indicate whether the specific replicate was used as a negative control (either blank control or solvent control), whether it was a positive control (reference substance to test the sensitivity of the system) or whether it was one of the treatment levels with the test substance.	Picklist with remarks
Exposure level	Indicate the exposure level that the organisms were exposed to.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Time point	Indicate the time since the start of the experiment at which the present observation/assessment was made.	Numeric (decimal including unit)
Basis for effect	Select the effect parameter, such as development, which the effect concentration relates to. As appropriate include further details in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. 'mean development rate, male and female midges pooled'.	Picklist with remarks
Response value type	Indicate the type of value reported for the measurement, in consideration of the statistical unit used in the experimental design.	Picklist
Response value	Provide the value of the response. In case the "Response value type" is "mean ± SD", "mean ± SE" or "mean ± CV", this field should be filled in with the mean response value.	Numeric (decimal)
Variation statistics	Report the measure of variability, i.e. the standard deviation (SD) or the standard error (SE). This field should be filled in only in case the "Response value type" is specified as "mean ± SD" or "mean ± SE".	Numeric (decimal)
Unit	Select the unit that is relevant for the reported response value and basis for effect.	Picklist
Sample size	Indicate the number of organisms that constitute the sample used as statistical unit. For example, if mortality is reported as the fraction of the total number of organisms (in a replicate) which are dead, report the total number of organisms (in a replicate).	Numeric

Any other information on results including tables – common block

Name	Instructions	Type
Any other information on results including tables		Header 1
	In this field, you can enter any other remarks on results. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit	Rich Text Field

	<p>any excerpt from a word processing or spreadsheet document, provided it was converted to the HTML format.</p> <p>Note: One rich text editor field each is provided for the MATERIALS AND METHODS and RESULTS section. In addition the fields 'Overall remarks' and 'Executive summary' allow rich text entry.</p>	
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Overall remarks, attachments – common block

Name	Instructions	Type
Overall remarks, attachments		Header 1
Overall remarks	<p>In this field, you can enter any overall remarks or transfer free text from other databases. You can also open a rich text editor and create formatted text and tables or insert and edit any excerpt from a word processing document. Use this field <u>only if strictly necessary</u> i.e. when no other specific fields such as repeatable blocks exist in the document to enter the data of interest.</p> <p>Note: One rich text editor field each is provided for the MATERIALS AND METHODS and RESULTS section. In addition, the fields 'Overall remarks' and 'Executive summary' allow rich text entry.</p>	Rich text area
Attachments	<p>Attach any background document that cannot be inserted in any rich text editor field, particularly image files.</p> <p>Copy this block of fields for attaching more than one file.</p>	
Type	<p>Classify the type of attachment uploaded e.g 'Appendix F mammalian toxicology result'</p> <p>Full study reports should be uploaded in the Literature reference entity</p>	Open list
Attached (confidential) document	<p>The original file only needs to be attached here if the non-confidential file uploaded under "Attached (sanitised) documents for publication" contains redactions. If a file is uploaded under this field (a) confidentiality claim(s) must be submitted for each part of the file considered confidential and the information claimed confidential must be clearly boxed or earmarked consistently with the redactions applied in the corresponding non-confidential file. This file will not be published.</p>	Single file attachment
Attached (sanitised) documents for publication	<p>Provide any additional documents relevant for the submission, not already provided under the literature reference entity.</p> <p>For test guidelines that provide a reporting template (data analysis file), that file must be completed and can be uploaded here if not yet done in the results section.</p>	Single File Attachment

	<p>See IUCLID templates for PPP Risk Assessment Templates on EFSA Knowledge Junction (zenodo).</p> <p>Any additional background documents uploaded here must be uploaded in their public (non-confidential) version . The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised. Save for the elements blackened, if applicable, content and layout-wise the public version must be fully identical with the confidential version. Upon conclusion of the confidentiality assessment, if applicable, a revised public version removing the redactions relating to confidentiality requests that were rejected in part or in full must be uploaded here. Any document uploaded here must be uploaded in their public (non-confidential) version. The public version will be published once the dossier has been considered valid/admissible. All elements therein claimed confidential should be sanitised.</p>	
Remarks	As appropriate, include remarks, e.g., a short description of the content of the attached document if the file name is not self-explanatory.	Text

Overall remarks, attachments

Overall remarks
None

Attachments + New item 📁 Import file ▼

#	Type	Attached (confidential) do...	Attached (sanitised) docu...	Remarks
1	other: Mammalian toxicology results	None	Template 5.1 - Template for presentation of results in tabular format for mamtox studies.docx	None

Illustration (picture/graph)
None

Applicant’s summary and conclusion – common block

Name	Instructions	Type
Applicant's summary and conclusion		Header 1
Validity criteria	When requested in the endpoint study record, include any validity criteria from the relevant test guideline.	Repeatable block
Validity criteria	Provide the addressed validity criteria.	Text area
Observed value	Provide the observation related to the respective validity criteria.	Text area
Validity criteria fulfilled	Indicate whether the validity criteria given by the test	Closed list

	<p>guideline have been fulfilled or not. Use the supplementary remarks field for entering any further remarks.</p> <p>Clearly indicate if the criteria used are not consistent with those given by the test guideline. If so, or if the validity criteria are not fulfilled, provide a justification in the field 'Rationale for reliability incl. deficiencies' as to why this study summary is considered reliable.</p>	
Interpretation of results	<p>This field is present ONLY in document 6.3 Magnitude of residues in plants" (OHT 85-5):</p> <p>Indicate overall interpretation of test results with regard to expected residues in crop commodities as given in the study report or as concluded by the submitter. You can give an explanation in the supplementary remarks field, e.g. for indicating at what plant back interval residues are taken up by rotational crop, i.e. in which crop fractions and at what levels, or for indicating if conclusions originally reported were changed by submitter. For more detailed discussion of test results, use field 'Conclusions'.</p>	Closed list with remarks
Conclusions	<p>This field should be used to summarize the conclusions by the applicant and will be used in study summaries produced using report generator.</p>	Text area
Executive summary	<p>If relevant for the respective regulatory programme, briefly summarize the relevant aspects of the study including the conclusions reached. If a specific format is prescribed, copy it from the corresponding document or upload it if provided as htm or html document.</p>	Rich text area

